

The role of companion animals in human well-being: A mixed methods approach with a focus on ornamental fishes

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Author's Declaration

The work described in this thesis was carried out between October 2017 – April 2022 at the University of the West of Scotland. The work presented herein represents entirely the author's own work and has not been submitted for any other degree. This work was funded in part by Mars Petcare UK, and conducted in collaboration with the Waltham Petcare Science Institute.

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Statement on the Impact of COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic had an extensive impact on my Ph.D. research. Most notably, restrictions brought about by the pandemic made it impossible to conduct research with certain populations. This resulted in the cancellation of two studies planned to examine the effects of ornamental fishes among people with dementia living in care homes and children in nurseries. Both studies received ethical approval prior to the pandemic and were in the participant recruitment phase at the time of the first lockdown. Thus, the postponement and ultimate cancellation of these studies was a setback which required major amendments to my planned programme of research, and resulted in substantial delays in the completion of my Ph.D.

In addition to the cancellation of these studies, one study examining the impact of ornamental fishes in the workplace (Chapter 3, Trial B) was ended prematurely due to lockdown, resulting in incomplete data for a small number of participants. A second study on the same topic (Chapter 4) suffered from repeated delays due to multiple lockdowns which contributed to the final sample being relatively small, and different workplaces participating under different levels of restrictions in terms of the requirement to work from home.

Nevertheless, the pandemic presented new opportunities to explore alternative aspects of Human-Animal Interaction. Research was conducted to examine the influence of companion animal guardianship on well-being during the pandemic, and among people working from home during a time where remote working has become the norm.

Abstract

Human-animal interaction has been linked to better well-being in various populations and settings, but most research has involved animals which interact with humans through physical touch, such as dogs. Less is known about the effects of engaging with animals such as ornamental fishes where the interaction is based primarily on visual exposure. The primary aim of this thesis was to improve understanding of whether and how engagement with ornamental fishes influences human well-being. A systematic review was conducted to identify the psychological and physiological effects of interacting with fishes in aquaria, and two studies (one mixed methods, one qualitative) were conducted to understand the effects of engagement with fishes in the workplace. Studies planned in nurseries and care homes could not proceed due to the COVID-19 pandemic; instead a secondary aim of the thesis became to understand the impact that companion animals, and in particular ornamental fishes, had upon human well-being during the pandemic and ongoing restrictions. A mixed methods study examined the relationships between companion animal guardianship, loneliness and mental well-being during the pandemic, and a quasi-experimental study assessed the effects of companion animal guardianship on the well-being and productivity of people working from home. Across all studies there was no quantitative evidence that engagement with ornamental fishes influences human well-being. Qualitative evidence suggested that human-fish interaction may have an emotional element, and so goes beyond the visual dimension; further research is needed to fully understand human-fish relationships. A tone of dismissiveness towards fishes was also identified, and suggested that fishes may be viewed with a lesser regard than other companion animals; this may have implications for fish welfare and warrants further consideration. With regards to companion animal guardianship more broadly, qualitative evidence suggested that guardians felt their companion animals were a positive influence during the pandemic, but there was no quantitative evidence to support this. There was also no evidence that companion animal guardianship was associated with well-being or productivity for people working from home.

Level of engagement was associated with well-being outcomes for dog guardians, and to a lesser extent cat guardians, and should be taken into consideration in future studies. Finally, there was qualitative evidence that some guardians found companion animals to be a source of stress; this may explain conflicting evidence regarding the benefits of companion animal guardianship as these additional stresses may counteract any benefits associated with human-animal interaction.

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- 1 **Chapter 1.**
- 2 **The role of companion animals in human health and**
- 3 **well-being**

4 Friedmann et al. (1980) were the first to identify a link between pet ownership (hereafter
5 “companion animal guardianship”) and human health. Ninety-two patients admitted to
6 hospital for myocardial infarction or angina pectoris were followed up one year after
7 discharge, and mortality rates among those who kept companion animals were significantly
8 lower than those of non-guardians. This effect remained even after dog guardians were
9 removed from the analysis, suggesting the link was due to factors other than the increased
10 physical activity associated with keeping dogs (Friedmann et al., 1980). In the decades
11 following this study a considerable body of research has examined the links between
12 Human-Animal Interaction (HAI) and human well-being (Serpell et al., 2017, Crossman and
13 Kazdin, 2018). This research typically falls into one of three categories: 1) the effects of
14 companion animal guardianship, 2) the effects of animal-assisted interventions, and 3) the
15 effects of brief interactions with companion animals (Friedmann and Gee, 2019). This
16 introductory chapter looks in detail at these three categories, and then reviews some of the
17 theories proposed to explain the effects of HAI: biophilia and distraction, attachment and
18 social support, and the biopsychosocial model of health. In addition, the restorative effects of
19 nature are discussed as an alternative explanation for the effects of HAI. Throughout the
20 chapter, links are made to the specific effects of interacting with ornamental fishes.

21 **1.1 Companion animals and human well-being**

22 **1.1.1 Companion animal guardianship**

23 Following the findings of Friedmann et al. (1980), several studies have found further
24 evidence of a connection between companion animal guardianship and mortality, particularly
25 in relation to cardiovascular disease. Friedmann, Thomas and Son (2011) found that among
26 patients who had survived for at least six months following myocardial infarction, compared
27 to those who did not keep companion animals, being a companion animal guardian was
28 associated with enhanced long-term survival during the follow-up period (average follow-up
29 period of 2.8 years). Similarly, previous and current companion animal guardianship were
30 both linked to lower cardiovascular disease and all-cause mortalities among a sample of

31 older adults being treated for hypertension (Chowdhury et al., 2016). Dog guardianship in
32 particular appears to be associated with lower risk of mortality. A nationwide cohort study
33 conducted in Sweden found that dog guardianship was associated with 8% lower risk of
34 cardiovascular disease in single-person households, and 20% lower risk of mortality in the
35 general population (Mubanga et al., 2017), while a prospective cohort study in the Czech
36 Republic reported that dog guardians had cardiovascular health scores that were around 2%
37 greater than non-dog guardians, inclusive of those who kept other types of companion
38 animal, and after adjusting for covariates such as age, sex and educational level (Maugeri et
39 al., 2019). Furthermore, the original findings of Friedmann et al. (1980) were replicated for
40 people who kept dogs, but not for companion animal guardians more broadly (Friedmann
41 and Thomas, 1995). A systematic review conducted on behalf of the American Heart
42 Association concluded that there is “probably” a link between companion animal
43 guardianship and reduced cardiovascular disease risk, particularly in relation to the
44 guardianship of dogs (Levine et al., 2013).

45 On the other hand, several studies have failed to replicate the association between keeping
46 companion animals and reduced mortality. A large scale ($n = 59352$) study linking data from
47 the Health Survey for England to the National Death Registry found no evidence that dog
48 guardianship was linked to either cardiovascular disease or all-cause mortalities (Ding et al.,
49 2018), and a study conducted in Norway found that those who did and did not keep dogs
50 had an almost identical risk of all-cause mortality (Torske et al., 2017). Other research has
51 provided mixed results. Ogechi et al. (2016) found that cat guardianship was associated with
52 lower risk of dying from cardiovascular events (hazard ratio = 0.62), but no similar
53 association was found for dog guardianship, while Qureshi et al. (2009) identified a link
54 between past cat guardianship and lower risk of death from myocardial infarction (relative
55 risk = 0.63) after controlling for confounding factors, such as demographic variables, health-
56 related behaviours (e.g. smoking) and health conditions (e.g. diabetes mellitus), but the
57 same effect was not observed for current cat guardians or people who kept dogs at any

58 stage of life. A conceptual replication of Friedmann et al. (1980) found that the likelihood of
59 death or re-admission to hospital in the year following an acute coronary syndrome was
60 higher among companion animal guardians (22.2%), and particularly cat guardians (27.3%),
61 than non-guardians (13.6%) (Parker et al., 2010), and a recent systematic review found no
62 robust link between companion animal guardianship and cardiovascular disease or all-cause
63 mortality (Yeh et al., 2019).

64 Inconsistent findings are also evident in relation to other health-related outcomes. For
65 example, several studies have identified a positive link between companion animal
66 guardianship and levels of physical activity (Raina et al., 1999, Müllersdorf et al., 2010, Mein
67 and Grant, 2018, Machová et al., 2019). This relationship appears strongest for dog
68 guardians (Serpell, 1991, Thorpe et al., 2006, Yabroff, Troiano and Berrigan, 2008, Rijken
69 and van Beek, 2011, Mein and Grant, 2018, Mičková et al., 2019), but may depend on
70 whether the individual is responsible for exercising their dog (Coleman et al., 2008, Hoerster
71 et al., 2011). Horse guardianship has also been linked to higher frequency and duration of
72 moderate physical activity, at least among young female guardians (Machová et al., 2019).
73 However, levels of physical activity among cat guardians appear similar to or lower than
74 those of people who do not keep companion animals (Yabroff, Troiano and Berrigan, 2008,
75 Rijken and van Beek, 2011), and at least one study failed to find evidence of a relationship
76 between dog guardianship and physical activity (Torske et al., 2017).

77 The role of companion animals in mental health has also been examined. Qualitative
78 findings suggest that people perceive their companion animals to be providers of
79 companionship and psychosocial support, and generally an enhancement to their lives
80 (Knight and Edwards, 2008, Scheibeck et al., 2011, Maharaj and Haney, 2015, Hayden-
81 Evans, Milbourn and Netto, 2018, Howe and Easterbrook, 2018, Brooks et al., 2019, Hui
82 Gan et al., 2020, Nitkin and Buchanan, 2020). Adopting a dog is also anticipated to have
83 benefits such as companionship, increased happiness and reduced stress (Powell et al.,
84 2018). Quantitative evidence is less clear, with a mix of positive, neutral and negative

85 findings (Brooks et al., 2018). For example, companion animal guardianship versus non-
86 guardianship has been associated with lower levels of depression among men with AIDS
87 (Siegel et al., 1999), and smaller increases in depressive symptoms among older adults
88 following loss of a spouse to divorce or bereavement (Carr et al., 2020). Adoption of a new
89 companion animal was also associated with improvements in treatment-resistant depression
90 relative to a control group of individuals who chose not to adopt a companion animal (Pereira
91 and Fonte, 2018). However, several studies have found no evidence of a relationship
92 between companion animal guardianship and mental health (Antonacopoulos and Pychyl,
93 2010, Rijken and van Beek, 2011, Batty et al., 2017) and there is evidence that people who
94 keep companion animals may have more mental health problems than non-guardians
95 (Müllersdorf et al., 2010).

96 Type of companion animal may also play a role, for instance, dog guardianship at 10 years
97 old was associated with maintenance of mental well-being at 12 years, whereas cat
98 guardianship was associated with a decline in mental well-being over the same period (Endo
99 et al., 2020). A systematic review of studies examining the relationship between companion
100 animal guardianship and loneliness concluded that there is no convincing evidence that
101 companion animals directly impact feelings of loneliness (Gilbey and Tani, 2015), although
102 there is evidence that a relationship exists for specific populations, such as children or
103 adolescents (Purewal et al., 2017).

104 **1.1.2 Animal-assisted interventions**

105 While companion animal guardianship may be initiated for purposes unrelated to human
106 health, such as pest control or protection (Gray and Young, 2011), some forms of HAI are
107 developed for the specific purpose of improving human well-being. Animal-assisted
108 interventions¹ (AAI) incorporate any programme that intentionally involves animals in the

¹ Animal-assisted interventions are also referred to using numerous other terms, such as “pet therapy”, “pet facilitated intervention”, and species-specific designations (e.g. “dog-facilitated intervention”, “equine-assisted therapy”) (O’Haire, 2013, Maujean, Pepping and Kendall, 2015, Bert et al., 2016).

109 therapeutic or treatment process (Kruger and Serpell, 2010). These interventions can be
110 further divided into “animal-assisted therapies” (AAT) and “animal-assisted activities” (AAA),
111 where the former refers to a structured and goal-oriented intervention delivered by qualified
112 healthcare professionals, and the latter to a more spontaneous programme, often delivered
113 by volunteers and lacking specific treatment goals (Kruger and Serpell, 2010). AAI is
114 typically used in a complementary capacity alongside traditional models of treatment, or to
115 help individuals cope (Nimer and Lundahl, 2007).

116 The effects of AAI have been explored in a wide range of populations and settings, with
117 many positive results. Among people with dementia for example, AAI has been associated
118 with improvements in outcomes such as social behaviour, agitation, anxiety, and aggression
119 (Hu et al., 2018, Yakimicki et al., 2019), while children with autism spectrum disorder have
120 shown improvements in social functioning and maladaptive behaviours (O’Haire, 2013,
121 Anderson and Meints, 2016). Positive effects are also found for physical health outcomes,
122 for instance, balance, posture, and gait have been found to improve among children with
123 cerebral palsy and adults with multiple sclerosis following engagement in equine-assisted
124 therapies (Muñoz-Lasa et al., 2011, Zadnikar and Kastrin, 2011, Charry-Sanchez, Pradilla
125 and Talero-Gutierrez, 2018, Charry-Sánchez, Pradilla and Talero-Gutiérrez, 2018). Other
126 populations in which AAI has been successful include people with cognitive impairment or
127 psychiatric illness (Virués-Ortega et al., 2012, Bernabei et al., 2013, Hu et al., 2018),
128 hospitalised patients (Bert et al., 2016), people with intellectual disabilities (Maber-
129 Aleksandrowicz, Avent and Hassiotis, 2016), people recovering from trauma (O’Haire,
130 Guérin and Kirkham, 2015), and children in educational settings (Brelsford et al., 2017),
131 although this list is by no means exhaustive.

132 As with companion animal guardianship, inconsistencies are found in evidence relating to
133 AAI. Among people with dementia for example, several studies have observed positive
134 effects of AAI on agitated behaviour and associated symptoms (Kanamori et al., 2001,
135 Richeson, 2003, Sellers, 2006, Majić et al., 2013, Dabelko-Schoeny et al., 2014, Edwards,

136 Beck and Lim, 2014), but other research has found no effect on agitation (Friedmann et al.,
137 2015, Olsen et al., 2016), and one study found a significant increase in verbal agitation at
138 the six month follow-up for participants in the intervention group, with no change among
139 those in the control group (Nordgren and Engström, 2014). Furthermore, many studies
140 assess numerous variables but find positive treatment effects for only a subset of these
141 outcomes, so overall the majority of outcomes are unaffected by the intervention (Lundqvist
142 et al., 2017).

143 **1.1.3 Brief interactions with companion animals**

144 A final category of evidence relates to the health effects of brief interactions with companion
145 animals. Evidence in this category is typically drawn from experimental research in which
146 outcomes are assessed following a short period of contact between the participants and a
147 companion animal (Friedmann and Gee, 2019). This research is often conducted within the
148 context of a stressor, and may involve a participant's own companion animal or an unknown
149 but friendly companion animal, with or without relevant training or certification (Friedmann
150 and Gee, 2019). Whereas AAI is usually conducted as part of the treatment process for a
151 specified population, research examining the effects of brief interactions usually involves
152 healthy populations, such as university students. Interactions are often highly structured and
153 may take place in a laboratory setting, although some are conducted in settings with greater
154 ecological validity. Consequently, these studies can provide an insight into the mechanisms
155 underlying the effects of HAI, but it is unclear whether the same effects would be observed
156 under more natural conditions (Friedmann and Gee, 2019).

157 Much research in this category has been conducted with student samples, and several
158 studies have identified that brief interactions with a companion animal can alleviate feelings
159 of stress or anxiety among this population. For example, college students who interacted
160 with a therapy dog for 10 minutes during an exam period experienced a reduction in both
161 state anxiety and perceived stress, although no changes were found for cognitive function
162 (Banks, McCoy and Trzcinski, 2018). Likewise, positive affect was maintained and negative

163 affect reduced among participants who read aloud to live budgerigars, but not among those
164 who read to toy birds or an empty cage (Jones, Skolnick and Anderson, 2021). Similar
165 effects were observed in studies comparing the effects of interacting with companion
166 animals – usually dogs – to interacting with other people (Lass-Hennemann et al., 2014),
167 interacting with toy animals (Lass-Hennemann et al., 2014), viewing the animal with no
168 physical contact (Crossman, Kazdin and Knudson, 2015), viewing images of the animals
169 (Pendry et al., 2018), completing alternative activities (Barker et al., 2016), or undertaking no
170 activity for the same time period (Crossman, Kazdin and Knudson, 2015, Pendry et al.,
171 2018). Interestingly, one study found that while interacting with a dog alone led to
172 improvements in well-being, mood, and anxiety, the positive effects on mood were
173 diminished when the dog handler was also present during the interaction; this may have
174 implications for the use of therapy dog and handler teams in AAI (Grajfoner et al., 2017).

175 Other research has been conducted with children and adolescents. For instance, children
176 who interacted with a dog for 15 minutes demonstrated enhanced attention and
177 concentration compared to those who interacted with a robotic dog (Hediger and Turner,
178 2014), and children who interacted with their family dog while experiencing social stress
179 induced by the Trier Social Stress Test reported greater positive affect than those whose
180 dogs were not present during the task (Kerns et al., 2018). Interaction with a therapy dog
181 was also linked to lower levels of cortisol than interaction with a toy dog or friendly human
182 among male children experiencing social stress (Beetz, Julius, et al., 2012).

183 Conversely, Straatman et al. (1997) found no effect of interaction with a friendly but
184 unfamiliar dog on self-reported state anxiety or physiological indicators of stress (heart rate
185 and blood pressure) among male students undertaking a speech task designed to induce
186 stress, and Mueller et al. (2021) found no evidence that interaction with a therapy dog, with
187 or without physical contact, influenced self-reported anxiety or physiological outcomes
188 among adolescents relative to interaction with a stuffed toy. Furthermore, as with research
189 on AAI, studies regarding brief interactions with companion animals typically assess many

190 outcomes but find only partial support for the anticipated effects (e.g. Lass-Hennemann et
191 al., 2014, Barker et al., 2016, Kerns et al., 2018, Machová et al., 2020).

192 **1.2 Potential negative consequences of human-animal interaction**

193 The research discussed so far has focused on how companion animals may positively
194 influence human health and well-being, but it should be recognised that these interactions
195 may also have negative consequences. Interaction with companion animals can be a risky
196 activity, with the potential of harm to physical and psychological well-being. An individual's
197 health may be compromised by the transmission of zoonotic pathogens, through accidental
198 injury caused by bites or scratches, or by fall-related injuries if the animal creates a tripping
199 hazard (Stevens, Teh and Haileyesus, 2010, Hodgson et al., 2015). The severity of these
200 risks will depend upon the population under study. For instance, the risk of injury and fatality
201 associated with falls increases with age and frailty (World Health Organization, 2007),
202 whereas the rate of injury and fatality caused by dog bites is much higher among children
203 than adults (Overall and Love, 2001), although the latter risk can be reduced through
204 appropriate training (Meints, Brelsford and De Keuster, 2018). Several populations including
205 young children, older adults, immunocompromised persons and pregnant women, are at
206 greater risk of contracting zoonotic diseases, and also have a greater likelihood of
207 experiencing more severe symptoms, complications, and a longer durations of illness (Stull,
208 Brophy and Weese, 2015).

209 With respect to psychological well-being, perhaps the most notable threat is the grief
210 associated with the death of a companion animal (Kemp, Jacobs and Stewart, 2016, Brooks
211 et al., 2018, Howe and Easterbrook, 2018). However, companion animal guardianship also
212 requires a substantial investment of resources including time, energy, and money (Serpell
213 and Paul, 2011); this may compromise the psychological well-being of individuals who find
214 themselves lacking the necessary financial resources to care for their companion animal
215 (Brooks et al., 2018, Howe and Easterbrook, 2018), or who become stressed about having
216 to leave their animals at home alone while out at work (Norling and Keeling, 2010, Wilkin,

217 Fairlie and Ezzedeen, 2016). Access to housing and support services may also be restricted
218 by companion animal guardianship, as companion animals are often not permitted in rented
219 accommodation, residential care, or rehabilitation facilities, and individuals may be unwilling
220 to part with their companion animal in order to access these services (Langfield and James,
221 2009, Hodgson et al., 2015, Howe and Easterbrook, 2018).

222 In addition, there are a number of barriers to successful interaction with companion animals
223 which should be recognised. Animal-assisted interventions are often volunteer-led and
224 require supervision to minimise risk to the client and animal; these factors may lead to
225 infrequent or inconsistent exposure, so limiting contact time between the human and animal
226 (Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014). Animal visitation
227 programmes will also be prohibited in settings where an individual is found to have allergies
228 or phobias (Lefebvre et al., 2008, Murthy et al., 2015), and the benefits of these interventions
229 will be limited to individuals who enjoy interacting with animals (Kamioka et al., 2014). Aside
230 from the increased risk of infection or injury, individuals with ill health or disability may
231 experience barriers to engagement with companion animals if, for example, they lack the
232 physical capacity or strength needed to walk a dog (Langfield and James, 2009).

233 Finally, interacting with humans may be detrimental to companion animal welfare.

234 Companion animals kept as pets may experience harm as a result of intentional animal
235 abuse or neglect, and while the presence of an animal handler during AAI and research
236 should minimise these risks, clients may still behave inappropriately towards the animal
237 leading to increased stress and/or aggression (Hatch, 2007). The animal may also
238 experience stress or fatigue even when working with well-behaved clients (Iannuzzi and
239 Rowan, 1991), and some researchers have noted that animal handlers do not always
240 respond appropriately to the needs of companion animals during AAI and HAI research, for
241 instance failing to provide sufficient water, or not allowing adequate rest (Iannuzzi and
242 Rowan, 1991, Hatch, 2007). The development of best practice guidelines may be useful in

243 minimising risk to all parties involved in AAI, but at present standardised tools for
244 assessment of risk and animal welfare are not widely used (Brelsford et al., 2020).

245 **1.3 Methodological issues in human-animal interaction research**

246 It is important to acknowledge limitations in methodology within the field of HAI. Firstly, as
247 companion animal guardianship involves substantial investment of resources (Serpell and
248 Paul, 2011), it is usually unrealistic to utilise research designs involving random
249 assignment.² Therefore, research has traditionally relied upon observational designs,
250 including cross-sectional and cohort studies. While this is necessary for ethical and practical
251 purposes, these correlational designs have limited value when attempting to make
252 judgements about causality, as it is impossible to determine which of two variables
253 influences the other, and the effects of confounding factors cannot be controlled (Mann,
254 2003, Ligthelm et al., 2007). Thus, health may influence the decision to become a
255 companion animal guardian, rather than the reverse (Herzog, 2011), or both factors may be
256 linked through confounding variables such as sociodemographic characteristics (Cline, 2010,
257 Müllersdorf et al., 2010, Utz, 2014, Marsa-Sambola et al., 2016, Mubanga et al., 2017,
258 Saunders et al., 2017), personality (Bao and Schreer, 2016), the type of companion animal
259 (Thorpe et al., 2006, Yabroff, Troiano and Berrigan, 2008, Utz, 2014, Bao and Schreer,
260 2016, Ogechi et al., 2016, Brooks et al., 2018, Mein and Grant, 2018), and the strength of
261 the human-animal bond (Watt and Pachana, 2007, Antonacopoulos and Pychyl, 2010,
262 Peacock, Chur-Hansen and Winefield, 2012, Brooks et al., 2018, Wu, Wong and Chu, 2018).

263 Studies regarding AAI and brief interactions with companion animals are not subject to the
264 same ethical and practical limitations that preclude randomisation, yet evidence has often
265 been drawn from studies lacking appropriate control groups, making it impossible to
266 determine whether any observed effects are a direct result of interaction with a companion

² One study has used a single-blinded, randomised controlled design to explore the effects of companion animal guardianship on older adults living in Korea. Improvements were found in depression, cognitive function, and quality of life; however, as this study involved a “pet” that is very atypical with respect to the research literature (crickets), the findings may not be generalisable to companion animal guardianship more broadly.

267 animal or other factors associated with the research (Kazdin, 2017, Serpell et al., 2017).
268 Lack of blinding is also a concern, as the animal will be clearly visible to both participants
269 and study personnel (Serpell et al., 2017, Friedmann and Gee, 2019). Thus bias may be
270 introduced through the preconceptions of those involved in the research (Schulz and
271 Grimes, 2002).

272 Many researchers also rely on small samples without conducting (or reporting having
273 conducted) power analyses prior to data collection, and so non-significant results may be
274 attributed to the lack of statistical power rather than the absence of an effect (Serpell et al.,
275 2017, Friedmann and Gee, 2019). Other methodological concerns include the lack of proper
276 randomisation techniques, failure to conceal allocation, and a reliance on anecdotal and
277 descriptive evidence (Chur-Hansen, Stern and Winefield, 2010, Serpell et al., 2017). In
278 general, research regarding the efficacy of AAI suffers from a paucity of randomised
279 controlled trials – widely accepted as the “gold standard” when evaluating healthcare
280 interventions (Schulz, Altman and Moher, 2010) – as well as a lack of trustworthy and
281 defensible qualitative research (Chur-Hansen, Stern and Winefield, 2010, Kazdin, 2017).
282 Conversely, studies examining brief interactions with companion animals are often highly
283 structured and laboratory-based, and so results may not be replicable under real-life
284 conditions (Friedmann and Gee, 2019).

285 A final limitation of evidence regarding HAI relates to the high degree of heterogeneity within
286 this body of research. Findings are often collated despite being drawn from diverse
287 populations, but factors such as sociodemographic characteristics, personality, and clinical
288 diagnoses may all influence how participants respond to the HAI (Saunders et al., 2017,
289 Serpell et al., 2017, Friedmann and Gee, 2019). Participants’ prior experiences with
290 companion animals are also likely to play a role, and any observed benefits are likely to be
291 limited to individuals who like animals (Kamioka et al., 2014, Friedmann and Gee, 2019).
292 With respect to AAI and experimental research, heterogeneity is also present within the

293 design and setting of different studies, the duration, length and intensity³ of the interaction,
294 the mode of delivery (i.e. group or individual), the type of comparator used, and the timing
295 and method of outcome assessments (Kazdin, 2017, Rodriguez et al., 2018, Friedmann and
296 Gee, 2019).

297 Variation is also present in the specific nature of the interaction between participants and the
298 companion animal(s). It is not clear whether interacting with different companion animal
299 types will have similar effects, and variation may even exist within species or breeds due to
300 differences in the temperament of individual animals (Kazdin, 2017, Serpell et al., 2017). The
301 ways in which people interact with companion animals may also influence outcomes;
302 research has suggested that physical contact with a companion animal has different effects
303 to visual exposure alone (DeMello, 1999, Gee et al., 2015), and the presence of an animal
304 handler may influence outcomes (Chur-Hansen, Stern and Winefield, 2010, Grajfoner et al.,
305 2017). Given these sources of heterogeneity, further research is needed to determine the
306 specific contexts under which interacting with companion animals may effectively promote
307 human well-being.

308 **1.4 The benefits of ornamental fishes**

309 Watching ornamental fishes is widely believed to promote relaxation, as demonstrated by
310 the frequent presence of fish aquaria in potentially stress-inducing environments, such as
311 doctors surgeries (O’Haire, 2010). Evidence also comes from research conducted with
312 people who keep ornamental fishes. In a survey of home aquarium owners, Kidd and Kidd
313 (1999) found that 47% of home aquarium owners reported relaxation as a benefit of keeping
314 aquaria, while all participants in a qualitative study of fish keepers reported feeling relaxed
315 while watching their fishes (Langfield and James, 2009). Other research has examined the
316 physiological effects of watching an aquarium. Katcher et al. (1983) found that blood
317 pressure was lower when experiencing an experimentally induced stressor (reading aloud)

³ “Duration” refers to the whole intervention period in weeks or months, “length” to the individual sessions in minutes or hours, and “intensity” to the number of sessions within the intervention period.

318 after participants observed an aquarium, while a lab-based study found that watching a
319 video of animals (fishes, birds or primates) prior to reading aloud was associated with lower
320 blood pressure than watching a soap opera or a blank screen (Wells, 2005).

321 Over the longer term, three studies conducted in specialised dementia units demonstrated
322 positive effects associated with the presence of fish aquaria in dining rooms. In the weeks
323 following installation of the tanks, residents were found to consume greater quantities of food
324 compared to before installation, leading to an improvement in body mass (Edwards and
325 Beck, 2002, 2013). Anecdotal reports from staff suggested these effects were due to the
326 aquaria having a calming effect on residents, which led them to exhibit fewer behavioural
327 symptoms (e.g. pacing, wandering) at mealtimes. In support of this hypothesis, a significant
328 reduction in behavioural and psychological symptoms was found among residents at 10
329 weeks post-installation compared to before installation (Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014). An
330 improvement was also found in job satisfaction among staff members, but it is unclear
331 whether this was due to the presence of the aquaria or the improvement in challenging
332 behaviours among residents (Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014).

333 Other research, however, has found only mixed support for the theory that fishes promote
334 relaxation. Katcher, Segal and Beck (1984) found that contemplation of an aquarium prior to
335 dental surgery increased comfort during treatment irrespective of whether the patient also
336 received hypnosis, whereas contemplation of a poster was effective only in combination with
337 hypnotic induction. Similarly, Barker, Rasmussen and Best (2003) reported that the
338 presence (*versus* absence) of aquaria in waiting rooms for patients undergoing
339 electroconvulsive therapy was associated with a trend ($p = 0.08$) towards lower self-reported
340 anxiety, and Gee et al. (2019) found that watching an aquarium containing live fishes, *versus*
341 an empty aquarium or one containing only plants, positively influenced perceptions of
342 relaxation, mood and anxiety. However, none of these studies found evidence of an effect
343 for physiological outcomes (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984, Barker, Rasmussen and Best,
344 2003, Gee et al., 2019). Furthermore, DeSchrive and Riddick (1990) found no evidence that

345 watching a live fish aquarium had any greater impact on physiological outcomes (heart rate,
346 skin temperature and muscle tension) during a reading aloud task, than did watching a fish
347 video or a placebo video of television lines and static.

348 Although findings are somewhat inconclusive, there may be circumstances where interaction
349 with ornamental fishes is advantageous compared to interaction with other companion
350 animal types due to lower levels of risk. As there is no physical contact between humans and
351 ornamental fishes, threats to physical health are much smaller than with other animals, and
352 although there is potential for zoonotic pathogens (e.g. *Mycobacterium marinum*) to be
353 transmitted *via* contact with fishes or aquarium water, this risk is very small and can be
354 effectively minimised by practicing good hygiene and using protective equipment (e.g.
355 waterproof gloves) during tank maintenance (Brodie, Biley and Shewring, 2002). Other
356 species frequently present within aquaria (e.g. anemones, corals) can produce toxins that
357 are damaging to human health (Bernasconi et al., 2012, Wood, Alexis, et al., 2018), but
358 these cases are extremely rare and artificial tank decorations provide a risk-free alternative.
359 No significant risks exist with regards to aggression or allergies, although individuals could
360 experience fish-related phobias, and accidental injury may occur in the event of aquarium
361 breakage. Issues regarding the use of electrical equipment (e.g. heaters, filters, or lights)
362 also need to be appropriately considered to prevent risk of electrocution.

363 With regards to psychological well-being, research with home aquaria owners has
364 demonstrated that some individuals become distressed at the loss of their fishes, whereas
365 others accept this as part of keeping home aquaria and view their animals as largely
366 replaceable (Langfield and James, 2009). Financial and time commitments associated with
367 keeping ornamental fishes are highly variable; some aquarium set-ups are very expensive
368 and time consuming to maintain, but for the most part the costs associated with keeping
369 home aquaria are lower than those associated with keeping other companion animal types
370 (Ebener and Oh, 2017). The contained aquarium environment also reduces the need for
371 vulnerable clients to be supervised when around the animals (Edwards and Beck, 2002),

372 and the passive nature of the interaction allows most individuals to engage with the animals
373 irrespective of physical capacity (Langfield and James, 2009). Furthermore, as a constant
374 feature within the environment, fish aquaria are available at any time and for as long as
375 required, potentially offering greater flexibility in exposure than other forms of HAI (Barker,
376 Rasmussen and Best, 2003).

377 Finally, while the potential will always remain for humans to cause harm to ornamental
378 fishes, whether intentional or unintentional, the controlled environment of the aquarium and
379 the lack of physical contact between the humans and animals somewhat mitigates these
380 risks. Thus, if the individual responsible for the ornamental fishes has relevant knowledge
381 regarding their care and welfare needs, the risk of harm from interacting with humans should
382 be minimised for ornamental fishes kept in aquaria. Given these potential advantages, fish
383 aquaria may be an appropriate alternative in situations where interaction with other types of
384 companion animal is prohibited, risky or otherwise undesirable. It is therefore important to
385 understand whether engagement with ornamental fishes in aquaria leads to benefits similar
386 to other forms of HAI. Key to the development of this understanding is determining exactly
387 how interaction with companion animals is associated with human well-being.

388 At present, there is no single widely accepted and empirically supported framework to
389 explain the varying effects of HAI upon human health and well-being (Kruger and Serpell,
390 2010). Researchers in this field have, however, drawn upon theories and research from
391 other areas to provide an insight into the mechanisms underlying these effects. While full
392 discussion of these mechanisms is beyond the scope of this thesis, those of greatest
393 relevance to the current research are outlined below.

394 **1.5 Theories of human-animal interaction**

395 **1.5.1 Biophilia and distraction**

396 Human beings have long demonstrated a propensity towards forming relationships with non-
397 human animals (O’Haire, 2010), and research indicates that our species typically prefers
398 natural environments to urban settings (Ulrich, 1983, 1993, Joye and van den Berg, 2011).

399 The biophilia hypothesis (Wilson, 1984, Kellert and Wilson, 1993) provides a potential
400 explanation for these inclinations, postulating that because attending to other living things
401 was adaptive in our ancestral environment, humans have evolved an innate tendency to
402 focus on and affiliate with other forms of life. Natural environments and non-human animals
403 provided our ancestors with sources of food and water, could alert individuals to the
404 presence of dangers in the environment, and offered places of safety and shelter to escape
405 and recover from these threats (Katcher and Wilkins, 1993, Ulrich, 1993, Beck and Katcher,
406 2003, Grinde and Patil, 2009, Beetz, 2017). Consequently, the biophilia hypothesis suggests
407 that humans are biologically prepared (Seligman, 1970) to respond affectively to
408 components of nature (Ulrich, 1993). Although the term “biophilia” implies affection for nature
409 (Grinde and Patil, 2009), these affective responses may vary widely from attraction to
410 aversion; threat-relevant components (e.g. spiders, snakes, cliff edges) may elicit negative
411 affect and fear, whereas non-threatening components (e.g. natural environments providing
412 safety and shelter, calm and friendly animals) may elicit positive affect and happiness
413 (Kellert, 1993, 2012, Ulrich, 1993). Although it is now widely accepted that biophilia is poorly
414 defined as a concept, lacks falsifiability, and that biophilic responses are likely influenced by
415 individual learning and culture (Beck and Katcher, 2003, Grinde and Patil, 2009, Joye and
416 De Block, 2011, Amiot and Bastian, 2015), theories and research based upon the concept of
417 biophilia may be useful in understanding the observed benefits of interacting with companion
418 animals.

419 One way in which biophilic tendencies may promote human well-being is through the
420 mechanism of distraction, as research has suggested that animals may capture human
421 attention more readily than other stimuli. Young children have been found to preferentially
422 attend to images or videos of animals over those of non-living objects (DeLoache, Bloom
423 Pickard and LoBue, 2011), while infants and their parents show greater interest in live (but
424 caged) animals, compared to toys which resemble those animals (Lobue et al., 2013).
425 Similarly, adults are found to more rapidly identify changes in the position of animate (human

426 or animal) versus inanimate objects such as plants, vehicles or buildings (New, Cosmides
427 and Tooby, 2007), while studies using point-light displays⁴ have demonstrated that infants
428 preferentially attend to biological motion over other forms of movement (e.g. random
429 movement, movement of inanimate objects) (Simion, Regolin and Bulf, 2008, DeLoache,
430 Bloom Pickard and LoBue, 2011). These findings suggest that movement in animals may be
431 especially effective at capturing human attention, and thus, interacting with companion
432 animals may promote human well-being by diverting attention away from negative
433 experiences or emotional states. This distraction effect is not, however, unique to interacting
434 with companion animals; other stimuli may have an equal or greater effect depending on
435 individual preferences (Beetz, 2017, Serpell et al., 2017).

436 Alternatively, biophilic tendencies may promote human well-being through what has been
437 referred to as the 'biophilia-effect' (Julius et al., 2013, Beetz, 2017). This theory suggests
438 that being around calm or resting animals can lead to reduced physiological arousal and a
439 shift towards greater relaxation in humans, because the behaviour of animals is indicative of
440 the presence or absence of threats in the environment (Julius et al., 2013, Beetz, 2017).

441 While this theory refers specifically to interactions with companion animals, there are clear
442 parallels with Stress Recovery Theory (Ulrich, 1983, Ulrich et al., 1991), which posits a
443 similar mechanism in relation to unthreatening nature more broadly (see section 1.6.2. for
444 further details). Both distraction and the biophilia-effect may be of greatest relevance in the
445 context of AAI and brief interactions with companion animals, where the aim is to provide
446 alleviation from unpleasant states, such as anxiety, pain or negative affect (Beetz, 2017).

447 However, a recent study which required participants to complete brief questionnaires at
448 random intervals throughout the day over a 5-day period found that the passive presence of
449 a companion animal was associated with reduced negative affect, suggesting that the
450 presence of a calm, friendly animal may act as a buffer against negative states (Janssens et

⁴ Point-light displays are representations of motion made up of dots of light. They are created by either attaching lights to the joints of an individual (or animal) and filming in darkness, or by editing videos to similar effect (DeLoache, Bloom Pickard and LoBue, 2011).

451 al., 2020). As both acute and chronic stressors can have deleterious effects on human
452 health (Krantz and McCeney, 2002, Glaser and Kiecolt-Glaser, 2005), this may have the
453 potential to promote human well-being over the longer term, perhaps explaining the apparent
454 link between companion animal guardianship and improved human health.

455 In keeping with these ideas, there is evidence that ornamental fishes can readily capture and
456 maintain human attention. Katcher, Segal and Beck (1984) for instance, found that viewing a
457 fish aquarium before dental surgery was associated with greater comfort during the
458 procedure irrespective of whether participants also received hypnosis; as viewing a poster
459 was only effective in combination with hypnotic induction, this finding suggests that watching
460 fishes swim may have a hypnotic or mesmerising quality which helps individuals to feel
461 relaxed. Research with home aquaria owners supports this notion, with some individuals
462 reporting that “watching movements” is a beneficial aspect of keeping home aquaria (Kidd
463 and Kidd, 1999). Furthermore, Langfield and James (2009) found that stress reduction was
464 reported as a positive aspect of keeping fishes, but only in relation to fishes kept in tanks; as
465 fishes kept in ponds would presumably be more difficult to watch, this suggests the stress-
466 reducing effects of ornamental fishes may be related specifically to their movement. It is
467 noteworthy, however, that in most experimental studies, participants are specifically
468 instructed to interact with the fishes in some manner (e.g. Buttelman and Röpke, 2014,
469 Sanchez et al., 2015). In contrast, Barker, Rasmussen and Best (2003) gave participants no
470 instructions regarding the aquaria, and did not find a significant effect of the presence of an
471 aquarium on anxiety, fear or depression among patients awaiting electroconvulsive therapy
472 treatment. Therefore, if ornamental fishes do provide alleviation from negative states, it is
473 unclear whether this effect occurs spontaneously or whether some form of instruction is
474 required.

475 **1.5.2 Attachment and social support**

476 Alternative perspectives take into consideration the social aspects of interaction with
477 companion animals, with these theories perhaps being of greatest relevance in the context

478 of companion animal guardianship. Attachment theory (Bowlby, 1969, 1973, 1980) proposes
479 that when infants are born, they are biologically driven to form a strong emotional attachment
480 with a primary caregiver or 'attachment figure' (usually their mother). This attachment bond
481 is characterised by the presence of *proximity seeking* behaviours and *separation distress*, as
482 well as the provision of unique emotional support which cannot be replicated in other
483 interpersonal relationships. Specifically, attachment figures are argued to provide a *secure*
484 *base* from which the infant can begin to explore the world, and a *safe haven* to provide
485 comfort and support should they perceive a potential threat to their well-being (Ainsworth
486 and Bell, 1970, Ainsworth, Bell and Stayton, 1971). Early experiences with attachment
487 figures are important in the development of an individual's attachment style (Mikulincer and
488 Shaver, 2013); where the primary caregiver is responsive to the infant's needs a secure
489 attachment bond will develop, whereas inconsistent or insensitive caregiving may result in
490 the infant becoming insecurely attached (Ainsworth, Bell and Stayton, 1971). This
491 attachment style continues to develop across the lifespan as the individual experiences
492 further attachments, such as with siblings or romantic partners (Hazan and Shaver, 1987,
493 Ainsworth, 1989, Mikulincer and Shaver, 2007, 2013). Secure attachments are associated
494 with a range of benefits to well-being, including more positive internal working models
495 (mental representations) of the self and others, greater efficacy in regulating emotions and
496 seeking support, and generally more favourable mental health (Maunder and Hunter, 2001,
497 Mikulincer and Shaver, 2007, 2013, 2019, Zilcha-Mano, Mikulincer and Shaver, 2011, 2012).

498 The application of attachment theory to human-animal relationships suggests that these
499 bonds may constitute attachments, as defined by attachment theory. For example, research
500 has shown that dogs display behaviours which indicate attachment to their guardians (Prato-
501 Previde et al., 2003, Palmer and Custance, 2008), and satisfy all four criteria of an
502 attachment figure for their guardians (Kurdek, 2008). Thus, both the individual and their
503 companion animal may serve as an attachment figure to provide feelings of comfort and
504 safety during times of uncertainty or stress (Beck and Madresh, 2008, Amiot and Bastian,

505 2015). Furthermore, the attachments formed with companion animals may be based on
506 different internal working models to those formed with people (Beck and Madresh, 2008),
507 meaning individuals with insecure attachment styles may find it easier to trust and seek
508 support from companion animals than they do from other people (Zilcha-Mano, Mikulincer
509 and Shaver, 2011, Beetz, Julius, et al., 2012), and this support may be preferred to that
510 provided by human attachment figures because it is unconditional and non-judgemental
511 (Kurdek, 2009a, 2009b, Meehan, Massavelli and Pachana, 2017). Oxytocin, a hormone
512 implicated in affiliative behaviours, may also be involved in these bonds; evidence has
513 indicated that levels of oxytocin increase following interaction with friendly dogs, while the
514 positive effects of HAI mirror those associated with oxytocin (Beetz, Uvnas-Moberg, et al.,
515 2012, Thielke and Udell, 2017, Powell et al., 2019). As oxytocin is released in response to
516 pleasant physical touch (Beetz, Uvnas-Moberg, et al., 2012), humans may benefit from
517 interaction with companion animals because physical contact is often prohibited with
518 humans but not animals (Beetz and Bales, 2016).

519 Companion animals may also provide an indirect source of social support by facilitating
520 interactions between individuals, an effect which has been referred to as 'social lubrication'
521 or the 'social catalyst effect' (McNicholas and Collis, 2000, Wells, 2009a, Beetz and Bales,
522 2016). Several studies have found evidence that the presence of a dog increases the
523 frequency of social interactions relative to being alone or walking with non-living objects
524 (Eddy, Hart and Boltz, 1988, Mader, Hart and Bergin, 1989, McNicholas and Collis, 2000,
525 Wells, 2004, Shyne et al., 2012). Puppies in particular appear to be effective at eliciting
526 positive social interactions, whereas dog breeds perceived as 'dangerous' (e.g. rottweilers,
527 pit bulls) may be more likely to elicit non-responses, indifference, or fear (Wells, 2004,
528 Gazzano et al., 2013), suggesting that the specific characteristics of the dog can play a role
529 in this effect. The presence of a dog may also improve an individual's prospects when
530 soliciting help from strangers (Guéguen and Ciccotti, 2008), and companion animals may
531 even play a role in the initiation of romantic relationships, with some individuals indicating

532 that the way their dog or cat responds to a potential romantic partner could influence
533 whether they choose to date that individual (Gray et al., 2015). In a series of studies, Wood
534 and colleagues demonstrated that companion animal guardianship is associated with higher
535 neighbourhood social capital and greater connections within the community (Wood, Giles-
536 Corti and Bulsara, 2005, Wood et al., 2007, 2015, 2017) adding further support for this social
537 catalyst effect. Furthermore, as these findings were not specific to those who kept dogs,
538 similar benefits may be experienced by those who keep other types of companion animal
539 (Wood et al., 2017).

540 With respect to ornamental fishes, there is some evidence that people who keep home
541 aquaria consider their fishes to be a source of companionship, and feel an emotional bond
542 towards these animals (Langfield and James, 2009). This suggests that attachment and
543 social support may play a role in the beneficial effects that fish aquaria have on human
544 health and well-being. Attachments are reciprocal relationships, however, and it is unclear
545 whether ornamental fishes kept as companion animals exhibit behaviours indicative of
546 attachment, such as proximity seeking or separation distress. Thus, while individuals may
547 believe there to be an emotional bond between themselves and their fishes, it is unclear
548 whether this constitutes a true attachment bond as described by attachment theory.

549 Evidence relating to fishes as social catalysts is equally lacking. Qualitative research and
550 anecdotal reports have suggested that ornamental fishes can become a talking point among
551 individuals (Riddick, 1985, DeSchriver and Riddick, 1990, Langfield and James, 2009) but
552 no quantitative research has explored this effect. Furthermore, in some cases the aquaria
553 were novel additions to the environment added for the purposes of the research (Riddick,
554 1985, DeSchriver and Riddick, 1990), and so it is unclear whether this social catalyst effect
555 would persist over time.

556 **1.5.3 The biopsychosocial model**

557 While these mechanisms are perhaps the most widely cited in academic literature, many
558 other theories have been proposed to explain the benefits of interacting with companion

559 animals (for example, see overviews by Kruger and Serpell, 2010, Beetz and Bales, 2016,
560 Beetz, 2017). One model, however, provides a potential framework for incorporating some –
561 or all – of these mechanisms. The biopsychosocial model (Engel, 1977) proposes that health
562 is a continuum influenced by interacting biological, psychological and social factors; changes
563 in one factor may influence the others and in turn impact health. For example, psychosocial
564 stressors may lead to physiological responses such as increased heart rate and blood
565 pressure, or reduced immune function. Ultimately, these responses may have a negative
566 effect on health, resulting in increased morbidity and mortality (Krantz and McCeney, 2002,
567 Glaser and Kiecolt-Glaser, 2005). Equally, however, some psychological and social factors
568 may have a protective influence on health; higher levels of social support for example, have
569 been linked to a reduced risk of cardiovascular disease (Krantz and McCeney, 2002). In the
570 context of this model, there are numerous ways in which interaction with companion animals
571 may impact human health. For example, owning a dog may lead to improved health through
572 increased physical activity, while companion animals may provide social support either
573 directly or indirectly, by acting as a social catalyst (Wells, 2009a, Chur-Hansen and
574 Winefield, 2013). Conversely, the grief associated with the loss of a companion animal may
575 have a detrimental effect upon human well-being (Chur-Hansen and Winefield, 2013). Thus,
576 while the biopsychosocial model provides a potential framework for integrating multiple
577 theories, it also highlights the likelihood that no one mechanism can account for the diverse
578 effects of HAI. Thus, when considering whether and how ornamental fishes may promote
579 human well-being, it is important to consider how the context in which these interactions
580 occur may influence results.

581 **1.6 The restorative value of nature: An alternative perspective**

582 **1.6.1 Animals in nature**

583 The discussion thus far has focused on the benefits of interacting with domesticated
584 companion animals,⁵ but this is not the only context in which humans may benefit from
585 contact with other species. A substantial body of research has explored the effects that
586 interacting with nature can have upon human health and well-being, with typically positive
587 results (for example, see reviews by Grinde and Patil, 2009, Abraham, Sommerhalder and
588 Abel, 2010, Bowler et al., 2010, Russell et al., 2013, Haluza, Schönbauer and Cervinka,
589 2014, Capaldi et al., 2015, Tillmann et al., 2018). Although much of this research has
590 focused on “green” (plants, trees, grass etc.) and/or “blue” (coastlines, lakes, rivers etc.)
591 aspects of the natural environment, some researchers have also incorporated non-human
592 animals into their conceptualisations of nature (e.g. Russell et al., 2013, Capaldi et al.,
593 2015). Furthermore, as many studies take place within real-life natural, urban or urban green
594 environments – such as forests, parks, nature reserves, gardens, city streets and residential
595 areas (Bowler et al., 2010) – controlling for the presence or absence of wildlife is an
596 impossibility. Thus, it is plausible that encounters with wildlife may contribute to the
597 beneficial effects of nature on human well-being.

598 Although few studies have directly explored the role that wildlife encounters play in human
599 well-being (Bell et al., 2018), research findings support the premise that these interactions
600 have beneficial effects. For instance, research has indicated that many people feed wild
601 birds because doing so brings them pleasure (Galbraith et al., 2014), and that watching wild
602 birds feeding is associated with increased relaxation and connectedness to nature (Cox and
603 Gaston, 2016); birdsong may also play a role in the beneficial effects of nature exposure
604 (Ratcliffe, Gatersleben and Sowden, 2013). Among a sample of nursing home residents
605 given the responsibility of caring for a bird feeder, improvements in self-reported control,

⁵ Farm-based interventions which involve animal husbandry may also be considered within the remit of AAI, however, as these interventions often include other activities such as horticulture, they are not discussed further here; for a review of farm-based interventions see Iancu et al. (2015).

606 happiness, and activity were observed, while no changes were observed among residents
607 who did not receive such an opportunity (Banziger and Roush, 1983). Other research has
608 explored how variation in the biodiversity of wildlife populations can impact human well-
609 being; several studies have identified an association between increased species richness in
610 wild birds and greater psychological well-being (Fuller et al., 2007, Luck et al., 2011,
611 Dallimer et al., 2012, Wolf et al., 2017), while coastal environments with higher levels of
612 perceived biodiversity are found to have increased emotional and cognitive restoration
613 potential, especially where the animals display more ‘fascinating’ behaviours (e.g. flocking
614 vs. sleeping) (White et al., 2017). In fact, research has indicated that for some individuals,
615 wildlife encounters are a key motivation for visiting coastal environments (de Bell et al.,
616 2017), while qualitative research has shown that interactions with wildlife are associated with
617 a range of benefits to human psychological well-being (Bell et al., 2018).

618 Interacting with ornamental fishes in aquaria may not be equivalent to interacting with
619 animals in nature, but there is one key similarity between these forms of interaction which
620 may be relevant in understanding the role that ornamental fishes have in human health and
621 well-being. Namely, both are largely reliant on visual exposure. The vast majority of research
622 relating to the benefits of companion animals has involved species that interact with humans
623 through physical touch. Thus, these findings may not translate to interaction with fishes in
624 aquaria and – if ornamental fishes are found to promote human well-being – current theories
625 regarding the effects of interaction with companion animals may not be sufficient to fully
626 explain these findings. Consideration of theoretical perspectives relating to the effects of
627 interaction with wildlife (and nature more broadly) may therefore, be useful in understanding
628 the role of ornamental fishes in human health and well-being.

629 **1.6.2 Theories of restoration**

630 Two theories are dominant in the literature regarding the effects of nature on human well-
631 being: Stress Recovery Theory (SRT; Ulrich, 1983, Ulrich et al., 1991) and Attention
632 Restoration Theory (ART; Kaplan, 1995). Reflecting the focus of research in this area, both

633 theories predominantly focus on natural or 'green' environments, but may also be applied to
634 research regarding the effects of wildlife and biodiversity. Furthermore, both theories operate
635 on the premise that the benefits of nature are most evident for individuals in need of
636 restoration, either due to the experience of psychophysiological stress (SRT) or mental
637 fatigue (ART).

638 *1.6.2.1 Stress Recovery Theory*

639 The premise of SRT is similar to that of the biophilia hypothesis (Ulrich, 1993). However,
640 while biophilia refers to a broad range of affiliative responses to different aspects of natural
641 environments, SRT focuses on the restorative effects of exposure to 'unthreatening' nature.
642 Central to this theory is the understanding of stress as the psychological, physiological, and
643 behavioural response to any situation which challenges or risks well-being. According to
644 proponents of SRT, individuals experiencing stress will find greater recovery in
645 unthreatening natural environments compared to other settings, because these
646 environments immediately and automatically elicit a positive emotional response which acts
647 to rapidly decrease the heightened state of physiological arousal associated with stress
648 (Ulrich et al., 1991). This response is argued to have evolved because in the ancestral
649 environment rapid recovery from psychophysiological stress would have been adaptive, and
650 natural environments would have supported this process through the provision of refuge and
651 other physical resources (e.g. food, water) (Ulrich, 1983, 1993). Furthermore, as stress can
652 also lead to a decline in cognitive function, restoration *via* stress recovery may also lead to
653 gains in cognitive performance (Ulrich et al., 1991).

654 *1.6.2.2 Attention Restoration Theory*

655 ART (Kaplan, 1995) provides a complementary perspective which centres on the concept of
656 directed attention, the mechanism through which individuals voluntarily maintain focus on a
657 specific task while inhibiting their response to outside distractions. Directed attention
658 requires effort and as such is susceptible to fatigue, leading to additional negative
659 consequences, such as irritability, inaccuracy and poor decision-making (Herzog, Maguire

660 and Nebel, 2003). ART suggests, however, that directed attention resources may be
661 restored where an individual engages in involuntary attention, or *fascination*; as natural
662 environments are intrinsically fascinating, exposure to nature can lead to recovery of
663 directed attention resources and thus, alleviate the negative consequences associated with
664 directed attention fatigue (Kaplan, 1995). Furthermore, natural environments are argued to
665 provide a specific form of fascination – *soft fascination* – in which attention is caught, but
666 opportunity for reflection remains. This is thought to enhance the restorative experience, and
667 contrasts with *hard fascination* which demands full attention and does not allow opportunity
668 for reflection (Kaplan and Berman, 2010).

669 While fascination is a necessary component of the restoration, ART suggests that three
670 additional components play important roles in the restoration process (Kaplan, 1995, Kaplan
671 and Berman, 2010); *being away* refers to the ability of environments to promote a sense of
672 escape, so that the individual can cease to focus on the thoughts demanding directed
673 attention resources, *extent* refers to the ability of the environment to engage the mind and
674 provide a sense of being connected the larger world, and *compatibility* refers to an
675 environment which supports the individual's purpose, so that they can carry out activities in a
676 comfortable and effortless manner (Kaplan, 1995, Kaplan and Berman, 2010). Although
677 theoretically any environment can provide these four components – fascination, being away,
678 extent and compatibility – Kaplan (1995) argues that they are more abundant in natural
679 compared to urban environments, thus potentially explaining the link between nature and
680 improved well-being. Furthermore, even very brief nature experiences – such as the view
681 through an office window – may support restoration from directed attention fatigue (Kaplan,
682 1993; Kaplan, 1992).

683 Although both theories of restoration focus on exposure to natural environments, these
684 frameworks may also be applied to visual interactions with animals. With respect to SRT,
685 this theory is largely unspecific with regards to what constitutes “unthreatening” nature (Joye
686 and van den Berg, 2011), and so encounters with unthreatening animal species may

687 contribute to the stress-reducing effects of natural environments. This parallels with the
688 biophilia-effect outlined above (see section 1.5.1). Similarly, ART provides little clarity over
689 which aspects of natural environments promote fascination (Valtchanov and Ellard, 2015,
690 Joye and Dewitte, 2018), and thus animals may contribute to the fascinating quality of these
691 settings (Kaplan, 1992, 1995).

692 **1.6.3 Ornamental fishes and restoration**

693 One study has specifically explored the effects of fishes within the context of restoration.
694 This research found that viewing a public aquarium exhibit was associated with reduced
695 physiological arousal and improved mood across the viewing period, as would be predicted
696 by SRT (Cracknell et al., 2016). Although these effects were observed even when the exhibit
697 contained no fish species, greater levels of biodiversity were associated with larger effects
698 for some outcomes, suggesting the presence of fishes contributed to a more restorative
699 experience. Furthermore, visitors to the aquarium were found to watch the exhibit for longer
700 periods when more fish species were present, which may be indicative of greater levels of
701 fascination. This is supported by findings from studies involving home aquaria, which have
702 shown that the addition of an aquarium to a window display increases attention from
703 passers-by (Windhager et al., 2011), and that watching fishes swim may have a
704 mesmerising quality (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984). As public aquaria provide a more
705 immersive experience than home aquaria, however, these environments may more readily
706 provide access to other components of restoration (e.g. being away, extent). Thus, it is
707 unclear whether these findings will fully translate to smaller scale home aquaria.
708 Furthermore, theories of restoration would suggest that if viewing ornamental fishes provides
709 an opportunity for restoration, improvements would be seen in cognitive performance;
710 however, no studies to date have examined the effects of aquaria (home or public) on
711 outcomes relating to cognitive performance (Cracknell et al., 2018). Thus, further research is
712 needed to understand whether fish aquaria may promote human well-being through these
713 restorative processes.

714 **1.7 Conclusion**

715 To summarise, there is evidence to suggest that interaction with companion animals may
716 promote human well-being. Although this research has typically focused on animals that
717 interact with humans through physical touch (such as dogs), interaction with ornamental
718 fishes may also have positive effects. In addition, the presence of fish aquaria may be
719 advantageous over interactions with other companion animals, as the contained nature of an
720 aquarium reduces the risk of harm to both parties. Therefore, fish aquaria may be a suitable
721 alternative where other forms of HAI are unsafe or otherwise undesirable. Currently,
722 however, there is limited evidence regarding the role of ornamental fishes in human well-
723 being. Therefore, the primary aim of this thesis was to improve understanding of whether
724 and how engagement with ornamental fishes influences human well-being. In response to
725 the COVID-19 pandemic, the secondary aim was to understand the impact that companion
726 animals, and in particular ornamental fishes, had upon human well-being within the context
727 of the pandemic and ongoing restrictions. These aims were achieved through the following
728 objectives:

- 729 1. Systematically review current evidence relating to the psychological and physiological
730 effects of interacting with fish in aquaria (Chapter 2).
- 731 2. Based on the findings of this review, investigate the influence of ornamental fishes on
732 well-being in the workplace⁶ (Chapters 3 and 4).
- 733 3. Examine the relationships between companion animal guardianship and loneliness and
734 mental well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic, with a focus on ornamental fishes
735 (Chapter 5).
- 736 4. Examine the influence of companion animals on the well-being and productivity of
737 individuals working from home (Chapter 6).

⁶ Chapter 2 also identified care homes and nurseries as settings where current research was lacking but where fish aquaria may be appropriate. Ethical approval for these studies was obtained prior to the start of the pandemic but the studies were subsequently cancelled as it was not possible to complete data collection in these two settings. However, protocols for these studies are attached in Appendices A and B and may be of use for future research in HAI.

738 The final chapter provides a summary and discussion of the key findings from these studies,
739 how they relate to existing literature, and suggestions for future research.

740 **Chapter 2.**

741 **The effects of interacting with fish in aquaria on**
742 **human health and well-being: A systematic review**

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746 (7), p.e0220524.

747 **2.1 Abstract**

748 Most research into the health benefits of HAI has focused on species that interact with
749 humans in a physical capacity, such as dogs. This may be unsuitable for certain populations
750 for reasons including accessibility, and the risk of negative consequences to both the person
751 and the animal. However, some research has associated viewing fish aquaria with positive
752 well-being outcomes; as there is no physical contact with the animal, this form of interaction
753 carries less risk. At present, little is known about the specific benefits of human-fish
754 interaction. Therefore, the aim of this review was to explore current evidence relating to the
755 psychological and physiological benefits of interacting with fish in aquaria. Systematic
756 searches were conducted to identify relevant primary research of any design. All forms of
757 interaction were considered, including keeping fish as companion animals and fish
758 aquarium-based interventions. “Non-live” alternatives, such as videos, were also considered.
759 This review was conducted according to a registered protocol (PROSPERO ID:
760 CRD42018090466). Nineteen studies were included. Two provided tentative evidence that
761 keeping home aquaria is associated with relaxation. The remaining studies involved novel
762 interactions with fish in home or public aquaria. Outcomes relating to anxiety, relaxation
763 and/or physiological stress were commonly assessed; evidence was mixed with both
764 positive and null findings. Preliminary support was found for positive effects on mood, pain,
765 nutritional intake and body weight, but not loneliness. All studies had methodological issues
766 and risk of bias was either high or unclear. Review findings suggest that interacting with fish
767 in aquaria has the potential to benefit human well-being, although research on this topic is
768 currently limited. Future research should aim to address gaps in the evidence, such as
769 whether and how the type of human-fish interaction can influence well-being outcomes.
770 Researchers should also aim to address the methodological concerns highlighted in this
771 review.

772 **2.2 Introduction**

773 Interacting with non-human animals (hereafter “animals”) has been associated with a range
774 of well-being benefits among humans. Companion animal guardianship has been linked with
775 improved physical and psychological outcomes, including lower blood pressure (Allen,
776 Shykoff and Izzo, 2001, Friedmann et al., 2013), reduced risk of cardiovascular disease and
777 lower rates of mortality (Levine et al., 2013, Mubanga et al., 2017), reduced loneliness
778 (Stanley et al., 2014), and increased emotional support during mental health crisis (Brooks et
779 al., 2018). In fact, research has indicated that many people choose to keep companion
780 animals for reasons associated with well-being, such as companionship, emotional support,
781 and improved physical health (Staats, Wallace and Anderson, 2008, Powell et al., 2018).
782 Similarly, animal-assisted interventions (AAI) are initiated with the specific purpose of
783 improving one or more aspects of human well-being; they include goal-oriented animal-
784 assisted therapies delivered by healthcare professionals, and animal-assisted activities
785 which are often volunteer-led and may lack specific treatment goals (Kruger and Serpell,
786 2010). These interventions have been used to support improvements in physical,
787 psychological, and behavioural outcomes for a wide range of populations across the lifespan
788 (Nimer and Lundahl, 2007, Kamioka et al., 2014, Maujean, Pepping and Kendall, 2015, Bert
789 et al., 2016, Charry-Sánchez, Pradilla and Talero-Gutiérrez, 2018).

790 Despite these positive findings, research into the benefits of HAI is far from conclusive.
791 Other studies have shown no relationship, or a negative relationship, between keeping
792 companion animals and physical or mental health outcomes (Parker et al., 2010, Amiot and
793 Bastian, 2015, Bao and Schreer, 2016, Torske et al., 2017, Ding et al., 2018, Mueller, Gee
794 and Bures, 2018). Furthermore, as most research in this area is correlational it is difficult to
795 determine causality; better health may increase the likelihood of adopting a companion
796 animal, rather than the reverse (Herzog, 2011), or health and companion animal
797 guardianship may be linked by other factors, such as sociodemographic characteristics or
798 health-related behaviours (Müllersdorf et al., 2010, Saunders et al., 2017, Mueller, Gee and

799 Bures, 2018). Similarly, while AAI are commonly perceived as beneficial, especially among
800 those with a positive attitude towards companion animals, some authors suggest that these
801 benefits have been overstated (Crossman and Kazdin, 2018). In reality, research concerning
802 these interventions is frequently anecdotal or descriptive in nature, with high levels of
803 heterogeneity in factors such as the type of animal, the nature of the interaction, and the
804 setting (Kazdin, 2017, Serpell et al., 2017). Methodological issues are also commonplace
805 and include the absence of appropriate comparison groups, reliance on small samples,
806 failure to randomise participants to conditions, and a lack of blinding for both participants and
807 assessors (Chur-Hansen, Stern and Winefield, 2010, Kazdin, 2017, Serpell et al., 2017,
808 Friedmann and Gee, 2019). It is therefore difficult to draw firm conclusions about the efficacy
809 of these interventions (Chur-Hansen, Stern and Winefield, 2010, Kazdin, 2017, Friedmann
810 and Gee, 2019).

811 These inconsistencies are further confounded by a lack of consensus about the mechanisms
812 through which HAI may improve human well-being (Kruger and Serpell, 2010). Researchers
813 have often referred to the biophilia hypothesis (Wilson, 1984, Kellert and Wilson, 1993),
814 which proposes that humans have an innate affiliation with other forms of life. This
815 perspective suggests that because human evolution occurred almost exclusively in natural
816 environments, people are predisposed to respond positively to aspects of nature that would
817 have increased fitness in the ancestral environment, and negatively to those which would
818 have decreased fitness (Ulrich, 1993). For example, people typically respond positively to
819 natural landscapes providing sources of food, water or shelter, and negatively to animals
820 which pose a threat, such as spiders or snakes (Ulrich, 1993). Although the biophilia
821 hypothesis has been criticised for offering too broad a perspective and for lacking falsifiability
822 (Joye and De Block, 2011), researchers have drawn on these ideas to develop theories with
823 more explanatory power. For example, the biophilia-effect suggests that because the
824 behaviour of animals is indicative of the presence or absence of threats in the environment,

825 interaction with a calm or friendly animal may support human well-being by promoting
826 relaxation and reducing physiological arousal (Julius et al., 2013, Beetz, 2017).

827 Other popular explanations centre on the social support provided by companion animals. In
828 the context of attachment theory (Bowlby, 1969, 1973, 1980) for example, humans are
829 argued to form bonds with their companion animals which are comparable to those formed
830 within close interpersonal relationships (Beck and Madresh, 2008). This theory suggests that
831 humans form strong emotional attachments with certain individuals, or “attachment figures”.
832 These attachments are characterised by the presence of proximity seeking behaviours,
833 distress at separation, and the provision of unique emotional support that cannot be
834 replicated within other interpersonal relationships. Although attachment theory originally
835 focused on the relationship between an infant and their primary caregiver (usually their
836 mother), it was later expanded to incorporate the bonds which form in other close
837 relationships, such as with siblings or romantic partners (Hazan and Shaver, 1987,
838 Ainsworth, 1989). More recently, attachment theory has been applied to human-animal
839 relationships, with findings suggesting that both the human and animal can serve as the
840 attachment figure and provide feelings of comfort and safety during times of uncertainty or
841 stress (Beck and Madresh, 2008, Amiot and Bastian, 2015). Furthermore, support provided
842 by animals may be particularly effective, as it is unconditional and non-judgemental
843 (Meehan, Massavelli and Pachana, 2017), and because physical touch – an important
844 component of emotional support – is often discouraged with other humans but not with
845 animals (Beetz and Bales, 2016).

846 Alternatively, HAI may operate *via* distraction, whereby attention is diverted away from a
847 perceived stressor to lessen the experience of negative mental states; this may be of most
848 relevance in the context of AAI (Serpell et al., 2017). Research has indicated that young
849 children preferentially attend to images or videos of animals compared to non-living objects
850 (DeLoache, Bloom Pickard and LoBue, 2011), and will choose to interact with real (but
851 caged) animals over toys resembling those animals (Lobue et al., 2013). Similarly, adults

852 have been found to more rapidly identify changes in the location of living targets (animals
853 and people), compared to inanimate objects (New, Cosmides and Tooby, 2007). These
854 findings suggest that animals may be particularly effective at attracting human attention.
855 However, animals are not unique in being an effective source of distraction, and so similar
856 benefits may be achieved through the use of alternative, and possibly more cost effective,
857 stimuli (Beetz and Bales, 2016, Serpell et al., 2017).

858 This brief overview is by no means exhaustive and several other theories have been
859 proposed (Kruger and Serpell, 2010, Beetz and Bales, 2016, Beetz, 2017). Despite these
860 divergent approaches, however, one model provides a framework which may potentially
861 incorporate some, or all, of the above discussed mechanisms. The biopsychosocial model
862 (Engel, 1977) proposes that health is a continuum influenced by interacting biological,
863 psychological and social factors; changes in one factor may influence the others and in turn
864 impact health. For example, psychosocial stresses may lead to physiological responses
865 including increased heart rate and blood pressure, or reduced immune function. Ultimately,
866 these responses may have a negative effect on health, resulting in increased morbidity and
867 mortality (Krantz and McCeney, 2002, Glaser and Kiecolt-Glaser, 2005). Equally, however,
868 some psychological and social factors may have a protective influence on health; higher
869 levels of social support for example, have been linked to a reduced risk of cardiovascular
870 disease (Krantz and McCeney, 2002). In the context of this model, there are numerous ways
871 in which interaction with companion animals may impact human health. For example, owning
872 a dog may lead to improved health through increased physical activity, while animals may
873 provide social support either directly, or indirectly by facilitating social interactions with other
874 individuals (Wells, 2009a, Chur-Hansen and Winefield, 2013). Conversely, however, the
875 grief associated with the loss of a companion animal may have a detrimental effect on
876 human well-being (Chur-Hansen and Winefield, 2013). As animals may be considered
877 providers of social support, this may potentially explain the link between companion animal
878 ownership and improved health.

879 Thus, while the biopsychosocial model provides a potential framework for integrating
880 multiple theories, it also highlights the likelihood that no one mechanism can account for the
881 diverse effects of HAI. One area which warrants further consideration is whether the
882 observed benefits are influenced by the type of animal involved in the interaction (Ebener
883 and Oh, 2017, Kazdin, 2017). Multiple reviews and meta-analyses have noted that dogs are
884 the animal most frequently involved in AAI (although other species such as horses are also
885 commonly involved) (Nimer and Lundahl, 2007, Bert et al., 2016, Ebener and Oh, 2017).
886 Similarly, much research into companion animals has focused on those animals that can
887 interact physically with humans, such as dogs and cats (Langfield and James, 2009, Levine
888 et al., 2013). This type of interaction may not, however, be suitable among all populations.
889 For instance, people in rented accommodation are often restricted in the types of companion
890 animal they may keep in their home, and physical interactions may be inappropriate for
891 people with declining health or limited physical capacity (Langfield and James, 2009).
892 Similarly, dog-assisted (or similar) interventions often rely on volunteer services (Ebener and
893 Oh, 2017) and may require supervision of the client and animal to minimise risk, which can
894 lead to infrequent and inconsistent exposure (Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Edwards,
895 Beck and Lim, 2014). Issues may also arise where there is potential for aggression from the
896 animal, where individuals have allergies, compromised immune systems, or phobias, or
897 where contact with the animal could lead to accidental injury (e.g. scratches, falls) (Lefebvre
898 et al., 2008, Murthy et al., 2015, Ebener and Oh, 2017). Animal welfare is also a concern, as
899 some clients may behave aggressively or unpredictably towards the animal, or the animal
900 may become stressed during the interaction (Hatch, 2007, Ebener and Oh, 2017). Therefore,
901 research into the effects of HAI with less physically interactive animals is needed to
902 determine whether benefits may be experienced.

903 One form of HAI which has attracted relatively little investigation is the role of fish aquaria.
904 Early research indicated a link between viewing fish in aquaria and benefits such as reduced
905 blood pressure and increased relaxation (Katcher et al., 1983, Riddick, 1985, Cole and

906 Gawlinski, 1995), perhaps contributing to the widespread notion that aquaria are beneficial in
907 healthcare settings (Cracknell et al., 2017). More recently, research has linked interaction
908 with fishes in aquaria to outcomes such as reduced anxiety (Buttelmann and Röpcke,
909 2014), increased tolerance to pain (Sanchez et al., 2015), and improvements in nutritional
910 intake and body weight among residents of specialised dementia units (Edwards and Beck,
911 2002, 2013). As with HAI research more broadly, the mechanisms underlying these benefits
912 are unclear. Research with people who keep home aquaria has indicated that some
913 individuals consider their fishes to be a source of companionship, and feel an emotional
914 bond with the animals (Langfield and James, 2009); this suggests social support and
915 attachment may play a role in the beneficial effects of human-fish interaction. However, while
916 research has shown the presence of attachment behaviours in other human-animal
917 relationships, such as with dogs (Prato-Previde et al., 2003, Palmer and Custance, 2008), it
918 is not evident that fishes exhibit behaviours such as proximity seeking or separation distress.
919 Thus, while individuals may believe there to be an emotional bond between themselves and
920 their fishes, it is unclear whether this constitutes a true attachment bond as described by
921 attachment theory (Bowlby, 1969, 1973, 1980). Alternatively, watching fishes swimming may
922 simply be a source of distraction; this is supported by research which has shown positive
923 physiological effects associated with viewing videos of animals, including fish (Wells, 2005).

924 An alternative perspective still comes from theories concerning the restorative value of
925 nature. These theories suggest that exposure to unthreatening nature can help restore
926 depleted cognitive resources, and support rapid emotional and physiological recovery from
927 stressful events (Berto, 2014). Although most of this research has focused on natural or
928 “green” landscapes, the role that encounters with wildlife play in human well-being has been
929 explored. For example, research has suggested that many people feed wild birds because
930 doing so brings them pleasure (Galbraith et al., 2014), while watching wild birds feeding is
931 associated with increased relaxation and connectedness to nature (Cox and Gaston, 2016).
932 Similarly, improvements in self-reported control, happiness, and activity were observed

933 among a sample of nursing home residents who were given the responsibility of caring for a
934 bird feeder, while no changes were observed among residents who did not receive such an
935 opportunity (Banziger and Roush, 1983). Furthermore, research has suggested that for
936 some individuals, wildlife encounters are a key motivation for visiting natural (coastal)
937 environments (de Bell et al., 2017), and are associated with a range of benefits to human
938 psychological well-being (Bell et al., 2018). Given that the ways in which people interact with
939 birds and other forms of wildlife are similar to the ways in which people interact with fishes in
940 aquaria (i.e. the interaction is largely visual), it may be that watching fishes swimming
941 promotes human well-being because this activity provides exposure to unthreatening nature,
942 leading to restoration.

943 Irrespective of the mechanism, these findings suggest that human-fish interactions may be a
944 viable alternative to more commonly researched forms of HAI. Furthermore, aquaria may
945 overcome some of the issues associated with these forms of interaction. As a constant
946 feature within the environment, fish aquaria are available to the client at any time and for as
947 long as required, thus may provide greater flexibility in exposure than AAI which rely on
948 visitation programmes (Barker, Rasmussen, et al., 2003). Even other types of resident
949 animal cannot provide constant interaction, as this would be detrimental to their welfare
950 (Ebener and Oh, 2017). The monetary cost associated with installation and upkeep of a fish
951 tank is also much smaller than that associated with other companion animals (Ebener and
952 Oh, 2017), although regular maintenance of the aquarium is needed, and requires an
953 individual with knowledge of the necessary processes to ensure the welfare of the fishes is
954 not compromised. Aside from the person responsible for maintaining the fish tanks, however,
955 the passive nature of viewing fishes in an aquarium means that even individuals with limited
956 physical capacity are able to interact with the animals (Langfield and James, 2009). There
957 are no significant risks from aggression or allergies, and fewer risks associated with
958 accidental injury due to the lack of physical contact with the animal (although possible injury
959 could be sustained while installing or maintaining the tank, or if someone or something

960 damages the tank, causing a break). While there is a small risk of bacterial infection
961 associated with keeping home aquaria, this is rare and requires physical contact with the
962 fishes or water, so can be effectively minimised through careful hygiene practices (Brodie,
963 Biley and Shewring, 2002).

964 Despite the potential benefits, however, research in this area is limited, and to date only one
965 review has sought to explore the potential benefits of fish aquaria to human health and well-
966 being (Cracknell et al., 2018). However, this narrative review explored these benefits in the
967 context of restorative environments and biodiversity, with a focus on the value of public
968 aquariums; although there was reference to research conducted with home aquaria, this
969 overview was not comprehensive. Furthermore, consideration should be given to the quality
970 and strength of evidence when drawing conclusions from existing research findings; for this
971 purpose, a systematic review of the literature is needed.

972 **2.2.1 Review questions**

973 Through a systematic review of the literature, this chapter aimed to explore the psychological
974 and physiological benefits of interacting with fishes in aquaria. Given that previous research
975 has highlighted potential benefits associated with viewing videos of fishes (Wells, 2005),
976 simulated or “non-live” alternatives were also considered. The following research questions
977 were addressed:

- 978 1. What influence does interaction with fishes in aquaria (live or non-live) have on the
979 psychological well-being of human participants?
- 980 2. What influence does interaction with fishes in aquaria (live or non-live) have on the
981 physiological well-being of human participants?

982 In addition, this review aimed to identify:

- 983 1. The attitudes of human participants regarding the benefits and challenges of interacting
984 with fishes in aquaria;

- 985 2. Any adverse effects which may be experienced by humans when interacting with fishes
986 in aquaria;
- 987 3. Any concerns regarding animal welfare which may be encountered during human
988 interaction with fishes in aquaria.

989 **2.3 Methods**

990 This systematic review was conducted according to a registered protocol (PROSPERO ID:
991 CRD42018090466), and adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews
992 and Meta-analysis (PRISMA) statements (Moher et al., 2009). Prior to commencing the
993 review, the PROSPERO register was searched to ensure no similar reviews were currently
994 underway; the following terms were used: “fish”, “aquarium”, “animal assisted intervention”,
995 “animal assisted therapy”, “pet therapy”, “human-animal interaction” and “companion
996 animal”.

997 **2.3.1 Search strategy**

998 Systematic searches conducted in January 2018 identified peer-reviewed evidence and grey
999 literature on the topic of fish aquarium-based HAI. A four-step search strategy was
1000 developed through discussion between the authors, and consulting previous systematic
1001 reviews in the field of HAI. Searches were conducted in the following electronic databases:
1002 Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Education Source,
1003 ERIC, Health Source – Nursing/Academic Edition, MEDLINE, PsycARTICLES, Psychology
1004 and Behavioural Sciences Collection, PubMed, SAGE Journals ONLINE, Science Direct,
1005 and Web of Science (Core Collection). Steps one to three involved identifying all records
1006 relating to 1) HAI and related theories, 2) relevant health and well-being outcomes, and 3)
1007 fish and/or aquaria. Steps one and two were conducted in all fields to maximise identification
1008 of relevant literature. However, as much research in this field is conducted with other
1009 species, step three was limited to title, abstract and keywords only (or the nearest
1010 alternative). Step four combined the results from these searches; an example search
1011 strategy is shown in Table 2.1. Results from electronic databases were supplemented with

1012 searches in Google Scholar, EThOS, and websites on HAI (WALTHAM Science, HABRI-
 1013 Central, and Animals and Society Institute), and by hand-searching the reference lists of
 1014 included studies and relevant review articles for additional references.

1015 **Table 2.1 Example search strategy (PubMed)**

Search step	Search number	Key terms
Step 1 (all fields):	#1	"human?animal interaction"
	#2	"human?animal relationship"
	#3	"human?animal bond"
	#4	"animal?assisted intervention"
	#5	"animal?assisted therap*"
	#6	"animal?assisted activit*"
	#7	"pet therap*"
	#8	"pet?facilitated therap*"
	#9	"pet?interaction"
	#10	"pet ownership"
	#11	"companion animal"
	#12	attachment
	#13	biophilia
	#14	biopsychosocial
	#15	"social support"
	#16	"social mediation"
	#17	"prepared learning theory"
	#18	"self-efficacy"
	#19	modelling

	#20	"role theory"
	#21	"polyvagal theory"
	#22	"attention restoration theory"
	#23	"stress recovery theory"
	#24	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12 OR #13 OR #14 OR #15 OR #16 OR #17 OR #18 OR #19 OR #20 OR #21 OR #22 OR #23
Step 2 (all fields):	#25	health
	#26	well?being
	#27	anxiety
	#28	arousal
	#29	stress
	#30	relaxation
	#31	"quality of life"
	#32	"life satisfaction"
	#33	restoration
	#34	recovery
	#35	pain
	#36	loneliness
		#37
Step 3 (title/abstract):	#38	aquarium
	#39	"aquatic environment"
	#40	aquaria
	#41	"fish"

	#42	"fish tank"
	#43	#38 OR #39 OR #40 OR #41 OR #42
Step 4:	#44	#24 AND #37 AND #43

1016 **2.3.2 Inclusion criteria**

1017 Based on preliminary searches, research in this area was anticipated to be both limited in
 1018 quantity and varied in design. Therefore, the inclusion criteria were deliberately broad to
 1019 incorporate the full scope of research related to effects of interacting with fishes in aquaria
 1020 on human health and well-being. The inclusion criteria were as follows:

1021 *2.3.2.1 Participants*

1022 There was no limitation on the participant populations of included studies. Studies involving
 1023 both healthy and clinical samples of any age were included.

1024 *2.3.2.2 Intervention/exposure*

1025 Any form of human interaction with fishes in aquaria was included, from passive exposure to
 1026 fish tanks, actively viewing fishes swimming, to caring for fishes in aquaria. Non-live
 1027 alternatives (e.g. videos) were also considered. There were no limitations regarding the
 1028 length, frequency or duration of exposure, or the setting. Studies were not excluded on the
 1029 basis that other animals (e.g. corals) were also present in the aquaria.

1030 *2.3.2.3 Comparator*

1031 Studies both with and without a control group were included. For those with a control group,
 1032 any type of comparator was considered, including no treatment controls, alternative AAI, and
 1033 alternative interventions without animal involvement.

1034 *2.3.2.4 Outcomes*

1035 The primary outcomes were psychological (e.g. anxiety, depression, behaviour change,
 1036 social interaction) and physiological (e.g. blood pressure, heart rate, motor skills) well-being.
 1037 Secondary outcomes were any adverse events experienced by human participants and any

1038 issues regarding animal welfare; participants' attitudes towards human-fish interaction were
1039 also considered, such as any benefits or limitations they had observed, or any evaluations of
1040 fish aquarium-based interventions.

1041 2.3.2.5 Study Design

1042 Included studies were limited to primary research, but there were no limitations on study
1043 design; both quantitative and qualitative studies were included.

1044 2.3.3 Exclusion criteria

1045 Research was limited to articles published in the English language, with no limitations on
1046 date of publication. To enhance the quality of included studies, articles were limited to those
1047 published in peer reviewed journals and doctoral theses. Only research involving live fishes
1048 or non-live alternatives (e.g. videos of fishes) was included. Research relating to the health
1049 benefits of fish consumption, studies involving invasive research conducted on fishes, and
1050 those relating to fishing/angling were excluded.

1051 2.3.4 Study selection

1052 The study selection process is outlined in Figure 2.1. All records identified *via* electronic
1053 databases ($n = 7248$) were exported into a single EndNote library and duplicates were
1054 removed. All remaining records ($n = 6978$) were then screened for inclusion in a two-stage
1055 process. Initially, the titles and abstracts of all records were assessed for relevance by two
1056 independent reviewers (HC/KS); the full-text of all remaining articles was then obtained and
1057 screened against the inclusion/exclusion criteria by two independent reviewers (HC/SV). At
1058 each stage, disagreements were resolved through discussion. Hand-searching of reference
1059 lists and supplementary searches on Google Scholar, EThOS, and HAI websites were also
1060 conducted to identify any additional studies of relevance ($n = 69$). The full-text of two
1061 records, including one unpublished thesis, could not be accessed and attempts to identify up
1062 to date contact details for the authors were unsuccessful, so these studies could not be
1063 included in the review. A third record (an unpublished thesis) could not be included for

1064 Figure 2.1 PRISMA flow diagram of study selection

1065 copyright reasons, as attempts at gaining the author's permission to cite the research were
1066 unsuccessful.

1067 **2.3.5 Data extraction and quality appraisal**

1068 Data from included studies were extracted by two independent reviewers (HC/SV) using a
1069 purpose-developed data extraction form (Appendix C). The following data were extracted:
1070 general information (author, year, publication type and source, country, funding, conflicts of
1071 interest); study details (aims/objectives, dates of data collection, theoretical framework);
1072 methods (design, participant recruitment and characteristics, intervention, control, allocation
1073 to conditions, setting/context, primary outcomes, secondary outcomes); results (method of
1074 analysis, psychological outcomes, physiological outcomes, secondary outcomes); author
1075 conclusions; and reviewer comments. All discrepancies were resolved through discussion.
1076 To reflect the inclusion of both quantitative and qualitative research, risk of bias was
1077 assessed using the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) Quality
1078 Appraisal Checklists for quantitative intervention studies, quantitative studies reporting a
1079 correlation, and qualitative studies (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE),
1080 2012). Quality appraisal was conducted by two independent reviewers (HC/SV) and
1081 disagreements were resolved through discussion.

1082 *2.3.5.1 Reporting bias*

1083 To assess for selective reporting of outcomes, the methods section of included studies was
1084 compared to the presented results to identify any discrepancies and determine whether an
1085 adequate description of the results was provided. As no studies were conducted according
1086 to a published or registered protocol, it was not possible to draw comparisons between the
1087 study protocols and published results. Furthermore, as there was much heterogeneity in
1088 study outcomes it was not possible to assess for publication bias using funnel plots, as this
1089 is not recommended for use on outcomes assessed in fewer than ten studies (Sterne et al.,
1090 2011).

1091 2.3.5.2 *Strength of evidence*

1092 The strength of the evidence was assessed using the Weight of Evidence approach (Gough,
1093 2007) for each of the two review questions independently. This approach involves assessing
1094 each study against four criteria. *Weight of Evidence A* is a generic assessment of study
1095 quality, while *Weight of Evidence B* and *C* are review-specific, and relate respectively to the
1096 appropriateness of the research design and the relevance of the evidence in addressing the
1097 review question(s). The final criterion (*Weight of Evidence D*) is an overall assessment of the
1098 extent to which the study addresses the review question(s), and was calculated as the most
1099 common rating from the first three criteria (where assessments were “low”, “medium” and
1100 “high” for the first three criteria, an overall weighting of “medium” was given). Assessments
1101 were made independently by two reviewers (HC/SV), with all disagreements resolved
1102 through discussion.

1103 **2.4 Results**

1104 Nineteen studies published in eighteen articles met the inclusion criteria and were included
1105 in the review (see Tables 2.2 and 2.3 for overview of included studies). All studies were
1106 published as peer reviewed journal articles, with publication years ranging from 1984 to
1107 2017. Two articles (Edwards and Beck, 2013, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014) reported
1108 research conducted as part of the same project but it is unclear whether the same sample
1109 was used for both studies; as the articles reported different outcomes they were treated
1110 independently in this review. Most research was conducted in the USA ($n = 11$), with four
1111 studies conducted in the UK and one each in Germany, France, Taiwan, and Australia.

1112 The broad inclusion criteria meant there was substantial clinical and methodological
1113 heterogeneity between included studies, and so statistical meta-analysis was deemed
1114 inappropriate. Therefore, a narrative synthesis of the evidence was conducted using
1115 techniques described by Popay et al. (2006). A preliminary synthesis was developed using
1116 textual descriptions, tabulation, groupings, and clusters; the relationships within and between
1117 studies were then explored through qualitative case descriptions and the use of idea

1118 webbing/conceptual mapping. The robustness of the synthesis was assessed by reflecting
1119 on the methods used in the review, and by considering the quality of included studies and
1120 the strength of the evidence. Findings from studies conducted with existing home aquaria
1121 owners ($n = 2$), and those using correlational designs ($n = 1$), are discussed independently
1122 from those involving novel interactions with fishes in aquaria ($n = 16$); as four studies in the
1123 latter group related specifically to public aquariums they are also considered separately.

Table 2.2 Summary of included studies: study characteristics

Study ID	Design	Participants			Aquarium Intervention(s)	Comparator(s)	Setting (Country)
		Population	Total sample size (<i>n</i>)	Age (Mean)			
<i>Fish as companion animals</i>							
Kidd and Kidd (1999)	Survey	Pet fish owners	100	37.1 years	50%	-	Not applicable (USA)
Langfield and James (2009)	Phenomenological study, in-depth interviews	Pet fish owners	9	34.9 years	33%	-	Not applicable (Australia)
<i>Correlational studies</i>							
Lin et al. (2013)	Survey	Medical directors at accredited hospitals	737	49 years	8%	Presence of aquarium in workplace	Presence of other interior amenities (indoor plants; music; art and exhibitions; private or personalised spaces) Accredited hospitals (Taiwan)
<i>Intervention studies</i>							
Barker, Rasmussen and Best (2003)	Within-subjects ("crossover") study	Patients awaiting electroconvulsive therapy treatment	42 (only 30 included in analysis)	48.4 years	74%	10-gallon aquaria containing around five African cichlids, approx. 20-minutes of passive exposure (<i>n</i> = 30)	No aquarium (<i>n</i> = 30) Holding/waiting rooms at outpatient treatment centre (USA)
Buttelmann and Römpke (2014)	Between-subjects study without randomisation	Undergraduate students	71	22.5 years	92%	Five-minute interaction with one veiltail goldfish in 5.5l goldfish bowl, to "try and accustom it to humans" (<i>n</i> = 18)	Five-minute interaction with dog (<i>n</i> = 18) or plant (<i>n</i> = 17), or no activity (<i>n</i> = 18) University laboratory (Germany)
Cole and Gawlinski (2000)	Before-and-after pilot study	Patients awaiting heart transplantation	10	55.9 years	20%	15-gallon saltwater tank containing four colourful fish, 11 days (<i>n</i> = 10)	- Hospital rooms (USA)
DeSchraver and Riddick (1990)	Between-subjects study with randomisation	Older adults in publicly subsidised housing	27	Median per condition	78%	Eight-minutes viewing 10-gallon tank with nine fishes (2 black mollies, 2 red wag swordtails, 2	Eight-minutes viewing "placebo" video of Purpose-built laboratory in publicly

				= 73-76 years		gold wag moons, 2 pineapple swordtails, 1 catfish) (<i>n</i> = 9), or video of tropical fish in an aquarium (<i>n</i> = 9)	television lines/static (<i>n</i> = 9)	subsidised housing complex (USA)
Edwards and Beck (2002)	Interrupted time-series with non-equivalent control	Residents of specialised dementia units	62	80.1 years	61%	Aquaria containing eight large colourful fish, up to four months (<i>n</i> = 62)	Scenic ocean picture, two weeks (<i>n</i> = 17)	Dining rooms of specialised dementia units (USA)
Edwards and Beck (2013)	Interrupted time-series	Residents of specialised dementia units	70	82.2 years	74%	As above (<i>n</i> = 70)	-	As above
Edwards, Beck and Lim (2014)	Before-and-after study	Residents of specialised dementia units	72	80.3 years	71%	Aquaria containing eight to ten large colourful fish, 10 weeks (<i>n</i> = 72)	-	As above
		Staff of specialised dementia units	71	NR	82%	Aquarium as above, 10 weeks (<i>n</i> = 71)	-	As above
Katcher, Segal and Beck (1984)	Between-subjects study with randomisation	Patients undergoing elective dental surgery	42	NR	NR	40-minute contemplation of aquarium with (<i>n</i> = 8) or without (<i>n</i> = 8) hypnosis	40-minute contemplation of poster with (<i>n</i> = 8) or without (<i>n</i> = 8) hypnosis, or no intervention (<i>n</i> = 10)	Dental surgery (USA)
Maranda et al. (2015)	Pilot Randomised Control Trial	Adolescents with type 1 diabetes mellitus	29	14.2 years	64%	Fishbowl containing <i>Betta splendens</i> fish, and instructions to pair diabetes self-management tasks with daily and weekly fish care duties, approximately 3 months	Usual care (<i>n</i> = 12)	At home (USA)
Riddick (1985)	Between-subjects study without randomisation	Older adults in publicly subsidised housing	24	Range 57-94 years	71%	2.5-gallon tanks containing two goldfish, plus nine visits from researcher over six-months (<i>n</i> = 7)	Ten visits from the researcher over six-months (<i>n</i> = 8), or no intervention (<i>n</i> = 7)	Publicly subsidised housing (USA)

Sanchez et al. (2015)	Before-and-after study with control group	Students/trainees in paediatric orthopaedics	69	28.2 years	58%	30-minutes viewing 265-gallon saltwater aquarium with >25 fish, including several species of surgeonfish ($n = 69$)	30-minutes viewing white wall ($n = 12$)	Hospital waiting room (France)
Wells (2005)	Between-subjects study with randomisation	University students	100	19.7 years	42%	10-minute video of 10 neon tetras swimming in a tank ($n = 20$)	10-minute video of birds in an aviary, primates in a zoo enclosure, a popular soap opera, or a blank screen (all $n = 20$)	University laboratory (UK)
<i>Public aquariums</i>								
Cracknell et al. (2016)	Between-subjects study, quasi-experimental	University students	84	24 years	76%	10-minutes viewing above exhibit when fully stocked ($n = 29$) or partially stocked ($n = 26$)	10-minutes viewing exhibit when unstocked ($n = 29$)	Public aquarium exhibit (UK)
Cracknell et al. (2017), Study 1	Within-subjects study	University students	39	19.5 years	74%	Images of public aquarium exhibits ($n = 39$)	Images of built, green, aquatic, or sub-aquatic environments (all $n = 39$)	University laboratory (UK)
Cracknell et al. (2017), Study 2	Within-subjects study	University students	40	20.8 years	68%	Images of public aquarium exhibits differing in species richness, abundance of individuals, and content (tropical/ temperature) (all $n = 40$)	-	University laboratory (UK)
Sahrman et al. (2016)	Before-and-after study	General public	165	Range 18-68 years	72%	10-minute interaction with stingrays at touch-tank ($n = 165$)	-	Public aquarium exhibit (USA)

1125 NR: Not reported

1126

Table 2.3 Summary of included studies: key findings

Study ID	Procedure	Psychological outcomes	Physiological outcomes	Risk of bias*
<i>Fish as companion animals</i>				
Kidd and Kidd (1999)	Customers of shop selling fishes and aquarium equipment completed survey.	<i>Benefits of aquarium ownership</i> : reported by 94% of respondents and included relaxation ($n = 47$), watching movements ($n = 32$), stress reduction ($n = 23$), companionship ($n = 5$), entertainment ($n = 4$) and education ($n = 1$).	-	-
Langfield and James (2009)	Semi-structured interviews conducted with current pet fish owners; the data were analysed using the constant comparison method.	Four themes identified: <i>reasons for owning fishes as pets; the environment; caring for pet fish; and benefits and limitations of owning fishes as pets.</i>	-	+
<i>Correlational studies</i>				
Lin et al. (2013)	Medical directors from all accredited hospitals in Taiwan were mailed a questionnaire, which assessed patient-related work stress, the presence of five interior amenities in the workplace (including aquaria), and self-rated health status.	<i>Self-rated health (compared to same age population, compared to medical peers, short-term health complaints, long-term health complaints)</i> : no relationship between presence of an aquarium in the workplace, and any dimension of self-rated health was found.	<i>Self-rated health (short-term health complaints, long-term health complaints)</i> : no relationship between presence of an aquarium in the workplace, and any dimension of self-rated health was found.	+
<i>Intervention studies</i>				
Barker, Rasmussen and Best (2003)	Patients assigned to rooms with/without aquarium on subsequent visits. Physiological outcomes assessed immediately after assignment and before treatment, psychological outcomes assessed before treatment only.	<i>Anxiety, depression, fear and frustration (VAS)</i> : no significant differences between aquarium and no aquarium conditions; trend towards a greater reduction in anxiety in the aquarium condition ($p = 0.08$).	<i>HR/DBP/SBP</i> : no significant differences found between aquarium and no aquarium condition before or after treatment.	+

Buttelmann and Röpcke (2014)	Participants about to give spontaneous presentation interacted with fish/dog/plant/nothing for 5-minutes. Outcomes assessed at baseline, following induction of anxiety (being informed of the presentation task) and after the interaction.	<i>Anxiety (STAI-S)</i> : reduced significantly more in fish, dog, and plant groups than no activity group; no significant differences between experimental groups. More participants in the dog group experienced a reduction to below baseline levels than those in control group; no differences between other groups. <i>Laughter (yes/no)</i> : more participants in the dog group laughed during the intervention than in all other groups; no differences between the other groups.	<i>DBP/SBP</i> : NR as influenced by participants' movement/speech.	-
Cole and Gawlinski (2000)	Aquaria installed into the hospital rooms of patients awaiting heart transplantation. Outcomes assessed at baseline then after 3 and 11 days.	<i>Anxiety, depression, hostility, dysphoria, sensation seeking and positive affect (MAACL-R)</i> : no significant differences between baseline and follow-up.	-	-
DeSchraver and Riddick (1990)	Participants seated comfortably and watched live fish/fish video/placebo video for eight minutes. An emotive article was read aloud to induce stress. Outcomes assessed every minute during procedure.	<i>Treatment evaluation (adapted LSS)</i> : all conditions were perceived as equally relaxing.	<i>HR, skin temperature (°F), muscle tension (µV)</i> : no significant differences between conditions.	-
Edwards and Beck (2002)	Aquaria/picture installed into dining rooms of specialised dementia units. Nutritional intake assessed daily for two weeks before and after installation, then weekly for six weeks. Body mass assessed at baseline then monthly for four months.	-	<i>Nutritional intake (grams consumed/meal)</i> : significantly increased in two weeks after installation, then again in following six weeks. No significant changes in control group two weeks after installation. <i>Body mass (lbs)</i> : significantly increased in month after installation, then continued to increase until end of study (total <i>M</i> gain = 1.65lb).	-

Edwards and Beck) 2013	<p>Aquaria installed into dining rooms. Nutritional intake assessed daily for two weeks before and after installation, then weekly for six weeks. Average body mass was calculated for three months prior to installation (baseline), the intervention period (weeks 3-5), and follow-up (week 10 to 3-months post-intervention).</p>	-	<p><i>Nutritional intake (grams consumed/meal)</i>: significantly increased in the two weeks after installation, but not in following six weeks.</p> <p><i>Body mass (lbs)</i>: significantly increased from baseline to intervention but not from intervention to follow-up (total <i>M</i> gain = 2.2lbs).</p>	-
Edwards, Beck and Lim (2014)	<p>Aquaria installed into dining rooms and outcomes assessed at baseline and after 10 weeks.</p>	<p><i>BPSD (Nursing Home Disruptive Behaviour Scale)</i>: significant improvements on domains of uncooperative, irrational, sleep, and inappropriate behaviours but not annoying or dangerous behaviours. Significant overall improvement.</p> <p><i>Job satisfaction (Assessment of Work Environment Scale)</i>: significantly improved following introduction of the aquarium.</p>	-	-
Katcher, Segal and Beck (1984)	<p>Participants received intervention immediately prior to treatment. Physiological measures assessed throughout intervention/procedure; psychological measures assessed during/after procedure.</p>	<p><i>Treatment comfort (Treatment Comfort Index)</i>: patients rated comfort as significantly higher after aquarium contemplation than poster contemplation. Also higher in both aquarium groups and the poster with hypnosis group than the no contemplation group.</p> <p><i>Anxiety (assessed by blind observer using a checklist) and patient compliance (assessed by dentist)</i>: no significant effect of aquarium observed.</p>	<p><i>DBP/SBP</i>: no significant differences during intervention or procedure.</p> <p><i>HR</i>: NR.</p>	-
Maranda et al. (2015)	<p>Participants obtained pet fish and were instructed to pair twice daily feeds with blood glucose readings, and weekly water changes with a parental review of their glucose logs. Outcomes assessed at baseline and follow-up (approximately 3 months).</p>	<p><i>Quality of life (PedsQoL Generic and Diabetes modules)</i>: no significant effects were found for generic or health-related quality of life.</p>	<p><i>Glycaemic control (A1C)</i>: significant reduction in A1C level for those in the intervention group compared to those in the control group. Younger participants (10-13 years) had a significantly greater response to the intervention than older participants (14-17 years).</p>	+

Riddick (1985)	Aquarium/visitor interventions were provided over six months. Outcomes were assessed <i>via</i> interview at baseline and six months.	<i>Leisure satisfaction (LSS)</i> : no significant difference between groups; one component (relaxation) bordered on significance ($p = 0.06$). <i>Loneliness (UCLA Loneliness Scale)</i> , <i>happiness (MUNSH)</i> , <i>anxiety (STAI-T)</i> : no significant differences between groups.	<i>DBP</i> : analysed as change from baseline to six-months for each group separately, due to differences at baseline. Only aquarium group underwent significant reduction. <i>SBP</i> : no significant differences between conditions.	-
Sanchez et al. (2015)	Participants watched aquarium continuously for 30-minutes. Outcomes assessed at 5, 10, 20 and 30-minutes, then at 10-minutes post-viewing.	-	<i>Pain threshold (measured using electrical stimulation device)</i> : significantly higher 5, 10, 20, and 30-minutes after viewing, compared to the initial values, and remained elevated 10-minutes after viewing ended. No significant changes in the control condition.	-
Wells (2005)	Participants watched one of the videos for 10-minutes then completed a reading aloud task designed to induce stress. Outcomes assessed at baseline (phase 1), after watching video (phase 2), and after reading task (phase 3).	-	<i>HR/SBP</i> : significantly lower in phase 3 in animal video groups compared to control video groups. No difference between animal videos groups. <i>DBP</i> : significantly lower in phases 2 and 3 in animal video groups compared to control video groups. No difference between animal videos groups.	+
<i>Public aquariums</i>				
Cracknell et al. (2016)	Participants viewed aquarium exhibit for 10-minutes; outcomes were assessed at baseline, 5-minutes, and 10-minutes.	<i>Valence (Feeling Scale)</i> : a significant effect of time showed that valence increased with viewing; there was no significant effect of stocking level. <i>Arousal (Felt Arousal Scale)</i> : a significant effect of time showed that arousal significantly decreased with viewing; there was no significant effect of stocking level.	<i>DBP/SBP</i> : no significant differences were found between different stocking levels. <i>HR</i> : a significant effect of stocking level indicated that participants in the two stocked conditions had greater reductions in HR than those in unstocked condition.	-
Cracknell et al. (2017), Study 1	Participants viewed each image and rated them on four dimensions.	<i>Attractiveness, willingness to display and affect</i> : built environments rated lower than all others, aquatic environments and aquaria rated highest. <i>Perceived restorativeness</i> : built environments rated lower than all others, aquaria rated higher than sub-aquatic and green environments, aquatic environments rated higher than aquaria.	-	+

Cracknell et al. (2017), Study 2	As above.	<i>Attractiveness, willingness to display, affect and perceived restorativeness</i> : vertebrates rated higher than invertebrates; tropical exhibits rated more highly than temperate exhibits; high abundance rated higher than low abundance; high species richness rated higher than low species richness in tropical scenes but lower in temperate scenes.	-	+
Sahrmann et al. (2016)	Participants interacted with stingrays at the touch-tank. Physiological outcomes assessed throughout, psychological outcomes assessed pre- and post-interaction.	<i>Hedonic tone</i> : significantly improved from pre- to post-touch. <i>Energetic arousal</i> : significantly increased from pre- to post-touch. <i>Tense arousal</i> : significantly decreased from pre- to post-touch. (All assessed using the UMACL)	<i>HR</i> : significant quadratic trends showed that HR became more elevated and less variable during touch, then began to return to normal towards the end of the touch period (but did not reach baseline levels).	-

1128 NR: not reported; BPSD: behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia; DBP: diastolic blood pressure; HR: heart rate; LSS: Leisure
1129 Satisfaction Scale; MAACL-R: Multiple Affect Adjective Checklist-Revised; MUNSH: Memorial University of Newfoundland Scale of Happiness;
1130 SBP: systolic blood pressure; STAI-S: State-Trait Anxiety Inventory State Scale; STAI-T: State Trait Anxiety Inventory Trait Scale; UMACL;
1131 University of Wales Institute of Science and Technology Mood Adjective Checklist; VAS: visual analogue scales

1132 *Risk of bias was assessed using the NICE (2012) Quality Appraisal Checklists for quantitative intervention studies and qualitative studies. ++
1133 indicates all/most criteria were fulfilled and conclusions are unlikely to alter; + indicates some criteria were fulfilled and conclusions are unlikely
1134 to alter; - indicates few or no checklist criteria were fulfilled, and conclusions are likely or very likely to alter.

1135 **2.4.1 Fish as companion animals**

1136 Two studies were conducted with individuals who currently kept fishes as companion
1137 animals to gain an understanding of their experiences. One was a phenomenological study
1138 which explored experiences of pet fish ownership through in-depth interviews ($n = 9$, M age
1139 = 34.9 years, 33% female) (Langfield and James, 2009), while the second utilised a survey
1140 design and provided descriptive statistics on qualitative aspects of keeping home aquaria (n
1141 = 100, M age = 37.1 years, 50% female) (Kidd and Kidd, 1999). Both studies identified
1142 relaxation and stress reduction as potential benefits of keeping fishes as companion
1143 animals; this appeared to be primarily associated with watching the movements of the fishes,
1144 although the sound of running water was also mentioned by some participants in one study
1145 (Langfield and James, 2009). Companionship was also identified as a potential benefit of
1146 keeping fishes, although this was experienced to a much lesser extent than relaxation, with
1147 only a minority (5%) of participants in one study reporting this benefit. Other benefits
1148 associated with keeping pet fishes included happiness (Langfield and James, 2009),
1149 entertainment, and education (Kidd and Kidd, 1999). A small number of participants (6%) in
1150 one study viewed their fish tanks as room decoration only (Kidd and Kidd, 1999). Limitations
1151 to keeping fishes were also identified. In one study, it was noted that fishes cannot provide
1152 the same level of emotional support as other types of animal, and that participants had to
1153 deal with the death of their animals on a regular basis (Langfield and James, 2009). These
1154 factors were associated with variation in the level of attachment participants felt to their
1155 fishes, with some reporting being highly attached, and others viewing their fishes as
1156 replaceable (Langfield and James, 2009). Other limitations that were identified were
1157 associated with the maintenance, cost, and time commitments of keeping home aquaria.

1158 **2.4.2 Correlational studies**

1159 One study used a correlational design to assess whether the presence of aquaria in the
1160 workplaces of hospital medical directors was associated with their self-rated health.
1161 Participants ($n = 737$, M age = 49 years, 8% female) were mailed a questionnaire to assess

1162 their patient-related work stress, and the presence of five interior amenities (aquaria, indoor
1163 plants, music, art, and exhibitions, and private or personalised workspaces) within their
1164 working environment. Four dimensions of self-rated health were also assessed, specifically:
1165 how participants rated their own health against that of the same age population and their
1166 medical peers, and their experience of various health complaints during the past month
1167 (short-term) and six months (long-term). Both physiological and psychological health
1168 complaints were included. The analyses indicated that after controlling for personal
1169 characteristics, work status and work stresses, the presence of interior amenities was
1170 associated with an improvement in participants' self-rated health. However, the presence of
1171 aquaria alone was not significantly related to any dimension of medical directors' self-rated
1172 health.

1173 **2.4.3 Intervention studies**

1174 Sixteen studies involved novel interactions with fishes in aquaria, however, four of these
1175 related specifically to public aquariums so are discussed separately below. Of the twelve
1176 remaining studies, three involved student or trainee samples (Wells, 2005, Buttelmann and
1177 Röpcke, 2014, Sanchez et al., 2015) and nine involved clinical populations, specifically:
1178 residents of specialised dementia units (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013, Edwards, Beck and
1179 Lim, 2014), dental patients (Katcher et al., 1984), electroconvulsive therapy patients (Barker,
1180 Rasmussen, et al., 2003), hospitalised patients awaiting heart transplantation (Cole and
1181 Gawlinski, 2000), older adults (Riddick, 1985, DeSchrive and Riddick, 1990), and
1182 adolescents with type 1 diabetes mellitus (Maranda et al., 2015). One study also explored
1183 how staff were affected by the intervention (Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014). Where reported,
1184 mean ages ranged from 19.7 to 82.2 years, although student samples were typically younger
1185 than those drawn from clinical populations. One study involved adolescents and reported the
1186 mean age to be 14.2 years. All samples included male and female participants (20 to 92%
1187 female), with the exception of one study which did not report gender (Katcher et al., 1984).
1188 Ethnicity was reported in four studies. In three cases the sample was predominantly

1189 Caucasian (72.8 to 98.5%) (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014);
1190 the fourth consisted 56% Caucasian and 44% African American in the intervention group,
1191 and 33% Caucasian, 58% African American, and 9% other ethnicity in the control group
1192 (Maranda et al., 2015). Estimates of socio-economic status were reported in four studies;
1193 two reported level of education (65 to 68% high school educated or above) (Edwards and
1194 Beck, 2002, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014), one reported marital status (43% married)
1195 (Barker, Rasmussen, et al., 2003), one reported ZIP code-based annual household income
1196 (intervention group: \$54,800; control group: \$51,800) (Maranda et al., 2015), and one
1197 reported that all participants qualified for “low income” publicly subsidised housing (Riddick,
1198 1985).

1199 There was substantial variation in study setting and design. Two studies were conducted in
1200 university laboratories (Wells, 2005, Butteltmann and Römpke, 2014), one in a purpose-built
1201 laboratory in a housing complex (DeSchriver and Riddick, 1990), one in a hospital waiting
1202 room but under laboratory conditions (Sanchez et al., 2015), two in participants’ homes
1203 (Riddick, 1985, Maranda et al., 2015), and six in clinical or therapeutic settings (Katcher,
1204 Segal and Beck, 1984, Cole and Gawlinski, 2000, Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013, Barker,
1205 Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014). Design of studies included
1206 before-and-after studies (Cole and Gawlinski, 2000, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014);
1207 controlled before-and-after studies (Sanchez et al., 2015); interrupted time series with
1208 (Edwards and Beck, 2002) or without (Edwards and Beck, 2013) control groups; within-
1209 subjects or crossover studies (Barker, Rasmussen, et al., 2003); between-subjects studies
1210 with (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984, DeSchriver and Riddick, 1990, Wells, 2005) or without
1211 (Riddick, 1985, Butteltmann and Römpke, 2014) randomisation; and a pilot randomised
1212 control trial (Maranda et al., 2015). Where comparators were used, they included no
1213 treatment or usual care controls, viewing alternative stimuli such as posters, and interacting
1214 with other animals (see Table 2.2 for further details).

1215 The majority of studies used home aquaria containing between one and nine fish, with the
1216 exception of one study which used a 265-gallon aquarium with over 25 fish, installed in a
1217 hospital waiting room (Sanchez et al., 2015). One study did not report details of the
1218 aquarium set-up (Katcher et al., 1984), and while another study specified the species of fish
1219 which participants were to purchase (*Betta splendens*), it was not clear whether all
1220 participants adhered to these instructions (Maranda et al., 2015). Two studies used videos of
1221 fishes in aquaria (DeSchraver and Riddick, 1990, Wells, 2005) and did not specify the size of
1222 the aquaria shown, although one was reported to contain 10 neon tetras (Wells, 2005). The
1223 type of interaction differed between studies and included: passive exposure (Edwards and
1224 Beck, 2002, 2013, Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014);
1225 actively watching the fishes swimming (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984, DeSchraver and
1226 Riddick, 1990, Wells, 2005, Sanchez et al., 2015); interacting with a fish to “try and
1227 accustom it to humans” (Buttelmann and Römpke, 2014); and caring for fishes in an
1228 aquarium in either a hospital (Cole and Gawlinski, 2000) or home (Riddick, 1985, Maranda
1229 et al., 2015) environment.

1230 2.4.3.1 Anxiety and relaxation

1231 Reflecting the findings of studies conducted with those who choose to keep home aquaria,
1232 several intervention studies ($n = 7$) assessed outcomes relating to anxiety or relaxation. A
1233 variety of instruments were used, and so meta-analytical techniques could not be applied.
1234 Two studies assessed whether brief exposure to an aquarium could alleviate anxiety
1235 associated with stress-provoking medical procedures. In Barker et al. (2003), patients
1236 attending electroconvulsive therapy treatment were assigned to waiting rooms with or
1237 without aquaria. At the end of the waiting period (approximately 20 minutes) participants
1238 assessed their levels of anxiety using a visual analogue scale. Although participants
1239 reported lower levels of anxiety in the aquarium *versus* no aquarium condition, this did not
1240 reach a level of statistical significance. Katcher et al. (1984) examined whether
1241 contemplation of an aquarium prior to dental surgery reduced anxiety during treatment; this

1242 was assessed by a blind observer who recorded overt signs of anxiety every five minutes
1243 throughout the procedure. Again, anxiety was lower in the aquarium groups compared to the
1244 comparator groups, but this difference was not statistically significant. However, scores from
1245 a Treatment Comfort Index indicated that patients who contemplated an aquarium before
1246 their dental surgery reported higher levels of comfort during the treatment than those who
1247 contemplated a poster or a blank wall. No differences were found in patient compliance as
1248 assessed by the dentist.

1249 Buttelmann and Römpke (2014) also assessed short-term changes in anxiety, this time in
1250 relation to a public speaking task. Student participants were asked to complete a short
1251 presentation on an unfamiliar topic with just five-minutes to prepare; a five-minute
1252 intervention period followed the preparation time during which participants interacted with a
1253 fish, dog, or plant, or were simply told to wait. Anxiety was assessed at baseline, after the
1254 stressor, and after the intervention period using the State scale of the State-Trait Anxiety
1255 Inventory (STAI); a score for each participant was calculated as the percentage of induced
1256 anxiety that was reduced following the intervention, where induced anxiety was calculated as
1257 the change from baseline to post-stressor. Participants who interacted with the fish had a
1258 greater reduction in induced anxiety than participants who received no intervention, and this
1259 reduction was equivalent to that experienced by participants who instead interacted with a
1260 dog or a plant. However, significantly more participants in the dog group experienced a
1261 reduction in anxiety to below baseline levels, relative to the control group; there were no
1262 significant differences between the other groups with regards to this outcome.

1263 Two studies assessed anxiety over longer intervention periods. No change in anxiety was
1264 found for patients awaiting heart transplantation three- or 11-days after fish tanks were
1265 installed in their hospital rooms, as measured using the Multiple Affect Adjective Checklist-
1266 Revised (MAACL-R) (Cole and Gawlinski, 2000). Similarly, older adults who were given fish
1267 to care for in their own home experienced no greater reduction in anxiety (measured using
1268 the Trait scale of the STAI) after six-months, than those who received visits from the

1269 researcher, or no intervention (Riddick, 1985). In the latter study, however, there was a
1270 borderline significant ($p = 0.06$) increase in relaxation (a component of the Leisure
1271 Satisfaction Scale) for residents in the aquarium group, compared to the comparator groups;
1272 there were no significant differences between groups for overall leisure satisfaction.

1273 Outcomes relating to anxiety were assessed in two further studies. In DeSchrive and
1274 Riddick (1990) participants viewed either a live fish aquarium, a video of fishes swimming or
1275 a placebo video of television lines and static; participants' responses to a treatment
1276 evaluation questionnaire (adapted from the Leisure Satisfaction Scale) indicated that all
1277 activities were perceived to be equally relaxing. Finally, Edwards et al. (2014) found that
1278 installation of aquaria into specialised dementia units was associated with a significant
1279 improvement in carer ratings of residents' behavioural and psychological symptoms,
1280 assessed using the Nursing Home Disruptive Behaviour Scale. This improvement in
1281 behaviour also coincided with an increase in job satisfaction among staff members,
1282 measured using the Assessment of Work Environment Scale.

1283 *2.4.3.2 Physiological stress*

1284 Six studies assessed indicators of physiological stress, although these outcomes were not
1285 reported in one study as the readings appeared to have been influenced by participants'
1286 movement and speech (Buttelmann and Römpke, 2014). Heart rate and/or blood pressure
1287 were the most commonly assessed outcomes, and were typically measured using
1288 automated devices (although in one case the device used was not stated (Riddick, 1985)).
1289 However, the number and timing of assessments varied across studies; combined with the
1290 heterogeneity in study and intervention design, this variation made the data unsuitable for
1291 meta-analysis.

1292 Two studies assessed whether the presence or contemplation of an aquarium could reduce
1293 heart rate and blood pressure among people undergoing medical procedures (Katcher,
1294 Segal and Beck, 1984, Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003), with neither study finding a
1295 significant effect on either variable (one study did not report the findings related to heart rate

1296 (Katcher et al., 1984)). DeSchriver and Riddick (1990) assessed differences in heart rate,
1297 skin temperature and muscle tension between participants who viewed a live fish aquarium,
1298 a fish video, or a placebo video. Heart rate was measured as beats per minute using an
1299 automated device, skin temperature in degrees Fahrenheit using a temperature meter
1300 mounted on the participant's finger, and muscle tension in microvolts using bicep
1301 electromyography (EMG); no significant differences were found between conditions for any
1302 of these variables. Wells (2005), however, found that participants who watched an animal
1303 video (fish, bird or primate) had lower heart rate and blood pressure (systolic and diastolic)
1304 after a subsequent reading aloud task than participants who watched a control video (soap
1305 opera or blank screen). Diastolic blood pressure was also significantly lower immediately
1306 after viewing the video for participants in the animal video groups compared to the control
1307 groups; there were no differences between the animal video conditions. One study examined
1308 changes in blood pressure over longer periods and found that diastolic (but not systolic)
1309 blood pressure was significantly reduced after six months for participants who were given
1310 fishes to keep in their own home, but not for those who received visits from the researchers,
1311 or had no intervention (Riddick, 1985).

1312 *2.4.3.3 Affective state*

1313 Four studies assessed a range of outcomes relating to participants' current mood or affective
1314 state. The presence of an aquarium in waiting rooms had no effect on fear, frustration or
1315 aggression (assessed using visual analogue scales) for participants awaiting ECT treatment
1316 (Barker, Rasmussen, et al., 2003). Similarly, responses to the MAACL-R showed no change
1317 in depression, hostility, dysphoria, sensation seeking, or positive affect among patients
1318 awaiting heart transplantation three- or 11-days after aquaria were installed in their hospital
1319 rooms (Cole and Gawlinski, 2000). One study assessed whether happiness (assessed using
1320 the Memorial University of Newfoundland Scale of Happiness) increased after six months for
1321 older adults who were given fishes to care for in their own home, but no significant
1322 differences were found between participants in the fish group and those who were visited by

1323 the researcher, or received no intervention (Riddick, 1985). In Buttellmann and Röpcke
1324 (2014), videotapes of the intervention period were coded for occurrence of laughter (yes/no);
1325 significantly more participants in the dog group were observed laughing compared to all
1326 other groups, with no significant differences between the fish, plant and control groups.

1327 *2.4.3.4 Loneliness*

1328 Riddick (1985) used the UCLA Loneliness Scale to assess whether loneliness improved for
1329 participants who were given a fish versus those who received visits from the researcher, or
1330 had no intervention. No significant difference was found between the three groups after six-
1331 months, although a trend towards reduced loneliness was seen for those in the visitor group
1332 ($p = 0.08$).

1333 *2.4.3.5 Nutritional intake and body mass*

1334 As weight loss is a risk factor for people with dementia (Volkert et al., 2015), two studies
1335 examined whether introducing fish aquaria into the dining rooms of specialised dementia
1336 units could influence residents' nutritional intake, and subsequently improve their body mass
1337 (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013). Nutritional intake was measured as the amount of food (in
1338 grams) consumed at each meal during the intervention period, and in both studies, was
1339 found to significantly increase in the two weeks following installation. This increase also
1340 continued over the following six weeks, but only to a statistically significant level in one study
1341 (Edwards and Beck, 2002). In addition, body mass significantly increased during the months
1342 following installation of the aquarium, with average weight gains of 1.65 lbs (Edwards and
1343 Beck, 2002) and 2.2 lbs (Edwards and Beck, 2013) at four months post-installation. No
1344 changes in nutritional intake were observed after two weeks in a non-equivalent control
1345 group ($n = 17$) used in the earlier study (Edwards and Beck, 2002).

1346 *2.4.3.6 Pain*

1347 One study involving healthy adults explored whether watching fishes in an aquarium could
1348 increase participants' pain threshold (Sanchez et al., 2015). Participants ($n = 69$) were
1349 seated in front of the aquarium and gripped an electrical stimulation device between their

1350 fingers; the device increased in intensity until participants indicated that they could feel the
1351 sensation. The procedure was then repeated, and participants instead indicated when they
1352 first experienced pain. Assessments made throughout the 30-minute viewing period
1353 indicated that, although there were no changes in sensation threshold, participants' pain
1354 thresholds were significantly increased after 5-, 10-, 20-, and 30-minutes compared to
1355 baseline readings. They also remained elevated 10-minutes after viewing ended. No
1356 changes in pain threshold were detected among a subset of participants who were retested
1357 while viewing a blank wall for the same amount of time ($n = 12$).

1358 *2.4.3.7 Glycaemic control*

1359 One study assessed whether pairing fish care duties with diabetes self-management tasks
1360 could lead to improved glycaemic control for adolescents with type 1 diabetes mellitus
1361 (Maranda et al., 2015). Participants randomly assigned to the intervention group were
1362 provided with a fishbowl and related equipment, and purchased a fish using a gift card
1363 provided by the researchers. They were then instructed to pair twice daily feeds (morning
1364 and evening) with blood glucose readings, and weekly water changes with a caregiver
1365 review of their glucose logs. Glycaemic control was assessed *via* A1C (an indicator of
1366 average blood glucose levels over the preceding three months) at baseline and follow-up
1367 (approximately three months). A significant improvement was found for the intervention
1368 group compared to the control group (usual care), with younger participants (10-13 years)
1369 having a greater response to the intervention than older participants (14-17 years). This
1370 study also assessed whether the intervention had an effect on generic and health-related
1371 quality of life, but no significant changes were observed from baseline to follow-up.

1372 *2.4.3.8 Secondary outcomes*

1373 Most intervention studies reported procedures that were in place to ensure animal welfare. In
1374 the three studies by Edwards and colleagues (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013, Edwards,
1375 Beck and Lim, 2014), the aquaria were specifically designed for use on a dementia unit; they
1376 were self-contained and locked to ensure the safety of fishes and residents, and were

1377 automated to reduce the burden on staff. Two studies used aquarium servicing companies
1378 (Cole and Gawlinski, 2000, Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003), with one also stating that
1379 participants were responsible for feeding the fishes and had to place their initials on a
1380 feeding calendar to prevent under/over-feeding (Cole and Gawlinski, 2000). Butteltmann and
1381 Röpcke (2014) reported that when data collection was underway, one of five fishes was
1382 taken from a communal tank and placed in a smaller goldfish bowl for the duration of the
1383 intervention, with the fishes used in rotation to reduce stress; procedures were also in place
1384 to minimise stress experienced by the dog used as a comparator. Of the two studies in
1385 which participants kept fishes in their own home, one reported that the tanks were initially
1386 maintained by the researchers and the participants, with the participants taking greater
1387 responsibility for fish care over the course of the study. Participants were also provided with
1388 information and literature on feeding and signs of fish illness, and could contact the
1389 researchers *via* telephone 24-hours a day (Riddick, 1985). The second study stated that
1390 participants were provided with instructions on how to care for their fish, but did not report
1391 any involvement in fish care on the part of the researchers (Maranda et al., 2015). This study
1392 also reported that the fishes of two participants had to be replaced due to them dying during
1393 routine fish care, although it was not reported whether the cause of these deaths was
1394 known, or whether steps were taken to prevent future mortalities. Otherwise, no studies
1395 reported whether the welfare of the fishes was affected due to their involvement in the
1396 research, so it is unclear whether these procedures were effective in practice. Similarly, no
1397 studies reported whether participants experienced adverse effects because of the
1398 interventions. Several studies provided anecdotal reports that participants responded
1399 positively to the interventions, however, none collected and reported these data in a rigorous
1400 and systematic manner.

1401 **2.4.4 Public aquariums**

1402 Four studies reported in three papers related specifically to public aquariums. Two were
1403 conducted within an aquarium setting (Cracknell et al., 2016, Sahrman et al., 2016) and two

1404 (published in the same paper) used images of public aquarium exhibits (Cracknell et al.,
1405 2017). Participants were either student samples (Cracknell et al., 2016, 2017) or healthy
1406 adults (Sahrman et al., 2016). Sample sizes ranged from 39 to 165 ($M = 82$); all samples
1407 included male and female participants (68 to 76% female) and mean ages ranged from 19.5
1408 to 24.0 years (one study reported only the age range of participants as 18 to 68 years
1409 (Sahrman et al., 2016)). Two studies were within-subjects designs with control groups
1410 (Cracknell et al., 2017), one was a before-and-after study (Sahrman et al., 2016), and one
1411 was between-subjects with pseudo-randomisation (Cracknell et al., 2016). Interactions
1412 included very brief exposure to images (Cracknell et al., 2017), viewing a 550,000-litre
1413 exhibit at various levels of stocking (Cracknell et al., 2016), and physically interacting with
1414 stingrays at a touch-tank (Sahrman et al., 2016).

1415 Two studies (Cracknell et al., 2016, Sahrman et al., 2016) examined changes in self-
1416 reported mood and physiological outcomes after interacting with fishes at public aquarium
1417 exhibits. In Cracknell et al. (2016), assessments using the Feeling Scale and Felt Arousal
1418 Scale indicated that participants' affective state significantly improved, and their levels of
1419 arousal significantly reduced after viewing an aquarium exhibit for 10-minutes, with no
1420 significant differences between three levels of stocking (unstocked, partially stocked and fully
1421 stocked). Similarly, blood pressure reduced in all conditions but there were no significant
1422 differences between the stocking conditions. However, heart rate was influenced by level of
1423 stocking, with significantly greater reductions observed in the partially and fully stocked
1424 conditions compared to the unstocked condition. In Sahrman et al. (2016), heart rate was
1425 found to be elevated and less variable while interacting with stingrays at a touch-tank,
1426 compared to before or after contact with the animals. Three dimensions of mood were
1427 assessed using the University of Wales Institute of Science and Technology Mood Adjective
1428 Checklist (UMACL); hedonic tone and energetic arousal were significantly increased, and
1429 tense arousal was significantly decreased, after the 10-minute interaction period compared

1430 to before contact. This is indicative of a short-term increase in physiological stress when
1431 touching the animals, but a decrease in mental stress after leaving the exhibit.

1432 In two studies (Cracknell et al., 2017), participants rated photographs of different
1433 environments on four dimensions of preference; the pleasantness of the scene, how willing
1434 they would be to display the image, how the image made them feel, and – of most relevance
1435 to this review – the perceived restorativeness of the scene. In study 1, public aquarium
1436 exhibits were compared to different natural and manmade environments. Aquaria were rated
1437 equally to, or higher than all other environments for all dimensions except perceived
1438 restorativeness, which was higher for aquatic environments (e.g. coastal landscapes). In
1439 study 2, different aquarium exhibits were compared. The findings indicated that tropical
1440 exhibits were preferred over temperate ones, and vertebrates were preferred over
1441 invertebrates; higher levels of biota were also preferred, but preference for species richness
1442 differed according to whether the exhibit was tropical or temperate (see Table 2.3 for further
1443 details).

1444 *2.4.4.1 Secondary outcomes*

1445 Of the studies relating to public aquariums two involved live animals; both used procedures
1446 which reflected typical visitor behaviours, and so animal welfare concerns were unlikely to be
1447 increased as a result of the research. Furthermore, Sahrman et al. (2016) reported that
1448 participants were shown proper touch techniques before being allowed to interact with the
1449 stingrays. Additionally, both studies asked participants about their feelings towards the
1450 exhibits. In Cracknell et al. (2016) participants' responses to evaluative statements indicated
1451 that they enjoyed watching the exhibit, found it interesting, felt better after watching, and
1452 would be happy to watch again. Furthermore, as the levels of stocking increased,
1453 participants' responses became more positive. In Sahrman et al. (2016), 80% of
1454 participants gave positive responses to an open-ended question about their experience of
1455 the exhibit. Adverse events to participants were not reported in either study, however,
1456 Sahrman et al. (2016) stated that 7% of participants indicated they felt nervous, anxious or

1457 unsure when touching the animals. As the two studies by Cracknell et al. (2017) used
1458 photographs in a laboratory setting, adverse events to participants were unlikely to have
1459 occurred, and there were no animal welfare concerns.

1460 **2.4.5 Risk of bias in included studies**

1461 *2.4.5.1 Qualitative studies*

1462 Two studies were assessed using the NICE Quality Appraisal Checklist for qualitative
1463 studies (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), 2012). Of these two
1464 studies, one used methods appropriate to the study aims and took steps to ensure rigor and
1465 trustworthiness (Langfield and James, 2009). However, the use of snowball sampling and a
1466 lack of clarity regarding whether two researchers were involved in the entire analytical
1467 process introduced some risk of bias to this study. By contrast, the second study consistently
1468 lacked sufficient detail to make sound judgements about risk of bias and the defensibility of
1469 conclusions (Kidd and Kidd, 1999). The study aims were not clearly stated, and there was
1470 insufficient description of the methods and data analyses to determine whether these were
1471 appropriate. As such, the findings of this study should be treated with caution. Further details
1472 are given in Appendix D.

1473 *2.4.5.2 Quantitative studies reporting a correlation*

1474 One study (Lin et al., 2013) was assessed using the NICE Quality Appraisal Checklist for
1475 quantitative studies reporting correlation/association (National Institute for Health and Care
1476 Excellence (NICE), 2012). This study involved a survey design to assess whether the
1477 presence of interior amenities (including aquaria) is related to self-rated health among
1478 hospital medical directors; therefore, the research relied on self-report data which can be
1479 highly subjective. Additionally, while the study controlled for personal characteristics, work
1480 status and work stresses, it is unlikely that all possible confounders were considered; health-
1481 related behaviours and pre-existing medical conditions for instance, were not assessed but
1482 are likely to impact self-rated health status. Finally, the response rate was fairly low

1483 (32.83%), so it is unclear whether the included participants were representative of the source
1484 population.

1485 *2.4.5.3 Quantitative intervention studies*

1486 The remaining sixteen studies were assessed using the NICE Quality Appraisal Checklist for
1487 quantitative intervention studies (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE),
1488 2012). One study was reported as a (pilot) randomised controlled trial (RCT) – usually
1489 considered the most rigorous form of experimental study design – and three others used
1490 between-subjects designs with random allocation (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984,
1491 DeSchriver and Riddick, 1990, Wells, 2005). Each of these studies had high or unclear risk
1492 of bias. One study reported that a randomisation schedule was developed using a
1493 computerised random number generator, and that this sequence was concealed until
1494 allocation, however, it was not clear how participants were allocated to this sequence
1495 (Maranda et al., 2015). No other studies reported the method of randomisation or whether
1496 allocation was concealed. One study reported that participants in the intervention and control
1497 groups were similar at baseline (Maranda et al., 2015), and a second stated that groups
1498 were balanced in terms of age and gender, although participants' baseline scores appeared
1499 to differ across conditions (DeSchriver and Riddick, 1990). The remaining two studies did not
1500 report whether groups were similar at baseline (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984, Wells,
1501 2005).

1502 Non-randomised, between-subjects designs were used in three studies (Riddick, 1985,
1503 Butteltmann and Römpke, 2014, Cracknell et al., 2016). One allocated participants on the
1504 basis of specific characteristics to ensure similarity between groups at baseline; whether
1505 balance was truly achieved is unclear, however, as the authors did not provide descriptive
1506 statistics to support this statement (Butteltmann and Römpke, 2014). Allocation could not be
1507 randomised in the second study due to the demands of the study site, and some differences
1508 between groups were observed at baseline (Cracknell et al., 2016). In the final study, the
1509 control group was handpicked by the centre manager, and allocation to intervention

1510 conditions was based primarily on participants' preferences; thus this study is subject to
1511 substantial bias (Riddick, 1985).

1512 Within-subjects or crossover designs were used in three studies, reported in two papers
1513 (Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Cracknell et al., 2017). In two studies, the order of
1514 presentation was randomised and determined by a computer, thus concealing allocation
1515 (Cracknell et al., 2017). In the third, participants were allocated on a first-come basis due to
1516 the needs of the service and allocation was not concealed (Barker, Rasmussen, et al.,
1517 2003).

1518 Six studies used before-and-after (Cole and Gawlinski, 2000, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014,
1519 Sanchez et al., 2015, Sahrman et al., 2016) or time series (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013)
1520 designs. Although two (Edwards and Beck, 2002, Sanchez et al., 2015) included a small
1521 number of participants from the treatment group in a control group, both analysed results
1522 from each group separately and based conclusions predominantly on findings from the
1523 treatment group in isolation, therefore, these two studies are considered alongside those
1524 without a comparator. Uncontrolled designs are typically considered to have low internal
1525 validity, and as only two studies interpreted results in relation to existing trends (Edwards
1526 and Beck, 2002, 2013), it is unclear whether the results observed in these studies differ from
1527 those which would have been observed naturally over time.

1528 Several potential sources of bias were present across included studies, irrespective of
1529 design. Blinding of participants was impossible due to the nature of the interventions (as
1530 people can see the fish), although three studies did report that participants were unaware of
1531 the study aims during data collection (Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Wells, 2005,
1532 Cracknell et al., 2016). Three studies reported blinding of study personnel (Katcher, Segal
1533 and Beck, 1984, Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Buttelmann and Röpcke, 2014) but in
1534 two cases this applied only to certain aspects of data collection, specifically, scoring of visual
1535 analogues scales (Barker, Rasmussen, et al., 2003) and coding of videos (Buttelmann and
1536 Röpcke, 2014). Only one within-subjects study reported using a sufficient washout period

1537 between conditions (Edwards and Beck, 2002), and contamination may have been an issue
1538 in studies where participants had access to the fish tank between testing sessions
1539 (DeSchriver and Riddick, 1990), or could have visited neighbours assigned to the aquarium
1540 group (Riddick, 1985). Most studies provided an adequate description of the aquaria,
1541 although additional details such as the species of fishes used would have been beneficial in
1542 some cases; only one study provided no details of the aquarium set-up (Katcher et al.,
1543 1984). In two studies, adequacy of exposure could be questioned; Sahrman et al. (2016)
1544 reported that visits to the touch-tank typically last around 20 minutes, but the intervention
1545 period lasted only ten, while Cole and Gawlinski (2000) stated that the type of patients
1546 included in their study usually experience a waiting time of two months, but the longest
1547 follow-up was just 11-days (although it is noteworthy that this was a pilot study). In one
1548 study, exposure to the intervention and control were non-equivalent by design of the
1549 research (Edwards and Beck, 2002), and in another it was unclear if length of exposure was
1550 standardised, or determined by the participant (Cracknell et al., 2017).

1551 In six studies, methods of statistical analysis were unclear or inadequately reported (Katcher,
1552 Segal and Beck, 1984, Riddick, 1985, DeSchriver and Riddick, 1990, Cole and Gawlinski,
1553 2000, Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Buttelman and Röpke, 2014). Several
1554 inappropriately used multiple comparisons in place of a single omnibus test (Edwards and
1555 Beck, 2002, 2013, Sanchez et al., 2015, Cracknell et al., 2016, 2017) and some also used
1556 parametric tests for Likert-type data which may be considered inappropriate (although this is
1557 highly debated) (Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014, Cracknell et al., 2016, 2017). Only two
1558 studies reported conducting power analyses (Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Maranda
1559 et al., 2015). In one study these were conducted on a *post-hoc* basis and so are of limited
1560 value (Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003), while in the second the data used as a basis for
1561 the power analysis was not clearly described (Maranda et al., 2015). Dropout rates were
1562 reported in only two studies (Riddick, 1985, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014) and while both
1563 were at an acceptable level (<10%), neither conducted an intention-to-treat analysis. One

1564 study reported excluding a participant because they bought a fish when assigned to the
1565 control group (Maranda et al., 2015). The problem of missing data was discussed in a further
1566 four studies (Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Butteltmann and Röpke, 2014, Cracknell
1567 et al., 2016, Sahrman et al., 2016) and was typically dealt with by excluding participants
1568 with incomplete data from the analyses.

1569 Only two studies adequately described the recruitment and selection process (Riddick, 1985,
1570 Sahrman et al., 2016), but one of these reported that participants for the control group were
1571 handpicked by the service manager (thus risk of bias was high) (Riddick, 1985). Most other
1572 studies provided some details such as the inclusion/exclusion criteria, but these were
1573 insufficient to determine whether risk of bias was minimised. Descriptions of participant
1574 characteristics were limited in most studies, with one providing no information about the
1575 sample (Katcher et al., 1984). For these reasons, it is unclear whether the findings from most
1576 studies are generalisable to the source populations.

1577 **2.4.6 Reporting biases**

1578 Evidence of potential selective reporting was identified in three studies. Katcher et al. (1984)
1579 reported collecting heart rate data but this outcome was not included in the results section of
1580 the article. Similarly, in discussion of their research findings, Edwards and Beck (2002)
1581 referred to data which indicated reduced use of nutritional supplements among participants,
1582 but this outcome was not discussed in either the methods or results sections. A third study
1583 (Butteltmann and Röpke, 2014) did not present data collected regarding heart rate and
1584 blood pressure, however, the authors explained the reason for this exclusion; the data failed
1585 to show successful anxiety induction in over 50% of participants, and may have been
1586 influenced by participants' movements and speech. Aside from omission of specific
1587 outcomes, two studies did not sufficiently report results, for instance failing to provide full
1588 details of the statistical test and significance levels (Cole and Gawlinski, 2000), or not
1589 reporting the results of *post hoc* testing (Riddick, 1985). For one study, a lack of detail
1590 regarding the methodology made it difficult to determine whether results were presented in

1591 full (Kidd and Kidd, 1999). Due to heterogeneity in study outcomes it was not possible to
 1592 assess for evidence of publication bias using statistical methods (i.e. funnel plots). However,
 1593 given that included studies were limited to those published in the English language, and that
 1594 additional research was identified during the search but could not be accessed, it is probable
 1595 that some relevant research was unintentionally omitted.

1596 2.4.7 Strength of evidence

1597 Strength of evidence assessments were made using the Weight of Evidence approach
 1598 (Gough, 2007). For this review, ratings of study quality (*Weight of Evidence A*) corresponded
 1599 directly to the assessments made using the NICE Quality Appraisal Checklists (National
 1600 Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), 2012) (see Table 2.3). Studies with high risk
 1601 of bias (-) were rated as 'low' ($n = 12$) and studies with unclear risk of bias (+) were rated as
 1602 'medium' ($n = 7$). As no studies were assessed as having low risk of bias (++), no studies
 1603 were rated as 'high' for this criterion (see Table 2.4 for more details).

1604 **Table 2.4 Weight of Evidence assessments**

(a) Psychological outcomes				
Study ID	Weight of Evidence A: Quality	Weight of Evidence B: Research design	Weight of Evidence C: Relevance	Weight of Evidence D: Overall weight
<i>Fish as companion animals</i>				
Kidd and Kidd (1999)	Low	Low	Low	Low
Langfield and James (2009)	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium
<i>Correlational studies</i>				
Lin et al. (2013)	Medium	Low	Low	Low
<i>Intervention studies</i>				
Barker, Rasmussen and Best (2003)	Medium	Medium	High	Medium
Buttelmann and Röpcke (2014)	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Cole and Gawlinski (2000)	Low	Medium	High	Medium
DeSchraver and Riddick (1990)	Low	High	High	High
Edwards et al. (2014)	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Katcher et al. (1984)	Low	High	High	High
Maranda et al. (2015)	Medium	High	High	High
Riddick (1985)	Low	Low	High	Low
<i>Public aquariums</i>				
Cracknell et al. (2016)	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Cracknell et al. (2017), Study 1	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
Cracknell et al. (2017), Study 2	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
Sahrmann et al. (2016)	Low	Medium	High	Medium

(b) Physiological outcomes				
<i>Correlational studies</i>				
Lin et al. (2013)	Medium	Low	Low	Low
<i>Intervention studies</i>				
Barker, Rasmussen and Best (2003)	Medium	Medium	High	Medium
DeSchraver and Riddick (1990)	Low	High	High	High
Edwards and Beck (2002)	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Edwards and Beck (2013)	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Katcher et al. (1984)	Low	High	High	High
Maranda et al. (2015)	Medium	High	High	High
Riddick (1985)	Low	Low	High	Low
Sanchez et al. (2015)	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Wells (2005)	Medium	High	High	High
<i>Public aquariums</i>				
Cracknell et al. (2016)	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Sahrmann et al. (2016)	Low	Medium	High	Medium

1605 With regards to study design (*Weight of Evidence B*), studies were rated as ‘high’ if they
1606 used randomised experimental designs ($n = 6$), and ‘medium’ if they used other
1607 experimental designs ($n = 9$). The exception was the study by Riddick (1985) which was
1608 rated as ‘low’ despite using a non-randomised experimental design; this was due to the
1609 inappropriate methods of allocation (participant choice and hand selection by the centre
1610 manager). Studies using qualitative or correlational designs ($n = 3$) were rated as ‘low’
1611 because these studies did not directly assess how interacting with fishes in aquaria
1612 influences well-being outcomes.

1613 The majority ($n = 14$) of studies received a rating of ‘high’ for relevance (*Weight of Evidence*
1614 *C*), as the findings related directly to the review question(s). Two studies were downgraded
1615 to ‘medium’ as they used photographs and assessed the perceived restorativeness of
1616 various public aquarium exhibits, rather than measuring actual changes in restoration
1617 outcomes (e.g. mood, physiological stress) (Cracknell et al., 2017). One qualitative study
1618 (Langfield and James, 2009) was also downgraded to ‘medium’ as while an insight into the
1619 psychological benefits of interacting with fishes in aquaria was given, well-being outcomes
1620 were not directly assessed. The second qualitative study (Kidd and Kidd, 1999) was rated as
1621 ‘low’ because the data were extremely limited, and there was inadequate description of the

1622 aims, design and results to determine the relevance of the study. Finally, the one study using
1623 a correlational design (Lin et al., 2013) was given a rating of 'low' for relevance because
1624 aquaria were a very small part of the study, and no description was given regarding the
1625 nature of the aquaria or the ways in which participants interacted with the fishes they
1626 contained.

1627 The overall weight for each study (*Weight of Evidence D*) was assigned based on the most
1628 common rating from the first three criteria. Most studies ($n = 12$) achieved an overall weight
1629 of 'medium', with three rated as 'low' (Riddick, 1985, Kidd and Kidd, 1999, Lin et al., 2013)
1630 and four as 'high' (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984, DeSchrive and Riddick, 1990, Wells,
1631 2005, Maranda et al., 2015). The lowest weighted evidence came from studies using
1632 correlational designs, or involving individuals who already kept fishes as companion animals;
1633 two studies were rated as 'low' and one as 'medium'. By comparison, evidence from the
1634 intervention studies was weighted more strongly; one study was rated as 'low', seven as
1635 'medium' and four as 'high'. Evidence from public aquarium studies was more consistent,
1636 with all four studies achieving an overall weight of 'medium'.

1637 With respect to the two review questions, psychological and physiological well-being were
1638 explored in fifteen and twelve studies, respectively. In both cases the majority of studies
1639 were assigned an overall weight of 'medium' ($n = 9$ for psychological outcomes, $n = 6$ for
1640 physiological outcomes). However, three studies relating to psychological well-being were
1641 rated as 'low' and three as 'high', whereas four studies assessing physiological well-being
1642 achieved an overall weight of 'high', with only two rated as 'low'. This suggests that the
1643 evidence relating to the physiological benefits of interacting with fishes in aquaria may be
1644 slightly stronger than that relating to the psychological benefits. It is noteworthy, however,
1645 that many studies relating to both types of outcome were 'upgraded' due to the high
1646 relevance of the evidence and the suitability of research designs, but had a high risk of bias
1647 (see Table 2.4 for details). Thus, while research related to physiological outcomes may be

1648 slightly stronger than that relating to psychological outcomes, overall the strength of
1649 evidence was fairly low and substantial limitations were present in both evidence bases.

1650 **2.5 Discussion**

1651 The purpose of this review was to investigate the psychological and physiological benefits of
1652 interacting with fishes in aquaria. Nineteen studies were included in the review,
1653 encompassing those relating to the benefits of keeping fishes as companion animals,
1654 correlational studies, and research involving novel interactions with fishes in home or public
1655 aquaria. The strength of evidence relating to physiological outcomes was slightly higher than
1656 for psychological outcomes, however, both evidence bases had mixed results. Of the fifteen
1657 studies that explored psychological outcomes, four studies of medium weight observed
1658 positive effects associated with human-fish interactions (Langfield and James, 2009,
1659 Butteltmann and Römpke, 2014, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014, Sahrman et al., 2016), but
1660 six ($n = 1$, high; $n = 3$, medium; $n = 2$, low) found only partial support (Katcher, Segal and
1661 Beck, 1984, Riddick, 1985, Kidd and Kidd, 1999, Cracknell et al., 2016, 2017) and five ($n =$
1662 2, high; $n = 2$, medium; $n = 1$, low) found no effect (DeSchrive and Riddick, 1990, Cole and
1663 Gawlinski, 2000, Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Lin et al., 2013, Maranda et al., 2015).
1664 Similarly, a positive effect on physiological outcomes was observed in six of twelve studies
1665 ($n = 2$, high; $n = 4$, medium) (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013, Wells, 2005, Maranda et al.,
1666 2015, Sanchez et al., 2015, Sahrman et al., 2016), but partial support was found in two ($n =$
1667 1, medium; $n = 1$, low) (Riddick, 1985, Cracknell et al., 2016), and no effect in four ($n = 2$,
1668 high, $n = 2$, low) (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984, DeSchrive and Riddick, 1990, Barker,
1669 Rasmussen and Best, 2003, Lin et al., 2013). Furthermore, there was substantial clinical and
1670 methodological heterogeneity between included studies, and risk of bias was either high or
1671 unclear. These factors must therefore, be considered when drawing conclusions from this
1672 collection of studies.

1673 Reflecting the widespread belief that watching fishes swimming is relaxing, there was
1674 tentative evidence from two studies (rated 'low' and 'medium' for weight of evidence) that

1675 keeping fishes as companion animals is associated with benefits such as stress reduction
1676 and increased relaxation. Other benefits were also identified, including happiness and
1677 companionship. Not all participants shared these experiences, however, with some reporting
1678 no benefits from keeping home aquaria. This reflects the inconsistency of research findings
1679 more widely in the field of HAI, specifically, the lack of conclusive evidence to demonstrate a
1680 direct link between companion animal guardianship (irrespective of the type of animal) and
1681 improved well-being (Herzog, 2011).

1682 One possible explanation for these inconsistent findings is that the benefits of companion
1683 animal guardianship are mediated by the strength of the attachment between a human and
1684 their companion animal (Zilcha-Mano, Mikulincer and Shaver, 2012, Amiot, Bastian and
1685 Martens, 2016, Meehan, Massavelli and Pachana, 2017). In both studies, variation was
1686 apparent in the level of attachment fish owners had to their animals; some participants
1687 indicated a strong attachment bond, while others indicated difficulty in forming attachments
1688 due to a lack of reciprocal affection from their fishes. This variation may therefore account for
1689 the divergent experiences of those who keep fishes as companion animals. Similarly, there
1690 were differences between participants in the degree to which they were involved in the care
1691 of their fishes. One study noted that most participants were responsible for feeding the fishes
1692 themselves, but some shared this responsibility with other family members (Kidd and Kidd,
1693 1999); participants in the second study noted that different species require different levels of
1694 care (Langfield and James, 2009). As increased effort can lead to people placing greater
1695 value on the product of that effort (Inzlicht, Shenhav and Olivola, 2018), home aquaria
1696 owners who take a greater role in the care of their fishes may perceive more benefits from
1697 their animals than those who take a lesser role. Alternatively, as research has indicated that
1698 the beneficial effects of companion animal guardianship may be mediated by factors such as
1699 sociodemographic characteristics and health-related behaviours (Müllersdorf et al., 2010,
1700 Saunders et al., 2017, Mueller, Gee and Bures, 2018), individual differences between people
1701 who keep pet fishes may explain some of the variation in findings. Future research should

1702 therefore, consider how differences in attachment, involvement in companion animal care,
1703 and population characteristics may account for variation in the experiences of those who
1704 keep fishes as companion animals.

1705 The findings from intervention studies were largely inconclusive. In contrast to research with
1706 other animals such as dogs and cats (for meta-analysis see Ein et al. (2018)), there was little
1707 evidence that fish aquarium-based interventions help to reduce psychological and
1708 physiological stress or anxiety. Promisingly, one highly weighted and two medium weighted
1709 studies found significant positive effects on outcomes related to physiological stress and
1710 anxiety or related outcomes (Wells, 2005, Buttelmann and Römpke, 2014, Edwards, Beck
1711 and Lim, 2014). However, two studies (one weighted high, one low) found only partial
1712 support (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984, Riddick, 1985) and three studies (one high, two
1713 medium) found no significant effects (DeSchriver and Riddick, 1990, Cole and Gawlinski,
1714 2000, Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003). Similarly, while previous research has linked
1715 contact with animals to reduced loneliness (Banks and Banks, 2005, Stanley et al., 2014),
1716 acquisition of a fish tank had no effect this outcome among older adults after six months
1717 (although the only study to explore this outcome was weighted low for strength of evidence,
1718 and had substantial risk of bias) (Riddick, 1985). As is common with research into HAI
1719 (Kazdin, 2017, Serpell et al., 2017), however, many studies had small sample sizes and thus
1720 may have been underpowered. As several studies with smaller samples observed greater
1721 improvements in the aquarium versus comparator groups, the possibility that these
1722 differences may have become statistically significant given sufficient power cannot be
1723 rejected.

1724 Alternatively, individual differences in participant characteristics may account for some of the
1725 variation in study findings. Ein et al. (Ein, Li and Vickers, 2018) for example, observed that
1726 pet therapy (with dogs and cats) reduced heart rate for healthy adults but not clinical
1727 samples and reduced subjective stress/anxiety among adults but not older adults. It was
1728 argued that these moderating effects may be due to the use of medication among clinical

1729 samples, and greater emotional stability in older adults. Although substantial clinical and
1730 methodological heterogeneity precluded the use of moderator and subgroup analyses in the
1731 current review, it is plausible that participant characteristics may have had similar
1732 moderating influences on the effectiveness of human-fish interaction. For instance, of the
1733 five studies assessing physiological stress, four involved clinical populations or older adults,
1734 and found either no effect (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984, DeSchraver and Riddick, 1990,
1735 Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003) or only mixed evidence (Riddick, 1985). Conversely,
1736 the final study involved a student sample and found significant improvements in heart rate
1737 and blood pressure associated with watching videos of fishes (Wells, 2005). While
1738 medication usage was not considered within these studies, it is possible this discrepancy in
1739 results may be at least partially accounted for by a higher level of medication use among the
1740 clinical and older adult samples, compared to student samples.

1741 There was some support for the effectiveness of fish aquarium-based interventions on pain
1742 (Sanchez et al., 2015), nutritional intake and body mass (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013),
1743 but attribution of these effects to human-fish interaction is limited by poor study design. For
1744 instance, in the two studies by Edwards and Beck (2002, 2013), staff members were
1745 required to track residents' food intake by physically weighing their food at mealtimes; as
1746 nursing home staff often overestimate food intake among residents (Simmons and Reuben,
1747 2000), tracking levels of consumption in this manner may have led to increases in residents'
1748 nutritional intake simply by raising staff members' awareness of under-eating. As these (and
1749 other) studies lacked appropriate control groups, it is not possible to separate any effects of
1750 the aquarium from other factors associated with the research, or from any changes that
1751 would have occurred naturally over time (Kazdin, 2017). Other common methodological
1752 concerns were the lack of randomisation, allocation concealment, and blinding of study
1753 personnel; it is noteworthy, however, that these methodological concerns are not uncommon
1754 in other areas of HAI research (Kazdin, 2017, Serpell et al., 2017).

1755 In some intervention studies the observed benefits may have been attributable to factors
1756 other than human-fish interaction. For instance, one study found that pairing diabetes self-
1757 management tasks with routine fish care activities led to improved glycaemic control among
1758 adolescents with type 1 diabetes (Maranda et al., 2015). Arguably, however, the fishes may
1759 not have been an integral component of this intervention; self-management behaviours may
1760 be paired with any regular activity, such as mealtimes, and waking or sleep routines
1761 (Sanders and Van Oss, 2013). While it is possible that adolescents may have greater
1762 motivation to adhere to an intervention because it involves interaction with live animals
1763 (Beetz, 2017), without direct comparison of fish care tasks to other routine activities, it is
1764 impossible to determine whether the fishes were a necessary component of this intervention.
1765 Likewise, while Butteltmann and Römpke (2014) found that interacting with a single fish in a
1766 goldfish bowl reduced anxiety to a greater extent than no intervention, this effect was
1767 equivalent for participants who instead interacted with a dog or a plant. Although a
1768 substantial body of research would predict benefit from interacting with a dog, it is less clear
1769 that these benefits should be observed from interacting with a single plant (although there is
1770 some evidence that the presence of indoor plants has psychological benefits (for overview
1771 see Bringslimark, Hartig, and Patil, (2009)), this research usually focuses on passive
1772 exposure and so the interaction within the current study – brushing the leaves of the plant
1773 with water – was not typical). As such, the authors acknowledged that these findings may be
1774 attributed to simple distraction, and so could be achieved with a variety of other activities
1775 provided they are engaging for the individual (Beetz and Bales, 2016, Beetz, 2017).

1776 Similarly, while the findings related to public aquariums were generally quite positive, it was
1777 not always clear whether these benefits were the direct effect of human-fish interaction.
1778 Cracknell et al. (2016) observed improvements in all participants irrespective of whether any
1779 fish species were present in the public aquarium exhibit. This suggests that benefits may be
1780 experienced from exposure to underwater scenes even in the absence of live animals, a
1781 finding which better aligns with theories of restorative environments than HAI. Interestingly,

1782 however, heart rate did improve to a greater extent as the abundance of fishes increased,
1783 and higher stocking levels were associated with longer viewing times in a separate sample
1784 of participants (Cracknell et al., 2016). Furthermore, photographs of aquaria were rated more
1785 highly when displaying a higher abundance of fish, although preference for diversity of
1786 species differed between tropical and temperate exhibits (Cracknell et al., 2017). These
1787 findings suggest that there may be additional benefits to interacting with live animals
1788 compared to other stimuli; as there are risks and animal welfare concerns associated with
1789 HAI (Bert et al., 2016, Ebener and Oh, 2017), additional research is needed to corroborate
1790 these findings.

1791 **2.5.1 Strengths and limitations**

1792 The major strength of this review is that it is the first attempt to systematically examine the
1793 psychological and physiological benefits of interacting with fishes in aquaria. One previous
1794 review has addressed this topic (Cracknell et al., 2018), but the narrative account focused on
1795 research from a restorative environments perspective and did not use a systematic
1796 approach. Consequently, evidence relevant to the current research questions was excluded,
1797 whereas the systematic approach used in the current review led to a more comprehensive
1798 overview of the research findings. The specification of inclusion/exclusion criteria also
1799 ensured that research met a minimum standard for inclusion; HAI research has often relied
1800 on evidence from poor quality sources that lack stringent peer review, such as books and
1801 conference proceedings (Katcher and Beck, 2010), but evidence from these sources was
1802 excluded from the current review. While studies of any design were included, assessing risk
1803 of bias and the strength of the evidence ensured that the research findings were considered
1804 in the context of methodological limitations. Overall, by using a systematic approach and
1805 adhering to PRISMA guidelines (Moher et al., 2009), this review provided a more rigorous
1806 and reliable synthesis of the research evidence, while aiming to meet the standards of
1807 transparency and reporting widely expected in other areas of health-related research.

1808 There are a number of limitations to this review which should be acknowledged. Firstly, bias
1809 may have been introduced by limiting included studies to those published in the English
1810 language. Furthermore, three potentially relevant studies could not be included due to issues
1811 in gaining access to the full-text, or for copyright reasons (in all cases attempts to
1812 identify/contact the authors were unsuccessful). As two of these studies were unpublished
1813 theses, this may signify the presence of publication bias; however, it was not appropriate to
1814 assess for publication biases statistically due to heterogeneity in study outcomes.

1815 The major limitations of this review were, however, the scope and quality of the current
1816 research evidence. While the inclusion criteria were deliberately broad to maximise results,
1817 only nineteen studies were included in the review; however, despite this small number of
1818 included studies, there was substantial clinical and methodological heterogeneity, which
1819 made it difficult to draw comparisons across research findings. Furthermore, in all studies
1820 risk of bias was either high or unclear, and the strength of evidence was fairly low, with only
1821 four of nineteen studies achieving a rating of 'high' for weight of evidence. While the
1822 identification of these limitations is crucial to support the development of future research,
1823 these inconclusive findings are unhelpful to practitioners wishing to provide their clients with
1824 evidence-based advice or interventions.

1825 **2.5.2 Future directions**

1826 Reflecting the field of HAI more broadly, there is a need for future research to address the
1827 discussed methodological limitations, and minimise sources of bias. Intervention studies
1828 should aim to meet the "gold standard" of RCTs, or use appropriate alternatives where this is
1829 not a possibility (for overview see Kazdin, 2017). Given the particularly low strength of
1830 evidence relating to keeping fishes as companion animals, there is also a need for large-
1831 scale observational research to better explore the effects of home aquaria ownership on
1832 well-being; this could be achieved through the incorporation of questions about companion
1833 animal guardianship into existing longitudinal studies (Mueller, Gee and Bures, 2018,
1834 Friedmann and Gee, 2019). Both experimental and observational research should take into

1835 consideration any mediating effects of attachment, sociodemographic characteristics, and
1836 health-related behaviours. Furthermore, as examining commonalities in qualitative research
1837 findings may be key in identifying the mechanisms underlying HAI (Kazdin, 2017), there is a
1838 need for additional qualitative research on the topic of human-fish interaction.

1839 Aside from addressing methodological limitations, there are several opportunities for future
1840 research highlighted by this review. While most of the intervention studies were conducted
1841 within specific clinical populations, there was preliminary evidence that human-fish
1842 interaction may be beneficial among non-clinical samples. For example, one study found that
1843 student anxiety decreased following brief interactions with a single fish in an aquarium
1844 (Buttelmann and Römpke, 2014), and another observed an improvement in job satisfaction
1845 among staff working in dementia units following the installation of fish aquaria (although it is
1846 unclear whether this was due to the presence of the aquaria or improvements in residents'
1847 behaviour) (Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014). These findings reflect research with dogs which
1848 has indicated that HAI may be beneficial in educational (Barker et al., 2016, Banks, McCoy
1849 and Trzcinski, 2018) or workplace environments (Barker, Knisely, Barker, Cobb, & Schubert,
1850 2012). Future research may therefore, wish to explore the influence of interaction with fishes
1851 in aquaria on student or employee well-being, although it is noteworthy that one study found
1852 no relationship between hospital medical directors' self-rated health and the presence of
1853 aquaria in their working environment (Lin et al., 2013). Additionally, as all but one of the
1854 included studies were conducted within adult populations, it would be of interest to further
1855 explore whether interacting with fishes in aquaria is beneficial for the well-being of child or
1856 adolescent participants.

1857 Another potential avenue of investigation is to explore which aspects of fish aquaria
1858 contribute to improved well-being. Research in public aquariums indicated that the
1859 abundance of fishes and diversity of species may have a positive impact on well-being
1860 outcomes (Cracknell et al., 2016, 2017), but it is currently unclear whether this translates into
1861 home aquaria. Furthermore, as this research observed benefits associated with exposure to

1862 an unstocked aquarium exhibit (Cracknell et al., 2016), future research should take into
1863 consideration the presence of additional aquarium features, such as other animals (e.g.
1864 snails, shrimp, corals), plants or ornaments, and whether the sound of running water
1865 produced by a fish tank plays a role in relaxation (Langfield and James, 2009). Similarly,
1866 consideration should also be given to the type and intensity of human-fish interaction. For
1867 instance, one study found positive effects associated with interacting with stingrays at an
1868 aquarium touch tank (Sahrman et al., 2016), but this interaction is very atypical in the
1869 context of this review. Thus, while the study furthers the evidence base regarding the
1870 benefits of human-fish interaction, it is unclear whether these effects will translate to the
1871 benefits of fish aquaria more broadly. Moreover, variation also exists within more common
1872 forms of interaction; being involved in the care of the animals may for example, lead to
1873 different effects than simply watching fishes swimming, and the effectiveness of
1874 interventions may be influenced by intensity of exposure, such as the duration and frequency
1875 of the human-fish interaction.

1876 Finally, future research should consider the impact of human-fish interactions on the animals
1877 involved. At present, much research into the health benefits of HAI has focused on human
1878 well-being, an approach which has been criticised as being human-centred (Shapiro and
1879 Demello, 2010, Adams, 2018). Some researchers have therefore argued for a greater
1880 emphasis on the reciprocal nature of HAI, with animals considered active participants in
1881 human-animal encounters (Amiot and Bastian, 2015, Adams, 2018). While research with
1882 other species (typically dogs) has begun to investigate the impact of HAI on the animals
1883 involved, the effects of human-fish interaction on the fishes involved were largely absent
1884 from the studies in this review. One paper reported that the fishes of two participants died
1885 during routine fish care and were replaced (Maranda et al., 2015), but did not specify
1886 whether the cause of these deaths was known, or whether steps had been taken to prevent
1887 future mortalities. No other studies reported whether the fishes experienced any adverse
1888 effects of the interactions, and no studies directly assessed fish welfare. Therefore, future

1889 research exploring the health benefits of interacting with fishes in aquaria should at minimum
1890 report whether (or not) any adverse effects to animal welfare are experienced as a result of
1891 human-fish interactions.

1892 Parallel to this, additional research is needed to determine the effectivity of non-live
1893 alternatives, such as videos of fishes swimming. As such interactions provide exposure to
1894 animals (albeit in simulated form) while eliminating animal welfare concerns, they may
1895 provide a suitable substitution for live fish aquaria. At present, however, only two studies (to
1896 my knowledge) have investigated the benefits of watching fish videos (DeSchraver and
1897 Riddick, 1990, Wells, 2005), with conflicting findings. More broadly, however, research has
1898 identified that robotic animals may have positive effects on well-being outcomes, such as
1899 loneliness, depression, and anxiety in older adults (Jøranson et al., 2015, Pu et al., 2019).
1900 Thus, it is possible that non-live alternatives to fish aquaria, such as videos, robotic fish, or
1901 computer simulations, may benefit human well-being while eliminating risks to both the
1902 human and the animal. However, more research is needed before conclusions can be
1903 drawn.

1904 **2.5.3 Conclusions**

1905 The findings of this review provide tentative support that interacting with fishes in aquaria
1906 may be beneficial for psychological and physiological well-being among humans. Although
1907 findings were mixed, many studies had small sample sizes, so it is possible significant
1908 effects would have been detected given adequate power. Conversely, however, many
1909 studies were subject to methodological limitations and had high or unclear risk of bias.
1910 Therefore, more research is needed before firm conclusions can be drawn. Future research
1911 on this topic should be well powered, and aim to use robust methodologies that minimise
1912 potential sources of bias. Consideration should also be given to any factors which may
1913 influence the effects of human-fish interaction, such as participant characteristics, features of
1914 the aquarium, or the type of interaction between the human and the animals. Finally, the

1915 details of the study design, and in particular the human-fish interaction, should be clearly
1916 described to allow for replication.

1917 **Chapter 3.**

1918 **An embedded mixed methods study examining the**
1919 **effects of watching fishes at work**

1920

1921

1922 **3.1 Abstract**

1923 Evidence collected from pet friendly workplaces has highlighted potential benefits associated
1924 with these schemes, including reduced stress among employees. This has implications for
1925 the promotion of employee well-being. However, these schemes may also introduce risk into
1926 the workplace. As ornamental fishes carry much lower risk than other companion animals,
1927 they may be a suitable alternative in situations where animals such as dogs would introduce
1928 too great a risk. The aim of the current study was to investigate whether watching an
1929 aquarium containing ornamental fishes during the working day influences employee well-
1930 being and cognitive performance. An embedded mixed methods study was conducted,
1931 consisting of two within-subjects experimental trials and a qualitative follow-up. Participants
1932 were university employees and research students who participated during their working day.
1933 In Trial A ($n = 30$), the immediate effects of watching live fishes on mood, physiological
1934 stress and cognitive performance were compared to the effects of watching a fish video or
1935 resting quietly. Although some outcomes improved from before to after each experimental
1936 activity, there was no evidence that watching fishes (live or on video) had any greater effect
1937 than resting quietly. In Trial B ($n = 27$), the effects on psychological and physiological well-
1938 being of repeatedly engaging in the same three activities over several weeks were
1939 examined; watching fish videos was associated with improvements in “high pleasure-low
1940 arousal” and overall job-related affective well-being but no further effects of condition were
1941 found. Several psychological outcomes improved over the 12-week study, independent of
1942 the experimental activities. Qualitative follow-up data collected from a subset of participants
1943 ($n = 13$) indicated that many found all three activities beneficial because leaving their desk
1944 allowed them to achieve detachment from work, and provided a short break which they
1945 otherwise would not have taken. While it did not translate to quantitative findings, qualitative
1946 data showed that live fishes were perceived as more engaging. Therefore, locating fish
1947 aquaria within offices (rather than in a separate location at the workplace) may promote well-
1948 being by encouraging ‘microbreaks’; further research is needed to investigate this theory.

1949 **3.2 Introduction**

1950 Work-related stress is a widespread problem in modern society, which during the year 2019-
1951 20 was estimated to have affected around 828,000 people in the UK alone (Health and
1952 Safety Executive, 2020). Though difficult to accurately estimate, the costs associated with
1953 work-related stress are substantial (Hassard et al., 2018). At the individual level, an afflicted
1954 person or group may experience both physical and psychological ill-health, including
1955 hypertension, ulcers, headaches, sleep disturbances, mental fatigue, depressed mood, and
1956 high rates of tension, anger or anxiety (van der Klink et al., 2001, Johnson et al., 2005,
1957 Colligan and Higgins, 2006). Furthermore, cases of prolonged or chronic stress can lead to
1958 burnout, a psychological syndrome characterised by feelings of overwhelming exhaustion,
1959 cynicism towards the job, and a sense of ineffectiveness (Maslach, Schaufeli and Leiter,
1960 2001, Johnson et al., 2005). This can negatively impact an individual's capacity to
1961 concentrate and retain information, leading to reduced performance on tasks requiring
1962 sustained attention or response inhibition (Van Der Linden et al., 2005, Colligan and Higgins,
1963 2006). There are also costs at a societal level, such as those incurred through absenteeism,
1964 loss of productivity, and consumption of healthcare resources (van der Klink et al., 2001,
1965 Hassard et al., 2018). For example, work-related stress, anxiety and depression accounted
1966 for an estimated loss of 17.9 million working days in the UK during the year 2019-20 (Health
1967 and Safety Executive, 2020). Although the causes of work-related stress are complex and
1968 differ by the individual, high prevalence is linked to occupations which involve emotional
1969 labour, such as in health and social care, education, public administration and defence, or
1970 customer services (Johnson et al., 2005, Health and Safety Executive, 2020).

1971 As HAI has been associated with improved human well-being in other contexts, the potential
1972 impact of companion animals on employee well-being has recently become a topic of
1973 investigation. Research within "pet friendly" workplaces suggests that most employees have
1974 positive or neutral attitudes towards companion animals at work, and their presence is
1975 perceived to help reduce stress, improve mood, increase social interaction and improve

1976 communication (Wells and Perrine, 2001a, Barker et al., 2012, Hall et al., 2017). One study
1977 conducted at a dog friendly workplace directly assessed employees' stress levels during the
1978 working day; no differences were observed in levels of salivary cortisol, but those who
1979 brought their dog to work reported lower levels of perceived stress than those without
1980 companion animals (Barker et al., 2012). Perceived stress among dog guardians who did not
1981 bring their dog to work increased throughout the day, possibly due to worries about leaving
1982 their dog at home alone (Norling and Keeling, 2010, Barker et al., 2012).

1983 Although no studies have examined the effect of HAI on cognition within the workplace,
1984 research conducted in other settings has shown positive effects. For example, the presence
1985 (*versus* absence) of a person or therapy dog during completion of a working memory task
1986 was associated with improved performance among university students, suggesting that the
1987 presence of animals may positively influence cognition in a similar way to the presence of
1988 other people (Gee et al., 2015). Similarly, hypertensive participants who completed a mental
1989 arithmetic task in the presence of a new companion animal showed greater improvements in
1990 performance than those who completed the task alone (Allen, Shykoff and Izzo, 2001). On
1991 the other hand, physical contact with a companion animal, opposed to their presence alone,
1992 may be detrimental to cognitive performance; Gee et al. (2015) found that physically
1993 touching a dog during completion of the working memory task led to the poorest
1994 performance, perhaps because the requirement to maintain contact interfered with
1995 completion of the task. Similarly, Stewart and Strickland (2013) found that task difficulty
1996 interacted with dog guardianship status to influence the effects of HAI; state anxiety was
1997 reduced among dog guardians who completed a task of moderate difficulty in the presence
1998 of a dog, but when the task was of extreme difficulty an increase in anxiety was observed.
1999 The authors suggested that participants who were dog guardians may have wished to
2000 interact with the animal, but could not due to the demands of the task (Stewart and
2001 Strickland, 2013). Thus, the presence of a companion animal in the workplace may be
2002 beneficial for individuals who have a positive attitude towards animals, assuming that the

2003 demands of their work allow them to interact with that animal. However, if the task is of
2004 greater difficulty, the presence of a companion animal may be detrimental to performance
2005 and/or well-being (Stewart and Strickland, 2013).

2006 To date, research exploring HAI in the workplace has focused almost exclusively on “pet
2007 friendly” workplaces. This approach requires employees to bring their own animals into the
2008 work environment, thus potentially limiting benefits to companion animal guardians only.
2009 There are also risks associated with dogs in the workplace (for review see Foreman et al.,
2010 2017) and so “pet friendly” approaches are unlikely to be suitable across all working
2011 environments. One alternative may be the installation of fish aquaria. To my knowledge, only
2012 one study has examined the influence of aquaria in the workplace on employee well-being;
2013 Lin et al. (2013) surveyed hospital medical directors in Taiwan and found that the presence
2014 of aquaria did not moderate the effects of patient-related stress on self-reported health.
2015 However, research in other settings has suggested that interacting with fish in aquaria may
2016 help alleviate stress or anxiety and reduce physiological arousal (see Chapter 2 for review).
2017 For example, Buttellmann and Römpke (2014) found that briefly interacting with a single fish
2018 in a goldfish bowl reduced anxiety among students preparing for an impromptu presentation
2019 compared to those who undertook no activity. Similarly, Gee et al. (2019) found that viewing
2020 an aquarium containing live fishes was associated with greater improvements in mood,
2021 relaxation and anxiety than was observing an empty tank or one containing only plants.
2022 Although DeSchraver and Riddick (1990) found no difference in physiological outcomes
2023 between individuals who watched a live fish aquarium, a fish video or a placebo video, a
2024 treatment evaluation questionnaire indicated that this was because all three conditions were
2025 perceived as equally relaxing. Furthermore, Wells (2005) found an association between
2026 watching videos of fish and reduced physiological arousal during an experimentally induced
2027 stressor, whereas no similar association was found for watching a soap opera or blank
2028 screen. This suggests that the presence of live fishes may not be necessary for individuals
2029 to experience benefits from watching ornamental fishes.

2030 A potential explanation for these findings relates to the biophilia hypothesis (Wilson, 1984,
2031 Kellert and Wilson, 1993), which suggests that because human evolution occurred in natural
2032 environments, we are predisposed to notice and respond emotionally to other living things in
2033 our surroundings. Threat-relevant stimuli (e.g. spiders, snakes) elicit negative emotions, but
2034 non-threatening stimuli (e.g. calm, friendly animals) can elicit positive affect and happiness
2035 (Kellert, 1993, 2012, Ulrich, 1993). Although the biophilia hypothesis has been widely
2036 criticised for being poorly defined and lacking falsifiability (Joye and De Block, 2011), some
2037 research has provided evidence that humans do preferentially attend to animals over non-
2038 living objects (New, Cosmides and Tooby, 2007, DeLoache, Bloom Pickard and LoBue,
2039 2011, Lobue et al., 2013). Fishes in particular appear to be effective at capturing human
2040 attention; higher levels of stocking and biodiversity were associated with longer viewing
2041 times at a public aquarium (Cracknell et al., 2016), and the presence of aquaria in shop
2042 windows has been associated with increased attention from passers-by (Windhager et al.,
2043 2011). Therefore, companion animals – and particularly ornamental fishes – may promote
2044 human well-being by readily capturing attention and diverting focus away from negative
2045 emotional states (Beetz, 2017). Although these effects may appear short-lived, it is known
2046 that psychosocial stressors can have longer term health implications (Krantz and McCeney,
2047 2002, Glaser and Kiecolt-Glaser, 2005). Thus, frequent engagement with companion
2048 animals may have longer lasting impacts on human well-being.

2049 A similar perspective comes from research regarding the restorative value of nature, which
2050 has shown an association between greater access to outdoor nature (e.g. urban green
2051 spaces), indoor nature (e.g. office plants) or indirect nature (e.g. *via* window views or
2052 videos), and lower levels of perceived stress and stress-related health complaints (Largo-
2053 Wight et al., 2011, Thompson and Bruk-Lee, 2019). Two complementary theories have been
2054 proposed to explain these findings. Stress Recovery Theory (Ulrich, 1983, Ulrich et al.,
2055 1991) posits that when an individual experiencing psychophysiological stress is exposed to
2056 unthreatening nature, a positive emotional response is automatically elicited which acts to

2057 rapidly reduce their heightened state of physiological arousal. It is argued that this rapid
2058 recovery would have been adaptive in the ancestral environment (Ulrich, 1983, 1993), and
2059 because stress impacts cognitive functioning, nature exposure may also lead to gains in
2060 cognitive performance (Ulrich et al., 1991). Alternatively, Attention Restoration Theory
2061 (Kaplan, 1995) centres on the concept of directed attention, the mechanism which allows an
2062 individual to focus on a task and inhibit outside distractions. Directed attention is argued to
2063 be limited in capacity and susceptible to fatigue, resulting in negative consequences
2064 including irritability and inaccuracy (Herzog, Maguire and Nebel, 2003, Basu, Duvall and
2065 Kaplan, 2019). Nature exposure is said to support the restoration of directed attention
2066 resources by capturing attention whilst allowing opportunity for reflection; this is referred to
2067 as 'soft fascination' (Kaplan and Berman, 2010). As fish tanks are one means of introducing
2068 nature into working environments (Largo-Wight et al., 2011), these theories support the
2069 notion that aquaria in the workplace may support employee well-being.

2070 Therefore, the purpose of this research was to investigate whether watching an aquarium
2071 containing ornamental fishes during the working day influences employee well-being and
2072 cognitive performance. An embedded mixed methods study was conducted, comprising two
2073 experimental trials (Trial A and Trial B) and a qualitative follow-up. As the theoretical
2074 frameworks discussed above would suggest that it is the act of watching fishes that induces
2075 relaxation, the experimental trials were conducted under laboratory conditions so that
2076 participants' engagement with the fishes was consistent and controlled, and to prevent other
2077 factors associated with the presence of fishes in the workplace (e.g. being involved in fish
2078 care activities) from influencing the results of the research. Furthermore, as previous
2079 research has identified potential benefits from watching videos of fishes (Wells, 2005), the
2080 effects of viewing a fish video were also assessed.

2081 The immediate effects of watching an aquarium on mood (affect and perceived arousal),
2082 physiological indicators of stress (salivary cortisol, blood pressure and heart rate), and
2083 cognitive performance (inhibitory control and working memory) were assessed in Trial A. As

2084 evidence suggests that fishes can readily capture human attention leading to increased
2085 relaxation, it was hypothesised that watching an aquarium would increase relaxation to a
2086 greater extent than sitting quietly with no stimulus. This would be evidenced by greater
2087 improvements in affect and cognitive performance, and larger reductions in perceived
2088 arousal and physiological indicators of stress. As live fishes are anticipated to capture
2089 attention to a greater extent than fishes on video, it was further hypothesised that watching
2090 an aquarium with live fishes would have a greater impact on relaxation than watching a
2091 video of the same aquarium.

2092 The longer-term effects of repeated exposure to the fishes were assessed in Trial B. It was
2093 hypothesised that repeatedly viewing an aquarium over several weeks would be associated
2094 with greater improvements in psychological (stress, anxiety, depression, and job-related
2095 affective well-being) and physiological (blood pressure and heart rate) well-being than would
2096 repeatedly taking short breaks with no stimulus. It was further hypothesised that repeatedly
2097 viewing an aquarium with live fishes would be associated with greater improvements in well-
2098 being than repeatedly viewing videos of the same aquarium.

2099 The final aspect of the research consisted of a qualitative follow-up with a subset of
2100 participants from both trials to develop a greater insight into the quantitative findings.

2101 **3.3 Methods**

2102 **3.3.1 Design**

2103 An embedded mixed methods design (Cresswell, 2014) was used (see Figure 3.1a).

2104 Quantitative data were collected through two concurrent experimental trials, with qualitative
2105 data collected *via* follow-up interviews and focus groups with a subset of participants.

a.

b.

c.

2106 Figure 3.1 Overview of study design; a) embedded mixed methods design, b) design of Trial A, c) design of Trial B

2107 **3.3.2 Participants**

2108 Trials A and B used independent samples drawn from the same population: university
2109 employees and research students. This population was selected for convenience, and
2110 because it includes professions found to experience higher than average work-related stress
2111 (e.g. teaching, education, business, research and administrative professionals; Health and
2112 Safety Executive, 2020). All university employees and research students were eligible to
2113 take part, but for logistical reasons the research was run at only two of the five university
2114 campuses. Recruitment was conducted *via* opportunity sampling, using a combination of
2115 written and electronic communications (posters, emails, adverts on the staff intranet/e-
2116 bulletin) and word of mouth. Participants were randomly assigned to either Trial A or Trial B,
2117 and provided written informed consent at the beginning of the first session. Power analysis
2118 conducted using G*Power (Faul et al., 2007) prior to data collection indicated that to detect a
2119 medium sized effect at 80% power, 28 participants were required for Trial A, and 24
2120 participants for Trial B. For both trials, sample sizes exceeded these minimum thresholds
2121 (Trial A, $n = 30$, 23-59 years, M age = 39.73 years, $SD = 11.05$, $n = 22$ female, $n = 8$ male;
2122 Trial B, $n = 27$, 23-60 years, M age = 41.41 years, $SD = 11.88$, $n = 19$ female, $n = 8$ male).
2123 Participants for the follow-up were a subset of individuals who had taken part in the original
2124 research. Recruitment commenced after all participants had completed the experimental
2125 trials and preliminary data analysis had been conducted. The same procedure as described
2126 above was followed, and all participants provided written informed consent prior to taking
2127 part. Thirteen individuals (25-59 years, M age = 40.53 years, $SD = 11.29$, $n = 9$ female, $n = 4$
2128 male) participated in the follow-up research, with representation from both Trial A ($n = 5$) and
2129 Trial B ($n = 8$).
2130 Participants received a voucher for a free hot drink or bottle of water from the university
2131 facilities for every session they completed in Trial A (max. 3 vouchers) or Trial B (max. 12
2132 vouchers), and for their participation in the follow-up (1 voucher).

2133 **3.3.3 Apparatus and Materials**

2134 **3.3.3.1 Experimental conditions**

2135 Three experimental conditions were used in Trials A and B: “aquarium”, “video” and
2136 “control”. The aquarium condition consisted of a 54-litre fish tank equipped with an internal
2137 filter, heater and thermometer, an automatic feeder, and various pieces of enrichment (~2
2138 inches of gravel, five plastic plants, and a decorative rock). An identical tank was used for
2139 each campus, and each was stocked with three tropical freshwater fish species: zebrafish
2140 (*Danio rerio*), variatus platys (*Xiphophorus variatus*) and peppered and/or albino cory catfish
2141 (*Corydoras paleatus*, albino *C. aeneus*). Although the aim was to stock each tank with the
2142 same number of fishes, due to issues with the supplier (fewer fishes than requested being
2143 delivered) and occasional fish mortality, in practice the tanks contained 5-6 zebrafish, 4-6
2144 platys, and 2-5 cory catfish. An example of the aquarium is shown in Figure 3.2.

2145 Figure 3.2 Standard aquarium set-up containing a) variatus platys, b) zebrafish, and c) cory
2146 catfish

2147 The video condition showed an identical tank to that used in the aquarium condition, stocked
2148 with six zebrafish, six variatus platys, and four cory catfish (peppered variety only). The
2149 video was displayed on a 24 inch (~61 cm) television, such that the size of the screen was
2150 similar to the viewing area of the fish tank. During applicable sessions, the television was
2151 placed directly in front of the fish tank, which was covered to prevent contamination between
2152 the conditions.

2153 No experimental stimuli were used in the control condition. The fish tank was covered, and
2154 the television screen was removed; participants were simply asked to sit quietly and relax.
2155 The sound of running water produced by the aquarium filter was present in all conditions, so
2156 that any observed effects could be attributed to the effect of visual exposure to the fishes
2157 rather than other factors associated with the presence of the aquarium.

2158 *3.3.3.2 Demographic questionnaire*

2159 For all samples, a purpose-developed questionnaire was used to collect demographic
2160 information about each participant, specifically their age, gender, and their job role
2161 (academic, research student, other). Companion animal guardianship history was also
2162 collected, including whether participants had ever kept companion animals, which type of
2163 animals they had kept, and during which stage(s) of life (if any) they had kept fishes
2164 (childhood, adulthood – not currently, adulthood – currently).

2165 *3.3.3.3 Outcomes assessed in Trial A*

2166 Trial A examined the immediate effects of watching fishes on well-being and cognitive
2167 performance. In accordance with this aim, responses to psychological outcomes were given
2168 in relation to participants' experience 'in the moment', and physiological and cognitive
2169 outcomes were selected based on the ability to detect fluctuations in these outcomes over
2170 short periods of time (i.e. minutes rather than days or weeks).

2171 *Mood: Positive and negative affect, and perceived arousal*
2172 Positive and negative affect were measured using the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule
2173 (PANAS; Watson, Clark and Tellegen, 1988). These scales are used extensively in
2174 psychological research and consist of 20 items (10 per scale) relating to positive and
2175 negative affect (e.g. “interested” or “ashamed”). Participants indicated their current
2176 experience on a scale from 1 = “very slightly or not at all” to 5 = “extremely”. Scores for
2177 positive and negative affect were calculated by summing responses to all items of the
2178 corresponding subscale (min = 10, max = 50 per scale), so that a higher score indicated
2179 greater positive (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.85$) or negative (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.77$) affect. Perceived
2180 arousal was measured using the Perceived Arousal Scale (PAS; Anderson, Deuser and
2181 DeNeve, 1995) consisting of 24 items relating to low and high arousal (e.g. “drowsy” or
2182 “active”). Responses were given as for the PANAS. A total score was calculated by reverse
2183 scoring items related to low arousal and summing all responses (min = 24, max = 120), so
2184 that a higher score indicated higher perceived arousal (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.92$).

2185 *Physiological stress: Heart rate, blood pressure and levels of salivary cortisol*

2186 Heart rate was measured using a Polar® H7 heart rate sensor, fitted under clothes and
2187 connected to a smartphone application (Polar Beat, Polar Electro®) to obtain real-time heart
2188 rate measurements. No participant data were recorded or stored within the application.
2189 Systolic and diastolic blood pressure were measured using an automatic blood pressure
2190 monitor (Omron M3, Model HEM-7131-E). Participants selected the arm which was most
2191 comfortable for measurement, and the same arm was used for all measurements within
2192 each participant. To measure levels of salivary cortisol, saliva samples were collected in
2193 sterile tubes *via* the passive drool technique; participants were asked not to eat or drink
2194 immediately prior to taking part in the research (though compliance could not be
2195 guaranteed), and were requested to rinse their mouth with water before providing the
2196 sample. All samples were collected during normal working hours (9am to 5pm), and
2197 wherever possible, each participant provided all their samples at approximately the same

2198 time-of-day. After collection, samples were immediately placed on ice and stored at -80°C
2199 until analysis with commercial ELISA kits (Enzo Life Sciences, Cortisol ELISA kits, ADI-900-
2200 071 and ADI-901-071); analysis was conducted in-house by the researcher (HC).
2201 Immediately before analysis, samples were defrosted and centrifuged (2 min, 4°C, 14000
2202 rpm). Steroid displacement reagent was added as per the manufacturer instructions, and
2203 samples were diluted using standard diluent at a ratio of 1:1 diluent to sample. To account
2204 for inter-plate variability, all samples for each participant were analysed on the same plate,
2205 except one sample that was re-run due to readings indicative of contamination.

2206 *Cognitive performance: Inhibitory control and working memory*

2207 Inhibitory control was measured using the Stroop Colour-Word Task (SCWT; Stroop, 1935).
2208 The task consisted of 100 colour words printed in an incongruent colour (e.g. the word
2209 “green” in blue ink). Participants were required to state the colour of each word, not the word
2210 itself, as quickly and as accurately as possible; this required them to override the automated
2211 response (reading the word) with a less automated response (saying the colour). The
2212 number of errors and time taken (in seconds) to complete the SCWT were recorded.
2213 Working memory was assessed using the digit-span forwards (DSF) and backwards (DSB).
2214 Participants heard a list of digits (e.g. “8, 9, 3”) and were required to repeat them back
2215 immediately. If successful, the length of the list was increased by one digit (max = 9 digits)
2216 until the participant failed to correctly recall a list of that length on two subsequent occasions.
2217 In the DSF the list was recalled in the same order it was presented; in the DSB it was
2218 recalled in reverse order (e.g. “8, 9, 3” as “3, 9, 8”). Scores for each were the length of the
2219 longest list correctly recalled. Both the SWCT and digit span tasks have been used to
2220 assess attentional capacity in past research (Ohly et al., 2016).

2221 *3.3.3.4 Outcomes assessed in Trial B*

2222 Trial B examined longer-term changes in psychological and physiological well-being, and
2223 this was reflected in the outcomes assessed. Responses to psychological outcomes were
2224 given in relation to the participants’ experiences over the past few weeks, opposed to in the

2225 moment. While heart rate and blood pressure may fluctuate in response to current
2226 experience, previous research has suggested that blood pressure may reduce in response
2227 to repeated exposure to fish aquaria (Riddick, 1985), and so these outcomes were also
2228 measured in Trial B. Salivary cortisol was not measured in Trial B because this outcome is
2229 highly influenced by extraneous variables and so variation across testing days could not
2230 have been attributed only to engagement in a specific condition. Similarly, in line with
2231 Attention Restoration Theory (Kaplan, 1995), any effect of watching fishes on cognitive
2232 performance was expected to be relatively transient and so was not assessed in Trial B.

2233 *Psychological well-being: Depression, anxiety, stress, and job-related affective well-being*
2234 The Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS; Lovibond and Lovibond, 1995) consist of
2235 three 14-item scales (42 items total). Participants indicated how much each statement (e.g.
2236 "I found myself getting upset by quite trivial things") had applied to them over the past week
2237 from 0 = "Did not apply to me at all" to 3 = "Applied to me very much, or most of the time".
2238 The scales can be used to measure changes in each state over time (Antony et al., 1998).
2239 Scores for each subscale were calculated as the sum of all responses for that scale (min =
2240 0, max = 42), so that a higher response indicated higher levels of each state (Cronbach's α =
2241 0.84-0.93). The short version of Job-related Affective Well-being Scale (JAWS; Van Katwyk
2242 et al., 2000) consists of 20 job-related emotion statements (e.g. "My job made me feel
2243 angry"). Participants indicated how much they had experienced each emotion over the past
2244 30 days from 1 = "never" to 5 = "extremely often". Negatively worded items were reverse
2245 scored and responses were summed for a total score (min = 20, max = 100), with a higher
2246 score indicating greater job-related affective well-being. The following subscales of the
2247 JAWS were also calculated (min = 5, max = 25 for each): high pleasure-high arousal (e.g.
2248 "enthusiastic"), high pleasure-low arousal (e.g. "calm"), low pleasure-high arousal (e.g.
2249 "angry"), low pleasure-low arousal (e.g. "depressed"), with a higher score for each indicating
2250 greater experience of that state (Cronbach's α = 0.74-0.94).

2251 *Physiological well-being: Heart rate and blood pressure*

2252 Heart rate and blood pressure were used to assess physiological well-being, and were
2253 assessed as in Trial A.

2254 *Covariate: Job satisfaction*

2255 It was recognised that attitudes towards one's job may influence psychological well-being at
2256 work, so participants in Trial B also completed the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS; Spector,
2257 1985) at baseline. Participants indicated how much they agreed with 36 statements (e.g. "I
2258 feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do") on a 6-point scale from 1 = "disagree
2259 very much" to 6 = "agree very much". Negatively worded items were reverse scored and all
2260 responses were summed for a total score, with higher scores indicating higher levels of job
2261 satisfaction (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.88$). Subscales of the JSS were not calculated.

2262 *3.3.3.5 Follow-up*

2263 Semi-structured focus group and interview schedules were used to collect qualitative data.
2264 Questions focused on participants' experiences and how these differed (if at all) across the
2265 three conditions. Participants also considered how these activities may be of most value if
2266 implemented within the working environment, particularly in relation to the presence of live
2267 fish aquaria and videos of fishes. However, participants were free to discuss any aspect of
2268 the activities which they found beneficial or otherwise, including the control. Data were audio
2269 recorded using a Sony ICD-PX470 digital dictation machine.

2270 Copies of all questionnaires, cognitive tasks and interview/focus groups schedules used in
2271 this research are provided in Appendix E.

2272 **3.3.4 Procedure**

2273 Ethical approval for this research was obtained from the School of Health and Life Sciences
2274 ethics committee at the University of the West of Scotland (Ref: 4940, Appendix F) and the
2275 Mars Research Review Board.

2276 3.3.4.1 Trial A: Two-way within-subjects design (Figure 3.1b)

2277 Trial A assessed the immediate effect of watching live fishes on mood, physiological stress,
2278 and cognitive performance. Participants completed three sessions over three consecutive
2279 weeks. Each 30-40 minute session involved participants engaging in one of the three
2280 experimental activities (“aquarium”, “video”, “control”) for a 10-minute intervention period,
2281 with outcomes assessed immediately before (“pre-test”) and after (“post-test”) the activity. A
2282 10-minute intervention period was selected based on previous research (Cracknell et al.,
2283 2016), and because it was acknowledged that a longer intervention period may not reflect
2284 what could be realistically achieved within a working environment.

2285 Informed consent was obtained at the start of the first session, after which participants
2286 completed the demographic questionnaire. With this exception, each session then followed
2287 the same procedure. Participants first completed the self-report assessments of positive and
2288 negative affect and perceived arousal. Heart rate and blood pressure were then measured
2289 while the participant was seated, and were noted by the researcher, after which the
2290 participant was requested to provide a saliva sample. The SCWT and digit span tasks were
2291 then conducted. This order (psychological, physiological, cognitive) was used for all
2292 participants as it was recognised that measuring physiological outcomes could influence
2293 responses to psychological outcomes, and completing the cognitive tasks could affect both
2294 psychological and physiological outcomes.

2295 After completing the pre-test assessments, participants engaged in one of the three
2296 experimental activities for 10 min. The order of exposure to the three conditions was
2297 counterbalanced across participants to control for order effects, with an order randomly
2298 assigned to each participant using a random number generator. Heart rate was noted
2299 halfway through the intervention period; no other assessments were made at this time as
2300 this would have interrupted participants’ engagement in the activity. All outcomes were
2301 reassessed following completion of the activity, in the same order as at baseline.

2302 During the intervention period, participants were seated comfortably and refrained from
2303 engaging in other activities, such as using mobile devices or reading. Attempts to minimise
2304 external sources of distraction were also made (e.g. closure of doors/windows and blinds,
2305 signage outside room) but due to the research being located on two busy university
2306 campuses, it was impossible to eliminate all sources of distraction. Data were collected from
2307 October 2018 to February 2020. As cortisol secretion follows a diurnal cycle, wherever
2308 possible sessions were conducted on the same day and at the same time each week, but
2309 this was not always possible in practice. Blinding of the researcher and participants was not
2310 possible due to the nature of the study, and while participants were not aware of the specific
2311 hypotheses being tested, the purpose of the study was easily surmised.

2312 *3.3.4.2 Trial B: One-way within-subjects design (Figure 3.1c)*

2313 Trial B assessed the effect of repeatedly viewing live fishes over several weeks on
2314 psychological and physiological well-being. The study lasted 12 weeks, consisting of weekly
2315 sessions divided into three 4-week study periods. Each study period involved repeated
2316 engagement in one of the three experimental conditions (“aquarium”, “video” and “control”),
2317 so that all participants completed all activities for a 4-week period once during the study.
2318 Order of exposure to the conditions was counterbalanced across participants to control for
2319 order effects.

2320 Written informed consent was collected at the start of the first session, after which
2321 participants completed the demographic questionnaire, the JSS and baseline psychological
2322 assessments. With this exception, each study period followed the same procedure. Weeks
2323 1-3 involved only the experimental activity; participants were seated comfortably and asked
2324 to engage in one of the three activities for 10 min. In the final week of each study period,
2325 heart rate and blood pressure were measured immediately before and after participants
2326 engaged in the activity, with heart rate also noted midway through the intervention period.
2327 Following the “after” physiological assessments, psychological outcomes were reassessed.
2328 As with Trial A, blinding of participants and the researcher was impossible, and sources of

2329 distraction could not be entirely eliminated. Data were collected between January 2019 and
2330 March 2020.

2331 *3.3.4.3 Follow up*

2332 Following preliminary analysis of the data collected in Trials A and B, qualitative follow-up
2333 data were collected to provide a deeper understanding of the quantitative findings. Data
2334 were collected during April and May 2020 *via* semi-structured focus groups and interviews.
2335 Written informed consent and demographic details were obtained *via* email prior to the focus
2336 group or interview. As the data collection period coincided with the COVID-19 pandemic, all
2337 data were collected remotely *via* video conferencing. Four focus groups were conducted,
2338 lasting 16 to 34 min; though planned to contain a minimum of four individuals, due to non-
2339 attendance on the day, in practice the focus groups contained 2-5 participants. One
2340 individual interview was conducted based on the preference of the participant, and lasted
2341 around 12 min.

2342 Each focus group began with the researcher asking participants to note down a few words
2343 that they would use to describe the three conditions. Participants were then asked to state
2344 the words they had used and explain why they had selected them; other participants had the
2345 chance to respond, and discuss whether their own experiences were similar or divergent.
2346 The researcher then followed up with questions about how the participants felt an aquarium-
2347 based intervention may be best implemented within the workplace. The one interview
2348 followed the same structure, minus the discussion between participants. With the permission
2349 of participants, all data were audio recorded and transcribed verbatim for analysis.

2350 **3.3.5 Animal welfare**

2351 The welfare of the fishes was prioritised at all times during this research. Each aquarium was
2352 filled with approximately 50 L of tap water, conditioned using an appropriate dose of API
2353 Quick Start® and API Stress Coat®. The internal heater was set to 26 °C, and the aquarium
2354 lights were set on a 12 h light/dark cycle; this was later adjusted to 8 h of light to help control
2355 algae growth. The tanks were set up a minimum of 2 weeks before stocking to allow time for

2356 the biological filter to mature; to help this establish, the automatic feeder was set to release 5
2357 mini pellets each day for 5 days after 3 days of no food, then every other day until the fishes
2358 were added. Water quality was assessed prior to stocking using API 5-in-1 and ammonia
2359 test strips; pH and carbonate hardness were low in both tanks, so coral sand was added in
2360 small plastic capsules to increase these parameters to appropriate levels.

2361 The fishes were ordered from a reputable local supplier, and either delivered directly to the
2362 university campus or collected by the researcher. At time of stocking (and restocking), water
2363 parameters were all within safe limits (temperature = 24.9-25.8 °C; general hardness (GH) =
2364 60-120 mg/L; carbonate hardness (KH) = 40-80 mg/L; pH = 6.5-7.0; nitrite (NO₂) = 0-1.0
2365 mg/L; nitrate (NO₃) = 0-40 mg/L; ammonia (NH₃/NH₄) = 0 mg/L), and further doses of API
2366 Quick Start® and API Stress Coat® were added. On arrival the bags containing the fishes
2367 were floated on the water for 15 min, then a small amount of tank water was added to each
2368 bag to allow mixing; this process was repeated three times, after which the fishes were
2369 released into the water and observed for a minimum of 30 min to check they were behaving
2370 normally. The automatic feeder was set to provide two meals daily, after one day of no food.
2371 Tank maintenance/cleaning and water changes were completed on a weekly basis;
2372 appropriate doses of API Quick Start® and API Stress Coat® were added to the new water
2373 to make it safe for the fishes. Following completion of the research, the fishes were kept at
2374 the university until they could be rehomed.

2375 **3.3.6 Data analysis**

2376 *3.3.6.1 Trial A*

2377 Self-report measures were checked for completeness prior to data entry. In four instances a
2378 response had not been provided to one of the items; these missing data were imputed using
2379 the mean of completed responses for the relevant scale. Due to equipment failure and
2380 erratic readings, heart rate could not be measured in five participants and was missing on at
2381 least one occasion for an additional thirteen. One participant declined to provide saliva
2382 samples, and two did not provide a sufficient quantity of saliva for analysis to be conducted.

2383 Two additional samples could not be included in the statistical analyses as concentrations of
2384 cortisol fell outside the standard curve and there was an insufficient quantity to re-run the
2385 samples at a greater dilution. No data were missing for the remaining variables.

2386 All data were analysed using *R* version 4.0.0 (R Core Team, 2020). Assumptions of the
2387 general linear model were checked through the visual inspection of boxplots, histograms and
2388 Q-Q plots, and the Shapiro-Wilk test of normality, and were violated in all cases. Therefore,
2389 data were analysed using robust methods which provide more reliable estimates in the face
2390 of violation of model assumption (Field and Wilcox, 2017). Separate robust within-by-within
2391 (condition-by-time) procedures were used for each dependent variable, and were conducted
2392 *via* the package *WRS* (Wilcox and Schönbrodt, 2014). All analyses utilised 20% trimmed
2393 means and bootstrapped samples ($n = 2000$). Where significant main effects were detected,
2394 the nature of these differences was identified through inspection of trimmed means and
2395 robust pairwise comparisons with Rom's corrected alpha levels. Due to the presence of
2396 missing data for heart rate and cortisol concentrations, these data were analysed using a
2397 robust linear mixed model *via* the package *robustlmm* (Koller, 2016) to ensure maximum
2398 data retention. Condition, time, and the interaction between these variables were entered as
2399 fixed factors; participant was entered as a random factor to account for each participant
2400 being assessed at multiple time points. As this package does not provide p -values, 95%
2401 Wald confidence intervals were calculated, and predictors were considered statistically
2402 significant if the confidence interval did not cross zero.

2403 3.3.6.2 *Trial B*

2404 Three participants dropped out of the trial before completion (two due to illness, one for
2405 reasons unknown), and two participants could not complete the study due to the COVID-19
2406 lockdown. Thirteen participants missed at least one session during the 12-week period for
2407 reasons such as illness or annual leave; if a participant attended fewer than two sessions
2408 during any study period, their data for that study period were excluded from the analyses.

2409 Where absence was pre-arranged (i.e. annual leave) and fell on a testing week,
2410 assessments were made one week early to avoid missing data.

2411 As with Trial A, completeness of self-report measures was checked prior to data entry. In
2412 seven instances, missing values were imputed using the mean score from all items on the
2413 relevant scale. One participant declined to answer 36% of items on the Job Satisfaction
2414 Survey, and as imputation was inappropriate, these data were recorded as missing. A further
2415 participant noted that many items on the anxiety scale of the DASS did not apply to them
2416 due to medical issues that caused anxiety-type symptoms, so was excluded from analyses
2417 relating to anxiety. Complete psychological data were thus available for 18 of the 27
2418 participants, with an additional five having been assessed on at least one occasion after
2419 baseline, and one participant having complete data for all outcomes except anxiety. Due to
2420 equipment failure and participant absence, there were large amounts of missing data for
2421 physiological outcomes. Blood pressure was successfully measured in a total of 24
2422 participants on at least one occasion after baseline, and heart rate in a total of 23
2423 participants. However, complete data regarding blood pressure and heart rate were available
2424 for only 17 and 13 participants, respectively.

2425 Data were analysed using separate linear mixed models for each outcome variable, *via* the
2426 package *lmerTest* (Kuznetsovs et al., 2017). In each model, participant was entered as a
2427 random factor and condition as a categorical predictor with three levels (aquarium, video, or
2428 control). For the psychological outcomes, scores at baseline and job satisfaction were
2429 entered as continuous predictors; for the physiological outcomes, time was entered as an
2430 additional categorical predictor with two levels for blood pressure (baseline and post-activity)
2431 and three for heart rate (baseline, mid-activity, post-activity). Normality of the residuals was
2432 assessed *via* visual inspection of Q-Q plots, univariate outliers were identified using
2433 boxplots, and influential cases were identified using Cook's distance *via* the package
2434 *influence.ME* (Nieuwenhuis, te Grotenhuis and Pelzer, 2012); cases were defined as
2435 influential where the value of Cook's distance was greater than $4/k$, where k is the number of

2436 nesting groups (in this case, the number of participants included in the analysis). In all cases
2437 data failed to meet the assumptions of the general linear model, so were analysed using
2438 robust linear mixed models *via* the package *robustlmm* (Koller, 2016); 95% Wald confidence
2439 intervals were calculated, and predictors were considered statistically significant if the
2440 confidence interval did not cross zero. Following the initial analyses, additional comparisons
2441 were conducted to assess whether watching fishes (irrespective of whether this was live or
2442 on video) had greater effects than the control, and to determine whether there were any
2443 differences between the live fish aquarium and video conditions. Due to the high level of
2444 missing data, where significant effects of condition were detected, sensitivity analyses were
2445 conducted to assess the robustness of the effect; this involved repeating the analysis for the
2446 subset of participants who provided complete data.

2447 Based on findings from the qualitative follow-up, additional robust linear mixed models were
2448 conducted to examine changes in psychological outcomes across the 12-week study. These
2449 analyses were conducted as described above, with study period (week 4, 8 and 12) entered
2450 as a categorical predictor, and participant as a random factor. To assess the robustness of
2451 any significant effects, sensitivity analyses were again conducted for the subset of
2452 participants who provided complete data.

2453 3.3.6.3 *Follow-up*

2454 Data were managed in NVivo 12 Pro (QSR International Pty Ltd, 2018) and analysed using
2455 reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2019, Braun et al., 2019). The analysis
2456 followed an essentialist approach, assuming that participants' accounts of their experiences
2457 accurately reflected reality, and aiming to understand these experiences to provide an
2458 insight into the quantitative findings. The analysis was conducted by one researcher (HC),
2459 and a second researcher (KS) reviewed the dataset and the final report to verify the analysis
2460 was a complete and accurate representation of the data.

2461 Familiarisation was achieved through verbatim transcription and active rereading of the
2462 dataset. Throughout this phase the researcher noted aspects of the data that appeared

2463 relevant to the research question, and a list of potential codes was compiled based on these
2464 notes. Generation of codes followed a predominantly inductive approach; potential codes
2465 noted during familiarisation formed the basis of the analysis but the researcher coded openly
2466 for all aspects of the dataset that were relevant to the research question. Coding was based
2467 on the semantic content of the data. Once all data were subject to initial coding, themes
2468 were constructed by organising codes into groups to identify “patterns of shared meaning
2469 across the dataset” (Braun and Clarke, 2019, p. 592). Thematic maps were used to support
2470 this process and visualise how themes may connect to one another. Candidate themes were
2471 reviewed by examining all extracts within each theme to ensure they formed a coherent
2472 pattern, and short textual descriptions of each theme were produced and compared to
2473 ensure there were no areas of overlap; adjustments were made as needed. Finally, the
2474 entire dataset was reviewed to confirm the final themes were an accurate and complete
2475 representation of the data.

2476 **3.4 Results**

2477 **3.4.1 Participant characteristics**

2478 A summary of participant characteristics for all samples is given in Table 3.1. All samples
2479 comprised a mix of academics, research students and those employed in non-academic
2480 roles, such as in student services, the library, or as technicians. For the most part, the
2481 composition of the follow-up sample reflected the total sample for the original research.
2482 However, academic staff were slightly over-represented in the follow-up compared the
2483 original sample, whereas those in non-academic roles were slightly under-represented.
2484 Furthermore, while the proportion of participants who had kept fishes at any stage during
2485 their life was similar in both the original and follow-up samples, a higher percentage of
2486 participants in the follow-up were current fish guardians, whereas fewer had kept fishes
2487 during childhood.

2488 **Table 3.1 Participant characteristics for original and follow-up samples**

	Original sample (<i>n</i> = 57)			Follow-up (<i>n</i> = 13)
	Trial A (<i>n</i> = 30)	Trial B (<i>n</i> = 27)	Total (<i>n</i> = 57)	
Trial				
A	-	-	30 (53%)	5 (38%)
B	-	-	27 (47%)	8 (62%)
Campus				
1	22 (73%)	21 (78%)	43 (75%)	10 (77%)
2	8 (27%)	6 (22%)	14 (25%)	3 (23%)
Job role				
Academic	9 (30%)	8 (30%)	17 (30%)	6 (46%)
Research student	8 (27%)	7 (26%)	15 (26%)	3 (23%)
Other	13 (43%)	12 (44%)	25 (44%)	4 (31%)
Gender				
Male	8 (27%)	8 (30%)	16 (28%)	4 (31%)
Female	22 (73%)	19 (70%)	41 (72%)	9 (69%)
Age in years	39.73 ±11.05	41.41 ±11.88	40.53 ±11.38	40.54 ±11.29
Fish guardianship				
Any time	21 (70%)	20 (74%)	41 (72%)	10 (77%)
Childhood	15 (50%)	15 (56%)	30 (53%)	4 (31%)
Adult – not current	5 (17%)	7 (26%)	12 (21%)	3 (23%)
Adult – current	4 (13%)	4 (15%)	8 (14%)	3 (23%)
Dropout	0	5 (19%)	-	-

2489 Note: data for categorical variables are frequencies and percentages, data for continuous
2490 variables are means and standard deviations.

2491 3.4.2 Trial A

2492 3.4.2.1 Mood

2493 No significant differences were detected for positive affect across the three conditions ($p =$
2494 0.053), but a significant difference was detected between pre-test and post-test ($p = 0.001$,
2495 Figure 3.3a). Positive affect was higher at pre-test ($M_t = 29.63$, 95%CI [28.20, 31.10]) than at
2496 post-test ($M_t = 26.95$, 95%CI [25.56, 28.50]). A similar pattern of results was found for
2497 negative affect, with a significant difference between the two time points ($p = 0.007$, Figure
2498 3.3b), but not across the three conditions ($p = 0.225$). Negative affect also reduced from pre-
2499 test ($M_t = 12.87$, 95%CI [11.65, 13.80]) to post-test ($M_t = 10.91$, 95%CI [10.43, 11.26]). For

2500 perceived arousal, no significant differences were detected for either condition ($p = 0.513$) or
2501 time ($p = 0.878$), and the condition-by-time interaction was not significant for any dimension
2502 of mood (positive affect $p = 0.376$; negative affect, $p = 0.316$; and arousal, $p = 0.307$).

2503 Figure 3.3 Boxplots showing a) total positive affect and b) total negative affect at pre-test
 2504 and post-test for each condition. Asterisk (*) denotes significance at $p < 0.05$, "ns" denotes
 2505 non-significance. Data are 20% trimmed means (black circles), median, interquartile range
 2506 and outliers (white circles), $n = 30$.

2507 3.4.2.2 *Physiological outcomes*

2508 A significant difference in systolic blood pressure was detected between pre-test and post-
2509 test ($p < 0.001$, Figure 3.4a); systolic blood pressure reduced from pre-test ($M_t = 117.07$
2510 mmHg, 95%CI [114.06, 120.02]) to post-test ($M_t = 111.59$ mmHg, 95%CI [108.20, 114.20]).
2511 There was a significant difference in systolic blood pressure across the three conditions ($p =$
2512 0.047) although this was not detected post-hoc by pairwise comparisons with Rom's
2513 corrected alpha levels (control vs. aquarium, $\hat{\psi} = 0.78$ mmHg, 95%CI [-4.08, 5.63]; control
2514 vs. video, $\hat{\psi} = -3.56$ mmHg, 95%CI [-11.21, 4.10]; aquarium vs. video, $\hat{\psi} = -5.56$ mmHg,
2515 95%CI [-11.14, 0.03]). No significant differences were detected in diastolic blood pressure
2516 for either condition ($p = 0.781$) or time ($p = 0.463$), with no significant interactions between
2517 factors for either systolic ($p = 0.931$) or diastolic ($p = 0.670$) blood pressure. There was no
2518 evidence of a significant difference in cortisol concentrations for either condition (control vs.
2519 aquarium, $b = -20.31$, 95%CI [-396.94, 356.32]; control vs. video, $b = 247.43$, 95%CI
2520 [-133.37, 628.24]) or time ($b = 237.87$, 95%CI [-138.76, 614.50]). Similarly, there was no
2521 significant change in heart rate from pre-test to mid-activity ($b = -3.42$, 95%CI [-9.24, 2.40])
2522 or pre-test to post-test ($b = -0.66$, 95%CI [-6.39, 5.06]), and heart rate was not affected by
2523 condition (control vs. aquarium, $b = -2.03$, 95%CI [-7.71, 3.65]; control vs. video, $b = -2.80$,
2524 95%CI [-8.49, 2.90]). No significant condition-by-time interactions were detected for either
2525 cortisol concentrations or heart rate (95% confidence intervals crossed zero in both cases).

2526

2527 Figure 3.4 Boxplots showing a) systolic blood pressure and b) diastolic blood pressure at
 2528 pre-test and post-test for each condition. Asterisk (*) denotes significance at $p < 0.05$, "ns"
 2529 denotes non-significance. Data are 20% trimmed means (black circles), median, interquartile
 2530 range and outliers (white circles), $n = 30$.

2531 3.4.2.3 Cognitive performance

2532 No significant difference was found for time taken to complete the SCWT across the three
2533 conditions ($p = 0.606$), but there was a significant effect of time ($p < 0.001$, Figure 3.5a) with
2534 participants completing the SCWT faster at post-test ($M_t = 86.48$ s, 95%CI [83.91, 89.33])
2535 than at pre-test ($M_t = 93.22$ s, 95%CI [89.13, 96.81]). The number of errors made on the
2536 SCWT were not affected by condition ($p = 0.325$) or time ($p = 0.080$), with no significant
2537 interactions between condition and time for either number of errors ($p = 0.329$) or time taken
2538 to complete the SCWT ($p = 0.823$). Performance on the digit span tasks did not differ
2539 between pre- and post-test (DSF, $p = 0.254$; DSB, $p = 0.554$), and there was no effect of
2540 condition on DSB ($p = 0.095$), but there was a significant effect of condition on DSF ($p =$
2541 0.008 , Figure 3.6a). Pairwise comparisons with Rom's corrected alpha levels indicated that
2542 participants' performance on the DSF was higher in the video than the control condition ($\hat{\psi} =$
2543 -0.78 , 95%CI [-1.42, -0.14]) and the aquarium condition ($\hat{\psi} = -1.00$, 95%CI [-1.53, -0.47]), but
2544 there was no difference between the control and aquarium condition ($\hat{\psi} = 0.06$, 95%CI
2545 [-0.77, 0.88]). No significant interactions were detected between condition and time for either
2546 DSF ($p = 0.395$) or DSB ($p = 0.814$).

2547 Figure 3.5 Boxplots showing a) time taken to complete b) number of errors made on the
 2548 Stroop Colour-Word Task at pre-test and post-test for each condition. Asterisk (*) denotes
 2549 significance at $p < 0.05$, "ns" denotes non-significance. Data are 20% trimmed means (black
 2550 circles), median, interquartile range and outliers (white circles), $n = 30$.

2551 Figure 3.6 Boxplots showing a) digit span forward b) digit span backward at pre- and post-
 2552 test for each condition. Asterisk (*) denotes significance at $p < 0.05$, "ns" denotes non-
 2553 significance. Data are 20% trimmed means (black circles), median, interquartile range and
 2554 outliers (white circles), $n = 30$.

2555 **3.4.3 Trial B**

2556 *3.4.3.1 Psychological well-being*

2557 All outcomes were significantly predicted by participants' scores at baseline ($b = 0.47-1.01$,
2558 $SE = 0.07-0.17$, 95%CI [0.14-0.78, 0.67-1.24]), but not their job satisfaction (95%CI crossed
2559 zero in all cases) and so the latter covariate was removed from each model. Condition did
2560 not significantly predict depression (control vs. aquarium, $b = -1.21$, $SE = 0.61$, 95%CI
2561 [-2.39, 0.02]; control vs. video, $b = -0.77$, $SE = 0.57$, 95%CI [-1.92, 0.38]), anxiety (control vs.
2562 aquarium, $b = -0.32$, $SE = 0.25$, 95%CI [-0.81, 0.18]; control vs. video, $b = -0.30$, $SE = 0.24$,
2563 95%CI [-0.78, 0.18]), or stress (control vs. aquarium, $b = -0.90$, $SE = 1.13$, 95%CI [-3.11,
2564 1.32]; control vs. video, $b = 0.23$, $SE = 1.09$, 95%CI [-1.91, 2.37]), and additional
2565 comparisons showed no significant difference between the two fish conditions and the
2566 control, or between the aquarium and video conditions for any variable (95% confidence
2567 interval crossed zero in all cases).

2568 Condition significantly predicted some aspects of job-related affective well-being (Figure
2569 3.7). Specifically, total scores for job-related affective well-being were significantly higher
2570 following engagement in the video condition compared to the control condition ($b = 3.67$, SE
2571 $= 1.16$, 95%CI [1.10, 5.64]), but not following engagement in the aquarium condition
2572 compared to the control condition ($b = 0.88$, $SE = 1.20$, 95%CI [-1.47, 3.23]). The same
2573 pattern of results was observed for both the "high pleasure-high arousal" (control vs.
2574 aquarium, $b = 0.82$, $SE = 0.48$, 95%CI [-0.13, 1.77]; control vs. video, $b = 0.98$, $SE = 0.47$,
2575 95%CI [0.06, 1.90]) and "high pleasure-low arousal" (control vs. aquarium, $b = -0.04$, $SE =$
2576 0.51 , 95%CI [-1.04, 0.97]; control vs. video, $b = 1.33$, $SE = 0.50$, 95%CI [0.36, 2.30])
2577 subscales. Sensitivity analyses indicated that these effects were robust for total job-related
2578 affective well-being (control vs. aquarium, $b = 0.40$, $SE = 1.24$, 95%CI [-2.03, 2.82]; control
2579 vs. video, $b = 3.54$, $SE = 1.24$, 95%CI [1.11, 5.96]) and the "high pleasure-low arousal"
2580 subscale (control vs. aquarium, $b = -0.14$, $SE = 0.54$, 95%CI [-1.20, 0.91]; control vs. video,
2581 $b = 1.51$, $SE = 0.54$, 95%CI [0.45, 2.56]) but not the "high pleasure-high arousal" subscale

2582 (control vs. aquarium, $b = 0.61$, $SE = 0.49$, $95\%CI = [-0.36, 1.58]$; control vs. video, $b = 0.62$,
2583 $SE = 0.49$, $95\%CI [-0.35, 1.59]$). Additional comparisons showed no difference between the
2584 two fish conditions and the control for any aspect of job-related affective well-being; this
2585 comparison was significant for the “high pleasure-high arousal” subscale, but sensitivity
2586 analyses indicated that this effect was not robust ($95\%CI$ crossed zero). Watching the fish
2587 video was found to have a greater effect than watching the live fishes for both total job-
2588 related affective well-being ($b = 1.60$, $SE = 0.62$, $95\%CI [0.36, 2.78]$) and the “high pleasure-
2589 low arousal” subscale ($b = 0.83$, $SE = 0.27$, $95\%CI [0.30, 1.35]$). Neither the “low pleasure-
2590 high arousal” (control vs. aquarium, $b = -0.20$, $SE = 0.54$, $95\%CI [-1.26, 0.86]$; control vs.
2591 video, $b = -0.50$, $SE = 0.53$, $95\%CI [-1.53, 0.52]$) or “low pleasure-low arousal” (control vs.
2592 aquarium, $b = -0.02$, $SE = 0.46$, $95\%CI [-0.93, 0.89]$; control vs. video, $b = -0.63$, $SE = 0.45$,
2593 $95\%CI [-1.51, 0.25]$) subscales were significantly predicted by engagement in the aquarium
2594 or video conditions, and additional comparisons were not significant for either dependent
2595 variable ($95\%CI$ crossed zero in all cases).

2596 Figure 3.7 Boxplots showing a) total job-related affective well-being, b) high pleasure-high arousal subscale and c) high pleasure-low pleasure
 2597 subscale after engagement in each condition. Asterisk (*) denotes significance at $p < 0.05$, "ns" denotes non-significance. Data are means
 2598 (black circles), median, interquartile range and outliers (white circles), $n = 24$.

2599 Changes in psychological outcomes across the 12-week trial are shown in Table 3.2.
2600 Significant reductions in scores for depression ($b = -1.28$, $SE = 0.65$, 95%CI [-2.54, -0.01])
2601 and stress ($b = -2.88$, $SE = 1.28$, 95%CI [-5.38, -0.37]) were observed at the end of the study
2602 compared to baseline; a significant reduction in anxiety scores was also observed but
2603 sensitivity analyses indicated that this effect may not be robust (see Table 3.2). No change
2604 was detected for total job-related affective well-being but scores for the “high pleasure-high
2605 arousal” ($b = -1.15$, $SE = 0.53$, 95%CI [-2.19, -0.11]) and both “low pleasure” (low pleasure-
2606 high arousal, $b = -1.66$, $SE = 0.52$, 95%CI [-2.68, -0.65]; low pleasure-low arousal, $b = -1.23$,
2607 $SE = 0.43$, 95%CI [-2.06, -0.39]) subscales were significantly lower at the end of the second
2608 study period (week 8) compared to baseline. For the subset of participants with complete
2609 data, these effects remained at the end of the study (week 12) for the “high pleasure-high
2610 arousal” and “low pleasure-low arousal” subscales (see Table 3.2). No changes were
2611 detected for the “high pleasure-low arousal” subscale across the 12-week study (95%CI
2612 crossed zero in all cases).

2613 3.4.3.2 *Physiological outcomes*

2614 The results of the robust linear mixed models for physiological outcomes correspond with the
2615 findings from Trial A. Specifically, systolic blood pressure significantly reduced from pre- to
2616 post-activity during the testing sessions ($b = -9.59$, $SE = 2.35$, 95%CI [-14.20, -4.97]), but
2617 there was no evidence of a significant difference across conditions (control vs. aquarium, $b =$
2618 -2.52 , $SE = 2.40$, 95%CI [-7.23, 2.19]; control vs. video, $b = -2.54$, $SE = 2.37$, 95%CI [-7.18,
2619 2.10]). Neither diastolic blood pressure nor heart rate significantly differed by condition or
2620 time, and the condition-by-time interaction was not significant for any outcome (95%CI
2621 crossed zero in all cases). Additional comparisons indicated no significant differences
2622 between the two fish conditions and the control, or between the aquarium and video
2623 conditions for any physiological outcome (95%CI crossed zero in all cases).

Table 3.2 Results of robust linear mixed models to examine changes in psychological outcomes across the 12-week study

	Analyses of all available data					Sensitivity analyses (complete data only)				
	<i>n</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	Lower 95%CI	Upper 95%CI	<i>n</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	Lower 95%CI	Upper 95%CI
Depression (0 = Baseline)										
Week 4	27	0.19	0.63	-1.04	1.42	19	-0.03	0.78	-1.55	1.49
Week 8		-0.66	0.63	-1.89	0.57		-0.70	0.78	-2.21	0.82
Week 12		-1.28	0.65	-2.54	-0.01		-1.68	0.78	-3.20	-0.17
Anxiety (0 = Baseline)										
Week 4	26	-0.48	0.39	-1.23	0.28	19	-0.58	0.50	-1.55	0.40
Week 8		-0.79	0.39	-1.55	-0.03		-0.70	0.50	-1.67	0.27
Week 12		-0.84	0.40	-1.62	-0.06		-0.92	0.50	-1.90	0.05
Stress (0 = Baseline)										
Week 4	27	-0.55	1.24	-2.98	1.89	18	-1.06	1.48	-3.96	1.84
Week 8		-0.16	1.24	-2.60	2.27		-0.43	1.48	-3.34	2.47
Week 12		-2.88	1.28	-5.38	-0.37		-3.24	1.48	-6.14	-0.34
JAWS Total (0 = Baseline)										
Week 4	27	1.30	1.34	-1.32	3.91	19	0.81	1.45	-2.03	3.65
Week 8		1.70	1.34	-0.91	4.32		1.08	1.45	-1.76	3.92
Week 12		-0.16	1.38	-2.86	2.54		-0.05	1.45	-2.88	2.79

JAWS-HPHA (0 = Baseline)											
Week 4			-0.49	0.53	-1.53	0.55		-0.96	0.55	-2.03	0.11
Week 8	27		-1.15	0.53	-2.19	-0.11	19	-1.75	0.55	-2.82	-0.68
Week 12			-1.05	0.55	-2.12	0.03		-1.32	0.55	-2.39	-0.25
JAWS-HPLA (0 = Baseline)											
Week 4			0.32	0.60	-0.85	1.49		0.39	0.67	-0.93	1.70
Week 8	27		-0.38	0.60	-1.55	0.79	19	-0.33	0.67	-1.65	0.98
Week 12			-0.62	0.62	-1.83	0.59		-0.35	0.67	-1.67	0.96
JAWS-LPHA (0 = Baseline)											
Week 4			-0.37	0.52	-1.39	0.64		-0.36	0.61	-1.56	0.84
Week 8	27		-1.66	0.52	-2.68	-0.65	19	-1.75	0.61	-2.95	-0.55
Week 12			-0.66	0.53	-1.70	0.39		-0.80	0.61	-2.00	0.41
JAWS-LPLA (0 = Baseline)											
Week 4			-0.64	0.43	-1.47	0.20		-0.76	0.51	-1.76	0.24
Week 8	27		-1.23	0.43	-2.06	-0.39	19	-1.31	0.51	-2.31	-0.32
Week 12			-0.85	0.44	-1.72	0.01		-1.01	0.51	-2.01	-0.01

2625
2626

Note: *b* are unstandardised regression coefficients, results in bold are significant as determined by the 95% confidence intervals not crossing zero.

2627 **3.4.4 Follow-up**

2628 Three themes were developed from the qualitative data. “Live fishes are more engaging than
2629 videos” relates to the idea that many participants felt that watching the live fishes was a
2630 more pleasurable and immersive experience than watching them on video. “It was good to
2631 get out of the office” and “Just taking ten minutes was beneficial” highlight that many
2632 participants experienced benefits from the research that were unrelated to the experimental
2633 conditions; these themes provide insight into the quantitative findings and how the
2634 implementation of an aquarium-based intervention might best work in practice.

2635 *3.4.4.1 Live fishes are more engaging than videos*

2636 Most participants described watching the live fishes as a calming and peaceful activity,
2637 which for some also provided interest and stimulation. By comparison, watching the video
2638 was described as lacking ‘something’, despite participants recognising it was of a high
2639 quality and aesthetically similar to the aquarium. For example, participants stated: “...it
2640 doesn’t make sense why watching a video or watching them live would be any different, but I
2641 definitely felt more engaged with watching the live fish than the video...” (Participant 5,
2642 Focus Group 1, Trial A), and “...although it was interesting even in the video to watch their
2643 behaviour, yeah it’s not that same as watching live fish or live animals is it? I still found it
2644 relaxing but just not in the same way...” (Participant 8, Focus Group 4, Trial B).

2645 Some participants felt a connection to the live fishes, expressing interest in their behaviours
2646 and social dynamics, for example: “...I started imagining they had little communities and
2647 there was like a bully fish and there was a big fat fish, and it was like ‘what’s going on with
2648 them?’...” (Participant 10, Focus Group 3, Trial B), and “...I found it quite interesting just to
2649 watch them and try and figure out like different, different characters in a way because
2650 obviously there was different types of fish in there...” (Participant 6, Focus Group 2, Trial B).

2651 In contrast, when watching the fishes on video, participants conveyed feeling a level of
2652 detachment and often found themselves focusing on the technical aspects of the set-up. For
2653 instance: “...I actually was thinking to myself ‘I’m watching a video of fish’ which in itself was

2654 a distraction to me although I did find it quite peaceful eventually, but I kept thinking ‘why am
2655 I watching this?’ and for the fish one, I found that – the words that I’ve used are pleasurable,
2656 thoughtful, and peaceful, it’s a pleasurable experience to me...” (Participant 7, Focus Group
2657 1, Trial A) and “... [when watching the video] rather than thinking about them, considering
2658 them as live animals, I started to think about ‘is this a live feed from a live fish tank?’ Which I
2659 knew it wasn’t because the fish tank was sitting behind the screen and of course it was a
2660 different room that it was actually filmed in, and ‘is it on a loop? Are these fish still alive? And
2661 what’s happened to my favourite big fat fish?’ Things like that...” (Participant 10, Focus
2662 Group 2, Trial B).

2663 These findings suggest that watching live fishes may provide a more engaging experience
2664 than watching a video of fishes. Nevertheless, several participants reported that all three
2665 conditions were beneficial; this is in line with the quantitative findings which, for the most
2666 part, found no significant differences between the three conditions. One possible explanation
2667 for this finding is that the presence of the covered aquarium during the video and control
2668 conditions had a positive effect on participants in all conditions; some participants noted that
2669 the sound of the aquarium filter helped to induce relaxation, and one reported that the smell
2670 from the fish tank elicited happy memories about fishes kept in childhood. As these effects
2671 would have been present irrespective of whether participants could see the live fishes,
2672 positive effects associated with the control and video conditions may be partially attributable
2673 to the presence of the covered aquarium.

2674 *3.4.4.2 It was good to get out of the office*

2675 Although this research was conducted within the workplace, the experimental sessions were
2676 conducted away from participants’ own offices, and several participants expressed that
2677 being away from their desk for that short period of time was in itself beneficial. Some
2678 participants likened the experience to taking an actual lunchbreak, as opposed to eating
2679 lunch at your desk; afterwards they felt more refreshed and had greater motivation to keep
2680 working. Although a small number of participants mentioned that the brief walk from their

2681 office to the testing location contributed to this effect, of greater importance was participants
2682 experiencing psychological distance from their work, which the change of location helped
2683 them to achieve. For instance, one participant stated:

2684 "...I certainly appreciated the fact that I was coming over to you and to part of the building
2685 that I didn't even know actually, it was good to come to somewhere totally different where I
2686 wasn't going to meet anybody from my office or anybody who was going to be asking any
2687 questions or starting up any conversations, it was absolutely separate which was good..."
2688 (Participant 8, Focus Group 4, Trial B).

2689 When considering the implementation of either a live aquarium or fish video within their
2690 office, several participants expressed that this environment might not be acquiescent to
2691 relaxation, particularly for those based in large, open-plan offices. These environments were
2692 considered too noisy and full of distractions for a fish tank or video to have any meaningful
2693 impact on well-being. Several participants expressed that an aquarium located within a quiet
2694 communal area, such as a break room, may have greater benefits as it would allow
2695 individuals a chance to get away from their desk and relax without work-related disruptions.
2696 For instance, one participant stated "...I personally would feel that putting an aquarium in a
2697 different location to what your desk would be, would help because it's just another way of
2698 removing yourself from the stress and the noise of that desk..." (Participant 5, Focus Group
2699 1, Trial A). It was also noted that locating the aquarium away from the office might have the
2700 added benefit of preventing it from becoming a normalised, for example: "...I think having the
2701 ability to go away somewhere specific and kind of yeah, immerse yourself and have a bit
2702 more of an experience would make it a bit more novel and a bit more unique ..." (Participant
2703 1, Focus Group 1, Trial B).

2704 Despite these perceptions, most participants could anticipate positive outcomes associated
2705 with the presence of an aquarium in their office. Watching the fishes for a brief period of time
2706 was expected to provide momentary relief, helping individuals to gather their thoughts and
2707 maintain focus. There was a general preference for live fishes over fish videos, as it was

2708 recognised that a live aquarium would have the benefit of diverting attention away from
2709 computer screens. However, some participants argued that this would be dependent on the
2710 size of the office and how the video was displayed within that space. For example, one
2711 participant stated: "...if it's a tiny little screen in a big office then it might seem a bit ridiculous
2712 but if it's maybe big enough and realistic enough that you almost forget that it's a screen
2713 then I think you know, it would work..." (Participant 5, Focus Group 1, Trial A).

2714 These findings suggest that conducting sessions away from participants' own offices likely
2715 influenced results in the current study; most participants perceived some degree of benefit
2716 from all three conditions, as the change of location afforded them psychological distance
2717 from their work. Correspondingly, many participants felt that the use of fish aquaria to
2718 promote well-being in the workplace may be of most success if the aquarium is located away
2719 from employees' desks. Nevertheless, positive outcomes were anticipated with regards to
2720 the presence of live or virtual aquaria within the office, provided the size and layout of the
2721 office space is taken into account when installing such features.

2722 *3.4.4.3 Just taking ten minutes was beneficial*

2723 Several participants expressed that taking time out of work to focus on their well-being was
2724 an unfamiliar concept, and in particular the idea of 'doing nothing' was completely alien. For
2725 this reason, most participants appeared to feel one of two ways towards the control
2726 condition. Some greatly appreciated the opportunity to sit quietly for 10 minutes, describing
2727 their experience as pleasant and peaceful, for example one participant stated "...I felt the
2728 control was – the words I've written were 'mind-clearing', 'calming' and 'reflective' – because
2729 it was the only time of your day really, where you just basically sit and look into space, so
2730 that was actually really enjoyable..." (Participant 3, Focus Group 2, Trial B). However, some
2731 participants found that sitting quietly without stimulus was quite stressful; they continued to
2732 think about work and everything they could be doing with that time. For example participants
2733 stated "...the quiet condition just made me think too much into my own head..." (Participant
2734 5, Focus Group 1, Trial A) and "...I actually found it quite stressful sitting staring at a blank

2735 wall because I started to think about all the things I should be doing and where I should be
2736 and what I should be catching up on..." (Participant 4, Focus Group 1, Trial A). Participants
2737 in the latter group expressed a clear preference for the aquarium and video conditions, as
2738 having something to focus on helped take their mind off work and prevent this rumination.

2739 Several participants noted that their responses to any intervention would differ according to
2740 their day-to-day circumstances; taking time for well-being on a particularly busy day may
2741 have negative consequences, as it would feel like they were wasting time. Nevertheless,
2742 participants expressed that allocating time for their well-being had been a beneficial act, for
2743 example "...having that time out, even just for that short time every week I think really
2744 helped, and it was definitely worthwhile..." (Participant 9, Focus Group 3, Trial B). To some
2745 extent, the current 'intervention' being part of a research project alleviated participants'
2746 feelings of guilt about being away from their desk for reasons unrelated to work; it allowed
2747 them to schedule the sessions in their diaries, and meant they felt better able to justify their
2748 use of time. For example, one participant commented:

2749 "...the thing that I found most useful from the experiment was allocating the time on my
2750 calendar where I was out with my office, I was doing something and it can be seen that I was
2751 doing something and I wasn't expected to answer emails or do anything else ..." (Participant
2752 7, Focus Group 1, Trial A).

2753 Some participants noted that these feelings of guilt could be overcome by locating tanks
2754 within the office, as this could eliminate individuals' worries about being away from their
2755 desk, for instance:

2756 "...if it was actually integrated into the workplace so you had a fish video on a television
2757 screen in your office or as a desktop background or a fish tank on the wall or something, I
2758 think that would probably make a difference, you wouldn't feel as guilty about what you were
2759 doing because you're not actually taking time away to go and do it, it's just something that's
2760 in the background..." (Participant 2, Focus Group 1, Trial A).

2761 These findings confirm that there is a need for interventions that promote workplace well-
2762 being among the studied population, which is unsurprising given that this population was
2763 chosen in part due to a higher than average prevalence of work-related stress, anxiety, and
2764 depression. Consequently, it appears that for many participants all three conditions were
2765 perceived to have positive effects because they provided a brief period of respite. This
2766 corresponds with the quantitative findings, which for the most part identified no significant
2767 differences between the conditions but did show evidence of improvement for several
2768 psychological outcomes from baseline to the end of Trial B. Furthermore, these findings
2769 highlight that for any workplace intervention (whether aquarium-based or not) to be
2770 successful, engagement in the intervention needs to become a normal and accepted part of
2771 working life; allowing employees to book time for well-being into their diaries might support
2772 this process. Alternatively, the presence of fish aquaria within the office might be a more
2773 sustainable and practical option.

2774 **3.5 Discussion**

2775 The purpose of this research was to investigate whether watching an aquarium during the
2776 working day influenced employee well-being and cognitive performance. Previous research
2777 has identified that watching fishes live or on video may induce relaxation in other populations
2778 (e.g. Wells, 2005, Gee et al., 2019), and the presence of animals and nature in the
2779 workplace has been associated with reduced stress (e.g. Barker et al., 2012, Largo-Wight et
2780 al., 2017). However, no studies have examined the effects of watching ornamental fishes in
2781 a workplace setting. Two experimental studies were conducted under controlled conditions,
2782 with a sample of participants who took part during their working day, and whose occupations
2783 are typically associated with higher than average rates of work-related stress, anxiety and
2784 depression (Health and Safety Executive, 2020).

2785 In Trial A, it was hypothesised that watching an aquarium would lead to a greater increase in
2786 relaxation than resting quietly for the same time period; this would be evidenced by greater
2787 improvements in mood and cognitive performance, and greater reductions in perceived

2788 arousal and physiological stress. It was further hypothesised that this effect would be greater
2789 after viewing an aquarium containing live fishes than after watching a video of the same
2790 aquarium. The data did not support these hypotheses. Although there were improvements in
2791 some outcomes (negative affect, systolic blood pressure and time taken to complete the
2792 SCWT) from baseline to post-activity, no significant condition-by-time interactions were
2793 detected for any outcome.

2794 Similar patterns of results have been observed in past research. For instance, DeSchraver
2795 and Riddick (1990) found that viewing a live fish aquarium or fish video had no greater
2796 impact on physiological arousal than viewing a placebo video, but all conditions were
2797 perceived to be relaxing, and Cracknell et al. (2016) found that observing a public aquarium
2798 exhibit led to improvements in mood over time, but these effects did not differ by level of
2799 stocking (unstocked, partially stocked or fully stocked). Although Gee et al. (2019) did
2800 identify significantly greater perceptions of relaxation and mood following observation of a
2801 live fish aquarium compared to observation of an empty tank or one containing only plants,
2802 no consistent effects were identified for physiological outcomes. This suggests that while
2803 watching ornamental fishes might be associated with improvements in psychological,
2804 physiological and/or cognitive outcomes, these effects may be no greater than those
2805 achieved through resting quietly with no stimulus. It is also possible that the benefits of
2806 aquaria go beyond the visual dimension. Several participants in the current study noted that
2807 the sound produced by the aquarium filter enhanced relaxation; this corresponds with past
2808 research showing that nature sounds promote restoration (Franco, Shanahan and Fuller,
2809 2017). As the sound of the filter was present throughout all conditions, it is unclear how the
2810 effects of watching fishes might be influenced by the engaging of senses other than sight.

2811 In Trial B, it was hypothesised that repeated observation of the fishes over several weeks
2812 would lead to greater improvements in psychological and physiological well-being compared
2813 to repeatedly engaging in the control condition; watching the live aquarium was again
2814 predicted to have a greater effect than watching the video. Findings were less

2815 straightforward than for Trial A. There was no evidence that watching the live aquarium had
2816 a greater impact on psychological or physiological well-being than the control condition, but
2817 watching the fish video was associated with significantly higher scores for job-related
2818 affective well-being. Further examination indicated that this effect was due to higher scores
2819 for the “high pleasure-low arousal” subscale; an effect was also detected for the “high
2820 pleasure-high arousal” subscale, but sensitivity analysis indicated that this effect was not
2821 robust.

2822 It is not clear why watching videos of fishes, but not live fishes, would be associated with an
2823 increase in high pleasure-low arousal emotions, particularly as qualitative follow-up data
2824 indicated that participants tended to prefer watching the live fishes to the video. Attention
2825 Restoration Theory (Kaplan, 1995) draws a distinction between hard fascination and soft
2826 fascination; both refer to the capturing of attention by a stimulus, but while hard fascination
2827 requires complete attention, soft fascination leaves scope for reflection and the processing of
2828 internal noise (Basu, Duvall and Kaplan, 2019). Although theory would indicate that watching
2829 fishes involves soft fascination, it was evident from the qualitative data that participants
2830 found the live fishes to be more engaging than the fish video. Perhaps the novelty of seeing
2831 the live animals demanded more attention than watching the same animals on video, thus
2832 impeding opportunity for reflection. Further research is needed to determine whether the
2833 effects of watching fishes may be influenced by the novelty of the activity.

2834 Qualitative data indicated that many participants found that taking part in the research was
2835 beneficial irrespective of the activity completed during sessions. Consistently, additional
2836 analysis of data collected in Trial B indicated that several psychological outcomes improved
2837 over time, irrespective of condition. While this effect cannot be conclusively attributed to
2838 participation in the study, qualitative data suggest a potential mechanism through which this
2839 effect occurred; sessions were located away from participants’ desks and this change of
2840 location afforded them an opportunity to experience psychological distance from their work.
2841 This is consistent with research in the field of occupational psychology, which has shown

2842 that psychological detachment from work, including both refraining from job-related activities
2843 and job-related thoughts, promotes recovery from work (Sonnentag, 2012). Although
2844 psychological detachment typically refers to recovery during non-work hours, it can arguably
2845 also be achieved at work during periods of rest (Sonnentag and Fritz, 2015). Some
2846 participants appeared to achieve psychological detachment across all conditions, however,
2847 this was not a universal experience and several reported finding the control condition
2848 particularly stressful. Consistent with the theory that animals may promote well-being by
2849 capturing attention and diverting it away from negative states (Beetz, 2017), these
2850 participants seemed to prefer the two fish conditions as they provided an alternative point of
2851 focus. Further research is needed to identify whether watching fishes during rest breaks has
2852 a greater impact on well-being for employees who find it difficult to detach from work.

2853 Although it did not translate to the quantitative findings, it was evident from the qualitative
2854 data that participants found the live fishes more engaging than the video. This is consistent
2855 with research which has indicated that live fishes readily capture and hold human attention
2856 (e.g. Windhager et al., 2011, Cracknell et al., 2016). As participants in the current study were
2857 directed to watch the fishes, it is unclear whether different effects would have been observed
2858 if engagement with the fishes or video was self-directed. It is also noteworthy that the control
2859 condition did not reflect a break that would typically be experienced within the workplace.

2860 During this condition participants rested quietly with no external stimuli, and several reported
2861 this experience of 'doing nothing' was unusual even if they found it enjoyable. Research has
2862 indicated that the activities undertaken during a rest break can influence the effectiveness of
2863 that break (Fritz et al., 2013). For example, using a smartphone has been linked to a lower
2864 reduction in emotional exhaustion than conventional break activities such as napping or
2865 walking (Rhee and Kim, 2016), and the use of a laptop computer can counteract the
2866 beneficial effects of nature exposure on attention (Jiang, Schmillen and Sullivan, 2019).
2867 Therefore, different effects may be observed where rest breaks are self-directed. If live

2868 fishes readily capture attention, the presence of an aquarium in a break room may be
2869 beneficial as it could redirect attention away from electronic devices.

2870 Alternatively, an aquarium located within the office may encourage employees to take micro-
2871 breaks. These are short, informal breaks which occur spontaneously during work but are not
2872 directly related to work activities, and are often taken in response to fatigue (Henning et al.,
2873 1989, Fritz, Lam and Spreitzer, 2011, Lee et al., 2015). Performance on a task of sustained
2874 attention was higher among participants who viewed nature during a microbreak, compared
2875 to those who viewed an urban environment (Lee et al., 2015). As aquaria are a form of
2876 indoor nature (Largo-Wight et al., 2011), it is possible that briefly observing fishes would
2877 have similar effects if an aquarium were located within the office environment.

2878 **3.5.1 Strengths and limitations**

2879 Experimental research regarding the benefits of ornamental fishes has frequently involved
2880 student samples (e.g. Wells, 2005, Buttelman and Römpke, 2014, Cracknell et al., 2016,
2881 Gee et al., 2019). The current sample was drawn from a population that includes several
2882 professions associated with higher than average work-related stress, anxiety and depression
2883 (Health and Safety Executive, 2020), and participants completed the research during their
2884 working day. This enhances generalisability of the findings to the target population (i.e.
2885 individuals experiencing work-related stress). Furthermore, this was the first study to
2886 investigate the impact of engagement with ornamental fishes on cognitive performance.

2887 Previous research has demonstrated interaction with dogs and cats may influence cognition
2888 (e.g. Allen, Shykoff and Izzo, 2001, Gee et al., 2015) and theories of restoration predict that
2889 exposure to nature enhances cognitive performance, either through restoration of directed
2890 attention (Attention Restoration Theory) or recovery from psychophysiological stress (Stress
2891 Recovery Theory). Therefore, it is important to understand under which circumstances (if
2892 any) engagement with ornamental fishes may have similar effects.

2893 The use of a controlled level of exposure to the fishes was both a strength and weakness of
2894 this study. The theoretical frameworks on which this research was based would suggest that

2895 any benefits associated with ornamental fishes occur primarily through visual exposure.
2896 Thus, controlling exposure prevented other factors associated with the presence of an
2897 aquarium in the workplace from influencing the study findings. On the other hand, this level
2898 of engagement was unlikely to reflect how employees would engage with ornamental fishes
2899 in their workplace. Therefore, further research is needed to understand the ways in which
2900 people engage with fishes at work, and how this may influence employee well-being.
2901 Qualitative methods may be particularly useful in identifying potential mechanisms and
2902 refining theories regarding the potential effects of fishes in the workplace.

2903 A key finding from the qualitative data was that participants found the live fishes more
2904 engaging than the video. However, HAI research is subject to self-selection biases; typically
2905 only individuals who enjoy interacting with animals will participate (Friedmann and Gee,
2906 2019). This was likely exaggerated within the qualitative aspect of this research, as social
2907 desirability biases may have prevented individuals with less positive opinions from
2908 participating in the follow-up. In future research, this could be overcome by obtaining
2909 feedback from all participants *via* an anonymous process.

2910 **3.5.2 Conclusions**

2911 The findings of this research did not support the premise that watching live fishes in the
2912 workplace has a greater impact on employee well-being and cognitive performance than
2913 watching a fish video, or resting quietly. Conversely, repeatedly viewing fish videos over
2914 several weeks was associated with greater job-related affective well-being, specifically in
2915 relation to high pleasure-low arousal emotions. The reason for this finding is unclear;
2916 possibly the less engaging nature of the fish video placed a lesser demand on the attention
2917 of participants than watching the live fishes, thus allowing them the mental space needed to
2918 engage in reflection. Further research is needed to examine this theory. Qualitative data
2919 indicated that psychological detachment from work was important for participants to
2920 experience benefits from any condition; this is in line with past research and suggests that
2921 aquaria may be of greatest benefit if placed within break rooms. Alternatively, the placement

2922 of aquaria within the office may be beneficial, as the ability of fishes to spontaneously
2923 capture human attention might encourage employees to engage in microbreaks. Therefore,
2924 further research is needed to understand how employees engage with fishes in the
2925 workplace, and whether this engagement influences employee well-being and cognition.

2926 **Chapter 4.**

2927 **Employee experiences of fishes in the workplace: A**

2928 **qualitative study**

2929 **4.1 Abstract**

2930 Human energy is a finite resource, and among employees the replenishment of energy is
2931 critical for positive well-being and performance; microbreaks may support this replenishment
2932 by providing momentary recovery. In the previous chapter, qualitative data suggested that
2933 watching live fishes was perceived as more engaging than watching fish videos or resting
2934 quietly. This corresponds with past research showing that live fishes are effective at
2935 capturing and holding attention. Therefore, fish tanks located within offices may
2936 spontaneously capture and hold human attention, thus promoting engagement in
2937 microbreaks. The purpose of this study was to develop an insight into the experiences of
2938 employees regarding the installation of aquaria in the workplace, to determine whether the
2939 presence of live fishes might promote microbreaks. As there are potential issues regarding
2940 the practicalities of installing aquaria in workplaces, the study also sought to identify barriers
2941 and facilitators regarding the presence of fishes in the workplace. Qualitative data were
2942 collected from three workplaces in West Scotland. A standard aquarium set-up was installed
2943 in each workplace and maintained by the researcher for a minimum of one month. Focus
2944 groups and interviews were then conducted with employees ($n = 13$) from each workplace,
2945 and data were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis. Three themes were developed.
2946 *Fishes may enhance rest breaks* highlighted that many participants engaged with the fishes
2947 in combination with other microbreak activities (e.g. getting coffee), though some participants
2948 reported not engaging with the fishes at all. *The importance of live fishes* related to the
2949 participants' appreciation of the 'aliveness' of the fishes, and the sense of connection many
2950 felt towards the animals. *Who will look after the fishes?* related to participants' concerns
2951 regarding maintenance of the aquaria. The study findings indicated that while participants do
2952 engage with fishes during microbreaks, the presence of fishes does not appear to prompt
2953 engagement in microbreaks. Furthermore, there were clear concerns about who would care
2954 for the fishes, and so any employer considering installation of an aquarium must carefully
2955 consider how fish welfare will be maintained within the working environment.

2956 **4.2 Introduction**

2957 Human energy is a limited resource which when depleted due to work demands can lead to
2958 negative consequences including stress, exhaustion and burnout (Trougakos and Hideg,
2959 2009, Fritz, Lam and Spreitzer, 2011). Replenishment of energy is therefore critical for
2960 employee well-being and productivity, and recovery from work is the process through which
2961 this replenishment occurs; during breaks from work employees have the opportunity to
2962 unwind and recover depleted energy resources (Fritz, Lam and Spreitzer, 2011, Fritz et al.,
2963 2013). Psychological detachment, whereby employees refrain from engaging in or thinking
2964 about work-related tasks, has been identified as an important aspect of recovery
2965 (Sonnentag, 2012, von Dreden and Binnewies, 2017). Correspondingly, most research on
2966 recovery has focused on time away from work, such as during vacations or at evenings and
2967 weekends (Fritz et al., 2013). However, recovery can also occur at work either during
2968 scheduled breaktimes or during microbreaks (Fritz et al., 2013, Kim, Park and Niu, 2017).

2969 Microbreaks are short, informal breaks which occur between work activities, provide
2970 momentary recovery, and may be taken in response to fatigue or the need for respite (Jett
2971 and George, 2003, Trougakos and Hideg, 2009, Kim, Park and Niu, 2017). Relatively few
2972 studies have examined the effects of microbreaks on employee well-being and productivity,
2973 and findings are inconsistent (Kim, Park and Niu, 2017). For example, employees who
2974 engaged in microbreaks were found to experience reduced fatigue and increased vitality
2975 throughout the workday (Zacher, Brailsford and Parker, 2014), and taking short, self-initiated
2976 breaks in the afternoon was associated with increased work engagement (Kühnel et al.,
2977 2017). Movement based microbreaks were also associated with positive effects on
2978 employee mental health (Mainsbridge et al., 2020). On the other hand, Fritz, Lam and
2979 Spreitzer (2011) found a link between higher vitality and breaks involving work-related
2980 activities, but non-work-related microbreaks were linked to greater fatigue and lower vitality.
2981 Furthermore, the effect of microbreaks may be moderated by the type of activity they
2982 involve; relaxation activities (e.g. napping, daydreaming), socialisation activities (e.g.

2983 chatting, texting) and consumption of caffeinated beverages were found to reduce end-of-
2984 workday negative affect, but negative affect was aggravated by cognitive activities (e.g.
2985 reading) and the consumption of non-caffeinated beverages or snacks (Kim, Park and Niu,
2986 2017).

2987 As discussed in the previous chapter, research has indicated that the presence of
2988 companion animals in the workplace can be beneficial for employee well-being (e.g. Wells
2989 and Perrine, 2001, Barker et al., 2012, Hall et al., 2017). A potential explanation for these
2990 findings is that companion animals provide a distraction, diverting focus away from negative
2991 emotional states (Beetz, 2017). As breaks are often taken in response to fatigue and the
2992 need to recover (Jett and George, 2003), this may suggest that HAI during microbreaks
2993 might facilitate recovery. The research presented in the previous chapter investigated the
2994 effects of watching fishes during the working day. Although no evidence was found to
2995 support the hypothesis that watching fishes would lead to greater relaxation than resting
2996 quietly, there was qualitative evidence to suggest that of the three conditions (watching live
2997 fishes, watching fish videos, resting quietly) watching live fishes was perceived as most
2998 engaging. This corresponds with previous research which has indicated that live fishes are
2999 effective at capturing and holding human attention (Windhager et al., 2011, Cracknell et al.,
3000 2016). Furthermore, rather than being taken in response to the need for recovery, the
3001 'breaks' taken in this research were prescheduled, and participants were explicitly directed to
3002 watch the fishes (live or on video) or rest quietly. This is unlikely to reflect how employees
3003 would naturally engage with ornamental fishes in their workplace. More precisely, if
3004 ornamental fishes are able to capture and hold human attention it is possible that aquaria in
3005 the workplace would spontaneously capture employee attention and momentarily divert their
3006 focus away from work, providing a brief opportunity for recovery. In other words, ornamental
3007 fishes may promote engagement in microbreaks.

3008 To our knowledge, no research has examined the effects of HAI – and specifically viewing
3009 ornamental fishes – during microbreaks. However, research regarding 'green' microbreaks

3010 supports the premise that watching fishes during microbreaks may be beneficial for
3011 employees. Lee et al. (2015) found that university students who viewed a computer
3012 simulation of a green roof for 40 seconds demonstrated significantly greater improvements
3013 on a task of sustained attention than those who viewed a simulation of a concrete roof. Lee
3014 et al. (2018) further investigated the effect of green microbreaks by developing and testing a
3015 work recovery model based on Attention Restoration Theory (ART; Kaplan, 1995). ART
3016 proposes that exposure to nature helps to replenish depleted cognitive resources through
3017 four components; *fascination*, the effortless capture of attention, *being away*, the sense of
3018 escaping thoughts that demand attention, *extent*, the feeling of being immersed within the
3019 environment, and *compatibility*, the match between an individual's purpose and their
3020 environment (Kaplan, 1995, Kaplan and Berman, 2010). Lee et al. (2018) found that views of
3021 a green roof were perceived as more coherent (a component of extent) than views of a
3022 concrete roof. This led to lower energy expenditure on tasks completed after a 90-second
3023 viewing, with consequent reductions in tension and improvements in performance (Lee et al.,
3024 2018). As fish tanks are considered a form of indoor nature (Largo-Wight et al., 2011),
3025 viewing ornamental fishes during microbreaks may have similar effects.

3026 When considering the introduction of live animals to the workplace (or any environment) it is
3027 important to consider potential risks. With regards to "pet friendly" workplaces for example,
3028 harm could occur to employees or clients *via* allergies, aggression, accidental injury or
3029 through the transmission of zoonotic diseases, yet policies regarding these initiatives are
3030 often unmoderated or unclear (Norling and Keeling, 2010, Foreman et al., 2017, Hall et al.,
3031 2017). There are also risks to animal welfare, as companion animals may become stressed
3032 in a working environment and must be given opportunity for exercise and other species-
3033 typical behaviours (Foreman et al., 2017). Furthermore, the presence of companion animals
3034 may influence perceptions of a workplace; occupants are anticipated to be friendlier and the
3035 atmosphere more welcoming when cats and dogs are present (Wells and Perrine, 2001b,
3036 Perrine and Wells, 2006), but the presence of these animals may also be considered

3037 unprofessional, unsanitary or detrimental to productivity (Wells and Perrine, 2001a, Perrine
3038 and Wells, 2006, Barker et al., 2012).

3039 The risks associated with aquaria are much smaller. Bacterial infection can occur through
3040 contact with fishes or fish tank water, but this is rare and the risk can be effectively
3041 minimised by wearing gloves and practising good hygiene while completing water changes
3042 (Brodie, Biley and Shewring, 2002); it is also only a concern for individuals actively involved
3043 in fish care activities. There is potential for accidental injury to occur if the tank were to leak
3044 (e.g. slipping on water, cuts from broken glass), but positioning the tank in a quiet area
3045 where it is unlikely to be damaged, and promptly cleaning up spills reduces these risks.
3046 While a risk to the welfare of the fishes remains, this can be minimised by ensuring that the
3047 individual(s) responsible for the fishes has sufficient knowledge regarding their care.

3048 The aim of the current study was to provide an insight into the experiences of employees
3049 regarding the installation of aquaria within the workplace. The purpose of this was twofold.
3050 Firstly, to understand whether ornamental fishes have the potential to facilitate recovery from
3051 work *via* microbreaks, it was important to understand how (if at all) employees naturally
3052 interact with fishes in their workplace. Secondly, given the potential risks associated with the
3053 presence of live animals in the workplace, it was important to understand practicalities
3054 surrounding the presence of fish aquaria in the workplace, including any barriers and
3055 facilitators experienced by employees throughout the study. A qualitative study was
3056 conducted to achieve these aims.

3057 **4.3 Methods**

3058 **4.3.1 Participants**

3059 Office-based workplaces in the West of Scotland that did not have a fish tank were recruited
3060 *via* contacts within the university (N = 2) or by direct approach from the researcher (N = 1).
3061 In each workplace, appropriate gatekeeper approvals were obtained before the study
3062 commenced. Participants were employees ($n = 13$) from the three participating workplaces
3063 (21-54 years, M age = 36.69 years, $SD = 11.59$, $n = 7$ female, $n = 6$ male). All employees

3064 from each workplace were eligible to participate, provided they were at least 18 years of age
3065 and their desk was based within the office housing the fish tank. Recruitment was supported
3066 by a key contact within each workplace, who circulated participant information sheets to
3067 eligible employees; interested employees could then contact the researcher for further
3068 information if required. Each key contact also helped to organise suitable times for focus
3069 groups and/or interviews.

3070 **4.3.2 Design and procedure**

3071 This research was approved by the School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee at
3072 the University of the West of Scotland (Ref: 8301, Appendix F), and the Mars Research
3073 Review Board. After obtaining appropriate gatekeeper approvals, the researcher installed an
3074 aquarium within each workplace. This tank was left unstocked for a minimum of two weeks
3075 to allow the biological filter to mature, after which the fishes were added. Qualitative data
3076 were then collected regarding employees' experiences of the fish tank. Data were collected
3077 in one workplace prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (December 2019), with the fishes added
3078 to the tank approximately two months before data collection. A tank was installed in the
3079 second workplace prior to the first nationwide lockdown but no fishes were added until
3080 restrictions were lifted; data collection again took place around two months following addition
3081 of the fishes (November 2020). In the final workplace, lockdown returned shortly following
3082 the addition of the fishes to the tank, and so most employees switched to remote working or
3083 were furloughed. An employee who was required onsite completed all fish care activities
3084 during this time, and data collection was conducted around two months after the remaining
3085 employees returned to the office (July 2021). Most employees within the two workplaces that
3086 participated during the pandemic continued to work from home on a part time-basis, so were
3087 asked to only participate if they were onsite at least one day per week.

3088 Data were collected *via* semi-structured focus groups and individual interviews, based on the
3089 preferences and availability of participants. One focus group was conducted face-to-face; it
3090 contained three participants and lasted around 23 minutes. All remaining data were collected

3091 remotely *via* video conferencing; this included one focus group ($n = 4$, approximately 21
3092 minutes) and six individual interviews (approximately 7-11 minutes). Where data collection
3093 was conducted face-to-face, participants provided written informed consent and completed a
3094 short demographic questionnaire (age, gender identity, and companion animal guardianship
3095 history) immediately before the focus group. Where data were collected remotely, the
3096 consent form and demographic questionnaire were sent to participants *via* email and
3097 returned to the researcher at some point prior to data collection; consent was reassessed
3098 verbally at the start of the focus group or interview. With the permission of participants, all
3099 data were audio recorded using a Sony ICD-PX470 digital dictation machine, and
3100 transcribed verbatim for analysis.

3101 **4.3.3 Animal welfare**

3102 The aquaria followed the same standard set-up as described in Chapter 3, Section 3.3.3.1.
3103 In each workplace, a suitable location for the aquarium was agreed between the researcher
3104 and a key contact, such that its placement would not pose a hazard to humans or affect fish
3105 welfare. Set-up and stocking procedures followed those described in Chapter 3, Section
3106 3.3.5, and water parameters at time of stocking were all within safe limits (temperature =
3107 25.6-26.8 °C; GH = 30-60 mg/L; KH = 40 mg/L; pH = 6.5-7.0; NO₂ = 0 mg/L; NO₃ = 0 mg/L;
3108 NH₃/NH₄ = 0 mg/L). A key contact within each workplace was asked to check the fish
3109 regularly for signs of illness or distress, and alert the researcher promptly of any issues. The
3110 researcher conducted tank maintenance on a weekly basis; where this was not possible due
3111 to restrictions associated with the COVID-19 pandemic, maintenance was conducted by an
3112 employee who followed instructions provided by the researcher.

3113 Each tank was stocked with the same species and number of fishes as in the previous
3114 chapter: six zebrafish, six variatus platies and five cory catfish. Due to occasional fish
3115 mortality, however, in practice the tanks contained 4-6 zebrafish, 3-6 variatus platies and five
3116 cory catfish. The cause of mortality could not be determined in most cases as no water
3117 quality issues or signs of illness were detected; in one case mortality was attributed to a

3118 spike in ammonia levels shortly after adding the fishes, and was remedied through additional
3119 water changes to improve water quality and prevent further mortalities.

3120 After completion of the study, each workplace was permitted to keep the aquarium and
3121 ownership was transferred to a named individual at that site; all necessary equipment and at
3122 least one month's supply of consumables were provided. A follow-up visit to check the
3123 welfare of the fishes was conducted after 3-6 months; in one workplace this follow-up was
3124 delayed due to nationwide lockdowns and restrictions associated with the COVID-19
3125 pandemic. Follow-up within the remaining two workplaces was conducted within the planned
3126 3-6 months.

3127 **4.3.4 Materials**

3128 Semi-structured interview and focus group schedules were used (see Appendix G).
3129 Questions focused on participants' experiences regarding the presence of the fish tank in
3130 their office, including their initial thoughts upon learning that an aquarium was going to be
3131 installed in their workplace, any benefits, or downsides they had experienced during the
3132 study period, and how (if at all) they engaged with the fishes. Participants were also asked
3133 their opinions on the presence of other animals in the workplace (e.g. "pet friendly" schemes)
3134 and the use of virtual alternatives (e.g. fish videos). At the end of the focus group/interview
3135 participants were given the opportunity to raise any additional points not otherwise
3136 discussed. A short questionnaire was used to obtain demographic information, including
3137 companion animal guardianship status and whether participants had ever kept fishes.

3138 **4.3.5 Data analysis**

3139 Data were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2019, Braun
3140 et al., 2019), following the same procedure as outlined in Chapter 3, Section 3.3.6.3.

3141 **4.4 Results and Discussion**

3142 Three themes were developed from the qualitative data. *Fishes may enhance rest breaks*
3143 explores the ways in which participants engaged with the fishes in their workplace, and how

3144 this related to their well-being, *The importance of live fishes* focuses on the idea that
3145 engagement with live animals was a key aspect of the benefits participants associated with
3146 the presence of a fish tank in their office, and *Who will look after the fishes?* relates to
3147 concerns regarding fish welfare and maintenance of the aquarium.

3148 **4.4.1 Fishes may enhance rest breaks**

3149 Fishes are often associated with relaxation and stress relief, and several participants did
3150 mention that the fish tank was a calming feature within the office environment. However, only
3151 one participant reported actively choosing to watch the fishes in response to a stressor,
3152 "...it's just nice to have them in the office to, you know when you're a bit stressed to look at
3153 them, when you have a shitty phone call with somebody and you just want to, you just go
3154 and stare at the fish for a bit..." (Participant 8, Workplace B, Interview). Others tended to
3155 engage with the fishes in a more spontaneous manner, either when passing by the tank as
3156 part of existing work routines, "...it's usually quite a good opportunity to stop and have a look
3157 at the fish while you're heading toward the chocolate store..." (Participant 6, Workplace B,
3158 Interview), or when glancing up from their desk while working, "...if you're kind of looking
3159 about the room and you see the fish it kind of takes your eye for a minute or two, you can
3160 just watch and I would say it's been a really positive thing, it brightens up your mood..."
3161 (Participant 13, Workplace C, Interview). This finding suggests that many participants did
3162 engage with the fishes during microbreaks, albeit usually in combination with other common
3163 microbreak activities such as daydreaming, snacking or making hot beverages. Furthermore,
3164 there was evidence that participants found this engagement beneficial; briefly observing the
3165 fishes was seen as a "nice distraction every now and then" (Participant 4, Workplace B,
3166 Interview) which took participants' minds off their work and provided a moment of respite.
3167 This is consistent with the theory that engagement with companion animals can promote
3168 human well-being by diverting attention away from negative states (Beetz, 2017), and
3169 research which found that undertaking relaxation activities during microbreaks led to positive
3170 effects on employee well-being (Kim, Park and Niu, 2017).

3171 However, this experience was not reflective of all participants. Some had very little or no
3172 engagement with the fishes during the study, and did not associate the presence of the tank
3173 with any positive effects. The size and position of the tanks may be relevant here,
3174 particularly as some participants reported being unable to directly observe the fishes from
3175 their desk. For example one participant stated, "...you kind of have to look to see them [the
3176 fishes], they kind of camouflage in as well, I think if it was, yeah brighter and colourful and
3177 just bigger for an office in general, I think it would make a bit of a difference..." (Participant
3178 11, Workplace C, Focus Group). In the context of ART, this could be interpreted as the
3179 aquarium lacking extent, or the feeling of being immersed within the environment (Kaplan
3180 and Berman, 2010). Previous research has shown that window views higher in coherence, a
3181 component of extent, promoted greater recovery from work during microbreaks (Lee et al.,
3182 2018). The small home aquaria used in the current study may therefore, have lacked the
3183 extent needed to impact employee well-being.

3184 Aside from directly engaging with the fishes during microbreaks, several participants noted
3185 that the fishes provided a topic of conversation. For example, participants stated "...we're all
3186 sitting there working away quietly in the office and you glance over at the fish tank and then
3187 you start a conversation about the fish..." (Participant 7, Workplace B, Interview), and
3188 "...we've all stood out there and shot the breeze over the fish for ten minutes or so..."
3189 (Participant 1, Workplace A, Focus Group). Social activities are included under the umbrella
3190 of microbreak activities, and have been associated with benefits, such as reduced fatigue
3191 and lower end-of-day negative affect (Kim, Park and Niu, 2017, Bellini, Hartig and Bonaiuto,
3192 2019). Previous research has also highlighted the ability of companion animals to act as
3193 social catalysts, encouraging interaction between humans (McNicholas and Collis, 2000,
3194 Wells, 2004, Beetz and Bales, 2016), an effect which was documented in previous
3195 qualitative research conducted with ornamental fish guardians (Langfield and James, 2009).
3196 This suggests that fishes in the workplace may indirectly promote employee well-being by
3197 promoting conversation between colleagues. While this could be interpreted as the fishes

3198 being a cause of distraction, several participants indicated that other companion animals
3199 such as dogs had much greater potential for causing disruption. For example, "...I think if
3200 you bring a dog in there'd be a wee bit more disruption than fish..." (Participant 13,
3201 Workplace C, Interview) and "...the only thing about the dogs in the office is sometimes it
3202 can be quite disruptive..." (Participant 6, Workplace B, Interview).

3203 **4.4.2 The importance of live fishes**

3204 Several participants mentioned that one feature of the aquarium that they particularly
3205 appreciated was the 'aliveness' of the fishes. This fostered a sense of responsibility and
3206 allowed participants to develop an emotional connection to the animals, "...I think part of why
3207 it's nice to have them is that they are alive, there is a bit of responsibility, and yeah, you
3208 know there is something to lose there ..." (Participant 8, Workplace B, Interview). Despite
3209 most participants playing no active role in taking care of the fishes, several expressed
3210 concern about their welfare, and sadness in relation to occasional fish mortality, "...the main
3211 downside was the two fish that died and that was a bit of a worry..." (Participant 2,
3212 Workplace A, Focus Group) and "...when some of them died it was a bit sad and we were all
3213 trying to figure out what was wrong with them..." (Participant 5, Workplace B, Interview).
3214 Emotional attachment towards the fishes was also evident in participants expressing feelings
3215 of ownership towards them, for example "...they're our fish..." (Participant 1, Workplace A,
3216 Focus Group) and "...there's more of a connection with it being yours..." (Participant 7,
3217 Workplace B, Interview). This emotional connection appeared to be particularly strong
3218 among employees from one workplace, who reported naming the fishes and considering
3219 them "...a nice addition to the team..." (Participant 5, Workplace B, Interview); these feelings
3220 are demonstrated in the following statement "...I think we'd all be really gutted if we had to
3221 give up our fish now that we've named them..." (Participant 8, Workplace B, Interview).
3222 Conversely, it was evident that some participants felt indifference towards the fishes, for
3223 example "...it wouldn't bother me if they [the fishes] we're still there, it wouldn't bother me if
3224 they weren't..." (Participant 10, Workplace C, Focus Group) and "...I'm not emotionally

3225 attached to the fish to be honest...” (Participant 3, Workplace A, Focus Group). A comment
3226 from one participant suggested that this may be due to difficulty in distinguishing the fishes
3227 as individuals, which had made it difficult to give them names and understand their individual
3228 characters, “...I think there’s too many to name and I don’t know how we would tell the
3229 difference...” (Participant 2, Workplace A, Focus Group). The role of attachment in human-
3230 animal relationships has been the subject of much research, and there is evidence that
3231 these bonds may constitute attachment bonds as defined by Bowlby’s (1969, 1973, 1980)
3232 attachment theory (e.g. Prato-Previde et al., 2003, Kurdek, 2008, Palmer and Custance,
3233 2008). However, the role of attachment in human-fish relationships has not been subject to
3234 investigation. While qualitative data has suggested that ornamental fish guardians can feel
3235 an emotional connection to their fishes (Langfield and James, 2009), true attachment bonds
3236 are reciprocal relationships, and there is no evidence that fishes display behaviours
3237 indicative of attachment to their guardians, such as proximity seeking or separation distress.
3238 Furthermore, physical touch has been identified as an important component of attachment
3239 bonding which is lacking in the human-fish relationship dynamic (Beetz, Uvnas-Moberg, et
3240 al., 2012). Therefore, it is unclear whether experiencing an emotional connection towards the
3241 fishes might influence the effects of ornamental fishes in the workplace on employee well-
3242 being.

3243 Several participants expressed appreciation of the aquarium at a more aesthetic level, as the
3244 tank brightened up their otherwise bland office space “...it’s a nice fish tank and it looks good
3245 and it’s improved the décor...” (Participant 1, Workplace A, Focus Group) and “...I think it
3246 added colour, some colour to the office because the [department name] is quite dull...”
3247 (Participant 9, Workplace C, Focus Group). This corresponds with previous research which
3248 identified that some home aquarium owners see their fishes as ‘room decoration’ (Kidd and
3249 Kidd, 1999), and with research that considered aquaria ‘interior amenities’ alongside
3250 features such as art or plants (Lin et al., 2013). Given the potential risks associated with the
3251 presence of live animals in the workplace – particularly with regards to concerns around

3252 animal welfare – if ornamental fishes are viewed only as ‘ornaments’, there is a clear
3253 argument in favour of using non-live alternatives that provide a similar visual aesthetic to the
3254 aquarium. When considering the use of fish videos as an alternative, however, there was a
3255 general feeling that this would be less effective than a live fish aquarium. One reason was
3256 due to the lack of an emotional connection to the fishes, “...if you’re just watching a video
3257 you can just switch it off and forget about them...” (Participant 2, Workplace A, Focus
3258 Group), but even those who appreciated the aquarium at a primarily aesthetic level indicated
3259 preference for the live fishes. Although a fish video may be similar visually, the live fishes
3260 were argued to provide a greater level of interest and novelty, “...I think a consistent video of
3261 fish or nature or so on could be boring after about a week...” (Participant 4, Workplace B,
3262 Interview). Several participants also commented that an advantage of the live aquarium was
3263 that it gave them a break from looking at screens, and that using fish videos as an
3264 alternative would nullify this benefit. Qualitative data from the previous chapter indicated
3265 similar findings; live fishes were perceived to be more engaging than fish videos, and a
3266 perceived benefit of the aquarium was that it provided a break from computer screens. Thus,
3267 it appears that the presence of live fishes is an important aspect of fishes in the workplace,
3268 whether employees develop an emotional connection with the fishes or appreciate the
3269 aquarium at a purely aesthetic level.

3270 **4.4.3 Who will look after the fishes?**

3271 Across all three workplaces, the main concern regarding the presence of an aquarium
3272 related to who would maintain the fish tank and be responsible for the fishes. That the
3273 researcher assumed this responsibility throughout the study was a clear benefit for some
3274 participants, “...it’s not been a negative so far because you’ve been coming in [to look after
3275 the fishes]...” (Participant 1, Workplace A, Focus Group). Looking towards to the end of the
3276 study when each workplace would have the option of keeping the fish tank, a small number
3277 of participants expressed that they wanted no involvement in the care of the fishes, either
3278 due to disinterest or lack of time, “...I don’t think I could be responsible for the fish, no, I

3279 would forget they were there to be honest...” (Participant 12, Workplace C, Focus Group)
3280 and “...when we’re like rushed off our feet my worry is that you would forget to feed them...”
3281 (Participant 9, Workplace C, Focus Group). Many participants, however, indicated that they
3282 would be happy to help out with maintaining the tank provided they were given instructions
3283 on how to do so, “...if someone could show me what to do etc., I wouldn’t mind [cleaning the
3284 tank] to be honest...” (Participant 13, Workplace C, Interview).

3285 Fishkeeping experience within the office was a facilitator, for instance one participant stated
3286 “...I would have been concerned if none of us had experience of fish, you know then I would
3287 have been concerned, but I knew that [colleague] had kept fish and [colleague’s relative] still
3288 keeps fish, so I was quite relaxed that if there was anything that needed attending to and you
3289 weren’t available then I was sure we could work it out ourselves...” (Participant 7, Workplace
3290 B, Interview). Similarly, employees from one workplace had considered getting a fish tank for
3291 some time and appreciated the provision of equipment and advice. However, ongoing
3292 support was seen as unnecessary, “...I think if you were rolling it out and providing the
3293 companies with everything they needed, yeah, I think that would probably be a hit, I wouldn’t
3294 necessarily think you would need to take on the care of them...” (Participant 2, Workplace A,
3295 Focus Group). Previous research used such an approach in a home setting; adolescents
3296 with diabetes who participated in a behavioural intervention to improve medication
3297 adherence were given fishkeeping equipment, a voucher to purchase a *Betta splendens* fish,
3298 and instructions on how to set up and maintain the tank (Maranda et al., 2015). Fish welfare
3299 was not assessed, but the authors reported that the fishes of two of the 16 participants were
3300 replaced due to mortality. Before adopting such strategies, it would be prudent to assess
3301 how well they are implemented in various settings (including the workplace), particularly in
3302 relation to issues surrounding the welfare of the fishes.

3303 A small number of participants reported actively taking the opportunity to research and learn
3304 about fishes and fishkeeping during the study. One of these participants noted that they had
3305 previously underestimated the level of care fishes needed, stating “...there’s a bigger

3306 learning curve with fish than I expected...” (Participant 8, Workplace B, Interview). This
3307 experience merits consideration, as to avoid threats to fish welfare it is important that new
3308 fish guardians fully comprehend the responsibilities associated with fishkeeping before they
3309 install an aquarium, whether that be in the workplace or elsewhere. Therefore, based on the
3310 workplaces involved in this research, many (but not all) employees would willingly engage in
3311 the care of fishes in the workplace. However, it is likely that some of these employees lack
3312 the fishkeeping experience needed to ensure good fish welfare. In such situations, expert
3313 advice should be sought to facilitate the successful introduction of fishes to the workplace
3314 and ensure a high level of welfare for the fishes.

3315 **4.5 General discussion**

3316 The purpose of this study was to develop an insight into employee experiences regarding
3317 the installation of aquaria in the workplace. Specifically, this research aimed to understand
3318 how (if at all) employees engage with fishes at work, and any barriers and facilitators to
3319 keeping aquaria within working environments. This builds on the research presented in
3320 Chapter 3, which examined the effects of watching ornamental fishes during the working
3321 day.

3322 The first key finding from this study was that some employees did engage with the fishes
3323 during microbreaks, and this was perceived to have a positive, if somewhat transient, effect
3324 on their well-being. However, while previous research has indicated that fishes may be
3325 effective at capturing and holding human attention (e.g. Windhager et al., 2011, Cracknell et
3326 al., 2016), there was little evidence that the presence of fishes in the workplace prompted
3327 engagement in microbreaks. Instead, participants tended to engage with the fishes in
3328 addition to existing microbreak activities, some of which (e.g. socialising, daydreaming) have
3329 been associated with positive effects (e.g. Kim, Park and Niu, 2017, Bellini, Hartig and
3330 Bonaiuto, 2019). In Chapter 3 there was no evidence that watching an aquarium during the
3331 working day led to short-term improvements in psychological, physiological, or cognitive
3332 outcomes that were greater than those achieved through resting quietly. Further research is

3333 needed to determine whether engagement with fishes during microbreaks leads to benefits
3334 beyond those achieved *via* existing microbreak activities.

3335 The second key finding was that for most participants, the presence of live fishes was an
3336 important aspect of the 'intervention'. Some had developed an emotional connection towards
3337 the fishes that would not exist with non-live alternatives. Most studies examining the health
3338 and well-being effects of engagement with ornamental fishes have focused on visual
3339 exposure (e.g. DeSchraver and Riddick, 1990, Wells, 2005, Sanchez et al., 2015, Cracknell
3340 et al., 2016) but this finding is indicative of an alternative mechanism that centres around
3341 being a fish caregiver. To my knowledge, no research has examined the effects of engaging
3342 in fishkeeping activities on human well-being, however, one study identified a trend towards
3343 greater relaxation among older adults who were given goldfish to care for in their homes,
3344 *versus* those who received visits from the researchers or had no intervention (Riddick,
3345 1985). As participants in the current study were not actively involved in fishkeeping activities
3346 (except where COVID-19 restrictions prevented the researcher from accessing the
3347 workplaces), giving employees the responsibility to undertake fish care activities (e.g.
3348 feeding, water changes) may have increased engagement with the fishes, potentially leading
3349 to a greater effects than visual exposure alone. Furthermore, previous qualitative research
3350 has suggested that ornamental fish guardians can develop attachments to their fishes
3351 (Langfield and James, 2009), and so identifying the specific nature of these attachments
3352 may provide insight into whether ornamental fishes promote human well-being *via*
3353 mechanisms other than visual exposure. Other participants appreciated the aquarium at an
3354 aesthetic level, but felt that the live fishes provided more novelty than would non-live
3355 alternatives. It is important to identify how long this novelty effect persists as this may have
3356 implications for the longevity of the 'intervention'.

3357 The final point raised in this study related to who would maintain the aquarium, with opinions
3358 being very individualised. Some employees were happy to be involved but others were not,
3359 and lack of expertise was a clear barrier to the presence of aquaria in the workplace. As

3360 there are animal welfare implications associated with the presence of live animals in
3361 workplaces, any organisations planning to install an aquarium should have plans in place to
3362 ensure the tank is maintained in all eventualities. Although not part of the study itself, the
3363 follow-up visit to check on the welfare of fishes after the study was complete found no issues
3364 with regards to the welfare of the fishes in two of the workplaces. However, in one workplace
3365 it became apparent that employees had been unable to access their office during the
3366 nationwide lockdown which ultimately resulted in fish mortality. While this occurred as a
3367 direct result of the COVID-19 pandemic, thought should be given to how fish welfare will be
3368 ensured if access to the building is restricted for any reason. Consideration should also be
3369 given to factors such as employee turnover and sickness; the typical lifespan of a zebrafish,
3370 for example, is around 3.5 years (Gerhard et al., 2002) and so strategies must be in place to
3371 ensure the welfare of the fishes should the employee(s) responsible for them leave their
3372 position during this time.

3373 **4.5.1 Strengths and limitations**

3374 The major strength of this study was that it was the first to collect in-depth data regarding the
3375 experiences of employees in relation to fishes in the workplace. Qualitative data is
3376 necessary for the refinement of theory (Kazdin, 2017), and so the findings presented here
3377 can be used to refine theories regarding human-fish engagement both within the workplace
3378 and more generally. Furthermore, the research was conducted in a real-world setting which
3379 increases the ecological validity of the findings. Previous studies which have identified
3380 positive effects of engagement with fishes have been conducted in laboratories or under
3381 laboratory conditions (e.g. Wells, 2005, Butteldmann and Römpke, 2014, Sanchez et al.,
3382 2015, Cracknell et al., 2016), but these findings may not reflect what would be observed in a
3383 real-life setting. For example, one paper regarding the effects of indoor plants in the
3384 workplace found positive effects on performance among students in a laboratory setting, but
3385 was unable to replicate these findings in field studies (Thatcher et al., 2020).

3386 However, there are also limitations to the current research. Primarily these related to the
3387 overlap between the data collection period and the COVID-19 pandemic. Due to the nature
3388 of the research, it was essential that employees had access to the workplace both to allow
3389 them to experience engagement with the fishes, and to ensure fish welfare. However, as the
3390 workplaces were office-based and most jobs could be conducted remotely, repeated
3391 lockdowns and work from home restrictions created delays and placed limitations on the
3392 workplaces that were able to participate. As a result only three workplaces took part, and the
3393 final sample size was small. Thus findings are unlikely to be generalisable. Furthermore,
3394 many participants from the two workplaces that participated after the initial lockdown
3395 continued to work from home on a regular basis. This limited their engagement with the
3396 fishes, and so greater depth in the data may have been achieved if participants had the
3397 opportunity to spend more time around the fishes.

3398 **4.5.2 Conclusions**

3399 The research presented here indicates that some employees engaged with fishes during
3400 microbreaks, and perceived these interactions to have a positive influence on their well-
3401 being. When combined with the findings presented in the previous chapter, however, there is
3402 reason to doubt whether the benefits of engaging with fishes are any greater than those
3403 which would be achieved *via* existing microbreak activities; this requires further research.
3404 There was also evidence that the presence of live fishes is important to employees, which is
3405 consistent with findings from the previous chapter. However, the greatest source of concern
3406 related to who would look after the fishes. When combined with the potential issues around
3407 animal welfare, the findings presented here and in the previous chapter do not provide
3408 sufficient evidence to support the use of live fish aquaria as an intervention to promote
3409 employee well-being. Should an organisation wish to install aquaria within the working
3410 environment it is imperative that animal welfare is given full consideration, and contingency
3411 plans are put in place to ensure that fish welfare is maintained in all circumstances, such as
3412 employee turnover or sickness.

3413 **Chapter 5.**
3414 **Companion animal type and level of engagement**
3415 **matter: A mixed-methods study examining links**
3416 **between companion animal guardianship, loneliness**
3417 **and well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic**
3418

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3422 guardianship, loneliness and well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Animals*. Vol.11 (8),
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3424 **5.1 Abstract**

3425 To reduce the spread of COVID-19, countries worldwide placed limitations on social
3426 interaction, which is anticipated to have severe psychological consequences. Although
3427 findings are inconsistent, prior research has suggested that companion animals may
3428 positively influence human well-being and reduce loneliness. In the context of COVID-19,
3429 this has important implications, as companion animal guardians may be less negatively
3430 affected by the pandemic. The primary aim of this research was to investigate the influence
3431 of companion animals on mental well-being and loneliness during the pandemic, with
3432 specific interest in the role of ornamental fishes. A mixed-methods study was conducted,
3433 using an international sample. Quantitative data were collected *via* an online survey ($n =$
3434 1199) and analysed using robust hierarchical multiple regression analyses; the influence of
3435 level of engagement with companion animals was examined for dogs, cats and ornamental
3436 fishes. There was no evidence that companion animal guardianship was associated with
3437 loneliness and mental well-being during the pandemic but spending more time engaging
3438 physically or socially with dogs (and to a lesser extent cats) was generally associated with
3439 poorer outcomes. Qualitative data were collected through open-ended survey responses (n
3440 = 757) and semi-structured interviews ($n = 25$) and analysed using reflexive thematic
3441 analysis. Two themes were developed – one related to companion animals as providers of
3442 social and emotional support, and the other to companion animals as providers of purpose
3443 and perspective. Concerns regarding the impact of the pandemic on animal welfare were
3444 also identified. Compared to other animal types, more participants expressed indifference
3445 regarding the impact of their fishes on their well-being during the pandemic, possibly
3446 because fishes cannot provide comfort *via* physical touch. The findings of this study reflect
3447 the wider field of human–animal interaction; although qualitative data suggest guardians
3448 believe their companion animals are a positive influence in their lives, there is little
3449 convincing quantitative data to support these beliefs. This highlights the need to refine
3450 theories regarding which aspects of companion animal guardianship may influence human
3451 well-being; the findings from this research may be useful in the refinement of such theories.

3452 **5.2 Introduction**

3453 On 11 March 2020, the World Health Organisation (WHO) declared the COVID-19 outbreak
3454 to be a pandemic. The impact of this pandemic is catastrophic; at the time of writing, over
3455 187 million cases and 4 million deaths have been recorded globally (World Health
3456 Organization, 2021). To inhibit the spread of the virus, countries worldwide adopted
3457 strategies to limit physical contact between individuals from different households; this
3458 included nationwide lockdowns, travel restrictions and social distancing (ACAPS, 2020).

3459 The psychological consequences of the pandemic are potentially severe (Holmes et al.,
3460 2020). It is well established that social isolation and loneliness are detrimental to physical
3461 and mental health, with a risk of premature mortality comparable to that of factors such as
3462 obesity or substance abuse (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015, Leigh-Hunt et al., 2017). Worries
3463 related to the pandemic are also a cause of psychological distress. For example, one study
3464 conducted during the first six weeks of lockdown in the United Kingdom (UK) identified two
3465 aspects of anxiety associated with COVID-19 – disease anxiety related to catching or
3466 transmitting the virus, and consequence anxiety related to the longer-term impacts of the
3467 pandemic, such as in relation to the economic cost (McElroy et al., 2020). Numerous studies
3468 from various countries have already reported psychological issues associated with the early
3469 stages of the pandemic (Best et al., 2020, Huang and Zhao, 2020, Rodríguez-Rey, Garrido-
3470 Hernansaiz and Collado, 2020, Shevlin et al., 2020).

3471 Companion animals are widely believed to promote positive well-being. For instance,
3472 companionship and emotional support were among the most common reasons given for
3473 keeping companion animals among a sample of dog and cat guardians (Staats, Wallace and
3474 Anderson, 2008), while qualitative findings have indicated that companion animals are
3475 considered important sources of mental health support (Knight and Edwards, 2008, Wells,
3476 2009b, Brooks et al., 2018, 2019). On the other hand, several cross-sectional studies have
3477 found no association, or a negative association, between companion animal guardianship
3478 and mental or physical health (Parslow et al., 2005, Koivusilta and Ojanlatva, 2006,

3479 Müllersdorf et al., 2010, Rijken and van Beek, 2011, Torske et al., 2017, Ding et al., 2018).
3480 There is also no convincing evidence that companion animals directly influence loneliness
3481 (Gilbey and Tani, 2015), although an indirect effect may occur *via* social facilitation (Wood et
3482 al., 2015, Gilbey and Tani, 2020). Furthermore, human–animal interaction (HAI) research
3483 frequently suffers from methodological issues, such as inadequate sample sizes, high levels
3484 of heterogeneity, and a lack of blinding (Kazdin, 2017, Serpell et al., 2017, Friedmann and
3485 Gee, 2019, Rodriguez, Herzog and Gee, 2021), plus participants are likely to have positive
3486 attitudes towards companion animals, and so findings may not be generalisable (Friedmann
3487 and Gee, 2019). Thus, the influence of companion animals on loneliness and mental well-
3488 being remains unclear, but if an effect exists, this may have important implications regarding
3489 the psychological impact of the COVID-19 pandemic; companion animal guardians may be
3490 less negatively affected in comparison to non-guardians.

3491 However, companion animals may also have detrimentally impacted well-being during the
3492 pandemic. Previous research has highlighted negative aspects of keeping companion
3493 animals, such as the financial cost and the burden associated with their care (Brooks et al.,
3494 2018). It is possible that these negative aspects were amplified during the pandemic, for in-
3495 stance if restrictions on movement or loss of income impacted the ability of guardians to care
3496 for their companion animals. There is also evidence that some guardians are concerned
3497 about the potential of companion animals to transmit or contract the SARS-CoV-2 virus
3498 (Parry, 2020). Therefore, the primary aim of this research was to investigate the relationship
3499 between companion animal guardianship, and mental well-being and loneliness during the
3500 COVID-19 pandemic; at conception of this study, no published research on this topic was
3501 identified.

3502 A secondary aim of this research relates to a broader question in the field of HAI; how any
3503 effects associated with companion animal guardianship are influenced by the type of
3504 companion animal. Much research has focused on animals that interact with humans in a
3505 physical or social manner, namely dogs, cats and horses. Comparatively few studies have

3506 examined the impact of other animal types, such as ornamental fishes (Clements et al.,
3507 2019). Fishes represent a significant proportion of companion animals, for example they are
3508 the third most popular companion animal in the UK and are by far the most numerous, as
3509 one home aquarium may contain many fishes (www.pfma.org.uk). Only one study to date
3510 has examined the impact of fish guardianship on loneliness, and no effect was observed
3511 (Riddick, 1985). However, qualitative evidence has demonstrated that some fish guardians
3512 believe their fishes provide companionship, along with other psychological benefits such as
3513 relaxation (Langfield and James, 2009). Fishes have also been associated with positive
3514 outcomes such as reduced agitation, increased food intake and improved body mass among
3515 people with dementia (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014),
3516 reduced anxiety among students preparing for an impromptu presentation (Buttelmann and
3517 Römpke, 2014), and improved mood among visitors to a public aquarium (Cracknell et al.,
3518 2016). Thus, the secondary aim of this study was to investigate the specific relationship
3519 between keeping ornamental fishes and mental well-being and loneliness during the
3520 pandemic.

3521 As the comparison of companion animal guardians and non-guardians may represent an
3522 oversimplification of the relationship between companion animal guardianship and well-being
3523 (Saunders et al., 2017, Barcelos et al., 2020), factors such as sociodemographic
3524 characteristics are now widely accounted for in cross-sectional HAI research. Less well
3525 understood is how the type and amount of engagement between an individual and their
3526 companion animal may influence the relationship between companion animal guardianship
3527 and well-being (Barcelos et al., 2020, Rodriguez, Herzog and Gee, 2021). Thus, the current
3528 study examined how these relationships may be influenced by the amount of time
3529 participants spent engaging in specific behaviours with their companion animal.

3530 Finally, as it is possible that neither quantitative nor qualitative methods are sufficient to
3531 understand the relationship between companion animal guardianship and well-being when
3532 used in isolation, the current study used an embedded mixed-methods approach. The

3533 purpose of using this approach was to obtain qualitative data that could support the
3534 interpretation of quantitative findings.

3535 **5.3 Methods**

3536 **5.3.1 Design and procedure**

3537 This study was approved by the School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee at the
3538 University of the West of Scotland (Ref:12045, Appendix F), and the Mars Research Review
3539 Board. An embedded mixed-methods design (Cresswell, 2014) was used, with the
3540 qualitative component embedded within the larger quantitative study (Figure 5.1). A
3541 convergent approach was used. Quantitative data were collected from June to November
3542 2020 via an online, cross-sectional survey, and qualitative data were collected from June
3543 2020 to January 2021 via open-ended survey questions and in-depth interviews; all
3544 participants who completed both components completed the survey prior to the interview.
3545 Both datasets were analysed independently, with the qualitative findings used to inform the
3546 interpretation of the quantitative results.

3547 Figure 5.1 Embedded mixed methods design

3548 **5.3.2 Participants and recruitment**

3549 Survey participants ($n = 1199$) were an international sample of adults (18+ years) proficient
3550 in the English language. The sample comprised mainly individuals from the UK (51%) and
3551 USA (32%). Participants were recruited through opportunity sampling (e.g. via social media),
3552 with fish-specific organisations/networks purposively targeted. Interview participants ($n = 25$)
3553 were recruited either by them contacting the researcher following completion of the survey,

3554 or *via* the same process described above; they comprised individuals from either the UK
 3555 (84%) or the USA (16%). Both companion animal guardians and non-guardians were eligible
 3556 to participate in the survey, whereas only companion animal guardians could take part in an
 3557 interview. Very few participants kept ornamental fishes as their only companion animal, thus
 3558 data from fish guardians represent the experiences of those who keep ornamental fishes in
 3559 addition to other companion animals. Informed consent was obtained from all participants
 3560 prior to their participation.

3561 **5.3.3 Materials**

3562 *5.3.3.1 Survey*

3563 The survey consisted of a mix of open- and closed-ended questions split over six sections,
 3564 as described in Table 5.1; questions are provided in full in Appendix H.

3565 **Table 5.1 Description of survey questions by section of survey**

Section of survey	Description
Section 1: Demographic details	Closed questions: age group, gender, ethnicity, highest level of education, marital status, country of residence, and number of adults and children living in the household.
Section 2: Social and lifestyle behaviours during the pandemic	Closed questions regarding the level of social interaction experienced during the pandemic; frequency of communication with friends and family outside the household <i>via</i> written methods (e.g. text messaging, email), verbal methods (e.g. phone or video calls) or face-to-face, and frequency of having left the home to exercise or complete essential errands (responses from 1 = “Never” to 7 = “More than once a day”); employment status during the pandemic; period of self-isolation greater than one week (yes/no).
Section 3: Companion animal guardianship and level of engagement	Mix of closed and open questions. Participants who kept companion animals indicated which types (dogs, cats, fish, small mammals, exotic animals, birds, and/or other), and for each type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of individuals (plus number of tanks/ponds for fishes). • If they were the primary caregiver(s). • Where the animal lived (inside the home/outside). • Where the animal slept (dogs and cats only). • Whether interaction with that animal type had been affected by the pandemic (open-ended question).

-
- The perceived influence of that animal type on their well-being during the pandemic (1 = “Extremely negative” to 7 = “Extremely positive”).
 - Level of engagement, i.e., the amount of time spent undertaking different behaviours relating to that companion animal type on a typical day during the pandemic (1 = “None” to 8 = “More than four hours”); some behaviours were measured for all animal types (e.g. time spent feeding/talking to animals), some were species-specific (e.g. time spent walking dogs/conducting tank or pond maintenance). Level of engagement was measured rather than human–animal bond, as it is unclear how the latter applies within the fish guardianship dynamic.

Additional questions regarding the general experience of companion animal guardianship during the pandemic included:

- Problems accessing supplies or veterinary treatment (yes/no).
- Other pandemic-related issues regarding care of companion animals.
- Level of concern about contracting/giving SARS-CoV-2 from/to companion animals (1 = “Not at all concerned” to 4 = “Extremely concerned”).
- Any new animals purchased/adopted during/because of the pandemic.

Section 4:

Well-being assessments

Series of four validated scales to measure loneliness and well-being:

1. The short-form UCLA Loneliness Scale (UCLA-LS) (Hughes et al., 2004) measured overall loneliness. Thinking about their life “at the moment”, participants gave responses to three items (e.g. “How often do you feel that you lack companionship?”) on a 3-point scale from 1 = “Hardly ever” to 3 = “Often”. Scores were calculated by summing responses (min = 3, max = 9). This scale is commonly used to measure loneliness in HAI research (Gilbey and Tani, 2015), and has satisfactory levels of reliability and validity (Hughes et al., 2004).
 2. The De Jong Gierveld Loneliness Scale is considered a reliable and valid instrument to measure social, emotional and overall loneliness (De Jong Gierveld and Van Tilburg, 2006). Responses to six items (e.g. “I miss having people around me”) could be “yes”, “more or less” or “no”. Participants responded with regard to how they were currently feeling. One point was given for items 1–3 if the response was “yes” or “more or less”, and for items 4–6 if the response was “no” or “more or less”. Emotional loneliness was calculated by summing items 1–3, social loneliness by summing items 4–6 (min = 0, max = 3 for each), and overall loneliness by summing all items (min = 0, max = 6).
 3. The Warwick–Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale (WEMWBS) (Tennant et al., 2007) measured mental well-being. Participants indicated how much 14 statements (e.g. “I’ve been feeling optimistic about the future”) had applied to them over the past two weeks using a 5-point scale (1 = “None of the
-

time” to 5 = “All of the time”). Scores were calculated by summing responses to all items (min = 14, max = 70). The WEMWBS is used extensively in psychological research and is considered psychometrically sound (Tennant et al., 2007). The long version was used as it covers both psychological functioning and positive affect, while the short version covers only psychological functioning.

4. The short-form of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21) (Lovibond and Lovibond, 1995, Henry and Crawford, 2005) required participants to respond to 21 statements (e.g. “I found it hard to wind down”) using a scale from 0 = “Did not apply to me at all” to 3 = “Applied to me very much” to indicate how much each statement had applied to them over the past two weeks. The timescale for the DASS-21 is usually the past week but was altered to match the WEMWBS. A total score for each construct was calculated by summing responses to all items from the relevant scales (min = 0, max = 21 per subscale). The DASS-21 has high internal consistency and discriminant validity (Antony et al., 1998).

Section 5: Rating scales for change in well-being during the pandemic	Participants indicated how anxious, low or depressed, stressed, and lonely they had felt during the pandemic, on a scale from 1 = “Much less than normal” to 7 = “Much more than normal”. Overall well-being during the pandemic was rated on a scale from 1 = “Much worse than usual” to 7 = “Much better than usual”. These items were used to support the understanding of whether any relationships identified between companion animal guardianship and well-being related to the influence of companion animals during the pandemic or are tapping into existing differences in the populations.
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Section 6: Open-ended questions	Two items allowed participants to describe in their own words how they had supported their mental well-being during the pandemic, and the specific contribution of their companion animals (if they had any).
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3566 *5.3.3.2 Interviews*

3567 A semi-structured interview schedule was used (see Appendix H). Demographic information
 3568 was collected *via* closed questions, after which participants were asked to tell the researcher
 3569 “a little bit” about their companion animals. The rest of the interview focused on their
 3570 experiences of being a companion animal guardian during the pandemic. All interviews were
 3571 conducted remotely *via* phone ($n = 7$) or video conferencing ($n = 18$), and were audio
 3572 recorded with the permission of the participant.

3573 **5.3.4 Data analysis**

3574 *5.3.4.1 Quantitative data management*

3575 Survey data were checked for accuracy and completeness prior to analysis; three
3576 participants provided inconsistent answers and so their data were removed. Ambiguous
3577 responses and those of “prefer not to say” were recorded as missing data but did not exceed
3578 2% of responses per item. Where data were missing for the standardised assessments
3579 (<2% per scale), total scores were not calculated. Several demographic variables had low
3580 response rates for one or more categories. Where there was reasonable justification, these
3581 categories were combined prior to analysis (e.g. for country of residence “Australia or New
3582 Zealand” ($n = 39$) and “Canada” ($n = 19$) were collapsed into the category of “other” country).
3583 Where there was no reasonable justification, the original categories were retained unless cell
3584 sizes were too small to be included in the analyses (e.g. the category of “partner, not living
3585 together” ($n = 72$) for marital status was retained, but genders other than male or female ($n =$
3586 6) could not be included).

3587 The response categories for the social and lifestyle variables were also condensed to reduce
3588 the number of parameters in the analyses and provide greater balance in group sizes. For
3589 each variable, the median was identified and responses within the corresponding category
3590 were assigned a value of ‘average’. Responses for the categories above and below the
3591 median were recorded as ‘more than average’ and ‘less than average’, respectively. For
3592 example, for frequency of exercise outside the home the median fell within the category “A
3593 few times a week” so these responses were recorded as average; responses of “Never” to
3594 “Once a week” were recorded as less than average, and responses of “Once a day” or “More
3595 than once a day” as more than average. Where the median fell within the highest or lowest
3596 category, that variable was not included in the analyses. Variables relating to the level of
3597 engagement with companion animals (e.g. time spent walking dogs) were condensed using
3598 the same procedure. Due to wide variation in employment status, participants were
3599 categorised as either “working” or “not working” during the pandemic.

3600 *5.3.4.2 Companion animal guardianship, mental well-being and loneliness*

3601 Separate hierarchical multiple regression analyses (as in Antonacopoulos and Pychyl
3602 (2014)) were conducted to determine whether companion animal guardianship was related
3603 to scores on the standardised assessments of depression, anxiety, stress, mental well-being
3604 and loneliness. The model had three stages. Demographic characteristics were entered in
3605 stage one; it was not possible to include ethnicity as the sample was predominantly white (n
3606 = 1096, 91%). Social and lifestyle factors were entered at stage two; bivariate correlations
3607 were used to determine which variables significantly correlated with at least one dependent
3608 variable, and these variables were included in the model. Companion animal guardianship
3609 was entered in the final stage as separate dichotomous predictors for whether participants
3610 kept any type of companion animal, and whether they kept dogs, cats, fish or other types of
3611 companion animal (yes/no for each).

3612 Data were analysed using *R* version 4.0.0 (R Core Team, 2020). There was no evidence of
3613 multicollinearity, but in all cases, diagnostics indicated that assumptions were violated due to
3614 the presence of influential data points and non-normality of residuals. As robust analyses are
3615 recommended for data which violate model assumptions (Field and Wilcox, 2017), robust
3616 regression analyses were conducted *via* the “*lmrob*” function of the “*robustbase*” package
3617 (Maechler et al., 2020), using the default settings recommended by Koller and Stahel (2017).
3618 At each stage a Wald-type test statistic was used to assess whether the inclusion of the
3619 additional predictors resulted in a significant change in robust deviance compared to the
3620 reduced model; p -values < 0.05 were deemed to be statistically significant.

3621 Multiple scales were used to measure loneliness, but no differences were found with regard
3622 to influence of companion animal guardianship across these measures, so only results
3623 pertaining to the UCLA-LS are reported.

3624 *5.3.4.3 Level of engagement with companion animals, mental well-being and loneliness*

3625 To examine the influence of level of engagement between a guardian and their companion
3626 animal, further robust multiple regression analyses were conducted for the subsets of

3627 participants who kept dogs, cats and fishes. Each model included both general and species-
3628 specific engagement variables, and whether the participant was the primary caregiver for
3629 their companion animal (yes, no or responsibility equally shared with another). All predictors
3630 were entered into the models simultaneously, otherwise the analyses were conducted as
3631 described above.

3632 *5.3.4.4 Qualitative data analysis*

3633 Data analysis was conducted using NVivo 12 Pro (QSR International Pty Ltd, 2018).

3634 Interview data were combined with responses to the survey question “In what ways, if any,
3635 do you feel your companion animals have influenced your mental well-being during the
3636 pandemic?” ($n = 757$), and analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke,
3637 2006, 2019, Braun et al., 2019). An essentialist approach was followed, assuming that
3638 participants’ accounts reflected reality, and seeking to understand these experiences to
3639 deepen understanding of the quantitative findings. The analysis was conducted by HC; KS
3640 read the entire dataset and the final report to ensure the analysis provided an accurate and
3641 complete representation of the data.

3642 Familiarisation was achieved through verbatim transcription of the interviews and active
3643 rereading of the dataset. Generation of codes was based on the semantic content of the
3644 data and followed a predominantly inductive approach; potential codes identified during
3645 familiarisation formed the basis of the analysis, but the researcher coded openly for any
3646 relevant features of the dataset. Following initial coding, themes were constructed by
3647 organising codes into groups to identify “patterns of shared meaning across the dataset”
3648 (Braun and Clarke, 2019, p.592); thematic maps were used to support this process and
3649 visualise the structure of the analysis. Candidate themes were then ‘tested out’ against the
3650 data; all extracts coded onto each theme were examined to determine whether they formed
3651 a coherent pattern, and brief textual descriptions were produced and compared to identify
3652 areas of overlap. Adjustments were made as needed. Finally, the entire dataset was
3653 reviewed to ensure the themes accurately and fully represented the data. Each of the final

3654 themes represents a patterned response within the data that captures something of
3655 importance to the research question; they were not selected based on prevalence alone.

3656 Data were analysed across all types of companion animal collectively. However, in line with
3657 the objective to focus on ornamental fishes, extracts were chosen to represent companion
3658 animal guardianship in general, with additional quotations from fish guardians provided
3659 where relevant.

3660 **5.4 Results**

3661 **5.4.1 Sample characteristics**

3662 *5.4.1.1 Survey*

3663 Survey data were available for 1199 participants; 1159 (97%) responded to the question “Do
3664 you have any companion animals (pets)?” and 1069 (89%) reached the end of the survey.
3665 Most participants ($n = 1005$, 84%) kept at least one companion animal, with 42% ($n = 419$) of
3666 these individuals keeping a mix of companion animal types. Dogs were the most popular
3667 species both overall ($n = 661$, 66%) and where they were the only type of companion animal
3668 kept in the household ($n = 329$, 33%); cats were the second most popular (total $n = 469$,
3669 47%; single species $n = 200$, 20%). Fewer individuals kept fishes ($n = 218$, 22%), small
3670 mammals ($n = 87$, 9%), exotic animals ($n = 77$, 8%), birds ($n = 65$, 6%) or other types of
3671 companion animal ($n = 47$, 5%), and in all cases 2% or less were kept as the only species.
3672 “Other” companion animals included horses, ponies or farm animals, insects/invertebrates,
3673 and wild birds. With regard to ornamental fishes, most participants kept their fishes in tanks
3674 ($n = 171$, 78%), or tanks and ponds ($n = 33$, 15%); only 10 participants (5%) kept fishes in
3675 ponds alone (four participants did not state whether their fishes were kept in tanks or ponds).
3676 Survey sample characteristics for companion animal guardians and non-guardians are
3677 summarised in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2 Survey sample characteristics by companion animal guardianship status and type of companion animal

	Dog guardians (n =661)	Cat guardians (n =469)	Fish guardians (n =218)	Other companion animal guardians (n =226)	All companion animal guardians (n =1005)	Non- companion animal guardians (n =154)	Total (n =1159)
Age							
18-34	214 (32%)	172 (37%)	98 (45%)	105 (46%)	364 (36%)	74 (48%)	438 (38%)
35-50	241 (36%)	169 (36%)	77 (35%)	75 (33%)	353 (35%)	41 (27%)	394 (34%)
51-69	185 (28%)	112 (24%)	39 (18%)	43 (19%)	254 (25%)	27 (18%)	281 (24%)
70+	20 (3%)	16 (3%)	3 (1%)	3 (1%)	32 (3%)	12 (8%)	44 (4%)
Prefer not to say	1 (<1%)	0	1 (<1%)	0	2 (<1%)	0	2 (<1%)
Gender							
Female	554 (84%)	404 (86%)	157 (72%)	196 (87%)	839 (83%)	111 (72%)	950 (82%)
Male	102 (15%)	57 (12%)	59 (27%)	28 (12%)	154 (15%)	41 (27%)	195 (17%)
Other	2 (<1%)	3 (1%)	0	1 (<1%)	4 (<1%)	2 (1%)	6 (1%)
Prefer not to say	3 (<1%)	5 (1%)	2 (1%)	1 (<1%)	8 (1%)	0	8 (1%)
Ethnicity							
White	604 (91%)	429 (91%)	205 (94%)	219 (97%)	920 (92%)	141 (92%)	1061 (92%)
Asian	11 (2%)	10 (2%)	4 (2%)	2 (1%)	18 (2%)	5 (3%)	23 (2%)
Black or African American	4 (1%)	3 (1%)	0	1 (<1%)	5 (<1%)	1 (1%)	6 (1%)
Hispanic or Latino	24 (4%)	15 (3%)	0	0	32 (3%)	3 (2%)	35 (3%)
Two or more	8 (1%)	4 (1%)	3 (1%)	2 (1%)	12 (1%)	1 (1%)	13 (1%)
Prefer not to say/unclear	10 (2%)	8 (2%)	6 (3%)	2 (1%)	18 (2%)	3 (2%)	21 (2%)

Education							
High school or below	91 (14%)	64 (14%)	42 (19%)	43 (19%)	135 (13%)	15 (10%)	150 (13%)
Undergraduate	269 (41%)	198 (42%)	100 (46%)	99 (44%)	415 (41%)	47 (31%)	462 (40%)
Masters	183 (28%)	127 (27%)	49 (22%)	42 (19%)	270 (27%)	57 (37%)	327 (28%)
Doctorate	111 (17%)	75 (16%)	21 (10%)	38 (17%)	172 (17%)	35 (23%)	207 (18%)
Prefer not to say/don't know	7 (1%)	5 (1%)	6 (3%)	4 (2%)	13 (1%)	0	13 (1%)
Marital							
Married/living with partner	426 (64%)	276 (59%)	145 (67%)	137 (61%)	620 (62%)	77 (50%)	697 (60%)
Partner, not living together	26 (4%)	30 (6%)	20 (9%)	16 (7%)	57 (6%)	14 (9%)	71 (6%)
Single, separated, divorced or widowed	206 (31%)	156 (33%)	51 (23%)	72 (32%)	320 (32%)	61 (40%)	381 (33%)
Prefer not to say/unclear	3 (<1%)	7 (1%)	2 (1%)	1 (<1%)	8 (1%)	2 (1%)	10 (1%)
Live with children							
Yes	175 (26%)	125 (27%)	80 (37%)	72 (32%)	244 (24%)	38 (25%)	282 (24%)
No	486 (74%)	344 (73%)	138 (63%)	154 (68%)	761 (76%)	116 (75%)	877 (76%)
Country							
United Kingdom	277 (42%)	216 (46%)	139 (64%)	139 (62%)	473 (47%)	113 (73%)	586 (51%)
United States	244 (37%)	174 (37%)	52 (24%)	60 (27%)	351 (35%)	24 (16%)	375 (32%)
Other	139 (21%)	78 (17%)	27 (12%)	27 (12%)	179 (18%)	16 (10%)	195 (17%)
Prefer not to say	1 (<1%)	1 (<1%)	0	0	2 (<1%)	1 (1%)	3 (<1%)
Frequency of written communication							
Less than an average amount	261 (39%)	185 (39%)	81 (37%)	92 (41%)	390 (39%)	64 (42%)	454 (39%)
An average amount	400 (61%)	284 (61%)	137 (63%)	134 (59%)	615 (61%)	90 (58%)	705 (61%)

Frequency of verbal communication							
Less than an average amount	204 (31%)	148 (32%)	69 (32%)	78 (35%)	305 (30%)	31 (20%)	336 (29%)
An average amount	249 (38%)	198 (42%)	92 (42%)	91 (40%)	404 (40%)	61 (40%)	465 (40%)
More than an average amount	208 (31%)	123 (26%)	57 (26%)	57 (25%)	296 (29%)	62 (40%)	358 (31%)
Frequency of face-to-face communication							
Less than an average amount	214 (32%)	161 (34%)	76 (35%)	65 (29%)	330 (33%)	48 (31%)	378 (33%)
An average amount	163 (25%)	119 (25%)	51 (23%)	58 (26%)	258 (26%)	38 (25%)	296 (26%)
More than an average amount	284 (43%)	188 (40%)	91 (42%)	103 (46%)	416 (41%)	67 (44%)	483 (42%)
Prefer not to say	0	1 (<1%)	0	0	1 (<1%)	1 (1%)	2 (<1%)
Frequency of exercise outside the home							
Less than an average amount	195 (30%)	171 (36%)	77 (35%)	67 (30%)	323 (32%)	44 (29%)	367 (32%)
An average amount	119 (18%)	121 (26%)	57 (26%)	53 (23%)	233 (23%)	50 (32%)	283 (24%)
More than an average amount	345 (52%)	175 (37%)	84 (39%)	106 (47%)	445 (44%)	60 (39%)	505 (44%)
Prefer not to say	2 (<1%)	2 (<1%)	0	0	4 (<1%)	0	4 (<1%)
Frequency of essential errands							
Less than an average amount	190 (29%)	139 (30%)	63 (29%)	66 (29%)	291 (29%)	41 (27%)	332 (29%)
An average amount	260 (39%)	188 (40%)	72 (33%)	81 (36%)	387 (39%)	69 (45%)	456 (39%)
More than an average amount	211 (32%)	142 (30%)	83 (38%)	79 (35%)	327 (33%)	44 (29%)	371 (32%)
Working							
Yes	494 (75%)	356 (76%)	147 (67%)	167 (74%)	756 (75%)	122 (79%)	878 (76%)
No	163 (25%)	110 (23%)	69 (32%)	58 (26%)	241 (24%)	32 (21%)	273 (24%)
Prefer not to say	4 (1%)	3 (1%)	2 (1%)	1 (<1%)	8 (1%)	0	8 (1%)

Period of isolation greater than 1 week							
Yes	189 (29%)	149 (32%)	72 (33%)	64 (28%)	305 (30%)	31 (20%)	336 (29%)
No	471 (71%)	319 (68%)	145 (67%)	161 (71%)	697 (69%)	123 (80%)	820 (71%)
Prefer not to say	1 (<1%)	1 (<1%)	1 (<1%)	1 (<1%)	3 (<1%)	0	3 (<1%)

3679 Note: 'Other' genders were recorded as missing data for analyses; examples of unclear responses include "human being" and "English" for
3680 ethnicity, and "boyfriend" and "engaged" for marital status.

3681 **5.4.1.2 Interviews**

3682 Twenty-five participants took part in an interview. Most identified as female ($n = 22$, 88%); 10
3683 (40%) were aged 18–34 years, with slightly fewer aged 35–50 years ($n = 7$, 28%) or 51–69
3684 years ($n = 8$, 32%). All resided in the UK ($n = 21$, 84%) or the USA ($n = 4$, 16%) and most
3685 lived with other people ($n = 21$, 84%). Dogs and cats were the most popular companion
3686 animals ($n = 13$ for both, 52%). Seven participants (28%) kept fishes, four (16%) kept small
3687 mammals, and three (12%) kept exotic animals; no participants kept birds or other
3688 companion animals. Some individuals did report keeping invertebrates, but these were
3689 always kept alongside fishes. Eleven participants (44%) kept a mix of companion animal
3690 types; all participants who kept fishes kept at least one other type of companion animal.
3691 Fourteen participants (56%) were the primary caregiver for at least one companion animal,
3692 and all other participants shared this responsibility with another person.

3693 **5.4.2 Quantitative findings**

3694 Participants who kept companion animals overwhelmingly rated them to have had a positive
3695 effect on their well-being during the pandemic (Figure 5.2). Most participants believed their
3696 dogs and cats had an extremely or moderately positive effect on their well-being, while fewer
3697 individuals believed they had a slightly positive effect or no effect at all. To a lesser extent,
3698 the same pattern of results was observed for guardians of other companion animals, whereas
3699 for fishes there was a more even split across these four categories. For all animal types, only
3700 a very small minority of participants rated their companion animals as having had any
3701 degree of negative effect on their well-being (<2%).

3702 Eighteen per cent of participants had experienced issues obtaining pet care supplies and
3703 14% reported problems accessing veterinary treatment; 13% reported additional negative
3704 impacts associated with the pandemic (e.g. reduced frequency of dog walking, no access to
3705 professional grooming services). Twelve per cent of participants ($n = 125$) reported adopting
3706 or purchasing a new companion animal during the pandemic, with around a quarter (24%)
3707 agreeing that the pandemic was instrumental in their decision to adopt. Most participants

3708 Figure 5.2 The percentage of participants who responded with each category across the
 3709 scale by type of companion animal. ‘Other companion animal’ is inclusive of small mammals,
 3710 exotic animals, birds, and otherwise unspecified companion animals (e.g. horses). Dogs $n =$
 3711 661, cats $n = 469$, fish $n = 218$, and other companion animal $n = 276$.

3712 (92%) reported being not at all concerned about contracting SARS-CoV-2 from their
 3713 companion animals; 7% were a little concerned and less than 1% were somewhat or
 3714 extremely concerned. More individuals reported being a little (20%), somewhat (6%) or
 3715 extremely (1%) concerned about passing SARS-CoV-2 onto their companion animals.
 3716 However, most (73%) were not at all concerned about this possibility.

3717 5.4.2.1 Companion animal guardianship, mental well-being and loneliness

3718 Correlations between participants’ scores on the standardised assessments and their
 3719 subjective ratings of how the pandemic had influenced their loneliness and mental well-being
 3720 ranged from medium to large in size ($r_s = 0.36-0.51$, $p < 0.001$ in all cases). This suggests
 3721 that scores on the standardised assessments likely reflected a combination of pre-existing
 3722 mental states and pandemic-related changes.

3723 Full results of the robust hierarchical regression analyses are shown in Appendix I, Table S1.

3724 Participants’ demographic characteristics explained between 7.1% and 12.9% of variance in

3725 their scores on the standardised assessments. In all cases, this was a statistically significant
3726 improvement in the model fit (χ^2 (12) = 74.94–150.85, $p < 0.001$ in all cases). Social and
3727 lifestyle factors explained an additional 2.6% to 3.6% of variance; again, the model fit was
3728 significantly improved for all dependent variables (χ^2 (8) = 27.66–42.54, $p < 0.01$ in all
3729 cases). The addition of companion animal guardianship factors did not significantly improve
3730 the model fit for any dependent variable (χ^2 (5) = 1.40–9.88, $p > 0.05$ in all cases). Dog
3731 guardianship was found to be significantly associated with depression, and guardianship of
3732 other companion animals was found to be significantly associated with anxiety. However, in
3733 both cases there was no overall change in robust deviance, suggesting that these
3734 associations emerged because dog and other companion animal guardianship shared
3735 variance with a predictor or predictors already included in the model.

3736 *5.4.2.2 Level of engagement with companion animals, mental well-being and loneliness*

3737 The results of the robust regression analyses are given in Appendix I, Table S2. Level of
3738 engagement with dogs explained between 4.8% and 7.1% of variance in scores on the
3739 standardised assessments, and in all cases this was a statistically significant improvement in
3740 the model fit (χ^2 (12) = 28.19–48.03, $p < 0.01$ in all cases). With respect to the contribution of
3741 individual predictors, spending less time than average talking to dogs was associated with
3742 higher mental well-being ($\hat{\beta} = 2.41$, $SE = 1.22$, $t = 1.97$, $p < 0.05$). Lower mental well-being
3743 ($\hat{\beta} = -2.22$, $SE = 1.08$, $t = 2.07$, $p = 0.039$) and higher depression ($\hat{\beta} = 1.78$, $SE = 0.88$, $t =$
3744 2.03 , $p = 0.043$) were associated with a greater than average amount of time spent petting
3745 dogs, while spending a less time than average petting dogs was associated with lower
3746 anxiety ($\hat{\beta} = -1.59$, $SE = 0.58$, $t = 2.74$, $p = 0.006$). Walking dogs for less time than average
3747 per day was associated with both higher anxiety ($\hat{\beta} = 1.38$, $SE = 0.46$, $t = 3.02$, $p = 0.003$)
3748 and higher loneliness ($\hat{\beta} = 0.41$, $SE = 0.17$, $t = 2.35$, $p = 0.019$); loneliness was also
3749 associated with less time than average spent undertaking 'other' activities with one's dog ($\hat{\beta} =$
3750 0.49 , $SE = 0.20$, $t = 2.40$, $p = 0.017$). Finally, being the primary caregiver for a dog, or
3751 sharing this responsibility with another person, was associated with more positive scores

3752 across all dependent variables relative to not being the primary caregiver ($p < 0.05$ in all
3753 cases).

3754 The model for level of engagement with cats was a statistically significant improvement on
3755 the null model for depression, anxiety, and stress ($\chi^2(10) = 20.48-23.39$, $p < 0.05$ in all
3756 cases). These models explained between 4.5% and 5.2% of variance in the relevant
3757 dependent variable. Spending more time than average talking to cats was associated with
3758 lower anxiety ($\hat{\beta} = -1.76$, $SE = 0.75$, $t = 2.35$, $p = 0.019$) whereas spending less time than
3759 average was associated with lower depression ($\hat{\beta} = -4.29$, $SE = 1.15$, $t = 3.73$, $p = <0.001$);
3760 lower stress was associated with spending both more ($\hat{\beta} = -3.01$, $SE = 1.35$, $t = 2.23$, $p =$
3761 0.026) and less ($\hat{\beta} = -3.65$, $SE = 1.25$, $t = 2.92$, $p = 0.004$) time than average talking to cats.
3762 For mental well-being and loneliness, level of engagement with cats did not significantly
3763 improve the model fit (mental well-being, $\chi^2(10) = 14.24$, $p = 0.162$; UCLA-LS, $\chi^2(10) =$
3764 14.83 , $p = 0.139$).

3765 The model for level of engagement with fishes did not result in a significant improvement in
3766 model fit for any of the dependent variables (mental well-being, $\chi^2(10) = 5.37$, $p = 0.865$;
3767 loneliness, $\chi^2(10) = 9.45$, $p = 0.450$; depression, $\chi^2(10) = 5.33$, $p = 0.868$; anxiety, $\chi^2(10) =$
3768 7.34 , $p = 0.693$; stress, $\chi^2(10) = 9.46$, $p = 0.489$).

3769 **5.4.3 Qualitative findings**

3770 Two themes were developed from the data. “Companion animals as providers of social
3771 support” related to the notion that companion animals offered an alternative to interpersonal
3772 connections during a time of isolation. “Companion animals as providers of purpose and
3773 perspective” related more to the practicalities of being a companion animal guardian, and
3774 how this helped participants retain a sense of normality and feel useful when they may have
3775 otherwise become dispirited. There was also evidence that animal welfare may have been
3776 influenced by the pandemic, but these data did not relate to the current research question
3777 and so are not reported here. Example quotations are provided in Tables 5.3 and 5.4.

3778 *5.4.3.1 Theme 1: Companion animals as providers of social support*

3779 *“It meant never being alone”*

3780 Most participants felt their companion animals had provided comfort and support, both prior
3781 to and during the pandemic. This support was experienced at two levels. At a basic level,
3782 participants were comforted by the mere presence of a companion animal as another living
3783 being in their home. At a deeper level, companion animals provided psychological and
3784 emotional support, helping their guardians cope with the uncertainty caused by the
3785 pandemic. Individuals experiencing a greater degree of isolation particularly appreciated the
3786 support provided by their companion animals, such as those who lived alone or had
3787 switched to remote working during the pandemic.

3788 Despite being isolated from friends, family or colleagues, having companion animals meant
3789 that participants were never truly alone; they were surrogates for interpersonal contact when
3790 connections with other humans were restricted. Although the quantitative results showed no
3791 evidence of a relationship between companion animal guardianship and loneliness, some
3792 participants clarified that their companion animals could not fully replace the need for
3793 human-to-human connections. Therefore, the comfort and support provided by companion
3794 animals may have been insufficient to alleviate feelings of loneliness to an extent that it was
3795 observable *via* quantitative assessments.

3796 *“A substitute for human talk and touch”*

3797 Given the need to maintain physical distance from other humans, it is unsurprising that
3798 cuddling and other forms of physical affection were an important aspect of the support
3799 provided by companion animals during the COVID-19 pandemic. Many participants also
3800 reported talking to their companion animals, and their non-verbal responses provided
3801 comfort by showing that somebody was listening. Again, these effects were of particular
3802 importance to individuals who were more isolated from their social networks, suggesting that
3803 where human-to-human interactions were impossible due to pandemic-related restrictions,
3804 companion animals provided an accessible alternative. This corresponds with the

3805 quantitative finding that a higher level of engagement with dogs, and to a lesser extent cats,
3806 was associated with poorer outcomes for some dependent variables; individuals
3807 experiencing greater isolation may have simultaneously experienced poorer mental states
3808 and been more inclined to seek support from their companion animals. Furthermore, if the
3809 comfort and support provided by companion animals was dependent on these physical and
3810 social interactions, it would explain why participants were less positive about the impact of
3811 ornamental fishes on their well-being during the pandemic; as put succinctly by one
3812 participant, it is “hard to hug a fish” (Survey, Participant 171).

3813 *“Bridging interpersonal connections during social distancing”*

3814 Companion animals also benefitted their guardians by facilitating interpersonal connections.
3815 Even during the tightest restrictions, leaving the house was permitted for reasons related to
3816 animal welfare, such as to walk dogs or attend to horses. This often led to brief socially-
3817 distanced interactions that were vastly appreciated during the period of isolation.
3818 Correspondingly, the quantitative results indicated that walking dogs for less time than
3819 average each day was associated with higher loneliness; possibly, those who spent less
3820 time walking their dogs had fewer opportunities for these brief social encounters.

3821 Within existing interpersonal relationships, activities such as playing with or exercising
3822 companion animals were an opportunity to connect, particularly when other social or leisure
3823 activities were unavailable. Even when communication took place *via* electronic methods,
3824 companion animals acted as social catalysts by providing a topic of conversation. However,
3825 these benefits may not have been limited to companion animal guardians. Some participants
3826 noted that friends, family and strangers were interested in hearing about, or interacting with
3827 their companion animals, and it is unclear whether these individuals kept companion animals
3828 themselves. As the quantitative results did not account for human–animal interaction outside
3829 of the companion animal guardianship dynamic, these interactions could have confounded
3830 the results, particularly as participants of a survey about companion animals are likely to
3831 have positive attitudes towards animals, irrespective of their current guardianship status.

Table 5.3 Example quotations for "Companion animals as providers of social support"

Subtheme	Example Quotations
It meant never being alone	<p data-bbox="475 309 1390 394">“They are company, comfort, a living presence in my empty home” (Survey, Participant 677)</p> <p data-bbox="475 432 1390 869">“...my husband his work is outside of the home, so during lockdown he had to be at home...when he left it was a big change because we were like three months, you know, we were on top of each other in a one bedroom flat and it was really, really nice because you know I’d get on with work and he’d be doing things around the house and yeah he was just there, but then when he started going back to work I was like “oh my gosh” you know, and then I’m not going back to work, I’m here at home still so I think at that point having the cats and dog became even more important” (Interview, Participant 21)</p> <p data-bbox="475 907 1390 1043">“...having her for company in a time when I am very isolated has been not a perfect substitute for human interaction but it has been something...” (Survey, Participant 318)</p>
A substitute for human talk and touch	<p data-bbox="475 1081 1390 1317">“As I’ve had less face to face contact with friends and family my dog’s company has been exceptionally important. I think I would have felt very alone otherwise. I normally have a hug with friends/family, so it’s been good to have my dog curl up next to me for a cuddle.” (Survey, Participant 51)</p> <p data-bbox="475 1355 1390 1585">“They have been company for me and the only other beings I could have any physical contact with for three full months. They’re very loving and sweet, but I’ve still felt the lack of a human hug too—dog snuggles are lovely but it’s also not the same as being held.” (Survey, Participant 222)</p> <p data-bbox="475 1624 1390 1917">“...even though they don’t answer me back, to be able to speak with them in such a way that it’s humanising, yes it’s anthropomorphising them but that’s part of it, that yes you can talk with them and they do seem to respond and you know, a dog cocks his head when you’re talking to him and it’s because he’s confused but it’s still—you know he’s listening...” (Interview, Participant 14)</p>

Bridging interpersonal connections during social distancing	<p>“When I have taken my dogs out it has sometimes been because of them that strangers might at least say hello, this may have been my only interaction with a human some days” (Survey, Participant 96)</p> <p>“...it’s been really nice to sort of see everyone on zoom calls with their respectively pets and random cats and dogs wandering into frame, so I think that’s been quite nice to see as well, it kind of builds a like ‘oh I didn’t know you had a dog’ or ‘what type of dog do you have’, so that’s been nice...” (Interview, Participant 19)</p> <p>“...I’ve really enjoyed learning new things about the fish or keeping the fish etc. I’ve also enjoyed—I use Instagram and I share pictures [of aquaria] and things on there, which has been cool because I’ve met and been speaking to new people...” (Interview, Participant 10)</p> <p>“...my son [son’s name] wants me to send photos of the dogs and things like that so, so yeah I think because maybe people have got more time on their hands—other people in the family—they’ve wanted to do more with them...” (Interview, Participant 24)</p>
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3833 5.4.3.2 Theme 2: Companion animals as providers of purpose and perspective

3834 “They help maintain a normal routine”

3835 Being unable to understand the concept of a pandemic, companion animals continued to
3836 adhere to their usual schedules, and expected activities such as meals and walks to occur at
3837 specific times of day. As participants recognised their responsibility to their companion
3838 animals, they also continued to adhere to these routines. This was beneficial as it added
3839 structure to their day and allowed them to experience something which resembled normal
3840 life; ornamental fishes were particularly beneficial in this regard, as regular tank maintenance
3841 was essential for fish welfare (see Table 5.4 for supporting quotations). The timing of data
3842 collection may explain why these benefits are not reflected in the quantitative findings. Data
3843 collection began around three months after COVID-19 was declared a pandemic by the
3844 WHO. At this time, many individuals had recommenced work outside the home, while those
3845 working remotely will have had the opportunity to develop new working routines. Had data

3846 collection commenced earlier during the pandemic, these effects may have been evident as
3847 participants had not yet adjusted to the “new normal”.

3848 Exercise routines were also appreciated, and many participants felt that without the need to
3849 walk their dogs they would have lacked the motivation to engage in regular physical activity.
3850 These routines also gave participants an opportunity to be outdoors, which was greatly
3851 valued during the restrictions imposed due to the pandemic. There was quantitative
3852 evidence that having primary or shared responsibility for a dog was associated with more
3853 positive scores for all dependent variables. As having a greater level of responsibility for a
3854 dog presumably increases the likelihood of walking that dog, this supports the idea that the
3855 maintenance of exercise routines was an important benefit of dog guardianship during the
3856 pandemic.

3857 *“Something good to focus on”*

3858 Many participants indicated that their companion animals provided a source of positive
3859 distraction throughout the pandemic. Companion animals not only helped to take their
3860 guardians’ minds off negative thoughts associated with the pandemic, but also provided a
3861 much-needed source of pleasure; their antics gave their guardians a reason to smile. Among
3862 participants who kept ornamental fishes, watching home aquaria was frequently cited as a
3863 beneficial activity; the movement and behaviour of the fishes in the tank captured
3864 participants’ attention, distracting them and inducing relaxation. These findings suggest that
3865 the effect of companion animals on well-being during the pandemic may have been relatively
3866 transient; a guardian may have experienced relief from negative mental states while actively
3867 watching or interacting with their companion animal, but it is unclear how long this effect was
3868 retained once the interaction concluded. As the assessments used in the current study
3869 related to well-being over the previous two weeks, they unfortunately provide no insight into
3870 the role of companion animals as providers of momentary relief.

3871 *“A reason to keep going”*

3872 The responsibility of being a companion animal guardian gave many participants a sense of
3873 purpose. For those experiencing employment issues, caring for a companion animal was a
3874 source of the meaningful activity, whereas others were motivated to ‘carry on’ by the
3875 knowledge that their companion animal was entirely dependent on them. Thus, companion
3876 animal guardianship may not have protected against the negative psychological impact of
3877 the pandemic, but may play a role in how participants cope with these negative
3878 consequences going forward.

3879 Conversely, many participants expressed concern about whether the imposed restrictions
3880 would impact their ability to care for their companion animals, particularly in relation to
3881 obtaining supplies and veterinary treatment. Although for most these concerns were not
3882 realised (a finding corroborated by the quantitative data), several participants expressed that
3883 this was an added stress during an already stressful time. Some participants also expressed
3884 greater concern regarding the impact of the pandemic on their companion animals, than on
3885 their own well-being. This suggests any benefits associated with being a companion animal
3886 guardian during the pandemic may have been negated by additional stresses associated
3887 with this responsibility. Thus, the quantitative analyses may have failed to find evidence of
3888 any associations between companion animal guardianship and loneliness and mental well-
3889 being during the pandemic because the relationship between these variables is more
3890 complex than was accounted for in the statistical models.

3891
3892

Table 5.4 Example quotations for "Companion animals as providers of purpose and perspective"

Subtheme	Example Quotations
They help maintain a normal routine	<p data-bbox="475 344 1385 779">“...one thing with the fish particularly, because they need quite a lot of ongoing care, you know they need regular water changes, you know, all the looking after of the water, you can’t sort of think ‘oh I really can’t be bothered this week’ you have to do it, and having that routine has actually been quite a good thing—everybody laughs about you don’t know what day of the week it is let alone what month of the year it is, because every day’s just the same at the moment, and actually having that regular routine with the fish has been a good thing actually...” (Interview, Participant 17)</p> <p data-bbox="475 819 1385 1003">“They are normal. They act normal. The routine is normal. They seem to like that I am home more. At home, things are normal. This makes it easier to cope with things not being normal outside the home. And makes it easier to stay home.” (Survey, Participant 659)</p> <p data-bbox="475 1043 1385 1375">“Having a dog has definitely helped because I have walked every single day of lockdown so it’s a great excuse for exercise, which also gave me the opportunity to get out and explore what’s on my doorstep, so I’ve discovered new things about where I live. The feeling of getting away from the four walls when we could only exercise once a day was a real mental health lifesaver...” (Survey, Participant 348)</p>
Something good to focus on	<p data-bbox="475 1420 1385 1603">“...you feel out of control, you don’t know who’s going to get sick, when and how badly, there’s a lot of fear and those little moments of escaping that to deal with a companion [animal] is invaluable...” (Interview, Participant 23)</p> <p data-bbox="475 1644 1385 1774">“...it’s so nice on an evening or something if I’m feeding them, they’ll come running in and playing and they’re really cute and make me laugh, they’re better than the television...” (Interview, Participant 5)</p> <p data-bbox="475 1814 1385 1899">“The fish tank has provided relaxation as you can sit and stare at it for a long time and it keeps interest.” (Survey, Participant 462)</p>

A reason to keep going	<p>“I have struggled with feeling useless due to being furloughed but having the dog to feed/walk/train has given my days structure and purpose” (Survey, Participant 668)</p> <p>“...the responsibility of making sure they are okay is motivating to keep going and look after myself also and, in the extreme times, it’s an important reason to stay alive...” (Survey, Participant 706)</p> <p>“Overall the fish have had a positive influence during this time. But there has been anxiety as my fish needed a bigger tank. Impossible to get a tank during lockdown. I had issues buying seafood for my fish as panic buyers bought it all. I had trouble with buying essential items locally. When I thought I had COVID and was told to go into hospital I had no one to look after my fish. So this influenced my decision to stay in hospital.” (Survey, Participant 469)</p> <p>“...I’ve got a cupboard absolutely stashed with the kind of food that I think she’s probably going to like and it’s ok, just because if suddenly I can’t go to the shops “oh my gosh” so—and I’m probably more so on her behalf because for myself, ok I’ll just have plain pasta and I’m quite ok with that but I feel more responsible for her well-being and I want to make sure that she’s got everything she needs...” (Interview, Participant 20)</p>
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3893 **5.5 Discussion**

3894 This study aimed to examine the relationship between companion animal guardianship and
3895 loneliness and mental well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic. Quantitative data analyses
3896 found no evidence of a linear relationship between keeping companion animals and
3897 loneliness or mental well-being, either for all animal types collectively or for specific species
3898 (dogs, cats, ornamental fishes). However, most participants positively rated the impact of
3899 their companion animals on their well-being during the pandemic, and qualitative data
3900 indicated that being a companion animal guardian was associated with a range of benefits in
3901 the context of COVID-19. These findings correspond with research conducted prior to the
3902 pandemic; there is a lack of convincing quantitative evidence to demonstrate differences in

3903 loneliness and well-being between companion animal guardians and non-guardians (Herzog,
3904 2011, Gilbey and Tani, 2015), yet qualitative studies show that people believe their
3905 companion animals positively influence their well-being (Knight and Edwards, 2008, Maharaj
3906 and Haney, 2015, Brooks et al., 2019, Nitkin and Buchanan, 2020).

3907 **5.5.1 Engagement with companion animals during the pandemic**

3908 How people engage with their companion animals may influence the relationships between
3909 companion animal guardianship and loneliness and well-being (Barcelos et al., 2020,
3910 Rodriguez, Herzog and Gee, 2021). The present study found evidence that spending more
3911 time than average talking to or petting dogs tended to be associated with more negative
3912 scores for loneliness and well-being, while the reverse was true for more positive scores.
3913 Causality cannot be established from the current data, but qualitative findings indicated that
3914 companionship, including physical and social interaction, was a benefit of keeping
3915 companion animals during the pandemic, particularly for more isolated individuals. This
3916 finding is corroborated by other research conducted during the pandemic (Shoesmith et al.,
3917 2021). More isolated individuals may therefore have experienced greater loneliness and
3918 poorer mental well-being during the pandemic, and subsequently spent more time engaging
3919 with their dogs as a substitute for interpersonal contact. Correspondingly, previous research
3920 has shown that among people with low levels of social support from humans, higher
3921 attachment to companion animals is associated with higher levels of loneliness
3922 (Antonacopoulos and Pychyl, 2010). However, contact with companion animals was an
3923 imperfect substitute for contact with other humans. Future research may wish to identify
3924 which aspects of interpersonal contact can and cannot be replicated by companion animals
3925 in order to identify which populations may benefit most from human–animal interactions.

3926 The relationships between level of engagement with cats and well-being were less clear;
3927 more positive scores were associated with both greater than average and lower than
3928 average levels of engagement. A possible reason for this finding is that personality
3929 differences between dog and cat guardians influenced their experiences of the pandemic.

3930 Previous research has shown that self-identified 'dog people' tend to be more extraverted
3931 than 'cat people' (Gosling, Sandy and Potter, 2010). While extraversion is usually associated
3932 with less loneliness and greater well-being, these protective effects may have been lost in
3933 the context of the pandemic due to restrictions on social interaction (Gubler et al., 2021).
3934 Due to their more extraverted nature, dog guardians may have had a greater desire for
3935 interpersonal contact which could not be satisfied through engagement with their companion
3936 animals. Cat guardians may have experienced a lesser need for social interaction, and so in
3937 some cases found that engagement with their companion animal was sufficient to alleviate
3938 the negative impacts of the pandemic. Further research is needed to examine how
3939 personality traits may interact with companion animal guardianship to influence the effects of
3940 social isolation.

3941 Previous research has suggested that being a dog guardian may have greater benefits than
3942 the guardianship of other companion animals (Levine et al., 2013, Bao and Schreer, 2016,
3943 Mein and Grant, 2018, Hajek and König, 2020). The current study found that primary or
3944 shared responsibility for a dog was associated with more positive outcomes for all
3945 dependent variables, suggesting that actively caring for a dog has benefits beyond the
3946 simple presence of a dog in the home. A probable explanation relates to the need to
3947 exercise dogs on a regular basis. Not only is there a known link between frequent physical
3948 activity and improved mental health (Chekroud et al., 2018), qualitative data indicated that
3949 dog walking had additional benefits, such as providing opportunities for social interaction and
3950 to spend time outdoors. Spending less time than average walking dogs was also associated
3951 with higher loneliness, possibly because participants had fewer opportunities for social
3952 interaction (although this finding is dependent on self-report data which were not verified with
3953 the use of pedometers or activity trackers). Previous research conducted both prior to and
3954 during the pandemic corroborates the finding that dog walking is associated with increased
3955 social connectedness (McNicholas and Collis, 2000, Wood et al., 2007, Oliva and Johnston,
3956 2020, Shoesmith et al., 2021), while numerous studies have demonstrated benefits

3957 associated with spending time in nature (White et al., 2019, Martin et al., 2020). As having a
3958 greater level of responsibility for a dog presumably increases the likelihood of walking that
3959 dog, this would explain why more positive outcomes are associated with primary or shared
3960 responsibility of a dog, but not for cats or ornamental fishes.

3961 **5.5.2 Negative aspects of companion animal guardianship during the pandemic**

3962 Both quantitative and qualitative data indicated that relatively few participants had
3963 experienced issues ensuring the welfare of their companion animals during the pandemic.
3964 Despite this positive finding, qualitative data suggested that proper care of companion
3965 animals was a significant source of worry for guardians during this time; this finding is
3966 corroborated by other research conducted during the pandemic (Ratschen et al., 2020,
3967 Kogan et al., 2021). Previous research has also indicated that people are willing to delay
3968 hospitalisation (Canady and Sansone, 2019) or refuse access to support services (Howe
3969 and Easterbrook, 2018) for the sake of their companion animals, and similar attitudes were
3970 present in the current study. Participants were often more concerned about the potential
3971 negative impact of COVID-19 on their companion animals than on themselves. For in-
3972 stance, while most participants had no concerns about transmitting SARS-CoV-2 either to or
3973 from their companion animals, a slightly larger proportion reported being concerned about
3974 transmitting the virus to their companion animals than the reverse; this finding is replicated in
3975 other research (Kogan et al., 2021). Therefore, the relationship between companion animal
3976 guardianship and well-being during the pandemic may have been confounded by the unique
3977 stresses associated with keeping companion animals.

3978 A small number of individuals had very negative attitudes regarding the influence of their
3979 companion animals on their well-being during the pandemic. Although these individuals were
3980 very much in the minority, it is important to acknowledge their experiences, particularly as
3981 research in the HAI discipline is subject to self-selection biases; individuals are more likely to
3982 partake if they have positive attitudes towards companion animals (Friedmann and Gee,
3983 2019). As such, the current study findings should be interpreted with this population in mind,

3984 and future research should aim to blind study participants wherever possible to reduce the
3985 impact of these biases.

3986 **5.5.3 Ornamental fishes and the pandemic**

3987 A secondary aim of this research was to investigate the specific relationship between
3988 keeping ornamental fishes and loneliness and mental well-being during the pandemic.

3989 Quantitative analyses provided no evidence of an association between keeping ornamental
3990 fishes and scores on the standardised assessments; there was also no evidence that these
3991 relationships were influenced by the level of engagement between participants and their
3992 fishes. Very little research has examined the relationship between ornamental fish
3993 guardianship and loneliness and mental well-being (Clements et al., 2019), but these
3994 findings are in agreement with one study which examined the effects of adopting two
3995 goldfish on well-being among older adults; after six months no differences were found in
3996 loneliness, anxiety, leisure satisfaction, or happiness between the group who were given the
3997 goldfish and a no-treatment control (Riddick, 1985).

3998 Most participants rated ornamental fishes as having a positive impact on their well-being
3999 during the pandemic, but around a quarter appeared to feel indifferently and reported that
4000 their fishes had no effect. A likely explanation is that ornamental fishes are not viewed as
4001 companions in the same way as animals such as dogs and cats. Though some people who
4002 kept fishes felt they had bonded with their animals, many appreciated their home aquaria on
4003 a purely aesthetic level; watching fishes was an enjoyable and relaxing activity but provided
4004 little in the way of social or emotional support. Correspondingly, previous research found that
4005 many people who kept ornamental fishes associated them with benefits such as stress
4006 reduction, but 22% also viewed their home aquarium as 'room decoration' (Kidd and Kidd,
4007 1999). Physical touch was identified as an important aspect of the support provided by
4008 companion animals, a finding corroborated by other research conducted during the
4009 pandemic (Oliva and Johnston, 2020, Ratschen et al., 2020, Shoesmith et al., 2021). As
4010 fishes cannot interact with humans in a physical manner, it is therefore unsurprising that they

4011 were perceived as having a slightly less positive impact on the well-being of their guardians
4012 compared to other types of companion animals.

4013 However, some aspects of fishkeeping were perceived to have positively impacted well-
4014 being during the pandemic. The need to provide ongoing care, irrespective of animal type,
4015 helped participants maintain a normal routine and made them feel needed. The relaxing
4016 effect of watching home aquaria was also commonly cited as a benefit of keeping
4017 ornamental fishes, though no association was found between time spent watching fishes
4018 each day and outcomes relating to relaxation, such as stress or anxiety. Current evidence
4019 regarding the relaxing effects of fish aquaria is inconclusive; although studies have
4020 demonstrated results indicative of relaxation (Wells, 2005, Cracknell et al., 2016, Gee et al.,
4021 2019), others have failed to find evidence of an effect (DeSchraver and Riddick, 1990,
4022 Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003), and methodological issues make it difficult to draw firm
4023 conclusions (Clements et al., 2019). Furthermore, most studies finding positive results have
4024 assessed outcomes immediately after viewing an aquarium, with a lack of evidence
4025 regarding how any transient benefits of watching a fish tank may translate into longer-term
4026 effects on well-being. As it is evident from this study and past research (Kidd and Kidd,
4027 1999, Langfield and James, 2009) that people believe watching fishes promotes relaxation,
4028 further research is needed to determine the specific circumstances under which this
4029 relaxation is induced, and how this may relate to overall well-being among ornamental fish
4030 guardians.

4031 **5.5.4 Strengths and limitations**

4032 The mixed-methods design used in the current research provides a more complete
4033 understanding of the role that companion animals (and specifically, ornamental fishes)
4034 played in loneliness and mental well-being during the pandemic. Quantitative analysis is
4035 useful in summarising and comparing large quantities of data, but qualitative findings are
4036 needed to support the refinement of theory, and understand why interaction with companion
4037 animals may or may not influence well-being outcomes; despite this there is a lack of

4038 rigorous qualitative HAI research (Kazdin, 2017). While cross-sectional data showed no
4039 association between companion animal guardianship and loneliness or well-being,
4040 qualitative findings demonstrated that companion animal guardians believe such effects
4041 exist. Identifying the specific aspects of keeping companion animals that were beneficial
4042 during the pandemic allows researchers to develop and test more nuanced theories
4043 regarding the importance of companion animals in the lives of their humans. Furthermore,
4044 the use of semi-structured interviews provided a deeper insight into the experiences of
4045 companion animal guardians than could be achieved through open-ended survey questions
4046 alone. While preferably qualitative data analysis would be conducted collaboratively by two
4047 authors, this was not possible due to time constraints. However, the final report was
4048 reviewed by a second author familiar with the data to ensure that the dataset was accurately
4049 and fully represented.

4050 A cross-sectional design was used as the unprecedented nature of the pandemic precluded
4051 collection of baseline data. There were significant correlations between participants' ratings
4052 of how their loneliness and well-being had changed during the pandemic and their scores on
4053 the standardised assessments, suggesting that to some degree these scores captured how
4054 participants had been affected by the pandemic. However, these scores likely also reflected
4055 participants' levels of loneliness and mental well-being pre-pandemic. Some research has
4056 indicated that companion animal guardians may have poorer mental health than non-
4057 guardians (Parslow et al., 2005, Müllersdorf et al., 2010), so it is possible that no
4058 associations were found between companion animal guardianship and loneliness and
4059 mental well-being in the current study, because existing differences between the groups
4060 masked any protective effects of companion animal guardianship. A UK-based study
4061 conducted during the first lockdown found that companion animal guardians experienced
4062 less deterioration in well-being and smaller increases in loneliness than those without
4063 companion animals, but these differences were very small, and the authors cautioned

4064 against claiming that companion animals strongly protected against the negative
4065 consequences of the pandemic (Ratschen et al., 2020).

4066 Unlike other research conducted during the pandemic (Oliva and Johnston, 2020, Ratschen
4067 et al., 2020, Holland et al., 2021, Shoesmith et al., 2021), the current study was not
4068 conducted under strict lockdown conditions. Consequently, participants will have
4069 experienced greater variation in COVID-19-related restrictions than in other research. This
4070 may explain why the statistical models explained relatively little variation in participants'
4071 scores on the standardised assessments, despite accounting for a variety of demographic,
4072 social and lifestyle factors beyond companion animal guardianship. In particular, variation in
4073 employment status was reduced to a dichotomous variable, and it is possible that
4074 companion animal guardianship may have had differing influences for those whose
4075 employment was affected by the pandemic. Internet access was also required, which likely
4076 limited the number of older adults able to participate; as this population was at higher risk
4077 from COVID-19, different effects may have been identified if the sample contained more
4078 older adults. The study findings should therefore be interpreted in the context of the sample
4079 from which they were derived: predominantly white, female, residents in either the UK or
4080 USA, and quite highly educated relative to the general population.

4081 **5.5.5 Future considerations**

4082 It has been argued that the ways individuals engage with their companion animals may
4083 influence the relationship between companion animal guardianship and well-being (Barcelos
4084 et al., 2020, Rodriguez, Herzog and Gee, 2021), and there was evidence to support this in
4085 the current study. Further research is needed to consider which elements of HAI are most
4086 important for well-being, so they may be accounted for in data analysis; qualitative findings
4087 from this study and other research may be used to refine and test existing HAI theories to
4088 identify these elements.

4089 While the collection of pre-pandemic data was not possible for the current study, it may be
4090 possible to utilise existing data to compare pre- and post-pandemic effects of companion

4091 animal guardianship. Previously, data from large-scale longitudinal studies have been used
4092 to examine the impact of companion animal guardianship on well-being (Mueller, Gee and
4093 Bures, 2018). Where such studies have collected data pre- and post-pandemic, it may be
4094 possible to examine any longer-term influences of companion animal guardianship during
4095 the pandemic and beyond.

4096 Finally, further research is needed regarding the specific impact of ornamental fishes on
4097 well-being within the context of companion animal guardianship. To date, most research has
4098 focused on the shorter-term impacts of fish aquaria in a clinical or health care context
4099 (Clements et al., 2019), and while qualitative data from this and other research (Langfield
4100 and James, 2009) have suggested that watching fish aquaria can induce relaxation, there is
4101 no quantitative data to support this within the home environment. It is also unclear whether
4102 fish guardianship translates to longer-term effects on well-being, and whether certain
4103 populations experience greater or lesser benefits from their home aquaria. Future research
4104 should aim to address these gaps in the evidence.

4105 **5.5.6 Conclusions**

4106 In conclusion, there was no quantitative evidence that being a companion animal guardian
4107 was associated with less loneliness and greater mental well-being during the COVID-19
4108 pandemic, nor was this influenced by specific companion animal types (dogs, cats,
4109 ornamental fishes). There was some evidence that a greater level of engagement with dogs,
4110 and to a lesser extent cats, was associated with higher loneliness and poorer mental well-
4111 being, which may indicate that these individuals experienced higher levels of social isolation.
4112 Further research is needed to investigate this theory. Qualitative data indicated that
4113 companion animal guardians had experienced a range of benefits during the pandemic;
4114 these insights may be useful in refining theories regarding the impact of companion animals
4115 on human well-being. Negative aspects of companion animal guardianship during the
4116 pandemic typically related to animal welfare concerns, but a small number of participants
4117 had very negative experiences regarding the impact of their companion animals on their

4118 well-being. These experiences warrant further consideration, as they may shed light on
4119 conflicting findings within HAI research. Findings regarding ornamental fish guardians
4120 generally reflected those of companion animals more broadly, though there was evidence
4121 that a larger proportion held indifferent views regarding the impact of their companion
4122 animals on their well-being, and level of engagement with ornamental fishes was not
4123 associated with loneliness or well-being. More research is needed to understand the impact
4124 of ornamental fishes within the context of companion animal guardianship.

4125 **Chapter 6.**

4126 **Working from home: Are companion animals a**

4127 **benefit or a distraction?**

4128

4129 **6.1 Abstract**

4130 The COVID-19 pandemic led to a dramatic increase in the number of people working from
4131 home, meaning that it is now more important than ever to identify factors that promote well-
4132 being and productivity among remote workers. The presence of companion animals has
4133 been linked to positive outcomes including reduced stress and improved cognitive
4134 performance, thus, companion animal guardians may experience similar benefits when
4135 working from home with their companion animals. However, companion animals could also
4136 be harmful to productivity by creating an additional source of distraction. Therefore, the
4137 current study aimed to investigate the impact of companion animals on the well-being and
4138 productivity of people working from home. Companion animal guardians ($n = 35$) and non-
4139 guardians ($n = 31$) completed online assessments of perceived stress and working memory
4140 (digit span forward and backward) at three timepoints (start- middle- and end-of-day) during
4141 one day they worked from home; self-report assessments of frequency of being distracted,
4142 productivity, quality of work, adherence to guidelines regarding rest breaks, and home-to-
4143 work conflict were also completed at end-of-day. The responses of companion animal
4144 guardians and non-guardians were analysed using robust methods; a significant effect of
4145 time-of-day was found for perceived stress and scores for the digit span forward, but there
4146 was no evidence that companion animal guardianship status influenced these outcomes.
4147 Although 44% of guardians identified “animals in the home” as one of the top three sources
4148 of distraction they had experienced that day, there was no overall difference in self-reported
4149 frequency of being distracted between companion animal guardians and non-guardians.
4150 These findings suggest that companion animals are neither a benefit nor a distraction to
4151 people working from home. However, type of companion animal and level of engagement
4152 could not be considered in the current research, and fewer than half of guardians indicated
4153 that they spent most of their day in the company of their companion animal. Therefore, future
4154 research should consider whether greater levels of engagement with a companion animal
4155 lead to more positive outcomes.

4156 **6.2 Introduction**

4157 The COVID-19 pandemic and associated restrictions led to a sudden and dramatic increase
4158 in the number of people working from home. In the United Kingdom for example, around
4159 5.7% of employees reported working from home in the first two months of 2020, but by April
4160 the same year this figure had risen to around 43.1% (Felstead and Reuschke, 2020) with the
4161 majority of employees stating that they worked remotely during this time due to COVID-19
4162 (Office for National Statistics, 2020). This sudden shift followed a very gradual but increasing
4163 trend in the number of employees working from home (Felstead and Henseke, 2017).

4164 Although rates of homeworking fell with the easing of restrictions, at the time of writing they
4165 remained elevated compared to pre-pandemic levels, and many believed that higher levels
4166 of remote working will continue into the future (George et al., 2021).

4167 Research conducted both prior to and during the pandemic has demonstrated positive
4168 findings associated with remote working. For example, government employees were found
4169 to experience greater positive affect and lesser negative affect on days they worked from
4170 home compared to days at the office (Anderson, Kaplan and Vega, 2015), and a sample of
4171 employees in Belgium reported lower work-to-home conflict on teleworking versus non-
4172 teleworking days (Delanoëije, Verbruggen and Germeys, 2019). During lockdown, working
4173 from home was associated with greater well-being among public sector workers, although
4174 the same was not true of private sector workers so it is unclear whether this was due to
4175 factors related to remote working or because reduced face-to-face contact with clients
4176 helped to ameliorate anxiety around contracting the virus (Parent-Lamarche and Boulet,
4177 2021). In a systematic review of evidence, Charalampous et al. (2019) identified links
4178 between remote working and benefits such as more positive emotions, lesser feelings of
4179 emotional exhaustion, increased job satisfaction and greater organisational commitment. It
4180 has been argued that working from home provides a better work-life balance, allowing
4181 employees to more easily deal with home-related demands (Charalampous et al., 2019,
4182 Delanoëije, Verbruggen and Germeys, 2019).

4183 Despite increased autonomy regarding scheduling, however, those working remotely often
4184 work longer hours and their work was more intensive (Felstead and Henseke, 2017,
4185 Charalampous et al., 2019). Employees have also been found to experience more
4186 interruptions to home life after working hours on teleworking versus non-teleworking days
4187 (Delanoeije, Verbruggen and Germeys, 2019), perhaps indicating a blurring of boundaries
4188 when work is brought into the home (Charalampous et al., 2019, Delanoeije, Verbruggen
4189 and Germeys, 2019); such blurring of boundaries has been linked to increased emotional
4190 exhaustion leading to reduced happiness (Pluut and Wonders, 2020). There are also
4191 concerns around productivity when working remotely, with telework linked to a greater
4192 quantity of home-related interruptions during worktime (Delanoeije, Verbruggen and
4193 Germeys, 2019), and evidence showing that number of distractions was a predictor of
4194 productivity for those working from home (Russo et al., 2021). Furthermore, evidence
4195 suggests that people working from home experienced a greater increase in the number of
4196 non-work-related interruptions compared to work-related interruptions since the start of the
4197 pandemic (Leroy, Schmidt and Madjar, 2021). However, qualitative research suggests that
4198 remote workers feel the home is more conducive to concentration than the office, because
4199 the latter involves greater levels of socialising (Charalampous, Grant and Tramontano,
4200 2021).

4201 Given the massive shift towards remote working brought about by COVID-19, it is more
4202 crucial than ever to consider factors which may influence the well-being and productivity of
4203 individuals working from home; the presence of companion animals may be one such factor
4204 (Kelemen et al., 2020). As discussed in chapter one, numerous studies have identified a link
4205 between interaction with companion animals and improved human well-being. Furthermore,
4206 chapter three highlighted that these benefits may extend to the working environment, with
4207 the presence of companion animals linked to outcomes such as reduced stress, increased
4208 social interactions, the promotion of positive emotions and greater organisational
4209 identification among employees (Wells and Perrine, 2001a, Barker, 2005, Perrine and Wells,

4210 2006, Barker et al., 2012, Foreman et al., 2017, Hall et al., 2017, Junça-Silva, 2022). To
4211 understand how these effects may translate into the context of remote working, two
4212 theoretical mechanisms are considered: biophilia and social support.

4213 As outlined in chapter one, the biophilia hypothesis refers to the innate tendency of humans
4214 to attend to other forms of life (Wilson, 1984, Kellert and Wilson, 1993). Although criticised
4215 for being poorly defined, the concept of biophilia has provided the basis for more nuanced
4216 theories regarding the role of companion animals in human well-being. For example,
4217 because animals more readily attract human attention than do inanimate objects (New,
4218 Cosmides and Tooby, 2007, DeLoache, Bloom Pickard and LoBue, 2011, Lobue et al.,
4219 2013), it has been proposed that companion animals may support well-being by diverting
4220 attention away from negative experiences or emotional states (Beetz, 2017). Similarly, the
4221 “biophilia effect” theorises that the presence of calm or resting animals indicates an absence
4222 of threats in the environment, leading to reduced physiological arousal and increased
4223 feelings of relaxation (Julius et al., 2013, Beetz, 2017).

4224 Correspondingly, evidence suggests that briefly interacting with a friendly companion animal
4225 – usually a dog – may lead to improvements in outcomes such as perceived stress, anxiety
4226 and mood (Crossman, Kazdin and Knudson, 2015, Wheeler and Faulkner, 2015, Barker et
4227 al., 2016, Grajfoner et al., 2017, Banks, McCoy and Trzcinski, 2018, Pendry et al., 2018,
4228 Williams et al., 2018, Wood, Ohlsen, et al., 2018, Jones, Skolnick and Anderson, 2021).

4229 These brief interactions may also reduce physiological arousal (Allen et al., 1991, Allen,
4230 Blascovich and Mendes, 2002, Wood, Ohlsen, et al., 2018), although findings are less
4231 consistent with several studies finding no evidence of an effect (Straatman et al., 1997, Gee
4232 et al., 2014, Barker et al., 2016, Williams et al., 2018, Jones, Skolnick and Anderson, 2021).

4233 One study conducted within a pet-friendly workplace demonstrated that participants who
4234 took their dogs to work experienced a decrease in perceived, but not physiological, stress
4235 throughout the working day, whereas those who did not have dogs or left their dogs at home
4236 experienced an increase in levels of perceived stress (Barker et al., 2012). Thus, companion

4237 animal guardians working from home may experience lower levels of stress than non-
4238 guardians, as they have the opportunity to interact with their companion animals throughout
4239 their working day.

4240 Social support refers to the ways in which relationships with others can buffer against the
4241 negative effects of stress (Cohen and McKay, 1984), and higher levels of social support
4242 have been associated with greater well-being among remote workers (Charalampous et al.,
4243 2019, Russo et al., 2021). Evidence suggests that companion animals are providers of social
4244 support for their guardians (Beck and Madresh, 2008, Meehan, Massavelli and Pachana,
4245 2017), and qualitative findings from the previous chapter support this theory. Furthermore,
4246 evidence from experimental research suggests that this provision of social support from
4247 companion animals may positively influence cognitive performance (Allen, Shykoff and Izzo,
4248 2001, Gee et al., 2015), while stress reactivity and recovery in response to tasks requiring
4249 mental effort improved in the presence of companion animals (Allen et al., 1991, Allen,
4250 Blascovich and Mendes, 2002). Companion animals can also provide social support
4251 indirectly by acting as social catalysts (McNicholas and Collis, 2000, Wells, 2009a, Oliva and
4252 Johnston, 2020, Carr et al., 2021, Clements et al., 2021, Shoesmith et al., 2021); this may
4253 be particularly salient in the context of homeworking, as quality of communication was found
4254 to be an important factor in the well-being and performance of remote workers (Shockley et
4255 al., 2021). Companion animals may therefore, promote well-being and productivity among
4256 people working from home *via* the direct or indirect provision of social support.

4257 However, companion animals could be a source of distraction for people working from home
4258 (Kelemen et al., 2020). One drawback of taking dogs to work is that they may cause
4259 disruption (Wells and Perrine, 2001a), and as a higher frequency of distractions has been
4260 associated with reduced productivity among people working remotely (Russo et al., 2021),
4261 companion animal guardians may be less productive than their non-guardian counterparts.
4262 However, one study found that the majority of employees who take their dogs to work
4263 reported doing so was problem free (Norling and Keeling, 2010), so it is unclear whether

4264 companion animals are a major source of distraction. Furthermore, not all interruptions to
4265 work are negative; Puranik, Koopman and Vough (2021) identified that interruptions by
4266 colleagues had a social aspect that increased feelings of belongingness. Being interrupted
4267 by a companion animal may be similarly beneficial if considered in the context of the theories
4268 discussed above, by briefly diverting attention away from any negative emotions associated
4269 with work to promote more positive emotional states (Julius et al., 2013, Beetz, 2017).
4270 Additionally, it is recommended that people working from home take regular breaks to avoid
4271 the risks associated with sedentary lifestyles (Ricci et al., 2020) and using display screen
4272 equipment (Health and Safety Executive, 2022). The previous chapter identified that
4273 companion animals helped their guardians maintain routine and structure during the
4274 pandemic, a finding supported by other researchers (Shoesmith et al., 2021). Therefore,
4275 even where companion animals do distract their guardians from work, this may be beneficial
4276 if it encourages healthier work-from-home behaviours such as taking regular breaks.

4277 To date, only one study has examined the influence of companion animals on individuals
4278 working from home (Hoffman, 2021). Participants with experience of both working remotely
4279 and in the office completed a survey regarding their experiences. There was no evidence
4280 that companion animal guardians and non-guardians differed in terms of job-related affective
4281 well-being or workplace location preference, but dog guardians were more likely to report
4282 that work and home interfered with one another and that family members caused distractions
4283 on work-from-home days. Among companion animal guardians, those who kept cats were
4284 less likely, and those with both dogs and cats were more likely, to report their companion
4285 animal was a distraction while they worked from home. The findings of this study are useful
4286 in providing an initial insight into the impact of companion animals on individuals working
4287 from home. However, data were collected during June 2020 meaning that most participants
4288 were working from home fulltime when they completed the survey, and so their responses
4289 reflected their experiences of working from home during the pandemic and working in the
4290 office pre-pandemic; the author acknowledged that this introduced recall bias (Hoffman,

4291 2021). Furthermore, Hoffman (2021) considered only whether participants kept dogs and/or
4292 cats, so the impact of other companion animal types remains unclear.

4293 The present study aimed to further investigate the impact of companion animals on the well-
4294 being and productivity of individuals working from home. Assessments of perceived stress
4295 and working memory capacity were completed by both companion animal guardians and
4296 non-guardians at three timepoints (start-, middle- and end-of-day) on a single day they
4297 worked from home; responses were collected in the moment to avoid recall biases (Hoffman,
4298 2021). At end of day only, data were collected regarding participants' perceptions of their
4299 productivity, quality of work, adherence to recommendations regarding rest breaks, level of
4300 distraction, and home-to-work conflict across the day. At the time of study conception and
4301 data collection, COVID-19 remained a major health concern within the UK and so it was
4302 anticipated that a large proportion of the population would be working fully remotely.

4303 Therefore, data were collected only in relation to working from home, with comparisons
4304 drawn between guardians and non-guardians. As past research has highlighted lack of
4305 blinding as an issue within HAI research (Serpell et al., 2017, Friedmann and Gee, 2019),
4306 participants were not informed of the aims regarding companion animal guardianship until
4307 after they had completed the study.

4308 In line with previous research conducted in the workplace (Barker et al., 2012), it was
4309 hypothesised that there would be a significant interaction between companion animal
4310 guardianship and time-of-day for perceived stress. Specifically, perceived stress was
4311 predicted to decrease across the day for companion animal guardians but increase for non-
4312 guardians. Similarly, as previous research has shown that the presence of companion
4313 animals is linked to improved working memory (Gee et al., 2015), it was hypothesised that
4314 there would be a significant interaction between companion animal guardianship and time-
4315 of-day for working memory capacity, whereby performance would improve or remain stable
4316 for companion animal guardians but decrease for non-guardians. As companion animals
4317 create another potential source of distraction, it was predicted that guardians would report

4318 being significantly more distracted than non-guardians, and would experience significantly
4319 higher levels of home-to-work conflict. To examine whether these distractions were
4320 detrimental (harmful to productivity) or beneficial (encouraged healthier work habits),
4321 participants' perceptions regarding their productivity, quality of work, and adherence with
4322 recommendations around rest breaks were also assessed. Finally, qualitative data were
4323 collected from guardians and non-guardians to identify any additional benefits and
4324 disadvantages of working from home with companion animals, and data were collected
4325 regarding type of companion animals and level of engagement with dogs, cats, and fishes.

4326 **6.3 Methods**

4327 **6.3.1 Participants**

4328 Participants were an opportunity sample of UK-based individuals who worked from home on
4329 a regular basis (at least one day per week), including individuals who usually worked from
4330 home and those who had switched to remote working due to COVID-19. Individuals were
4331 eligible to participate if they were 18 years or older, fluent in the English language and based
4332 in the UK. Participants were required to have a desk-based job, but no further restrictions on
4333 job role or industry were applied. Both companion animal guardians and non-guardians were
4334 eligible to take part, and participants were blinded to the aims regarding companion animal
4335 guardianship until completion of the study. Recruitment was conducted *via* social media
4336 (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) accounts belonging to the researchers and their institution,
4337 and calls for participants were also sent out *via* email. All recipients were encouraged to
4338 forward the survey to their own social networks. Participants followed a link to a QuestionPro
4339 survey, where they were given participant information and provided informed consent before
4340 completing the study. After completing the study participants read a debriefing statement to
4341 fully inform them of the study aims and remind them of their right to withdraw. As a small
4342 incentive, participants had the opportunity to enter a prize draw to win a £100 Amazon gift
4343 voucher.

4344 *A priori* power analysis in G*Power (Faul et al., 2007) indicated that a minimum of 28
4345 participants were needed per group (companion animals vs. non-guardians) to detect a
4346 medium sized effect; the final sample ($n = 66$; 23-62 years, M age = 40.02 years, $SD =$
4347 10.76; $n = 51$ female, $n = 15$ male) consisted of 35 guardians and 31 non-guardians,
4348 although complete data were not available for all participants (see section 6.3.5 “Data
4349 analysis” for further details).

4350 **6.3.2 Design**

4351 A two-way, mixed quasi-experimental design was used to examine the influence of
4352 companion animal guardianship (yes vs. no) and time-of-day (start vs. middle vs. end) on
4353 perceived stress and working memory. The effect of companion animal guardianship was
4354 also examined for perceived productivity, perceived quality of work, engagement in rest
4355 breaks, frequency of distractions, and daily home-to-work conflict; these dependent variables
4356 were measured at end-of-day only.

4357 **6.3.3 Materials**

4358 *6.3.3.1 Pre-study questionnaire*

4359 A pre-study questionnaire was used to collect participants’ demographic information,
4360 specifically, their age, gender, ethnicity, marital status, whether they had any children under
4361 16 years, whether they kept any pets⁷, their UK domicile, occupational category, and details
4362 of their working from home arrangements. This questionnaire also included the 10-item
4363 version of the Perceived Stress Scale (Cohen and Williamson, 1988) to measure stress at
4364 baseline; this scale has been used extensively in research and has adequate reliability and
4365 validity (Lee, 2012). Participants responded to 10 items (e.g. “In the last month, how often
4366 have you felt difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?”) on a
4367 scale from 0 = “Never” to 4 = “Very often”. Total scores were calculated by reverse scoring

⁷The term “pets” was used over “companion animals” as, while the latter is preferred in the academic literature, the former was anticipated to be more familiar to participants. As participants were blind to the true aims of the study the decision was made to use the more familiar term only, to avoid the potential of alerting participants to these aims.

4368 negatively worded items and summing all responses, so that a higher score indicated a
4369 higher level of stress (min = 0, max = 40, Cronbach's α = 0.88). Work protection preference
4370 and home protection preference, the extent to which an individual prefers to keep their work
4371 life free of home-related interruptions and *vice versa* (Methot and LePine, 2016), were
4372 assessed as in Delanoeije, Verbruggen and Germeys (2019) using scales developed by
4373 Methot and LePine (2016) and Kreiner (2006). For each scale, participants responded to
4374 four items (e.g. "I don't like thinking about non-work issues while I am at work" or "I prefer to
4375 keep work life at work") on a 7-point scale from 1 = "Strongly disagree" to 7 = "Strongly
4376 agree". Total scores were calculated by summing responses for all items so that a higher
4377 score indicated a stronger work or home protection preference (min = 7, max = 28 for each
4378 scale, Cronbach's α = 0.82-0.88).

4379 6.3.3.2 *Main study assessments*

4380 The main study comprised assessments of perceived stress and working memory conducted
4381 at three time points during one working day. Perceived stress was measured using digital
4382 visual analogue scales; participants were asked to indicate how much stress they felt "right
4383 now at this moment" by clicking on a straight horizontal line with the anchors "None" and
4384 "The most severe imaginable". Visual analogue scales have been used extensively in
4385 research to measure subjective experiences and are established as a reliable and valid
4386 technique (McCormack, Horne and Sheather, 1988); evidence also indicates there are no
4387 differences between responses made using paper or digital versions (Delgado et al., 2018,
4388 Escalona-Marfil et al., 2020). They were chosen for this study due to speed and ease of
4389 completion, so as to minimise participant burden. Working memory was assessed using digit
4390 span tasks; participants were presented with a list of digits (e.g. "8, 9, 3") and required to
4391 repeat them back immediately. If successful on two out of three trials, the length of the list
4392 was increased by one digit (e.g. "3, 5, 1, 8") until the participant failed to correctly recall a list
4393 of that length on two out of three trials. The list was recalled in the same order it was
4394 presented for the digit span forward, and in the reverse order for the digit span backwards

4395 (e.g. “8, 9, 3” as “3, 9, 8”), with a participant’s digit span being the length of the longest list
4396 they correctly recalled. Digit span tasks are a commonly used measure of working memory
4397 capacity in experimental research (Ohly et al., 2016).

4398 6.3.3.3 *Post-study questionnaire*

4399 The final component was a post-study questionnaire, completed at the end of the working
4400 day. Participants confirmed the number of hours they had worked that day, then responded
4401 to four digital visual analogue scales to assess their perceived levels of productivity (“Not at
4402 all productive” to “The most productive I could have been”), the perceived quality of their
4403 work (“Lowest quality” to “Highest quality”), the extent to which they agreed that they had
4404 adhered to guidance around rest breaks for users of display screen equipment (“Do not
4405 agree at all” to “Agree very much”), and how often they felt that they had been distracted
4406 from their work (“Not at all distracted” to “Distracted extremely often”). They then selected
4407 their top three sources of distraction from a list of potential distractions (e.g. “Other adults
4408 living in my house”, “Animals living in my house”, “Social media”). Home-to-work conflict, the
4409 extent to which work activities were interrupted by home-related issues during work time,
4410 was then assessed using an adapted version of the Work-Family Conflict Scale (Carlson,
4411 Kacmar and Williams, 2000) as in Delanoëije, Verbruggen and Germeys (2019). This scale
4412 consisted of four items (e.g. “Today, because I was stressed from responsibilities at home, I
4413 had a hard time concentrating on my work”); participants responded to on a scale from 1 =
4414 “Strongly disagree” to 7 = “Strongly agree” and scores were calculated by summing all items
4415 so that a higher score indicated greater home-to-work conflict (min = 7, max = 28,
4416 Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.73$). Participants then indicated whether there were any other people
4417 present in their home during their working hours (grouped into adults, young adults 17-18
4418 years, children 12-16 years, children 5-11 years, and children under 5 years), and if so, how
4419 long these individuals were present (more or less than half of the working day). Two open-
4420 ended questions were used to obtain qualitative data about the benefits and disadvantages
4421 of remote working.

4422 The final section of the post-study questionnaire focused on companion animal
4423 guardianship. Participants first indicated whether they kept dogs, cats, fishes, other
4424 companion animals, or had no pets. Those with dogs, cats or fishes then responded to
4425 further questions regarding how often they had interacted with each type of companion
4426 animal during their working day, inclusive of breaks (measured using digital visual analogue
4427 scales anchored with “Not at all” to “Extremely often”), and where that pet was located for
4428 most of the day (in the same room, elsewhere in the house, outside the house); participants
4429 with dogs also indicated whether they usually had the option to take their dogs to the office.
4430 Finally, two open ended questions asked about the benefits and disadvantages of working
4431 from home specifically with regards to companion animal guardianship; non-guardians were
4432 asked what they thought these benefits and disadvantages may be to gain an insight into
4433 whether perceptions of working from home with companion animals reflected actual
4434 experiences.

4435 Copies of the pre-study questionnaire, main study assessments and post-study
4436 questionnaire are provided in Appendix J.

4437 **6.3.4 Procedure**

4438 Ethical approval for this research was obtained from the School of Health and Life Sciences
4439 ethics committee at the University of the West of Scotland (Ref: 13562, Appendix F) and the
4440 Mars Research Review Board. Data were collected from April to October 2021. To enrol in
4441 the study, participants followed a link to a QuestionPro survey where they were provided
4442 with participant information and gave informed consent. Using the same platform,
4443 participants then completed the pre-study questionnaire as described in section 6.3.3.1.
4444 Participants were also asked to provide an email address where they could be contacted
4445 about the research, and after completing the questionnaire, received an email with
4446 instructions on how to complete the remainder of the study. These instructions stated that
4447 participants should complete the study on the next day they worked from home; the start-of-
4448 day assessments were to be completed immediately before commencing their workday, the

4449 midday assessments in the middle of their workday, ideally just before their lunch break (or
4450 equivalent), and the end-of-day assessments immediately after they finished work. The post-
4451 study questionnaire could be completed up until midnight that day, but participants were
4452 advised to complete it as soon as possible after the end-of-day assessments.

4453 The main study assessments were created using the open-source software PsychoPy
4454 (Peirce et al., 2019) and hosted on pavlovia.org. Each set of assessments followed the same
4455 procedure. Participants followed the relevant link from their instruction email, were presented
4456 with a brief description of the assessments, and proceeded by pressing any key. They then
4457 completed the assessment for perceived stress by clicking the relevant point on the visual
4458 analogue scale (see section 6.3.3.2 for further details). Instructions for the digit span forward
4459 were then presented, after which participants completed three practice trials; this was
4460 reduced to two practice trials for the midday and end-of-day assessments to reduce
4461 participant burden. After the practice trials, participants were reminded of the instructions
4462 and then completed the task for real. Each trial consisted of a fixation point (+) presented for
4463 one second, followed by a series of digits presented on-screen one at a time. Participants
4464 then saw a screen instructing them to “Recall” the digits and responded by typing them into
4465 their keyboard and pressing enter. Feedback (“correct” vs. “incorrect”) was presented for one
4466 second after each trial, after which the fixation returned. The tasks began with strings three
4467 digits in length, increasing by one digit each time the participant correctly responded to two
4468 strings of the same length, up to a maximum of 12 digits. If the participant failed to respond
4469 correctly to two out of three strings of the same length, the task ended. This procedure was
4470 then repeated for the digit span backward, with the only difference being that participants
4471 were required to recall the digits in the reverse order.

4472 After completing the digit span backward participants were given instructions reminding them
4473 when to complete the next component of the study; after the end-of-day assessments they
4474 were automatically redirected to the post-study questionnaire in QuestionPro (see section
4475 6.3.3.3 for further details), but were able to complete this up until midnight that day by

4476 following the link in their instruction email. Participants who completed the start-of-day
4477 assessments received reminder emails at approximately 11am and 4pm to remind them to
4478 complete the midday and end-of-day assessments, and received a reminder email for the
4479 post-study questionnaire if this had not been completed by 6pm. Following the post-study
4480 questionnaire, participants were provided with the debriefing statement.

4481 To reduce attrition, participants who completed the pre-study questionnaire but did not
4482 complete the remaining study components received a reminder email one week after
4483 enrolling in the study. After a further week of non-completion they were withdrawn by the
4484 researcher. Where participants completed one or more sets of assessments but not the
4485 post-study questionnaire, they were invited to restart the study the next day they worked
4486 from home. If this was not completed within one week, participants who had only completed
4487 the start-of-day assessments were withdrawn, and those who had completed two or more
4488 sets of assessments were emailed the debriefing statement and their data were retained. If
4489 participants missed one or more assessments but completed the post-study questionnaire,
4490 their incomplete data were retained as they had received the debriefing information and
4491 were no longer blind to the aims of the study.

4492 **6.3.5 Data analysis**

4493 *6.3.5.1 Data management*

4494 There were 161 complete responses to the pre-study questionnaire; 95 participants (59%)
4495 completed no further study components and were withdrawn from the study. Of the 66
4496 participants who finished the study, complete data were available for 44 participants (67%).
4497 Fifty-four participants (82%) completed assessments at all three time points, but nine of
4498 these did not complete the digit span backward on at least one occasion. Sixty-one
4499 participants (92%) completed the post-study questionnaire. Companion animal guardianship
4500 status was assessed in both the pre-study and post-study questionnaires, and four
4501 participants provided incongruent responses to these questions. One clarified that they were
4502 dog-sitting for a relative on the day they completed the study; the remaining three reported

4503 keeping dogs ($n = 1$) and fishes ($n = 2$). It is not clear why these participants provided
4504 divergent responses. One possibility is that they adopted new companion animals after
4505 completion of the pre-study questionnaire but before completion of the post-study
4506 questionnaire. Therefore, the latter response was used to assign companion animal
4507 guardianship status as it reflected their guardianship status on the day they completed the
4508 study assessments.

4509 *6.3.5.2 Sample characteristics*

4510 All statistical analyses were conducted using *R* version 4.1.1 (R Core Team, 2021).
4511 Differences in categorical demographic variables between companion animal guardians and
4512 non-guardians were examined using Pearson's chi-square tests *via* the package *gmodels*
4513 (Warnes et al., 2018); where assumptions were violated (minimum expected frequencies <5)
4514 Fisher's exact tests were instead conducted. Due to deviations from normality and the
4515 presence of outliers, continuous demographic variables were analysed using robust between
4516 groups procedures *via* the package *WRS* (Wilcox and Schönbrodt, 2014); all analyses
4517 utilised 20% trimmed means and bootstrapped samples ($n = 2000$).

4518 *6.3.5.3 Main analyses*

4519 To examine whether companion animal guardianship was associated with differences in
4520 well-being and productivity among people working from home, separate analyses were
4521 conducted for each of the dependent variables. Assumptions of the general linear model
4522 were assessed *via* inspection of boxplots, histograms, Q-Q plots, the Shapiro-Wilk test of
4523 normality and Levene's test of homogeneity of variance. In all cases, assumptions were
4524 violated due to deviations from normality and/or the presence of outliers, and so robust
4525 procedures were used (Field and Wilcox, 2017).

4526 Ratings of perceived stress and scores for the digit span tasks were analysed using robust
4527 linear mixed models *via* the package *robustlmm* (Koller, 2016); this allowed for maximum
4528 data retention in the presence of missing data. All analyses included participant as a random
4529 factor to account for each participant being assessed at multiple time points. Companion

4530 animal guardianship, time-of-day, and the interaction between these two variables were
4531 entered as fixed factors. Significance was determined by calculating 95% Wald confidence
4532 intervals; where the interval did not cross zero the effect was considered statistically
4533 significant at $p < 0.05$. Analyses were conducted using all available data, with sensitivity
4534 analyses also conducted for the subset of participants who provided complete data for each
4535 outcome.

4536 The remaining dependent variables (ratings of productivity, quality of work, engagement in
4537 rest breaks and frequency of distractions, plus scores for home-to-work conflict) were
4538 measured at only one timepoint, and so analyses included all available data. Pairwise
4539 correlations with Holm corrected alpha levels were conducted to examine the relationships
4540 between each of these variables; Kendall's Tau-b was used as data did not meet parametric
4541 assumptions. Robust between-groups procedures were then conducted *via* the package
4542 *WRS* (Wilcox and Schönbrodt, 2014) to identify any differences between companion animal
4543 guardians and non-guardians; these analyses utilised 20% trimmed means with
4544 bootstrapped samples ($n = 2000$).

4545 To further examine whether companion animals were a source of distraction for individuals
4546 working from home, in the post-study questionnaire participants were asked to indicate the
4547 main sources of distraction they had experienced that day. They selected up to three
4548 choices from a list of potential distractions, with the option to identify 'other' distractions that
4549 were not listed. Multilevel logistic regression was conducted *via* the package *lme4* (Bates et
4550 al., 2015) to examine whether these top three sources of distraction differed between
4551 companion animal guardians and non-guardians. Three models were compared using the
4552 likelihood ratio test: a null model containing only participant as a random factor, a model
4553 including distraction type (other adults, children, personal issues, social media, colleagues,
4554 work-related issues, friends or family, neighbours, current events, other), and a model
4555 including the interaction between distraction type and companion animal guardianship

4556 status. “Animals in the home” was not included as a distractor type as this was only
4557 applicable to companion animal guardians.

4558 *6.3.5.4 Companion animal type and level of engagement*

4559 Data regarding companion animal type and level of engagement were also collected.
4560 However, owing to the small number of participants who completed the study and provided
4561 complete data, there was insufficient power to explore the effects of companion animal type
4562 and level of engagement on the dependent variables. As these data provide an insight into
4563 the ways in which individuals working from home interact with their companion animals,
4564 descriptive statistics are reported so that they may inform future research.

4565 *6.3.5.5 Qualitative analyses*

4566 Open-ended survey questions were used to collect qualitative data about the benefits and
4567 disadvantages of working from home. As participants provided these data while blind to the
4568 aims of the study, any mention of companion animals within these data are representative of
4569 participants’ opinions and experiences free from the biases typically associated with
4570 companion animal guardianship research. Two researchers (HC and KS) manually searched
4571 these data for occurrences of words relating to companion animals (e.g. “pet”, “dog”, “cat”,
4572 “fish”). This was intended to be the first stage of a summative content analysis, however,
4573 there were an insufficient number of occurrences for further analysis and so only the
4574 frequency of occurrences and their content is reported.

4575 Data were also collected regarding the benefits and disadvantages of working from home
4576 specifically in relation to companion animals, with non-guardians asked to state their beliefs
4577 about possible benefits and disadvantages. These data were analysed using a combination
4578 of conventional and summative content analysis (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005); this approach
4579 was based upon that employed by previous research (e.g. Berlin et al., 2020, Brown et al.,
4580 2020). All data were first subject to conventional content analysis. Following familiarisation,
4581 these data were coded using an inductive approach whereby the researcher coded openly
4582 for all benefits and disadvantages identified by participants. This was an iterative process,

4583 with the researcher revisiting previously coded data items as new codes were identified in
4584 the data. Once all data were coded, these codes were organised into categories by grouping
4585 codes with related content. Finally definitions of each category were developed. The analysis
4586 was conducted by one researcher (HC) and a second researcher (KS) read the entire
4587 dataset to confirm accuracy of the analysis.

4588 In the second stage, data were subject to summative content analysis. Categories identified
4589 in stage one were applied using a deductive coding approach, with two researchers (HC and
4590 KS) independently coding each data item for the presence or absence of content related to
4591 each category. Inter-rater reliability analysis indicated that agreement after first coding
4592 ranged from substantial to almost perfect ($K = 0.64 - 0.95$, $p < 0.001$ in all cases), with one
4593 category showing perfect agreement. Discussion of disagreements identified overlap
4594 between two categories which were therefore combined; a third category was renamed to
4595 better reflect the intended content. It was also agreed that where a participant's response did
4596 not explicitly state whether an aspect of companion animal guardianship was beneficial or
4597 disadvantageous, this would be interpreted within the context of the question (i.e. whether it
4598 asked specifically about benefits or disadvantages). After all disagreements were resolved,
4599 the percentage of participants who made reference to each benefit and disadvantage was
4600 calculated for guardians of specific animal types (dogs, cats, fishes) to provide an insight into
4601 whether occurrences of these categories were similar across different types of companion
4602 animal. As some participants kept multiple companion animal types, where it was not
4603 possible to determine the type of animal to which they referred, their data were not included
4604 in these summaries. Percentages were also calculated for all companion animal guardians
4605 collectively and for non-guardians, to examine whether non-guardian expectations about the
4606 benefits and disadvantages of working from home with companion animals were reflective of
4607 the experiences reported by guardians.

4608 **6.4 Results**

4609 **6.4.1 Sample characteristics**

4610 The sample ($n = 66$) was predominantly white (95%), female (77%), married or co-habiting
 4611 (79%) and had no children (73%); a large proportion were in professional occupations (61%)
 4612 and worked from home always or most days (95%). Thirty-five participants (53%) were
 4613 companion animal guardians. Data on type of companion animal were available for 32
 4614 participants; 16 (46%) kept dogs, 14 (40%) kept cats, six (17%) kept fishes, and five (14%)
 4615 kept “other” companion animals, which included rabbits ($n = 2$), leopard geckos ($n = 1$),
 4616 chickens and a horse ($n = 1$), and one participant who was dog-sitting for a relative on the
 4617 day they completed the study. Seven participants (20%) kept a mix of companion animal
 4618 types. No significant differences were identified between companion animal guardians and
 4619 non-guardians for any demographic variables, or for work protection preference, home
 4620 protection preference or scores on the Perceived Stress Scale (see Table 6.1).

4621 **Table 6.1 Sample characteristics by companion animal guardianship status**

	Companion animal guardians ($n = 35$)	Non- guardians ($n = 31$)	p	Total ($n = 66$)
Age in years	41.51 \pm 10.09	38.32 \pm 11.39	0.154	40.02 \pm 10.76
Gender				
Female	26 (74%)	25 (81%)	0.538	51 (77%)
Male	9 (26%)	6 (19%)		15 (23%)
Ethnicity				
White	34 (97%)	29 (94%)	0.731	63 (95%)
Black or Black British	0	1 (3%)		1 (2%)
Mixed or multiple ethnicities	1 (3%)	1 (3%)		2 (3%)
UK region				
England	17 (49%)	16 (52%)	>0.999	33 (50%)
Scotland	17 (49%)	15 (48%)		32 (49%)
Wales	1 (3%)	0		1 (2%)

Marital status				
Married	21 (60%)	11 (35%)	0.178	32 (49%)
Co-habiting	7 (20%)	13 (42%)		20 (30%)
Divorced	3 (9%)	2 (7%)		5 (8%)
Single	4 (11%)	4 (13%)		8 (12%)
Other	0	1 (3%)		1 (2%)
Children under 16 years				
Yes	10 (29%)	8 (26%)	0.801	18 (27%)
No	25 (71%)	23 (74%)		48 (73%)
Occupation				
Manager, director or senior official	6 (17%)	2 (7%)	0.395	8 (12%)
Professional	17 (49%)	23 (74%)		40 (61%)
Associate professional or technical	3 (9%)	3 (10%)		6 (9%)
Administrative or secretarial	5 (14%)	2 (7%)		7 (11%)
Elementary	1 (3%)	0		1 (2%)
Sales and customer service	2 (6%)	1 (3%)		3 (5%)
Prefer not to say	1 (3%)	0		1 (2%)
Remote working pre-COVID-19				
Yes	23 (66%)	18 (58%)	0.523	41 (62%)
No	12 (34%)	13 (42%)		25 (38%)
Current frequency of remote working				
Once a week	1 (3%)	0	0.227	1 (2%)
A few times a week	2 (6%)	0		2 (3%)
Most days	8 (23%)	4 (13%)		12 (18%)
Always	24 (69%)	27 (87%)		51 (77%)
Type of working hours				
Fixed	13 (37%)	14 (45%)	0.456	27 (41%)
Flexible	22 (63%)	16 (52%)		38 (58%)
Prefer not to say	0	1 (3%)		1 (2%)
Perceived Stress Scale	25.40 ± 5.69	26.74 ± 5.69	0.401	26.03 ± 6.97
Work Protection Preference	19.51 ± 5.38	17.71 ± 4.41	0.294	18.67 ± 4.99
Home Protection Preference	22.63 ± 5.18	23.03 ± 5.01	0.817	22.82 ± 5.07

4622 Note: categorical variables were analysed using Pearson's chi-square tests, or Fisher's
4623 exact tests where minimum expected frequencies were <5; data reported are frequencies
4624 and percentages. Continuous variables were analysed using robust between groups
4625 analyses (Wilcox and Schönbrodt, 2014); data reported are means ± standard deviations.

4626 **6.4.2 Main analyses**

4627 The primary aim of the study was to determine whether companion animals could positively
4628 influence the well-being and productivity of individuals working from home. Robust linear
4629 mixed models identified no significant effects of companion animal guardianship for ratings
4630 of perceived stress or for performance on either of the digit span tasks, and the interaction
4631 between companion animal guardianship and time-of-day was not significant for any variable
4632 (95% confidence intervals crossed zero in all cases). However, there was a significant main
4633 effect of time-of-day on participants' ratings of their perceived stress (Figure 6.1); ratings at
4634 midday and end-of-day were significantly higher than those at start-of-day, indicating a
4635 higher level of stress. There was also a significant effect of time-of-day for performance on
4636 the digit span forward (Figure 6.2); scores at midday were significantly higher than at start-
4637 of-day indicating improved performance, but this effect was not retained at end-of-day. No
4638 evidence of an effect of time-of-day was found for the digit span backward (Figure 6.3). The
4639 same pattern of results was obtained when analysing all available data, and for sensitivity
4640 analyses including only the subset of participants who provided complete data for each
4641 outcome (Table 6.2).

4642 Figure 6.1 Boxplots showing ratings of perceived stress by companion animal guardianship
 4643 status and time-of-day. Asterisk (*) denotes significance at $p < 0.05$, as determined by 95%
 4644 confidence intervals not crossing zero. Data are mean (black circles), median, and
 4645 interquartile range. Companion animal guardians $n = 29$, non-guardians $n = 25$.

4646 Figure 6.2 Boxplots showing scores for digit span forward by companion animal
 4647 guardianship status and time-of-day. Asterisk (*) denotes significance at $p < 0.05$, as
 4648 determined by 95% confidence intervals not crossing zero; "ns" denotes non-significance.
 4649 Data are mean (black circles), median, interquartile range and outliers (white circles).
 4650 Companion animal guardians $n = 29$, non-guardians $n = 25$.

4651 Figure 6.3 Boxplots showing scores for digit span backward by companion animal
 4652 guardianship status and time-of-day. "ns" denotes non-significance at $p < 0.05$ as
 4653 determined by 95% confidence intervals crossing zero. Data are mean (black circles),
 4654 median, interquartile range and outliers (white circles). Companion animal guardians $n = 24$,
 4655 non-guardians $n = 21$.
 4656

Table 6.2 Results of robust linear mixed models for ratings of perceived stress and scores on the digit span tasks

	All available data				Complete data only			
	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	Lower 95%CI	Upper 95%CI	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	Lower 95%CI	Upper 95%CI
Perceived stress	Total <i>n</i> = 65; Guardians <i>n</i> = 35; Non-guardians <i>n</i> = 30				Total <i>n</i> = 54, Guardians <i>n</i> = 29, Non-guardians <i>n</i> = 25			
Companion animal guardian (vs. non-guardian)	0.97	6.06	-10.91	12.85	2.18	6.71	-10.98	15.33
Midday (vs. start-of-day)	7.58	2.84	2.00	13.15	7.06	3.20	0.78	13.33
End-of-day (vs. start-of-day)	7.13	2.92	1.40	12.86	7.34	3.20	1.07	13.62
Companion animal guardian, midday (vs. non-guardian, start-of-day)	-0.88	3.87	-8.46	6.70	-0.15	4.37	-8.71	8.42
Companion animal guardian, end-of-day (vs. non-guardian, start-of-day)	-2.48	3.99	-10.30	5.35	-2.30	4.37	-10.86	6.26
Digit span forward	Total <i>n</i> = 64, Guardians <i>n</i> = 34, Non-guardians <i>n</i> = 30				Total <i>n</i> = 54, Guardians <i>n</i> = 29, Non-guardians <i>n</i> = 25			
Companion animal guardian (vs. non-guardian)	0.04	0.35	-0.63	0.71	0.11	0.36	-0.59	0.80
Midday (vs. start-of-day)	0.64	0.25	0.15	1.13	0.63	0.27	0.11	1.15
End-of-day (vs. start-of-day)	0.34	0.26	-0.16	0.84	0.28	0.27	-0.24	0.81
Companion animal guardian, midday (vs. non-guardian, start-of-day)	-0.43	0.34	-1.10	0.25	-0.37	0.36	-1.08	0.34
Companion animal guardian, end-of-day (vs. non-guardian, start-of-day)	-0.16	0.35	-0.85	0.53	-0.14	0.36	-0.85	0.57
Digit span backwards	Total <i>n</i> = 64, Guardians <i>n</i> = 34, Non-guardians <i>n</i> = 30				Total <i>n</i> = 45, Guardians <i>n</i> = 24, Non-guardians <i>n</i> = 21			
Companion animal guardian (vs. non-guardian)	-0.65	0.38	-1.38	0.09	-0.45	0.46	-1.35	0.44
Midday (vs. start-of-day)	0.28	0.30	-0.30	0.86	0.28	0.36	-0.42	0.98
End-of-day (vs. start-of-day)	0.14	0.30	-0.45	0.74	0.12	0.36	-0.58	0.82
Companion animal guardian, midday (vs. non-guardian, start-of-day)	0.09	0.41	-0.71	0.88	0.20	0.49	-0.76	1.15
Companion animal guardian, end-of-day (vs. non-guardian, start-of-day)	0.40	0.41	-0.42	1.21	0.39	0.49	-0.57	1.35

Note: *b* are unstandardised regression coefficients, results in bold are significant as determined by 95% confidence intervals not crossing zero.

4659 The remaining variables were measured at one time point only (end-of-day); descriptive
 4660 statistics are given in Table 6.3. Pairwise correlations indicated that perceived frequency of
 4661 distractions had a moderate negative correlation with perceived productivity ($\tau_b = -0.35, p <$
 4662 0.05), and a moderate positive correlation with home-to-work conflict ($\tau_b = 0.39, p < 0.05$).
 4663 Perceived productivity also had a strong positive correlation with perceived quality of work (τ_b
 4664 $= 0.60, p < 0.01$); no further significant correlations were detected. Results of the robust
 4665 between-groups procedures identified no significant effects of companion animal
 4666 guardianship for participants' ratings of the frequency with which they had been distracted
 4667 from their work ($Y_t = 1.35, p = 0.162$), their productivity ($Y_t = 0.46, p = 0.628$) or the quality of
 4668 their work ($Y_t = 1.63, p = 0.097$), the extent to which they agreed they had complied with
 4669 guidance around taking rest breaks when using display screen equipment ($Y_t = 0.34, p =$
 4670 0.724), or their scores for home-to-work conflict ($Y_t = 0.86, p = 0.375$).

4671 **Table 6.3 Descriptive statistics for dependent variables measured at end-of-day only**

	Companion animal guardians ($n = 32$)			Non-guardians ($n = 29$)			Total ($n = 61$)		
	M	SD	M_t	M	SD	M_t	M	SD	M_t
Frequency of distractions	43.00	24.10	41.35	51.86	22.91	52.21	47.21	23.77	46.68
Productivity	62.75	18.86	64.4	58.62	23.23	61.63	60.79	20.98	63.46
Quality of work	73.81	19.27	75.50	62.86	23.20	64.74	68.61	21.76	71.03
Engagement in rest breaks	45.34	28.62	45.15	50.79	34.62	49.11	47.93	31.46	46.11
Home-to-work conflict	7.57	4.35	6.40	8.57	5.08	7.53	8.05	4.70	6.89

4672 Note: M = mean, SD = standard deviation and M_t = 20% trimmed means

4673 To further examine whether companion animals were a source of distraction for individuals
 4674 working from home, in the post-study questionnaire participants were asked to identify the
 4675 top three sources of distraction they had experienced that day. All participants identified at
 4676 least one source of distraction. Multilevel logistic regression indicated that the inclusion of
 4677 distraction type significantly improved model fit compared to the null model ($\chi^2(9) = 90.41, p$

4678 < 0.001). Pairwise comparisons showed that the odds of selecting “work-related issues” as a
 4679 top three source of distraction were significantly higher than for all other distraction types
 4680 (OR = 3.38-27.14, $p < 0.05$ in all cases), and the odds of selecting “other adults in the home”
 4681 or “social media” were both significantly higher than selecting either “friends or family” or
 4682 “neighbours” (OR = 6.95-8.04, $p < 0.05$ in all cases). No further differences were detected
 4683 between the odds of selecting each distraction type (Figure 6.4). Addition of the distraction
 4684 type by companion animal guardianship status interaction did not result in a significant
 4685 improvement in model fit ($\chi^2(10) = 13.91, p = 0.177$), indicating that the top three sources of
 4686 distraction reported by participants did not differ by their companion animal guardianship
 4687 status.

4688 Figure 6.4 Number of companion animal guardians and non-guardians who selected each
 4689 source of distraction to be among their top three; different letters denote a significant
 4690 difference in the odds of being chosen across types of distraction where shared letters
 4691 denote no significant difference. There was no evidence of a significant interaction between
 4692 distraction type and companion animal guardianship status.

4693 Although “animals in the home” was not included in the model, they were reported as one of
4694 the top three sources of distraction by 44% of guardians ($n = 14$). All those who identified
4695 companion animals as a source of distraction kept dogs ($n = 10$) and/or cats ($n = 6$), with
4696 one participant keeping fishes in addition to dogs.

4697 **6.4.3 Companion animal type and level of engagement**

4698 Dog, cat, and fish guardians provided data regarding the level of engagement they had with
4699 their companion animals throughout their working day. Of the dog guardians who provided
4700 these data, 43% ($n = 6$) reported that their companion animal spent most of the day in the
4701 same room as themselves, whereas 50% ($n = 7$) reported their dog spent most of the day in
4702 a different room; a similar pattern was observed for cats ($n = 5$, 42% in same room; $n = 6$,
4703 50% in different room). One dog guardian and one cat guardian reported that their
4704 companion animal spent most of the day outside. No fish guardians reported that their fish
4705 tank was located in the same room in which they were working; four (80%) reported that the
4706 tank was in a different room and one reported that the fishes were outside in a pond.
4707 Reported levels of engagement with companion animals during the day reflected these
4708 findings; mean ratings of engagement suggested that dog ($M = 44.5$, $SD = 33.24$, $n = 14$)
4709 and cat ($M = 58.33$, $SD = 26.80$, $n = 12$) guardians spent more time interacting with their
4710 companion animals than fish guardians ($M = 6.00$, $SD = 10.39$, $n = 5$). However, owing to
4711 the small sample sizes for each group it was not possible to analyse these data using
4712 inferential statistics.

4713 **6.4.4 Qualitative analyses**

4714 Six participants made explicit reference to companion animals when reporting the general
4715 benefits of working from home. These benefits included having more time or opportunity to
4716 interact with their companion animals ($n = 4$), and the positive effects of interacting with
4717 companion animals during breaks from work ($n = 2$). No references were made to
4718 companion animals when reporting the general disadvantages of working from home.

4719 Conventional content analysis of data relating to the benefits and disadvantages of working
4720 from home with companion animals led to the development of eight categories, shown in
4721 Table 6.4. These consisted of five benefit categories (positive mental health, routine
4722 maintenance and prompting breaks from work, benefits for the companion animal, financial
4723 benefits, and no benefits) and three disadvantage categories (negative disruption from work,
4724 disadvantages for the companion animal, and no disadvantages). Summative content
4725 analysis was conducted to identify the percentage of participants who made reference to
4726 each category; percentages were calculated for companion animal guardians, non-
4727 guardians, and guardians of specific animal types (dogs, cats, fishes) and are shown in
4728 Table 6.5. The opinions of non-guardians were included to examine whether their
4729 expectations regarding the impact of companion animals on people working from home
4730 reflected the experiences of companion animal guardians.

4731 A larger proportion of dog guardians, compared to cat guardians or fish guardians, felt that
4732 working from home was beneficial for their companion animal, with several suggesting that it
4733 allowed them to keep their dog company. For one participant this also had financial benefits,
4734 as they no longer needed to pay for dog sitting services. Conversely, a larger proportion of
4735 dog guardians suggested that working from home was disadvantageous to their companion
4736 animal, as they predicted it would cause future issues in terms of separation anxiety. A
4737 higher proportion of cat guardians than dog guardians suggested their companion animal
4738 was a source of negative disruption when working from home, while the majority of fish
4739 guardians reported there were no benefits or disadvantages to working from home with their
4740 companion animals, with one stating “we only have fish and I don't even notice them”
4741 (Participant 15).

4742 When comparing responses from guardians of all companion animal types to those of non-
4743 guardians, a larger proportion of guardians reported there were no disadvantages to working
4744 from home with companion animals, whereas very few non-guardians expressed similar
4745 beliefs. Specifically, a higher proportion of non-guardians believed that companion animals

4746 would be a negative disruption from work compared to the proportion of guardians who
4747 reported these disadvantages. A higher proportion of non-guardians also felt that companion
4748 animals would have a positive effect in terms of prompting breaks and routine. This suggests
4749 the expectations of non-guardians may not reflect the reality of working from home with
4750 companion animals. Generally, guardians appeared to be more concerned about how their
4751 working from home affected their companion animals, with a greater proportion than non-
4752 guardians reporting both benefits and disadvantages for companion animals.

Table 6.4 Categories of benefits and disadvantages identified through conventional content analysis

Category	Subcategory	Codes	Examples	Description
<i>Benefits</i>				
Positive mental health	Stress relief	Stress relief	"He is a great stress buster"	Participants reported that the presence of companion animals while working from home had (or was anticipated to have) positive effects on their mental health. These effects included companion animals providing stress relief, relaxation, or a sense of calm; providing company or helping to reduce loneliness; providing comfort and opportunities for physical affection/cuddling; and providing pleasure or happiness through interaction.
		Calming		
		Relaxation		
	Physical contact	Physical contact is relaxing	"It is relaxing to stroke her"	
		Cuddling/cuddles		
		Physical contact leads to feeling better		
		Physical affection		
	Companion animals provide company	Company for owner/guardian	"Feels like you have company even when you're on your own"	
		Company if alone		
		Someone to talk to		
		Talking to companion animals		
		Spending time together		
Happiness, enjoyment, improved mood	Nice to watch them	"During breaks I am able to interact with my cat, who cheers me up"		
	Mood improvement			
	Others enjoy seeing them onscreen			
	Increased happiness which affects other aspects of life			
	Playing			
Comfort	Positive mental health	"Having pets there for comfort in breaks"		
	Comfort			
		Source of comfort during breaks		

Routine maintenance and prompting breaks from work	Structure Taking breaks	Structure End to workday Encourages finishing on time Routine Taking breaks together Getting away from screens Positive distraction Distraction from screen Forces break from screens and sitting Forces a break Forces more regular breaks Encourage breaks	“Provide structure to the day, so stop work at 5.30 to take them for walk” “Can force a well needed break from work, 5 minutes to feed or pet”	Participants made reference to companion animals helping (or being anticipated to help) them maintain routines while working from home. This included adding structure to the workday such as by forcing them to stop working, forcing, or encouraging them to engage in rest breaks, and ensuring that guardians spent time exercising/outdoors.
	Exercise and getting outside	Spending time outside Increased exercise Getting outside Opportunity for exercise Forced to walk and get outside Get outside, away from home office Dogs make you exercise	“He gets me out the house for some fresh air!”	
Benefits for companion animals	More interaction	More interaction More time with pets More time for walks More opportunity for interaction	“Time to fit in an early morning dog walk”	Benefits of guardians working from home were also reported (or anticipated) for the companion animals. This included direct benefits, such as the

Benefits for the pet	<p>Cat has more freedom</p> <p>Company for the companion animal</p> <p>Dog not left alone</p> <p>Dog gets more exercise</p> <p>Dogs weren't suited to take your dog to work schemes</p> <p>Pets better cared for</p>	"Dog is not left alone for as long"	guardian having more time to interact with their companion animal, and indirect benefits, such as the guardian being better able to manage pet care activities.
Less worry about pet care	<p>No worries about pets being home alone</p> <p>Ownership is less stressful and more enjoyable</p> <p>Easier to take care of them when sick</p>	"Find it much easier to manage care for the horse particularly as I don't get stuck in traffic in the same way"	
Flexibility	<p>Flexibility in vet appointments</p> <p>Flexibility to walk dog whenever suits</p>	"Flexible veterinary appointments"	
Option to adopt a pet	<p>Working from home meant could get a dog</p>	"Working from home means we have been able to get a dog which is something we have wanted for years but haven't been able to due to work"	
Financial benefits	<p>Don't have to pay for doggy day care</p> <p>Don't have to spend on dog walker</p>	"I don't have to worry about dog care or pay for dog care (doggy day care)"	Participants stated that working from home has (or is anticipated to have) a positive financial impact.

No benefits			“Nothing as we only have fish and I don’t even notice them.”	Participants explicitly stated there are no benefits of working from home with companion animals. Sometimes this was in relation to a specific type of companion animal, while other companion animal types were recognised as providing benefits. This does not include instances where the participant made no comment with regards to a companion animal type.
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Disadvantages

Negative disruption from work	Negative distraction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distracting Disruptive Noisy Demanding of attention You want to interact with them Detrimental to work Disturb meetings Break concentration Takes time away from work Need attention 	“He was barking on a call today so that was very distracting!”	Participants reported companion animals were (or were anticipated to be) a source of disruption while they worked from home. This could be because the companion animal was a source of negative distraction which impacted productivity/work, or because conflicts between working from home commitments and meeting companion animal needs were a source of stress or other psychological distress (e.g. worry, guilt).
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	Causes of stress	Difficulty managing work/home chores, including pet care Guilt at not walking dog when have opportunity More stress Have to walk them in all weather Time consuming Need to work to their schedule	“They're another thing to worry about fitting around my work schedule”	
Disadvantages for companion animals	Negative effects on companion animals Future separation anxiety	Impact pets' routine at first Less interaction for dogs who usually go to the office with guardian Cat forced outside during meetings Pets used to guardians being home Pets more dependent on you Separation anxiety anticipated	“In the beginning of working from home, it was a change of routine for them to have you here every day so took a bit of getting used to” “The dog will probably get separation anxiety when we all go back to work/school”	Disadvantages of guardians working from home were also reported (or anticipated) for the companion animals. This included negative consequences predicted to occur in future.
No disadvantage			“None!”	Participants explicitly stated there are no disadvantages of working from home with companion animals. Sometimes this was in relation to a specific type of companion animal, while other companion animal types were associated with disadvantages. This does not include instances where the participant made no comment with regards to a companion animal type.

4755 **Table 6.5 Percentages of guardians (total and by type of companion animal) and non-**
 4756 **guardians referring to each benefit and disadvantage**

	Companion animal guardians				Non-guardians
	Dog	Cat	Fish	All	
<i>Benefits</i>					
Positive mental health	47%	55%	20%	53%	48%
Routine and breaks from work	27%	18%	0	22%	55%
Benefits for companion animals	47%	27%	0	34%	24%
Financial benefits	7%	0	0	3%	3%
No benefits	0	9%	60%	13%	10%
<i>Disadvantages</i>					
Negative disruption to work	53%	82%	0	50%	93%
Disadvantages for companion animals	33%	9%	0	19%	3%
No disadvantages	20%	18%	60%	31%	7%

4757 **6.5 Discussion**

4758 The purpose of this research was to investigate the impact of companion animals on the
 4759 well-being and productivity of individuals working from home. Previous research has
 4760 suggested that companion animals may positively influence human well-being, perhaps
 4761 because they divert attention away from negative emotional states (Beetz, 2017), create a
 4762 more relaxed atmosphere (Julius et al., 2013), or because they are providers of social
 4763 support (Beck and Madresh, 2008, Meehan, Massavelli and Pachana, 2017). Thus,
 4764 interaction with companion animals may lead to outcomes such as reduced stress (Barker et
 4765 al., 2012) or improved cognitive performance (Allen, Shykoff and Izzo, 2001, Gee et al.,
 4766 2015). In the context of remote working, however, companion animals may also be a source
 4767 of distraction, and so could potentially be harmful to productivity (Kelemen et al., 2020). To
 4768 date, only one study has examined the impact of companion animals on people working from
 4769 home (Hoffman, 2021); the current research sought to extend these findings.

4770 Companion animal guardians and non-guardians completed assessments of perceived
 4771 stress and working memory at three time points during one day they worked from home. It
 4772 was hypothesised that perceived stress would reduce over the day for companion animal

4773 guardians, but increase for non-guardians, while working memory performance would
4774 remain stable or improve for guardians, and decrease for non-guardians. No evidence was
4775 found to support these hypotheses. Perceived stress was elevated at midday and end-of-day
4776 compared to start-of-day, and performance on the digit span forward was improved at
4777 midday *versus* start-of-day, but no effects of companion animal guardianship were found.

4778 One probable explanation for these findings is that the effects of companion animal
4779 guardianship are dependent upon the level of engagement between an animal and their
4780 guardian. A recent study used ecological momentary assessments to determine how
4781 presence of, and engagement with companion animals influenced affect (Janssens et al.,
4782 2020). Participants were required to report their current levels of affect, and the extent to
4783 which they were currently interacting with their companion animals at ten random time-points
4784 each day for five days; results indicated that the presence of a companion animal was
4785 associated with less negative affect, while increased engagement was associated with
4786 greater positive affect (Janssens et al., 2020). Similarly, Barker et al. (2012) found that
4787 people who took their dogs to work experienced reduced levels of perceived stress during
4788 the working day, whereas those who did not bring their dogs to work experienced an
4789 increase in perceived stress that was similar to that observed in non-guardians. These
4790 findings suggest that simply being a companion animal guardian is insufficient to impact
4791 well-being; guardians must interact with their companion animal to experience any benefits.
4792 Furthermore, this corresponds with the theories discussed above, as a companion animal
4793 must be present in order to attract their guardian's attention, promote a relaxed atmosphere,
4794 or provide social support. Data regarding the presence or absence of companion animals at
4795 the time participants completed the study assessments were not collected in the current
4796 study, however, fewer than half of guardians reported that their companion animal was in the
4797 same room as them for most of the day. Therefore, some participants likely completed some
4798 of these assessments while alone, and so could not experience any positive effects
4799 associated with the presence of their companion animal.

4800 Other potential explanations relate to task difficulty and the type of interaction between
4801 guardians and their companion animals. Stewart and Strickland (2013) examined how
4802 presence of a dog influenced state anxiety during timed tasks. An interaction between task
4803 difficulty and companion animal guardianship status was found; presence of a dog during a
4804 task of moderate difficulty was associated with lower state anxiety for those who were
4805 companion animal guardians, but the same effect was not found when the task was of
4806 extreme difficulty. The highest levels of anxiety were found among dog guardians in the
4807 extreme difficulty condition, which the authors suggested may be due to dog guardians
4808 having a desire to interact with the dog, but being prevented from doing so by the difficulty of
4809 the task (Stewart and Strickland, 2013). Similarly, Gee et al. (2015) found that presence of a
4810 dog positively influenced performance on a working memory task, but physical contact with
4811 the dog was detrimental to performance, perhaps because this contact interfered with
4812 completion of the task. As participants in the current study completed assessments as part
4813 of their usual working day, there was no way to control for task difficulty, and data regarding
4814 the ways in which guardians interacted with their companion animals were not collected.
4815 Therefore, these factors should be considered in future research regarding the impact of
4816 companion animals on people working from home.

4817 The potential for companion animals to be a source of distraction to their guardians
4818 (Kelemen et al., 2020) was also considered in the current research. It was predicted that
4819 guardians would report a significantly higher frequency of being distracted, and significantly
4820 more home-to-work conflict than non-guardians. Although 44% of guardians indicated that
4821 “animals in the home” were one of the top three sources of distraction they had experienced
4822 that day, no significant differences were found between guardians and non-guardians in self-
4823 reported frequency of distractions or home-to-work conflict; there were also no differences
4824 for perceived quality of work and productivity. When specifically asked about the
4825 disadvantages of keeping companion animals when working from home, only 50% of
4826 guardians indicated that they were a source of negative disruption from work, whereas 93%

4827 of non-guardians suggested negative disruptions as a potential disadvantage. These
4828 findings indicate that while companion animals are expected to be a source of distraction for
4829 people working from home, the reality is that, overall, guardians experience no greater
4830 frequency of distractions than non-guardians. This corresponds with previous research in
4831 pet-friendly workplaces which indicated that companion animals at work can be a source of
4832 disruption (Wells and Perrine, 2001a) but the majority of people who take their dogs to work
4833 report that it is problem free (Norling and Keeling, 2010).

4834 These findings may, however, depend on the type of companion animal. Hoffman (2021)
4835 found that people with dogs were more likely than those without dogs to report that their
4836 work and home lives interfered with one another on work-from-home days, but the same
4837 results were not found for people who kept cats. The current study lacked the statistical
4838 power needed to examine the influence of companion animal type using inferential statistics,
4839 but all those who reported animals as a top three source of distraction kept dogs or cats.
4840 Interestingly, qualitative data indicated that a higher percentage of cat guardians than dogs
4841 guardians indicated negative disruption as a disadvantage of keeping companion animals
4842 while working from home, which contradicts Hoffman's (2021) findings. No fish guardians
4843 reported that their companion animals were a source of disruption, although this was a very
4844 small sample so may not be generalisable. Future research should consider how animal type
4845 may influence whether companion animals are a source of disruption; the temperament and
4846 behaviour of individual animals should also be considered (Hoffman, 2021), as more
4847 excitable or energetic animals may cause greater levels of disruption.

4848 Research conducted during the pandemic, including that presented in the previous chapter,
4849 suggested that the maintenance of routine was an important benefit of keeping companion
4850 animals during lockdown (Clements et al., 2021, Shoesmith et al., 2021). The current study
4851 sought to investigate whether this extended to the context of homeworking, specifically, if
4852 companion animals helped promote healthier work habits. There was no evidence that
4853 compliance with recommendations about rest breaks differed between companion animal

4854 guardians and non-guardians, although just under a quarter of guardians did report benefits
4855 of working from home with companion animals that related to routine maintenance and
4856 prompting breaks from work. Russo et al. (2021) examined predictors of well-being during
4857 the pandemic, and found that daily routines positively predicted well-being in wave one (April
4858 2020) but not wave two (May 2020). Therefore, the relatively small number of guardians that
4859 reported routine maintenance as a benefit of working from home with companion animals
4860 may reflect the timing of data collection (April to October 2021); this benefit may have been
4861 more evident at the beginning of the pandemic before remote workers had developed daily
4862 routines.

4863 Interestingly, a greater proportion of non-guardians than guardians suggested routine
4864 maintenance and prompting of breaks may be benefits of working from home with
4865 companion animals. This frequently related to potential for companion animals, specifically
4866 dogs, to encourage daily walks. Although the present study did not assess whether
4867 companion animal guardianship was associated with higher levels of physical activity during
4868 the working day, there is evidence from previous research that dog guardianship is
4869 associated with higher levels of physical activity (Yabroff, Troiano and Berrigan, 2008,
4870 Hoerster et al., 2011). However, Hoffman (2021) found no evidence that dog walking was
4871 higher among companion animal guardians on work-from-home days compared to days
4872 spent at the office. This may suggest that companion animal guardians did not report
4873 routines related to daily dog-walking as benefits in the present study because they would
4874 have engaged in this activity irrespective of whether they worked from home.

4875 **6.5.1 Strengths, limitations, and future directions**

4876 The major strength of this research was that participants were blind to the aims relating to
4877 companion animal guardianship until completion of the study. It is often impossible to
4878 achieving blinding in HAI research, leading to potential bias in the data (Serpell et al., 2017,
4879 Friedmann and Gee, 2019). As participants in the present study were free from these biases,
4880 the validity of the study findings is increased. Furthermore, the only other study to examine

4881 the influence of companion animals on people working from home was subject to recall bias,
4882 as participants' responses reflected their experiences of working from home during the
4883 pandemic and working in the office pre-pandemic (Hoffman, 2021). In the current study,
4884 participants' responses related to their experience 'in the moment' and so were not subject
4885 to this recall bias.

4886 This study also considered the influence of companion animals on cognitive outcomes
4887 (working memory), rather than focusing primarily on well-being. There is evidence that
4888 interaction with companion animals promotes cognitive performance (Allen, Shykoff and
4889 Izzo, 2001, Gee, Church and Altobelli, 2010, Gee, Crist and Carr, 2010, Gee, Belcher, et al.,
4890 2012, Gee, Gould, et al., 2012, Gee et al., 2015) but this is currently very limited and mostly
4891 restricted to studies with young children. However, theories such as the biophilia effect
4892 (Julius et al., 2013, Beetz, 2017) or companion animals as providers of social support (Beck
4893 and Madresh, 2008, Meehan, Massavelli and Pachana, 2017) would suggest that interaction
4894 with companion animals helps to reduce stress among humans, and there is experimental
4895 research to support this proposition (Wheeler and Faulkner, 2015, Barker et al., 2016,
4896 Banks, McCoy and Trzcinski, 2018, Wood, Ohlsen, et al., 2018). As acute stress is
4897 associated with reduced executive function (Starcke et al., 2016), it follows that interaction
4898 with companion animals should facilitate cognitive performance *via* stress reduction. More
4899 research is needed to investigate the impact of companion animals on cognitive outcomes,
4900 such as working memory.

4901 This research was conducted in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, and thus provides
4902 much needed insight into the experiences of people working from home. However, the
4903 pandemic also created some limitations. As COVID-19 remained a major threat at the time
4904 of data collection, for many individuals working from home was not optional and so it is
4905 unclear whether these findings would replicate in a sample of individuals who made the
4906 choice to work remotely (Russo et al., 2021). Furthermore, it was anticipated that most
4907 individuals would be working entirely remotely at the time of data collection; this was

4908 confirmed by 77% of participants reporting that they always worked from home. However,
4909 this precluded the comparison between working from home and working at the office.
4910 Although Hoffman (2021) made such a comparison, they relied on participants recalling
4911 experiences from prior to the pandemic, introducing recall biases. Therefore, future research
4912 should aim to use within-subjects designs to compare the effects of working from home with
4913 companion animals to working at the office, with or without companion animals. Ideally, such
4914 research will use objective assessments of productivity and quality of work, rather than
4915 relying on self-report measures as in the current study.

4916 **6.5.2 Conclusions**

4917 The findings of this research suggest that companion animal guardianship is not associated
4918 with lower levels of perceived stress or improved cognitive performance among people
4919 working from home. While companion animals were a source of distraction for some
4920 guardians, there was no evidence that guardians experienced a greater frequency of
4921 distraction overall, and no differences in self-reported productivity or quality of work were
4922 found between guardians and non-guardians. Around a quarter of guardians reported that a
4923 benefit of keeping companion animals was that they helped maintain routine and/or promote
4924 engagement in work breaks, but guardians did not report greater compliance with guidance
4925 around rest breaks than non-guardians. These findings suggest that companion animals
4926 were neither a benefit nor a distraction to people working from home. However, fewer than
4927 half of guardians reported spending most of the day in the same room as their companion
4928 animal, and qualitative data indicated that guardians of different companion animal types
4929 reported divergent experiences. Therefore, future research should aim to examine whether
4930 companion animal type and level of engagement influence the effects of companion animals
4931 on people working from home; ecological momentary assessments, which repeatedly assess
4932 level of engagement and well-being outcomes 'in the moment', may be an effective
4933 technique to achieve these aims.

4934 **Chapter 7.**

4935 **Thesis Discussion**

4936 **7.1 Introduction**

4937 The primary aim of this thesis was to improve understanding of whether and how
4938 engagement with ornamental fishes influences human well-being. This aim was achieved by
4939 first conducting a systematic review to identify current evidence relating to the psychological
4940 and physiological effects of interacting with fishes in aquaria (Chapter 2). Despite inclusion
4941 criteria being intentionally broad, only nineteen studies were identified and findings were
4942 mixed. All studies had high or unclear risk of bias, and there was considerable variation in
4943 factors such as the measured outcomes, the population under study, and the nature of the
4944 human-fish interaction. To address gaps in the evidence identified by this systematic review,
4945 studies were designed within three settings where, due to reasons such as disruption or
4946 increased risk, the presence of fish aquaria may be preferable to that of other companion
4947 animals: the workplace, dementia care homes and nurseries.

4948 Studies in the workplace (Chapters 3-4) were a combination of controlled trials and
4949 qualitative research. No evidence was found to support the hypothesis that watching a live
4950 fish aquarium during the working day would have a more positive effect on mood,
4951 physiological stress, and cognitive performance than watching a fish video or sitting quietly
4952 relaxing. Repeated viewings of the live fish aquarium over several weeks were also not
4953 associated with improvements in psychological and physiological well-being relative to
4954 repeatedly engaging in quiet relaxation, but there was evidence that repeated viewings of
4955 the fish video led to greater job-related affective well-being. Qualitative follow-up research
4956 suggested that although live fishes were perceived as more engaging than fish videos, some
4957 participants found benefit from all three conditions because taking part in the research
4958 provided psychological distance and a break from work. The second workplace study
4959 substantiated the importance of live fishes and some participants expressed an emotional
4960 connection to them. However, others appeared to appreciate the tanks on a purely aesthetic
4961 level, or expressed indifference towards the presence of fishes in the workplace.

4962 Although the COVID-19 pandemic prevented planned studies from being conducted in care
4963 homes and nurseries, it also presented alternative opportunities for the study of HAI.
4964 Therefore, the secondary aim of this thesis was to understand the impact of companion
4965 animals on human well-being within the context of the pandemic and ongoing restrictions. A
4966 mixed methods study was conducted to investigate the relationship between companion
4967 animal guardianship and levels of loneliness and mental well-being during the pandemic
4968 (Chapter 5). This was followed by a quasi-experimental study to examine the influence of
4969 companion animals on the well-being and productivity of people working from home
4970 (Chapter 6). Neither study found quantitative evidence that being a companion animal
4971 guardian was associated with more positive well-being outcomes, but there was also no
4972 evidence that companion animals detrimentally impacted productivity among people working
4973 from home. Within the general context of the pandemic, a greater level of engagement with
4974 dogs (and to a lesser extent cats) was associated with poorer outcomes, but no influence
4975 was found with regards to level of engagement with fishes. Qualitative findings indicated that
4976 the majority of companion animal guardians perceived their companion animals to have
4977 positively impacted their well-being during the pandemic, and around half reported positive
4978 mental health effects associated with the presence of companion animals when working
4979 from home. When considering the specific influence of ornamental fishes, some participants
4980 expressed that watching their fishes was relaxing and that engaging in fishkeeping activities
4981 helped them to maintain normal routines. However, some appeared to feel indifferently
4982 towards their fishes, and around a quarter reported that their fishes had no impact on their
4983 well-being during the pandemic.

4984 This final chapter discusses the implications of these findings in terms of existing research
4985 and theory. Limitations of the research are also considered, and suggestions are provided
4986 for future research.

4987 **7.2 Ornamental fishes and human well-being**

4988 Outcomes relating to relaxation, anxiety, and physiological stress were the most commonly
4989 assessed among papers included in the systematic review. Findings were mixed; although
4990 there were studies that demonstrated positive effects, others found no evidence that
4991 interacting with ornamental fishes influences relaxation or related outcomes. Since searches
4992 were conducted, only one additional paper (to my knowledge) has been published on this
4993 topic. Broadly corresponding with the findings of the review, this research identified that
4994 relaxation, anxiety, and mood were significantly improved after watching an aquarium
4995 containing live fishes *versus* an empty tank or one containing only plants and water, but no
4996 effects were found for physiological outcomes (Gee et al., 2019). The current research
4997 extended this body of evidence by examining whether watching ornamental fishes may
4998 induce relaxation among employees at work. There was no quantitative evidence to
4999 demonstrate an effect in this sample. However, qualitative data from both workplace studies
5000 and research conducted during the pandemic suggests that people do believe watching
5001 fishes has a calming effect.

5002 It is possible that the effects of watching aquaria differ based on situational factors and an
5003 individual's current needs. Studies have identified stress reduction as a benefit of keeping
5004 ornamental fishes (Kidd and Kidd, 1999, Langfield and James, 2009), but the circumstances
5005 under which fish guardians benefit from watching their fishes have not been examined.
5006 Research demonstrating a significant effect of fishes on outcomes related to relaxation has
5007 typically been conducted in the context of natural or experimentally-induced stressors
5008 (Katcher, Segal and Beck, 1984, Wells, 2005, Buttelman and Röpke, 2014). Presumably
5009 any stress-reducing effects of watching fishes at home occurs under similar conditions; fish
5010 guardians will only benefit when experiencing some degree of stress. For the workplace
5011 study in Chapter 3, although the sample was selected because it incorporated professions
5012 associated with higher than average work-related stress, qualitative evidence indicated that
5013 the simple opportunity to leave the office was of benefit to some participants. Thus,

5014 participants' levels of stress at baseline may have been too low for a meaningful increase in
5015 relaxation to occur. The workplace context may have also influenced findings. Previous
5016 research suggests that fishes effectively capture and maintain human attention (Windhager
5017 et al., 2011, Cracknell et al., 2016) but participants' experiences in the second workplace
5018 study (Chapter 4) provided no indication of such a mechanism; perhaps the fishes were
5019 unable to capture participants' attention because they were too focused on their work.
5020 Equally, participants in the first study (Chapter 3) may have been too distracted by work-
5021 related concerns to fully immerse themselves in the act of watching the fishes. More
5022 research is needed to identify the specific circumstances (if any) under which watching
5023 fishes may induce relaxation.

5024 Research for both workplace studies was conducted under the premise that any direct
5025 effects of ornamental fishes on well-being or cognition would occur *via* visual exposure.
5026 Specifically, watching fishes was anticipated to lead to relaxation either by diverting attention
5027 away from negative mental states (i.e. through distraction, Beetz, 2017), because the
5028 presence of calm animals signals an absence of threats in the environment (i.e. the biophilia-
5029 effect, Julius et al., 2013), or because exposure to elements of nature promotes restoration
5030 (i.e. stress recovery theory and attention restoration theory; Ulrich, 1993, Kaplan, 1995).
5031 Quantitative data did not support this premise, but there was some qualitative evidence that
5032 participants appreciated the aesthetics of the aquaria, implying that there is a visual
5033 component. However, there was also evidence that the effects of ornamental fishes go
5034 beyond the visual dimension. Most participants expressed a clear preference for live fishes
5035 over videos, and some demonstrated an emotional attachment to the fishes through actions
5036 such as giving them names. This was most evident in the second study (Chapter 4) where
5037 participants felt a level of responsibility towards the fishes, but was also present in the first
5038 study (Chapter 3) where the participants had no contact with the fishes outside of the
5039 experimental sessions. Previous research has suggested that some guardians feel an
5040 emotional attachment towards their fishes (Langfield and James, 2009). However, true

5041 attachment bonds are reciprocal in nature and evidence collected during the pandemic
5042 suggests that fishes provided their guardians with little in the way of social or emotional
5043 support, perhaps due to a lack of physical contact. As attachment can mediate the
5044 relationship between companion animal guardianship and well-being (Antonacopoulos and
5045 Pychyl, 2010), more research is needed to understand the nature of human-fish
5046 relationships, whether they constitute true attachment bonds, and the influence this may
5047 have upon human well-being.

5048 Despite some participants showing an emotional connection to the fishes, throughout all
5049 studies in this thesis fishes were discussed with a tone of dismissiveness. Participants made
5050 statements such as “I don’t even notice” the fishes, or appeared to appreciate the tank on a
5051 purely aesthetic level viewing the fishes more as decoration than living beings. This
5052 corresponds with previous research which suggested that some fish guardians view their
5053 aquaria only as ‘room decoration’ (Kidd and Kidd, 1999). Speciesism refers to the belief that
5054 humans are superior to other creatures and has implications for animal welfare (Potts,
5055 2010). Although contrasts are commonly made with regards to the treatment of companion
5056 animals *versus* those used in agriculture (Adams, 2018), the attitude of dismissiveness
5057 towards fishes may highlight potential variation among different companion animal types
5058 whereby ornamental fishes are viewed as inferior to animals such as dogs or cats. This has
5059 implications regarding ornamental fish welfare. After completion of the second workplace-
5060 based study (Chapter 4), workplaces were permitted to keep the fish tanks, provided there
5061 were no concerns regarding animal welfare. Unfortunately, a follow-up visit to check fish
5062 welfare found that employees in one workplace had their access restricted during the
5063 nationwide lockdown, ultimately resulting in fish mortality. While it is unclear whether a
5064 dismissive attitude towards fishes contributed to these events, it may be of interest in future
5065 research to examine how attitudes towards ornamental fishes compare to those regarding
5066 other companion animal types, and how this relates to issues surrounding fish welfare.

5067 As part of this thesis, studies were planned to investigate the influence of ornamental fishes
5068 in dementia care homes and nurseries, but these studies could not proceed due to the
5069 COVID-19 pandemic. In prior research, the introduction of aquaria into dementia units was
5070 associated with improved nutritional intake, body mass, and behaviour among residents
5071 (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014). The first study aimed to
5072 replicate and extend these findings; it was hypothesised that following installation of aquaria
5073 residents would demonstrate a significant reduction in agitated behaviour and improvement
5074 in body mass. Furthermore, as the authors of the original research suggested that reduced
5075 agitation led to improved body mass by calming residents at meal times (Edwards, Beck and
5076 Lim, 2014), these outcomes were predicted to be significantly negatively correlated so that a
5077 greater reduction in agitation would be associated with a greater improvement in body mass.
5078 The second planned study was based on research demonstrating the positive effects of HAI
5079 among preschool aged children; in a series of studies the presence of a therapy dog was
5080 associated with faster execution of motor tasks without a compromise to accuracy (Gee,
5081 Harris and Johnson, 2007), greater adherence to instructions when undertaking tasks
5082 requiring modelling of behaviour (Gee et al., 2009) and improved performance on a range of
5083 cognitive tasks (Gee, Church and Altobelli, 2010, Gee, Belcher, et al., 2012, Gee, Gould, et
5084 al., 2012). The planned study aimed to determine whether the presence of fish aquaria
5085 would have similar effects; it was hypothesised that the presence of an aquarium would be
5086 associated with improved cognitive performance and behaviour relative to the presence of a
5087 toy aquarium or no stimulus. An increased level of interaction with the fishes (the child being
5088 permitted to give the fishes a toy to 'play with' following completion of an object recognition
5089 task) was anticipated to lead to stronger effects. Furthermore, both studies were planned to
5090 include a qualitative component to understand the experiences of the population under
5091 study, and identify barriers and facilitators with regards to the presence of fish aquaria in
5092 each setting. It is anticipated that these studies would have provided a more complete
5093 picture regarding the impact of ornamental fishes in human well-being, by providing
5094 evidence from different stages of life and in different settings. Although they could not be

5095 conducted, protocols are included in the appendices (Appendices A and B) so that they
5096 might inform future research once restrictions to the accessibility of these populations related
5097 to COVID-19 are removed.

5098 **7.3 Companion animals and the pandemic**

5099 Although there was no quantitative evidence that companion animal guardianship was
5100 associated with greater well-being either within the general context of the pandemic or within
5101 the specific context of working from home, qualitative findings showed that guardians tended
5102 to have positive attitudes about the impact of their companion animals on their well-being.
5103 These findings reflect a wider pattern of results in the field of HAI; although people believe
5104 companion animals can promote well-being, quantitative evidence to support this premise is
5105 less forthcoming (Herzog, 2011).

5106 One possible explanation that could reconcile these conflicting findings is that the benefits of
5107 interacting with companion animals are offset by the unique stresses associated with
5108 companion animal guardianship. Across all studies, there was evidence of companion
5109 animals being a source of stress or worry. Companion animal welfare was a source of
5110 concern for guardians during the pandemic, as they were unsure whether restrictions would
5111 impact access to services such as veterinary care. Similarly, participants expressed that the
5112 greatest disadvantages of fishes in the workplace related to who would maintain the aquaria,
5113 whereas many guardians working from home felt that companion animals could be a source
5114 of disruption or stress. Research has considered some of the negative aspects of keeping
5115 companion animals but often this relates to more extreme outcomes, such as health-related
5116 issues like allergies, zoonoses, bites and scratches, or falls (Smith, Smith and D'Auria, 2012,
5117 Bert et al., 2016, Friedman and Krause-Parello, 2018), or the grief suffered at the loss of a
5118 companion animal (Kemp, Jacobs and Stewart, 2016, Reisbig et al., 2017). Less
5119 consideration has been given to whether the general day-to-day care of companion animals
5120 may negatively impact well-being among guardians. For example, a benefit of pet-friendly
5121 workplaces may be relief from feelings of stress associated with leaving dogs at home alone

5122 (Norling and Keeling, 2010), but the impact of this stress on people who do not have the
5123 option to take their dog to work is unclear. A small number of guardians reported very
5124 negative attitudes towards the impact of their companion animals during the pandemic, and
5125 it would be of interest to examine why these participants had very different experiences to
5126 the majority of guardians. Future research should aim to assess the negative consequences
5127 of companion animal guardianship and whether the day-to-day realities of being a
5128 companion animal guardian offset any positive impacts on human well-being.

5129 Another plausible explanation relates to the type and level of engagement between
5130 companion animals and their guardians. It was observed that level of interaction with dogs,
5131 and to a lesser extent cats, was associated with differences in well-being outcomes. This
5132 highlights the complex nature of the relationship between companion animal guardianship
5133 and well-being. Over recent years, researchers have begun to consider how this relationship
5134 may be influenced by factors such as sociodemographic characteristics (Saunders et al.,
5135 2017) and personality (Bao and Schreer, 2016), but it is also important to consider the
5136 nature of the HAI (Kazdin, 2017, Friedmann and Gee, 2019, Barcelos et al., 2020,
5137 Rodriguez, Herzog and Gee, 2021). For example, having primary or shared responsibility for
5138 a dog was associated with more positive well-being during the pandemic, suggesting that
5139 being involved in the care of companion animals (or at least dogs) may be critical for
5140 guardianship to have an effect. As the effect of level of engagement was not examined in
5141 relation to working from home, this may explain why no differences in well-being or cognition
5142 were found between companion animal guardians and non-guardians. Furthermore, while
5143 the presence of calm or friendly animals is argued to promote relaxation (Julius et al., 2013),
5144 physical contact may be an important component of HAI (Beetz, Uvnas-Moberg, et al., 2012,
5145 Beetz and Bales, 2016). Therefore, it is important that research considers how the effects of
5146 HAI are influenced by the type and level of engagement between the human and animal.
5147 This may also apply to the effects of ornamental fishes in the workplace; level of
5148 engagement with fishes was not controlled in the research presented in Chapter 4 and so

5149 participants may have interacted with the fishes to differing extents, potentially accounting
5150 for differences in their experiences. Furthermore, the participants in the workplace-based
5151 studies did not engage in fish care activities, except where the researcher could not attend
5152 the workplace due to COVID-19 related restrictions. It would therefore, be of interest to
5153 determine how being involved in the care of the fishes might influence their effects on
5154 employee well-being, and more broadly within the context of fish guardianship.

5155 Assessing the impact of the pandemic on companion animal welfare was beyond the scope
5156 of this thesis, but data collected as part of this research indicated that there may have been
5157 impacts for companion animals as well as their guardians. A minority of participants had
5158 experienced issues in obtaining pet care supplies or veterinary treatment for their companion
5159 animals, and some reported other issues such as limits on time walking dogs or having no
5160 access to grooming services. When asked about whether and how the pandemic had
5161 influenced interaction with companion animals several participants gave responses that
5162 related more to animal welfare than human well-being. These data were not formally
5163 analysed but there was evidence of both positive and negative effects. For example,
5164 guardians felt their companion animals (particularly dogs) had benefitted from the increased
5165 interaction, but it was also suggested that companion animals' daily routines may have been
5166 disrupted by their guardians being home more during the day, and many guardians
5167 expressed that they anticipated future issues relating to separation anxiety. These findings
5168 were mirrored in data relating to the benefits and disadvantages of working from home with
5169 companion animals, and reflect those observed in other studies conducted during this period
5170 (Esam, Forrest and Waran, 2021, Holland et al., 2021, Shosmith et al., 2021).

5171 One limitation of this thesis relates to the negative impact of the pandemic on participant
5172 recruitment. Research conducted in the workplace commenced prior to the pandemic and so
5173 the first nationwide lockdown meant one study was ended slightly prematurely (Chapter 3,
5174 Trial B) and another experienced significant and repeated delays (Chapter 4). In the latter
5175 study, some workplaces that had expressed an interest in taking part were no longer able to

5176 participate because employees switched to remote working. Although the remaining studies
5177 were conducted online, recruitment remained a challenge, perhaps because the pandemic
5178 caused a surge in the amount of internet-mediated research being conducted; participants
5179 may have been reluctant to take part due to being inundated with similar requests. These
5180 challenges with participant recruitment mean that quantitative studies (with the exception of
5181 Chapter 5) utilised relatively small sample sizes, which may have impacted statistical power.
5182 Although all studies met the minimum thresholds needed to find a medium sized effect,
5183 smaller effects would not have been detectable; however, while power analyses conducted
5184 based on the data collected so far indicate that much larger samples would be needed to
5185 detect effects, these effects would be so small they would be essentially meaningless.
5186 Nevertheless, these small samples also made it impossible to examine more nuanced
5187 relationships, such as whether the level of interaction with companion animals influenced the
5188 effects of companion animal guardianship on people working from home; additional data
5189 would be needed to assess these effects.

5190 **7.4 Future directions**

5191 The research presented here highlights a number of opportunities for the future research
5192 regarding the impact of ornamental fishes on human well-being. Firstly, the systematic
5193 review demonstrated that evidence relating to the effects of ornamental fishes is an under-
5194 researched topic within the field. Specifically, more high quality research conducted with
5195 more varied samples is needed. As studies planned in nurseries and care homes were
5196 cancelled due to the pandemic, it is important that future research addresses these gaps in
5197 the evidence. Consideration should also be given to the nature of human-fish interactions
5198 and how these influence well-being; questions remain regarding whether human-fish
5199 relationships constitute true attachment bonds, and whether being involved in the care of
5200 fishes leads to stronger effects than the simple presence of aquaria within the environment.
5201 It is also of interest to determine exactly how people naturally interact with ornamental fishes
5202 in their environment, and how this differs across different settings. For example, evidence

5203 collected in leisure settings (shopping malls, public aquaria) has indicated that fishes may
5204 capture and maintain human attention (Windhager et al., 2011, Cracknell et al., 2016), but
5205 this was less clear in current research conducted in the workplace. Perhaps employees
5206 would be more likely to observe and gain benefit from fish aquaria in a breakroom rather
5207 than in their office as the change in situational factors leaves more scope for relaxation.
5208 Finally, research should examine how attitudes towards ornamental fishes differ to those of
5209 other companion animals, and assess how this might impact ornamental fish welfare.

5210 In addition, opportunities were highlighted for the broader study of HAI. It is well established
5211 that the relationship between companion animal guardianship and well-being is more
5212 complex than whether or not someone keeps a companion animal (Herzog, 2011, Kazdin,
5213 2017, Saunders et al., 2017, Friedmann and Gee, 2019, Barcelos et al., 2020, Rodriguez,
5214 Herzog and Gee, 2021). As demonstrated in the present research, factors which require
5215 more consideration are the type and level of engagement between a companion animal and
5216 their guardian. Ecological momentary assessments involve repeatedly assessing
5217 participants' experiences within the moment, during their day-to-day lives (Shiffman, Stone
5218 and Hufford, 2008). A recent study applied these techniques to the study of HAI and found
5219 that the presence of, and level of interaction with companion animals was associated with
5220 participants' current affective state (Janssens et al., 2020). Using these types of
5221 assessments more broadly in HAI research may provide insight into how people naturally
5222 interact with companion animals (inclusive of ornamental fishes) in different settings, and
5223 how these interactions influence well-being. In addition, as very little research has
5224 considered the influence of companion animals on cognitive outcomes, particularly among
5225 adult populations, it may be of interest to apply ecological momentary assessments to
5226 examine whether and how HAI influences cognition.

5227 Finally, the negative aspects of companion animal guardianship require greater
5228 consideration. As discussed, a small number of guardians expressed very negative attitudes
5229 regarding the impact of their companion animals on their well-being during the pandemic,

5230 and it was clear that companion animals were considered a source of stress and distraction
5231 for some people working from home. In order to fully understand the links between HAI and
5232 human well-being, it is important to understand these negative experiences. An associated
5233 issue relates to the presence of social desirability and self-selection biases in HAI research;
5234 if people know the study relates to companion animals, they will be more motivated to
5235 participate where their attitudes towards companion animals are positive (Friedmann and
5236 Gee, 2019). Although often difficult to achieve in HAI research (Serpell et al., 2017,
5237 Friedmann and Gee, 2019), blinding participants to the true study aims until completion of
5238 the research may help to alleviate this issue. Furthermore, blinding may lead to a sample
5239 more balanced between companion animal guardians and non-guardians; blinding was not
5240 used in Chapter 5 and the resulting sample comprised 84% guardians, a composition similar
5241 to that observed in other research (e.g. Ratschen et al., 2020), whereas blinding was used in
5242 Chapter 6 and guardians accounted for only 53% of the sample.

5243 **7.5 Conclusions**

5244 The research presented in this thesis provides little convincing evidence that engagement
5245 with ornamental fishes influences human well-being. Although it is clear that people believe
5246 watching fishes is relaxing, whether this leads to quantifiable effects remains to be seen.
5247 Evidence indicates that the experience of engaging with fishes is a varied one. Some feel a
5248 connection with the animals which goes beyond the visual dimension and indicates a level of
5249 emotional attachment; others are quite dismissive of the fishes and view aquaria primarily as
5250 decoration. The key implications of these findings are twofold. Firstly, the nature of the
5251 human-fish relationship is currently unclear, and so to fully understand whether and how
5252 interaction with ornamental fishes influences human well-being, research must first examine
5253 how people engage with ornamental fishes in different settings. Secondly, the dismissive
5254 attitude towards fishes may have implications for ornamental fish welfare if people view
5255 fishes as inferior to other companion animal types; this requires further investigation.
5256 Although guardians overwhelmingly had positive perceptions regarding the influence of

5257 companion animals on human well-being during the pandemic, there was again little
5258 evidence of quantifiable effects; level of engagement with dogs and cats was related to
5259 some well-being outcomes, and so requires further consideration in future research. Both
5260 studies conducted during the pandemic (Chapters 5 and 6) also highlighted that companion
5261 animals could be a source of stress or worry for their guardians, which may partially account
5262 for the mixed results in HAI research. Future studies should aim to examine how these
5263 additional stresses might impact the relationship between companion animal guardianship
5264 and well-being.

5265

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Appendices

Appendix A: Protocol for study “The role of fish aquaria for people with dementia living in care homes: A mixed methods study”

This study was approved by the School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland (Ref: 3779), the Mars Research Review Board, and the Scotland A NHS Research Ethics Committee for Adults with Incapacity (Ref: 18/SS/0134). The protocol was registered with Research Registry (Ref: researchregistry5331). At the time of the first COVID-19 lockdown, this study was in the participant recruitment phase but was postponed and then later cancelled due to access restrictions associated with the pandemic; no participants were recruited and no data were collected.

Introduction

The biophilia hypothesis (Wilson, 1984, Kellert and Wilson, 1993) argues that because much of human evolution took place within natural environments, humans have developed a biologically based affiliation with other forms of life. This affiliation is said to have evolved because in the ancestral environment interacting with plants and animals would have aided survival through mechanisms such as resource acquisition or evasion of threats (Katcher and Wilkins, 1993). Furthermore, this connection to nature has been associated with improvements in human well-being; for example, evidence indicates that pet owners may have improved psychological and physical health in comparison to non-pet owners (Wells, 2009, c.f. Herzog, 2011). Drawing on these findings, researchers and practitioners have created animal-assisted interventions (AAI); programmes developed with the specific aim of improving human well-being through human-animal interactions.

The effectivity of AAI has been evidenced in much primary research, with benefits spanning psychological, physiological and social well-being (for example see reviews by Nimer and Lundahl, 2007, Bert et al., 2016). However, the ability to draw definitive conclusions from this body of evidence is somewhat limited by heterogeneity in study design (Kazdin, 2017). Perhaps the most salient issue within the AAI literature is the lack of clarity around the roles of different animals. While much research has focused on the role of dogs in human well-being (Nimer and Lundahl, 2007, Bert et al., 2016, Ebener and Oh, 2017), other animals such as horses are also commonly used. Beyond this, a smaller number of research studies have utilised animals such as cats, rabbits, birds and fish (Bert et al., 2016). However, it is

unclear whether the type of animal involved in the intervention will influence its overall effectivity, an issue further exacerbated by a lack of consensus around the mechanisms through which human-animal interaction supports well-being (Kazdin, 2017). From an attachment or social support perspective for example, the bond between the human and companion animal is key, and factors such as physical touch are of great importance (Julius et al., 2013). By contrast, research on restorative environments has indicated that visual exposure to nature, including wildlife, can alone lead to benefits such as improved mood and reduced physiological stress (Cracknell et al., 2016).

Understanding the role of different animals in human-animal interaction is necessary for the development of interventions tailored to specific populations or individuals. For example, while evidence supports the use of dogs in AAI, there are risks associated with this animal. A dog may cause harm through aggression, accidental injury (e.g. scratches, increased risk of falls), or the activation of allergies (Lefebvre et al., 2008, Murthy et al., 2015, Ebener and Oh, 2017). Such interventions may therefore, be unsuitable among populations with life-limiting conditions or poor health (Langfield and James, 2009). A less interactive form of human-animal interaction may be more suitable for these populations; fish aquaria may provide one such opportunity.

Early research by Cole and Gawlinski (2000) explored the possibility of using fish aquarium AAI in hospital settings. Although this pilot study found no statistically significant effect on well-being outcomes, the 10 patients involved reported positive feedback and associated the presence of fish tanks with increased relaxation. This corresponds with research which has shown that pet owners associate their animals with relaxation (Kidd and Kidd, 1999), and that viewing fish under experimental conditions is associated with a reduction in physiological stress (Katcher et al., 1983, DeSchriver and Riddick, 1990, Cracknell et al., 2016). While Cole and Gawlinski (2000) used their research as a platform from which to build a dog-assisted intervention programme, other researchers have further explored the role of fish aquaria. In laboratory experiments, fish aquaria have been associated with reduced anxiety (Buttelmann and Römpke, 2014), and increased tolerance to pain (Sanchez et al., 2015). Similarly, in a clinical setting the presence of fish tanks in waiting areas has been associated with a trend towards reduced anxiety ($p = 0.08$) for people awaiting electroconvulsive therapy treatment (Barker, Rasmussen and Best, 2003). Although very few studies have explored the effects of fish aquarium AAI over longer periods, Edwards and colleagues (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014) have demonstrated that the introduction of aquaria into specialised dementia units is associated with a reduction in the behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia, and increased

nutritional intake among residents. The current study aims to expand on these findings and further explore the role of fish aquaria for people with dementia living in care homes.

This study will build upon past research in several ways. Firstly, in previous research ratings of resident behaviour were assessed by proxy, whereas to minimise bias in the current study, direct observations of participants will be conducted. Secondly, while Edwards and colleagues (Edwards and Beck, 2002, 2013, Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014) demonstrated that the presence of an aquarium can lead to reduced symptomatology and weight gain among people with dementia, they did not directly explore the association between these two outcomes. Therefore, this study will directly examine the hypothesis proposed by these authors that the presence of an aquarium can support weight gain for people with dementia by reducing the behavioural and psychological symptoms they experience. Furthermore, although the previous authors argued that the benefits experienced by residents alluded to greater quality of life, the current study will directly assess whether residents' quality of life improves following introduction of the aquaria. Finally, the qualitative aspect of the study will explore how previous experience with companion animals – and in particular fish – can influence participants' experiences of the fish aquaria, as well as providing participants an opportunity to give feedback on the intervention. The specific objectives of this research are:

1. To assess whether the introduction of fish aquaria into care homes is associated with a reduction in agitated behaviour among residents;
2. To determine whether reductions in agitated behaviour following the introduction of fish tanks into care homes are associated with increased body weight among residents with dementia;
3. To determine whether the introduction of fish tanks into care homes leads to improved quality of life for residents with dementia;
4. To explore through qualitative methods, how previous experiences with companion animals – and in particular with fish – affect people's experiences of fish aquaria;
5. To identify through qualitative methods, barriers and facilitators to the use of fish aquaria in a care home environment.

These objectives will be explored through a mixed methods study consisting of a within-subjects ("pre-post-test") intervention trial (objective 1-3), followed by semi-structured interviews with residents and other relevant stakeholders (objectives 4 and 5). It is hypothesised that agitated behaviour will significantly reduce, and body weight will significantly increase following introduction of the fish aquaria. Furthermore, it is hypothesised that there will be a direct relationship between these two variables, such that those who experience the greatest reduction in agitation will have the greatest gains in body

weight. Finally, it is hypothesised that quality of life will significantly increase from baseline to post-intervention.

Methods

Design

A sequential, mixed methods study will be conducted to explore the effectiveness of using fish aquaria to improve quality of life for people with dementia living in a care home in the West of Scotland. The study will last twelve months in total. Following participant recruitment (months one to three), a within-subjects (“pre-post-test”) intervention trial will be conducted with participants’ baseline scores acting as their own controls (months four to ten); this will then be supplemented with semi-structured interviews with residents and other relevant stakeholders (months eleven and twelve). The care home has three residential units and all three units will take part in the study. The intervention will consist of a standardised 54l tropical freshwater aquarium installed within a communal area of each residential unit.

Quantitative data collection

Participants and recruitment

Participants will consist of residents from a single care home within the West of Scotland, providing care to older adults with dementia and/or physical disabilities. Residents will be eligible to participate if they have a diagnosis of dementia; there will be no limitations on the type or severity of the dementia, but this information will be collected as part of the research. There will also be no limitations on the age of residents, however the care home only provides bed for those aged greater than 65 years. Residents will be excluded where: 1) they have been resident in the care home for a period of less than three months at the beginning of the study, as these residents may be experiencing elevated levels of stress due to the change of circumstance, so may not be representative of the care home population as a whole; or 2) they are registered blind, as visual exposure is a key element of the fish aquaria, so these residents are unlikely to experience the intervention in the same way as sighted residents. Previous research using a fish aquaria among people with dementia has demonstrated an effect size of $d_z = 0.43$ (Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014); using this as an estimation, power analysis in G*Power (Faul et al., 2007) indicates that a minimum of $n = 35$ participants are required to achieve 80% power when $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, to account for attrition at 10% the current study will aim to recruit a target of $n = 39$ participants (although the sample may be larger, depending on the level of interest in participation, maximum sample size based on capacity of care: $n = 90$).

A process consent approach will be used (Dewing, 2007). First, the researcher will liaise with the care home manager to determine which residents meet the inclusion criteria and have the capacity to give informed consent. For any residents who lack capacity, informed consent will be obtained from their welfare attorney or guardian, or nearest relative (hereafter “proxy”) in line with the Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act. First brief leaflets will be circulated to residents, family members and care home staff *via* the care home, to make people aware of the research. For the same purpose, posters will also be provided for the care home to display. Potential participants or proxies will then be invited to an information session during which the researcher will inform them about the study and answer any questions they may have; they will also take examples of the measures which will be used in the study to enhance understanding of the procedures, and demonstrate the fish tank set-up using a video of a similar aquarium. In the invitation, potential participants and proxies will be provided with a participant/proxy information sheet outlining the study, along with an expression of interest form which can be returned to the researcher either at the information session, or later *via* the care home (expression of interest forms will be stored securely in a locked filing cabinet at UWS for the duration of the study after which they will be confidentially destroyed). The researcher will then individually contact those participants/proxies who express an interest to answer any additional questions and obtain informed consent. In all cases, the care home and the person giving consent will be provided with a copy of the consent form. For residents who lack capacity, once informed consent has been obtained from a proxy, the researcher will approach the residents directly to discuss their participation; an easy-read information sheet and the same props as above (example measures and fish aquarium video) will be used to facilitate this process where appropriate. During these initial discussions, and through speaking to staff/family members, the researcher will establish a basis for consent, and an understanding of how each resident communicates well- or ill-being. This process will be documented by the researcher to provide evidence of consent. Participant’s willingness to participate will then be assessed in an ongoing process throughout the study, and if there are any changes in residents’ willingness to participate or their well-being, the researcher will re-evaluate consent and document this process. The researcher will also regularly discuss the research with staff members from the care home, giving them the opportunity to feedback any issues with residents’ well-being arising due to their participation in the research. The researcher will reserve the right to withdraw participants from the study if it is deemed that participation is compromising their well-being.

Changes in capacity

If a participant loses capacity during the study, continuing consent will be assumed, and the resident will remain in the study unless the researcher identifies changes in their willingness to participate. An appropriate proxy will be informed of their participation in the study and any objections will be considered in light of the participant's original decision and their current willingness to participate. If it is deemed to be in the best interests of the participant, they will be removed from the study. Where a participant is withdrawn from the study, all data up until the point of withdrawal will be retained. If there is a substantial amendment to the protocol, informed consent will be obtained from a proxy and consent will be obtained from the resident using the process consent approach outlined above. If consent/assent is not obtained, the participant will be removed from the study, but all data collected up until the point at which the amendment came into effect will be retained. It is also possible, although unlikely, that a resident may recover capacity during the study. In such cases the researcher will seek informed consent directly from the resident; they will discuss the research with the resident, and inform them that their proxy provided informed consent and that they also agreed to participate themselves. The resident will be provided with a recovered capacity information sheet, which may be explained to them verbally if more appropriate, and will be asked to complete a consent form. Proxies will be informed of this possibility prior to giving consent on behalf of the resident. If a resident with recovered capacity does not give fully informed consent, they will be withdrawn from the study and all data collected about them will be confidentially destroyed.

Intervention

A 54-litre home aquarium will be installed within a common area of each residential unit during month two of the study and will remain as a permanent feature until the end of the study. The tanks will be set up and the start of the month, but will remain empty for two weeks to allow for maturation of the filter and to perform water checks. The same aquarium set up will be used within each unit; it will be equipped with an internal filter, heater, and thermometer, and will contain with two inches of gravel, five plastic plants and a decorative rock. Each tank will be stocked with tropical freshwater species that have the same water quality requirements and are suited to being held in a community tank, specifically: five corydoras catfish, six zebrafish, and six variatus platys. The researcher will take responsibility for maintaining the tanks and will assess water quality, clean the tanks, and perform water changes on a weekly basis. Each care home manager will be asked to ensure that the fish are fed and monitor the water quality; they will be given written and verbal instructions on the correct procedures and will have the researcher's contact details should

any problems arise. Residents will be permitted to assist with feeding the fish if it is deemed safe for them to do so by a member of staff and provided they are supervised by a staff member at all times. When not in use, all food and other equipment relating to the aquarium will be stored safely away from residents.

Outcomes

Demographic details

The following demographic information will be collected about each participant: age in years, gender, ethnicity, marital status, severity and type of dementia, Mini-Mental State Examination Score (MMSE), medication usage, and previous pet ownership. This data will be collected through a combination of a demographic questionnaire completed by the resident (or if necessary, a suitable proxy), and information provided by the care home.

Agitation

Participants' levels of agitation will be measured using the Agitation Behaviour Mapping Instrument (ABMI; Cohen-Mansfield, Werner and Marx, 1989). This measure consists of 14-items relating to physical and verbal indicators of agitation (e.g. pacing, complaining). Participants are observed in three-minute intervals, during which the researcher notes the number of times each behaviour occurs, up to a total of ten times. Participants are then given an overall agitation score, consisting of the total score from all items (max = 140). Previously, the ABMI has been found to have an inter-rater reliability of 93% (Cohen-Mansfield, Werner and Marx, 1989). As video recording is prohibited in the care home environment (and is considered intrusive by the researchers) observations will be made in situ. Observations will be made once weekly throughout the study. One observer will conduct all observations, with a second observer who is blind to the aims of the study present during a minimum of 25% of observations so that inter-rater reliability can be conducted.

Quality of life

Residents' quality of life will be assessed using the DEMQOL and the DEMQOL-Proxy (Smith et al., 2005, 2007) at baseline (month one) and six-month follow-up (month seven). The DEMQOL is an interview administered patient reported outcome measure, designed to assess health-related quality of life in people with dementia. It consists of 28 items covering feelings (e.g. "in the last week, have you felt cheerful?"), memory (e.g. "in the last week, how worried have you been about forgetting who people are?"), and everyday life (e.g. "in the last week, how worried have you been about not having enough company?"), plus an item enquiring about overall quality of life. Participant responses range from "a lot" to "not at all",

and are indicated using a printed response card. The researcher will conduct the DEMQOL in a quiet area of the care home, with a relative present if desired by the resident, and following the instruction manual provided by the authors (https://www.bsms.ac.uk/_pdf/cds/interviewer-manual.pdf). The DEMQOL has been demonstrated to have good internal consistency and test-retest reliability, and moderate validity for people with mild/moderate dementia (Smith et al., 2007) but high levels of missing data for people with severe dementia have precluded testing of psychometric properties among this population. The DEMQOL-Proxy is a complementary, 31-item outcome measure answered by a caregiver (in this study a family member or a staff member from the care home) and routinely used in conjunction with the DEMQOL. Administration follows the same procedure as the DEMQOL. The DEMQOL-Proxy has been found to have psychometric properties which are comparable to other available proxy-reported measures of health-related quality of life in people with dementia (Smith et al., 2005, 2007). More recently, research has demonstrated that the assessments using DEMQOL and DEMQOL-Proxy total scores have excellent reliability, thus total scores will be used in this study (Chua et al., 2016).

Routinely collected data

At the end of the study, the care home will share routinely collected data with the researcher. This will consist of participants' body weight (kg), body mass index (BMI), and Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool (MUST) Score. Data will be shared for the duration of the intervention trial (total seven months). Details of incidents/accidents occurring in the care home for the same period will also be shared, and information about meal plans will also be provided to give context to the findings; however, this information will not relate to specific participants.

Engagement with the intervention

Throughout the intervention period the care home staff will record when participating residents assist in feeding the fish, using a purpose-developed data collection form. As involvement in the care of the animals is indicative of greater engagement with the intervention, this data will be used to assess whether a resident's level of engagement influences the effectiveness of the intervention. It will also be used to determine whether levels of engagement change over time.

Procedure

The intervention trial will be conducted over a seven-month period (months four to ten); the first month will be the baseline period and the intervention will be introduced during the second month. Agitation will be assessed weekly during the study. Participants will be

selected using a random number generator and observed for a period of three minutes, after which the researcher(s) will complete additional details regarding the context of the observations (e.g. number of people, time of day) and rest briefly before commencing observation of the next participant. Using this procedure, around 12 observations can be completed per hour; therefore, it is estimated that each observation session will last approximately 1-1.5 hours in each unit to ensure that all participants can be observed once during each session. All observations will take place within the communal area of the care home containing the fish aquarium, and the times/days of observation sessions will be agreed with the care home manager in advance. Quality of life will be assessed once during the first month and again during the final month (i.e. at six-month follow-up) using the DEMQOL and DEMQOL-Proxy; the demographic questionnaire will be administered during the baseline phase only. Throughout the study, routine data will be collected by the care home as per standard care⁸, and at the end of the study the care home will share the above outlined data with the researcher. Data will be shared in person identifiable format (either *via* a single hardcopy or on an encrypted USB drive) but will be pseudo-anonymised by the researcher at the earliest opportunity, after which the person identifiable copy will be confidentially destroyed.

Qualitative data collection

Participants and recruitment

Interviews will be conducted with residents, family members and staff members after completion of the intervention trial (months eleven and twelve). The purpose of these interviews will be to gain a more in-depth insight into the effects of the fish aquaria, and give residents and other relevant stakeholders an opportunity to voice their opinions on the intervention.

Residents

Residents will be eligible to participate in an interview if they meet the criteria for intervention trial (see above). As interviews will take place after the intervention trial, residents (or proxies) cannot make an informed decision as to whether they would like to participate in an interview at commencement of the study. Therefore, consent for interviews will be obtained at a more appropriate time and separately from other aspects of data collection. A process consent approach, as outlined above, will be used. Residents who are able to give informed consent will be given an information sheet during month seven of the study and asked to

⁸ Data is collected by the care home weekly for residents with a MUST score of 0, and weekly for those with a MUST score of 1 or 2 or greater.

inform the researcher or a member of staff if they are interested in participating; the researcher will then arrange with the resident a suitable time for the interview (commencing month eight), and informed consent will be obtained immediately prior to the interview. For residents who lack capacity but are able to engage in an interview with the researcher, informed consent will first be obtained from a proxy. The proxy will be provided with an information sheet during month seven of the study and asked to consider whether they will give consent on behalf of the resident. If consent is obtained, the researcher will discuss the interview with the resident, providing easy-read information where appropriate, and will establish whether they are happy to take part. If the resident agrees, the researcher will arrange with them a suitable time for the interview; consent will be re-evaluated immediately before the interview. Again, this process will be documented by the researcher. Interviews will be audio recorded with the permission of the resident and/or proxy, otherwise notes will be taken throughout.

Family members and care home staff

Family and staff members will be informed about the study prior to the commencement of data collection and will have the opportunity to ask questions, express any concerns, and complete an expression of interest form. However, formal recruitment will not commence until month seven of the study. At this stage potential participants will be provided with an information sheet inviting them to participate in an interview with the researcher; this will be provided *via* the care home or directly by the researcher where an individual has already expressed an interest in participation. Family members will be eligible to participate if their relative has a diagnosis of dementia, had been living in unit for a minimum of three months prior to commencement of the study, and is not registered blind. Staff members will be eligible to participate if they are directly involved in residents care or hold a managerial/supervisory role; auxiliary staff members such as catering staff or cleaners will be excluded. The researcher will arrange a suitable time for interview with interested participants and they will be conducted either *via* telephone or in person at the care home. Written informed consent will be obtained from all participants immediately prior to the interview (or earlier if the interview is to be conducted *via* telephone, with verbal consent obtained immediately before the interview); with permission of the participant the interview will be audio recorded otherwise notes will be taken throughout.

There are no firm rules regarding sample sizes in qualitative research, however previous literature has documented that evidence of meta-themes can be found in as few as six interviews, and data saturation in around twelve (Guest, Bunce and Johnson, 2006).

Therefore, the current research will aim to recruit 12-18 participants, split approximately evenly among residents, relatives, and staff members.

Procedure

Interviews will be conducted in months eleven and twelve of the study. They will take a semi-structured format and will be audio recorded with the permission of participants; otherwise notes will be taken throughout. Separate interview schedules will be used for each group. To ensure the interview schedules meet the needs of the research, the first interview in each group will be used as a pilot. After each of these interviews, the researcher will review the relevant interview schedule and assess whether substantial changes are required; if necessary, the schedule will be amended and relevant ethical approvals for these amendments will be obtained. Resident interviews will focus on past experiences with companion animals, experiences and opinions of the fish aquaria, and how it compares to other forms of animal-assisted intervention (e.g. dog-visitation programmes). Family member interviews will explore any effects of the intervention they have observed in their relative, and their own opinions on the utility of fish aquaria. Staff member interviews will explore any benefits to the use of fish aquaria both for residents and themselves, but will also consider any barriers to having fish aquaria in a care home setting. The semi-structured format of the interviews will also allow the researcher to explore other areas of interest which are highlighted by the participant. All interviews will be audio recorded with the permission of the participant and will be transcribed verbatim for analysis.

Proposed analysis

Quantitative data analysis

All quantitative data will be analysed using SPSS version 25 and/or R Studio. The following is given as an indication of the planned statistical analyses; however, the final statistical protocol may be amended following inspection of the quality and completeness of the data. The researcher will examine the data to assess the level of missing data and the presence of outliers, and ensure the data meets the assumptions of the proposed statistical analyses. If any issues are identified steps will be taken to rectify these, such as the imputation of missing values using an appropriate imputation method; removal of outliers where they represent non-legitimate data; or use of non-parametric tests where the assumptions of parametric tests are violated.

Participant characteristics

Descriptive statistics will be used to examine participant characteristics and baseline scores. The comparability of these demographics will also be explored across the three units; if

differences are apparent across the three units, the analytical protocol may be amended to incorporate this variable and investigate whether these differences are associated with differences in intervention outcomes.

Intervention effects

Data will be analysed using both “last case carried forward” and “completer’s only” methods. In the last case carried forward method, the last data point for any participants who drop out part way through the study will be carried forward and used in the analysis, whereas these participants will be excluded from the completer’s only analysis.

Scores for each of the dependent variables will be calculated as follows. Agitation will be calculated for each month of the intervention as the mean score from all assessments conducted within that period (min = 0, max = 140); inter-rater reliability will be assessed using the intra-class correlation coefficient (ICC). Scores for quality of life will be calculated according to the method outlined by the authors; the positively worded items will be reverse scored, and a total score will be calculated from all items (DEMQOL: min = 28, max = 112; DEMQOL-Proxy: min = 31, max = 124). Where insufficient participants are able to engage with the researcher to complete the DEMQOL, only the DEMQOL-Proxy will be used in the analysis. For body weight a score will be obtained for each month of the intervention from the data shared by the care home (if body weight data is of insufficient quality, body-mass index (BMI) or malnutrition universal screening tool (MUST) scores may be used as an alternative).

Separate one-way repeated measures ANOVAs will be conducted to examine whether there is a significant changes in each dependent variable across the course of the study. Where a significant change is observed, Bonferroni adjusted comparisons will be conducted between sequential time periods (e.g. month one to month two, month two to month three etc.) to determine the nature of these effects. As quality of life will only be measured at two time points, a paired *t*-test will be used to examine whether there is a significant change from baseline to six-month follow-up. Standardised effect sizes and 95% confidence intervals will also be reported.

The relationship between agitation and weight gain

A multiple linear regression model will be conducted to investigate the hypothesis that increases in body weight are directly associated with a reduction in agitated behaviour. The change in body weight from baseline to six-month follow-up will be used as the dependent variable, with the change in agitation over the same period will be used as the predictor variable. Additional predictor variables to be included in the analysis will be age, gender,

severity of dementia, medication usage and previous pet/fish ownership, as it is recognised that these variables may also influence the effectivity of the intervention.

Qualitative data analysis

Data collected *via* interviews will be analysed using the Braun and Clarke (2006) method for inductive thematic analysis. This involves a six-step process of: familiarisation with the data; generating initial codes, searching for themes, refining themes, defining and naming themes, and writing the report. Familiarisation with the data will be achieved *via* verbatim transcription of the interviews and repeated readings of these transcripts. The entire data set will then be subject to initial coding, whereby extracts of data are assigned codes which identify features of the data; this is an iterative process which is likely to require revisiting and recoding earlier coded transcripts. The researcher will then seek to identify patterns in the data to develop an initial set of candidate themes; these will then be refined by first checking whether all data coded within these themes forms a coherent pattern, and then working through the entire dataset again to identify any data missed during early coding. Finally, the themes will be defined and named so that the essence of each theme is clear and supported by extracts from the data.

The findings from the quantitative and qualitative aspects of this study will be triangulated during the interpretation stage of the study.

Appendix B: Protocol for study “Fish aquaria in nurseries: A mixed methods study”

This study was approved by the School of Health and Life Sciences Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland (Ref: 8513) and the Mars Research Review Board. At the time of the first COVID-19 lockdown, a small amount of data had been collected for Part 1 (survey), and gatekeeper permissions had been obtained from two nurseries for Parts 2 and 3 (experimental trials and follow-up interviews). The study was postponed and later cancelled due to access restrictions associated with the pandemic; no participants were recruited and no data were collected for Parts 2 and 3.

Introduction

Evidence indicates that the presence of animals in educational settings is beneficial for cognitive, social and emotional development among children (Brelsford et al., 2017, Gee, Griffin and McCardle, 2017). For example, the presence of a dog has been associated with improvements in aspects of cognition such as reading ability, attention, and concentration (Hediger and Turner, 2014, Hall, Gee and Mills, 2016), as well as improvements in behaviour and social interaction (Kotrschal and Ortbauer, 2003). Similarly, an 8-week intervention involving guinea pigs in the classroom was associated with greater social functioning among both typically developing children and those with autism spectrum disorders (O’Haire et al., 2013, 2014). In a series of studies conducted with pre-schoolers, Gee and colleagues found that the presence of a therapy dog was associated with faster execution of motor tasks without a compromise to accuracy (Gee, Harris and Johnson, 2007), greater adherence to instructions when undertaking tasks requiring modelling of behaviour (Gee et al., 2009), and improved performance on a range of cognitive tasks (Gee, Church and Altobelli, 2010, Gee, Belcher, et al., 2012, Gee, Gould, et al., 2012). Furthermore, the dog’s presence was associated with fewer prompts during completion of an object recognition task, suggesting the presence of the animal is not a distraction to the child (Gee, Crist and Carr, 2010).

Most of this research has been conducted with animals that interact with children in a physical capacity; a recent systematic review regarding animal-assisted interventions in the classroom found that of 25 articles, 21 involved dogs and the others involved small animals such as rabbits and guinea pigs (Brelsford et al., 2017). However, there are risks associated with such approaches; the animal may cause harm to the child through aggression,

transmission of zoonoses, or accidental injury (e.g. scratches, causes trips/falls), individuals may have allergies or phobias of the animal, and the welfare of the animal may be compromised by its involvement in the activity (e.g. inappropriate behaviours from the children, failure of handler to provide sufficient water, stress caused by continuous contact with the children).

Fish aquaria may be an alternative option where other forms of human-animal interaction are inappropriate. Research from the US indicates that fish are the most common classroom pet (American Humane Society, 2015), but no published research to date (to our knowledge) has been conducted to investigate the effects of fish aquaria in school or nursery environments. In adults, interacting with fish in aquaria has been associated with many positive outcomes, such as reduced anxiety (Buttelmann and Römpke, 2014), increased relaxation (Riddick, 1985), and fewer problem behaviours among people with dementia (Edwards, Beck and Lim, 2014), so it is likely that the presence of fish aquaria in classroom settings may be beneficial for the well-being and learning of children. Furthermore, as interacting with fish in aquaria is a largely visual activity, there is a lesser risk of harm than when interacting with other animals; although there is a very small risk of *Mycobacterium marinum* infection, this requires contact with the fish or water, and so can be minimised by wearing gloves and through good hygiene practices (and should not be an issue for the children, who will not be placing their hands in the water). The lack of physical contact also reduces the likelihood that children can behave inappropriately towards the animal, and ensuring the welfare needs of fish are fully met requires a lesser time commitment than for other types of companion animal.

It is important to acknowledge however, that caring for ornamental fish does require specialist knowledge on the part of the responsible adult(s), and many animal welfare organisations recommend *against* keeping companion animals (of any kind) in classrooms, because the noisy/busy environment may be detrimental to their welfare; alternatives such as soft toys, videos, or observing wildlife in their natural environment are instead endorsed. Furthermore, several studies have failed to find an effect of interacting with fish in aquaria on human well-being outcomes (see Clements et al. (2019) for overview). This may be due to the nature of human-fish interactions, which are typically more passive than interactions with animals such as dogs. Therefore, it is important to understand how the effect of interacting with fish in a nursery setting may differ according to the level of interaction. Thus, the current research aims are:

1. To identify the prevalence of nurseries in the Glasgow and West Scotland areas that keep ornamental fish and understand how these fish are cared for in the nursery environment;
2. To investigate whether the presence of ornamental fish in nurseries leads to improved behaviour and cognitive performance among pre-school aged children, relative to a non-live alternative (toy aquarium), and standard practice;
3. To investigate whether increasing the level of interaction between the children and the fish leads to greater effects on behaviour and cognitive performance;
4. To explore the experiences of children and staff members with regards to the presence of ornamental fish in a nursery environment.

Methods

A mixed methods study will be conducted to explore the potential role of fish aquaria in nurseries. This will be conducted in three stages (Figure 1). First a survey will be conducted to identify the proportion of nurseries in the Glasgow and West Scotland⁹ areas that currently keep ornamental fish, and understand how these fish are cared for in the nursery setting. Two nurseries that do not currently keep ornamental fish will then be purposively sampled to participate in Parts 2 and 3. Part 2 will consist of two experimental trials (one in each nursery) to assess (a) whether the presence of a fish tank has an influence upon behaviour and cognitive performance among a sample of young children in a nursery environment, and (b) whether increasing the level of interaction between the children and fish leads to greater effects on behaviour and cognitive performance. Part 3 will involve semi-structured interviews with children and staff members to gain a more in-depth insight into their experiences of having fish tanks within the nurseries.

Figure 1: Overview of study design

⁹Consisting of the following council areas: Argyll & Bute (Dumbarton only), East Dunbartonshire, East Renfrewshire, Inverclyde, North Ayrshire, Renfrewshire, West Dunbartonshire, Glasgow City, and South Lanarkshire (Rutherglen only).

Part 1

Participants and recruitment

Private and voluntary nurseries in the Glasgow and West Scotland areas will be eligible to participate in the first stage of this research; local authority nurseries will be excluded. A list of eligible nurseries in these areas will be collated using online resources (e.g. local authority websites, scottishnurseries.com, daynurseries.co.uk). A preliminary search using daynurseries.co.uk suggests that there is a total of around 240 nurseries in these areas. A sample size calculation conducted *via* <https://www.qualtrics.com/blog/calculating-sample-size/> indicates that for a population of this size, 69 participants are required to achieve a 10% margin of error. Therefore, a random sample of 100 nurseries (stratified by area) will initially be approached to take part; if fewer than the target number of nurseries (N = 69) respond, nurseries will be selected at random and invited to participate until a sufficient sample size is achieved. This target may be amended depending on the final number of nurseries identified, but is unlikely to exceed 100 (e.g. for a population of 500, 81 participants would be required to achieve a 10% margin of error).

Nurseries will be recruited *via* email or telephone. Where an email address is available, a standardised email will be sent by the researcher to each nursery asking them to consider taking part in the survey. The email will include the Participant Information Sheet and a link to the survey online; the option to complete the survey *via* telephone or on paper will also be available. After approximately two weeks a reminder email will be sent to each nursery. Where no email address can be identified for a nursery, they will be invited to take part *via* telephone; a member of the research team will contact a key informant (usually the manager) from each nursery, and ask if they are interested in participating in a short survey to investigate the role of fish aquaria in nurseries. Interested individuals will be sent a copy of the study information and a link to the online survey *via* email; if any participants indicate that they would rather complete the survey *via* mail or telephone, these options will also be provided. For surveys completed online or on paper, completion of the survey will be deemed as consent to participate and this will be specified in the study information provided to participants; for those completed *via* telephone, the researcher will use a set script to obtain verbal consent and complete a record of consent. At the end of the survey, nurseries that have indicated they do not currently keep ornamental fish will be asked if they are interested in taking part in further research (although it will be made clear that an expression of interest does not guarantee that their nursery will be selected to take part).

Design and procedure

The survey will be administered online, *via* telephone, on paper (*via* post), depending on the preference of the participant. Written study information will be provided to the participant prior to completion of the survey. Once agreeing to take part, participants will be asked to provide some details about their nursery, specifically, the location (postcode), the age range they cater for, and the number of places (either by age group or total). They will then be asked some questions regarding the presence of fish aquaria in the nursery, opinions towards/experiences of having fish aquaria in the nursery environment, and – where they have a fish tank – information regarding the fish care routine. Following completion of the survey, participants will be thanked for their participation. Any participants who have completed the questionnaire on paper will return this to the researcher *via* post, in the envelope provided. Participants from nurseries that do not currently have ornamental fish will also be asked if they would like to participate in further research and if so, provide contact details for the researcher.

Parts 2 and 3

Participants and recruitment

Potential nurseries will be identified in Part 1, whereby nurseries that do not currently keep fish will be able to indicate whether they are interested in participating in further research. Two nurseries will be purposively selected, based primarily on logistical factors (i.e. whether the size of the nursery is likely to satisfy sample size requirements (see below), and the locality of the nursery to the researcher's place of work). The researcher will then contact the nurseries to discuss the study further and, if they would like to participate, arrange an initial visit to ensure there is a safe location to install the aquarium that does not create a hazard or compromise the welfare of the fish. If the location is appropriate, local gatekeeper permission will be obtained prior to commencing participant recruitment.

All children attending the nurseries, who are aged between three and five years when they start the study will be eligible to take part. Information packs will be supplied to parents/carers *via* the nursery to inform them of the study; these will contain a letter inviting the parent/carer to consider giving permission for the researcher to invite their child to take part, a Parent/Carer Information Sheet giving more detail about the nature of the study, a consent form, a demographic questionnaire, and an envelope. The researcher's contact details will be available on the information sheet for parents/carers who may wish to ask questions. Parents/carers who are willing to give permission for their child to take part will be asked to complete the consent form and the questionnaire, then return them to the nursery in the envelope provided, where they will be collected by the researcher. A copy of the

consent form will be retained by the parent/carer, and another will be given to the nursery for their records. As this research involves very young children, it is not deemed appropriate to obtain written informed consent from participants. Instead, consent will be assessed verbally in an ongoing process throughout the study. First, a member of staff from the nursery will tell each child that the researcher wants to talk to them, and ask if they are happy with this. If they agree, the researcher will then use a set script to explain to the child that they are there to collect information about them, and that their parent/carer has given permission for the researcher to speak to them, but that this does not mean they have to agree to speak to the researcher. If the child does agree to speak to the researcher, consent will be assessed in an ongoing process at each stage of the research, and the child may withdraw at any stage if they wish. The researcher will also monitor the behaviour of the child throughout each session to ensure their well-being is not compromised as a result of their participation. Where a child declines to participate in any aspect of the research, or withdraws from the study, the researcher will make a record of this.

With respect to the quantitative aspect of this study, power analyses conducted in G*Power indicate that for a medium sized effect, 28 participants are required to achieve sufficient statistical power for Part 2a and 24 participants for Part 2b. As no previous research has been conducted with fish tanks in a nursery setting, these estimates will be used as a basis for the target sample size in each study. With respect to the qualitative aspect of this study, data analysis will commence as soon as the first interview is complete, and will be conducted in an ongoing process as more data is collected. Data collection will cease once a point of theoretical saturation has been achieved. There are no firm rules about the number of participants required for qualitative research, but research suggests that themes can be identified in as few as six interviews (Guest, Bunce and Johnson, 2006). Therefore, it is anticipated that interviews will be conducted with $n = 6-12$ children.

Staff members from the nursery will be invited to participate either directly by the researcher or *via* the manager of the nursery; they will be given a Participant Information Sheet and asked to let the researcher know if they would like to take part. A minimum of one week will be given between provision of the Participant Information Sheet and the interview, with written informed consent obtained immediately before the interview commences. If any interviews are conducted by telephone, written informed consent will be obtained at an earlier stage and verbal consent will be obtained at the start of the interview. A target of $n = 6$ interviews will be conducted with staff members.

Intervention and comparators

Live fish aquarium

Fifty-four litre home aquaria will be used, each containing a selection of tropical freshwater fishes: five *corydoras* catfish, six *variatus* platy and six zebrafish. Each tank will also be equipped with an internal heater, filter and thermometer, an automatic feeder, and various pieces of enrichment (five plastic plants, a decorative rock, and approximately two inches of gravel). A fish tank will be installed in each nursery at the beginning of the study and will remain present until data collection is complete. A suitable position will be agreed between the researcher and manager of the nursery, so that a workspace can be set up nearby without creating a hazard or affecting the welfare of the fish. The aquarium lights will be set on 12-hour light/dark cycle, and the fish will be fed twice daily using the automatic feeder; this will minimise staff burden and prevent over/underfeeding. If staff from the nursery express an interest in allowing the children to be involved in feeding the fish, this will be permitted provided the child is supervised at all times by a staff member; the researcher will give the nursery staff instructions regarding feeding, and if any concerns are raised regarding over/under feeding the researcher will revert to using the automatic feeder. The researcher will perform tank maintenance on a weekly basis, and an emergency contact number will be given to a manager of the nursery, so they are able to alert the researcher promptly should any issues arise. During testing sessions, the researcher will set up a workspace close to the fish tank, such that it will be visible to the participant throughout the session.

Toy fish aquarium

An aquarium containing toy fish will be constructed and positioned in the same location as the live fish aquarium during applicable sessions. The aquarium will be similar in size to the aquarium containing the live fish and will be designed to be similar in appearance (e.g. containing plants, rocks, gravel). Toy fish will be suspended from the lid of the aquarium, to mimic the distribution of live fish throughout the body of water in the live fish aquarium. The toy fish will be similar to the live fish in size and number, and wherever possible in appearance. During sessions involving the toy fish, the live fish aquarium will be covered.

Control

In the control condition, the researcher and participant will be positioned in the same location as during the live fish aquarium and fish video conditions, but the tank will be covered, and the television screen will be switched off.

Outcomes

Demographic information

A purpose-developed demographic questionnaire will be used to collect the following information about participants: age, gender, ethnicity, and companion animal ownership. This questionnaire will be completed by parents on behalf of their child. The child's companion animal preference will be assessed in the first session; the researcher will show the child images of popular companion animals (dog, cat, rabbit, bird, and fish) and ask them to indicate which they like best, and which they like second best.

Cognitive performance

An object categorisation task will be conducted, based on that used by Gee, Gould, et al., (2012). The task will consist of a set of 12 toys relating to one of two environments (ocean or farm), and the child will be required to help the researcher sort each toy into the relevant category. Each set of toys will consist of six ocean-related toys and six farm-related toys; half in each category will represent animate objects (e.g. dolphin or pig) and half will represent inanimate objects (e.g. boat or tractor). Four sets of toys will be used, with a set selected at random for each child in each condition. At the start of the task, the researcher will use a set script to inform the child that they need help sorting the toys into the relevant category. They will present the child with each toy, one at a time, and ask the child "Do you think the toy [object name] comes from the farm or the ocean?" The child will be permitted to hold the toy while they decide. After each response the child will be praised and asked to place the toy in a box relating to the relevant environment. Performance will be assessed as accuracy (i.e. number of correct responses) and response latency (i.e. time from presentation of stimulus to participant response). A practice trial will then be conducted prior to the task commencing to ensure the child understands what is required.

Behaviour

Each of the experimental sessions will be video recorded with permission of the parent and child; these videos will be used to assess participants' behaviour during each session using observational techniques. An observation schedule will be developed based on previous literature and behaviours identified as being of interest by the researcher during data collection and re-watching of the videos; this is likely to include whether the child is on or off task, prosocial behaviours, antisocial behaviours, verbalisations, positive emotional responses, negative emotional response, and overt signs of anxiety (e.g. restlessness, fidgeting, nail biting, rocking). A scan sampling technique will be used, such that behaviours are assessed every 15 seconds from the start to end of the task (indicated by the first and

last teacher instructions of the session). The number of prompts (general and task-specific) given by the researcher throughout the session will also be coded from the video footage, as will the length of time taken for the child to respond during assessments (response latency). A second observer will code at least 25% of videos such that inter-rater reliability can be calculated (these videos will be selected at random from the entire dataset).

Design and procedure

Experimental trial: Part 2a

A one-way, within-subjects experimental design will be used, with three conditions: live fish aquarium, toy fish aquarium and control (no stimulus). The dependent variables will be cognitive performance and behaviour, as outlined above. Permission for the child to participate will be obtained from the parent/carer of each participant prior to the commencement of data collection, and the demographic questionnaire will also be completed and returned to the researcher at this time. Children who participate in Part 2a will complete three sessions of data collection, spaced approximately one week apart, with a different set of toys used each week. Informed consent from the child will be assessed verbally, in an ongoing process throughout the study. At the start of the first session, the child's companion animal preference will be assessed as described above. Each session will then follow the same procedure. First the researcher will ask the child if they want to take part in the session (described as a "game"); if the child agrees, they will be seated at a workstation set-up near to the fish tank. The researcher will then tell the child that they have some toys from two different locations (ocean and farm), but that these have been mixed up and need to be sorted into two separate boxes; they will then ask the child to help them sort the toys, and if they agree, the object categorisation task will be completed. Once all twelve toys have been sorted, the researcher will give the child a sticker as a small thank you for taking part.

Experimental trial: Part 2b

A two-way, within-subjects design will be used with the independent variables of condition (live fish aquarium and toy fish aquarium) and level of interaction (high and low). The dependent variables, recruitment and consent processes, collection of demographic details and assessment of companion animal preference will be identical to Part 2a. Children who participant in Part 2b will complete four sessions of data collection, spaced approximately one week apart. These sessions will be counterbalanced to account for order effects, with a different set of toys used each week. For the two sessions with a low level of interaction the procedure will be identical as for that used in Part 2a. For the two sessions with a high level of interaction, the researcher will start the task by "introducing" the fishes and saying they

like their “home” but that they are a little bored. They will then explain that the fishes would like some new toys to play with, but that they only like toys from the farm, not toys from the ocean. The researcher will then ask the child to help sort out the toys, so that they can choose one for the fishes to play with. The object categorisation task will then proceed as outlined above. At the end of the task the researcher will ask the child to choose one toy from the relevant category; the researcher will then place this in the fish tank and observe the fishes with the child as they react to the new piece of enrichment. All toys placed in the tanks will be plastic and cleaned thoroughly before use. At no point will the children be permitted to place the toys in the tank, and the researcher will make clear to each child that only an adult is allowed to do this. At the end of the session, the researcher will give the child a sticker as a small thank you for taking part.

Interviews: Part 3

Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with children and staff members from the nurseries. Permission for the researcher to ask the child to participate in an interview will be obtained from a parent/carer at the beginning of the study, and verbal assent will be obtained from the child immediately before the interview commences. Interviews will take place within the nursery, near to the fish tank, which may be used as a visual aid/discussion point during the interview. At the start of the interview, the researcher will provide the child with coloured pens/pencils and paper, and ask them to draw a picture of their favourite animal. Once the child has drawn a picture, the researcher will then ask them what animal they have drawn, and why this animal is their favourite animal. This will lead into discussion of what they like/dislike about other animals, and in particular what they like/dislike about fish. The interview will be audio recorded with permission of the parent/carer and child, otherwise notes will be taken throughout. The researcher will ask the child if they can keep the image that is drawn and potentially include it in publications/other research outputs (i.e. “Can I keep this drawing?”, “Can I show this drawing to other people, I won’t tell them it was you who drew it?”), and the child will receive a sticker for their participation.

Staff interviews will be conducted at the nursery or *via* telephone. For interviews conducted in person, written informed consent will be obtained immediately prior to the interview; for those conducted *via* telephone, this will be obtained at an earlier stage and verbal consent will be obtained immediately before the interview commences. Interview schedules will cover participants’ experiences of having fish tanks in the nursery including the influence these have on the children in the nursery, facilitators and barriers to having fish tanks in the nursery environment, and general opinions towards the presence of animals in nurseries.

The semi-structured format will also allow the researcher to explore other areas of interest raised by the participant, or identified through responses to the initial questionnaire (Part 1).

Proposed analysis

Quantitative analyses

All quantitative data will be analysed using SPSS version 24 (or later) and/or R. The following is given as an indication of the planned statistical analyses; however, the final statistical protocol may be amended following inspection of the quality and completeness of the data. The researcher will examine the data to assess the level of missing data and the presence of outliers, and ensure the data meets the assumptions of the proposed statistical analyses. If any issues are identified steps will be taken to rectify these, such as the imputation of missing values using an appropriate imputation method; removal of outliers where they represent non-legitimate data; or use of non-parametric tests where the assumptions of parametric tests are violated.

Data collected *via* the survey will be explored using descriptive statistics to identify the number of nurseries in the Glasgow and West Scotland areas that keep ornamental fish, and the characteristics of these nurseries. Where there is sufficient data to compare the characteristics of nurseries that do and do not keep ornamental fish, independent samples *t*-tests will be used. Data collected *via* the first experimental trial (Part 2a) will be analysed using separate one-way, repeated measures ANOVA for each dependent variable; the independent variable will be condition (live fish, fish video, control). Data collected *via* the second experimental trial (Part 2b) will be analysed using separate two-way, repeated measures ANOVA for each dependent variable; the independent variables will be condition (live fish aquarium, toy fish aquarium) and level of interaction (high, low). Cognitive performance will be assessed as accuracy (number of correct responses) and response latency (time taken from presentation of target stimulus until participant's response) for the object categorisation task. Behaviour will be assessed as the number of occurrences of each relevant behaviour throughout the session; inter-rater reliability will be calculated as intraclass correlation coefficient.

Qualitative analyses

Qualitative data collected *via* the survey and interviews will be analysed using the Braun and Clarke (2006) method for inductive thematic analysis. This involves a six-step process of: familiarisation with the data; generating initial codes, searching for themes, refining themes, defining and naming themes, and writing the report. Familiarisation with the data will be achieved *via* verbatim transcription of the interviews and repeated readings of these

transcripts. The entire data set will then be subject to initial coding, whereby extracts of data are assigned codes which identify features of the data; this is an iterative process which is likely to require revisiting and recoding earlier coded transcripts. The researcher will then seek to identify patterns in the data to develop an initial set of candidate themes; these will then be refined by first checking whether all data coded within these themes forms a coherent pattern, and then working through the entire dataset again to identify any data missed during early coding. Finally, the themes will be defined and named so that the essence of each theme is clear and supported by extracts from the data.

The findings from the quantitative and qualitative aspects of this study will be triangulated during the interpretation stage of the study.

Appendix C: Data extraction form

Reviewer:

Date:

Full study reference:

General	
Author/year	
Publication type and source	
Country	
Funding	
Conflict of interest	
Study details	
Aim/objectives	
Dates of data collection	
Theoretical framework	
Methods	
Study design	
Participant recruitment	
Participants	<i>Population:</i> <i>Age:</i> <i>Sex:</i> <i>Ethnicity:</i> <i>SES:</i> <i>Total sample size:</i> <i>Sample size per condition:</i>
Intervention/Independent Variable	
Control	
Allocation to conditions	
Setting/context	

Primary outcomes	<i>Psychological outcomes (anxiety, depression, behaviour change, social interaction, etc.):</i>
	<i>Physiological outcomes (heart rate, blood pressure, motor skills etc.):</i>
Secondary outcomes (adverse events, animal welfare, attitudes)	
Brief study description	
Results	
Method of analysis	
Primary outcomes	<i>Psychological outcomes (anxiety, depression, behaviour change, social interaction, etc.):</i>
	<i>Physiological outcomes (heart rate, blood pressure, motor skills etc.):</i>
Secondary outcomes (adverse events, animal welfare, attitudes)	
Author conclusions:	
Reviewer comments:	

Appendix D: Risk of bias assessments

Quantitative intervention studies:

Study ID	Barker 2003	Buttelmann 2014	Cole 2000	Cracknell 2016	Cracknell 2017 Study 1	Cracknell 2017 Study 2
1.1 Is the source populations or source area well described?	++ Population demographics and referral source described well although the location and county should have been stated	- Undergraduate students stated but no more detail provided	+ Some description given, but lacking detail	- Source population not described beyond 'students from a University population'	- Poor description beyond "university students"	- Poor description beyond "university students"
1.2 Is the eligible population or area representative of the source population?	+ Recruitment was not well described	+ Recruitment was not described	+ Recruitment not described and the sample size was too small to be adequate, however it was a pilot study	+ Recruitment and selection not well described	+ Recruitment not well described	+ Recruitment not well described
1.3 Do the selected participants or areas represent the eligible population or area?	+ It is not clear how many of the eligible participants agreed to take part, and inclusion/exclusion criteria are not stated	+ Selection not described and percentage of potential participants who agreed to take part not given. Inclusion/ exclusion criteria not stated. Over 90% of participants were female	- Selection not well described but appears that participants were selected by the researchers which introduced bias. It is not clear how many of the selected participants agreed to participate. Inclusion/exclusion criteria were given but lacked detail	+ Selection not described and percentage who agreed to take part not stated. Inclusion/ exclusion criteria not given	+ No description of selection process and the percentage of eligible participants who agreed to take part not stated. Some inclusion/exclusion criteria given	+ No description of selection process and the percentage of eligible participants who agreed to take part not stated. Some inclusion/exclusion criteria given
2.1 How was selection bias minimised?	- Allocation intended to alternate on consecutive appointments, but in reality was determined by service demands	- Participants were placed in groups from baseline measures instead of randomisation	NA No group allocation or cross-over	- Different participants for each condition at different time points, and participants not randomised (quasi-random)	++ Order of photographs was randomised	++ Order of photographs was randomised
2.2 Were the interventions (and comparisons) well described and appropriate?	++ Interventions and control are described well	++ Three interventions described well using descriptions and images	++ Aquarium well described and image included, however the type and number of fish used could have been described	++ Excellent description of interventions provided, and stocking information given in supplementary information	++ Photographs were described and example images included	++ Photographs were described and example images included

Study ID	Barker 2003	Buttelmann 2014	Cole 2000	Cracknell 2016	Cracknell 2017 Study 1	Cracknell 2017 Study 2
2.3 Was the allocation concealed?	NA All participants experienced both conditions	- The person determining allocation strongly influenced the allocation as they determined allocation	NA No group allocation	- Each condition at a different time point so person determining group allocation could not be concealed to allocation	NA No group allocation	NA No group allocation
2.4 Were participants or investigators blind to exposure and comparisons?	+ Participants were not aware of the aim of the study, and it appears a researcher who did not collect the data evaluated the data. VAS were rescored by a blind assessor. However, nurses taking measurements were not blinded	- Participants could not be blinded due to the nature of the intervention. It is not clear whether the assessor was blinded, but unlikely	- The participants could not be blinded to the conditions, and it was not reported whether the researchers scoring were blinded, but unlikely	+ Participants blind to study aims, but assessors not blinded	+ All responses recorded electronically but not possible to blind participants	+ All responses recorded electronically but not possible to blind participants
2.5 Was the exposure to the intervention and comparison adequate?	++ Exposure time seems appropriate	+ Exposure equal in all conditions, but was only 5 minutes, which may not be sufficient	- Longest exposure was eleven days but average time on ward is two months, so not adequate (although this was a pilot)	++ Exposure time was consistent across all groups and seemed of adequate duration	+ Duration of viewing for each picture not given, but it appears the participants could look at any one image for as long as they liked. Therefore there was no standardisation for the duration of each 'intervention' (image)	+ Duration of viewing for each picture not given, but it appears the participants could look at any one image for as long as they liked. Therefore there was no standardisation for the duration of each 'intervention' (image)
2.6 Was contamination acceptably low?	+ All participants completed both conditions and the wash-out period was not stated, but due to the nature of study contamination is unlikely	+ Contamination unlikely but not explicitly stated that participants didn't take part in more than one condition, and as participants were probably known to one another they could have discussed participation	NA Only one condition	+ Contamination unlikely but not explicitly stated that participants didn't take part in more than one condition, and as participants were probably known to each other they could have discussed participation	NA Participants took part in all conditions	NA Participants took part in all conditions
2.7 Were other interventions similar in both groups?	NR Not clear whether participants took part in any other treatments which differed across sessions.	++ The intervention duration was the same in all conditions. No group received additional interventions.	NA All participants took part in all conditions.	- It is not known whether participants were treated equally in all groups, and authors acknowledged differences in contextual factors across conditions (e.g. weather, number of visitors)	++ No other interventions described and due to the short nature of the study duration (one time point) and all participants taking part in all conditions, all can be considered similar per condition	++ No other interventions described and due to the short nature of the study duration (one time point) and all participants taking part in all conditions, all can be considered similar per condition

Study ID	Barker 2003	Buttelmann 2014	Cole 2000	Cracknell 2016	Cracknell 2017 Study 1	Cracknell 2017 Study 2
2.8 Were all participants accounted for at study conclusion?	NR Drop out not reported	NR Drop out not reported	NR Drop out not reported	NR Drop out not reported	+ There is no report of drop-outs, however participants must have evaluated all images with the nature of the study protocol so it assumed all images were evaluated for those participants	+ There is no report of drop-outs, however participants must have evaluated all images with the nature of the study protocol so it assumed all images were evaluated for those participants
2.9 Did the setting reflect usual UK practice?	++ The hospital setting described could be applicable in the UK	++ University setting probably reflects UK	++ The hospital setting described could be applicable in the UK	NA Setting was a National Aquarium so not related to health treatment	NA Not a medical intervention	NA Not a medical intervention
2.10 Did the intervention or control comparison reflect usual UK practice?	NA Not a standard intervention	NA University setting	NA Not a standard intervention	NA Setting was a National Aquarium so not related to health treatment	NA Not a medical intervention	NA Not a medical intervention
3.1 Were outcome measures reliable?	+ VAS, HR and BP are standard outcomes. Reports of outcome measure validation from previous studies was included, however VAS may be subjective	+ Reliability not explicitly reported for all measures, but likely adequate	++ Reliability of the measure was described, based on reports from previous studies	++ Outcome measures seem appropriate and validity was reported from previous research for some outcome measures	- Subjective outcome measured using a Likert scale without reports of validity	- Subjective outcome measured using a Likert scale without reports of validity
3.2 Were all outcome measures complete?	- Some participants did not complete both conditions so were excluded	- Some participants were excluded because they failed to show anxiety induction	NR Missing data were not reported	+ Physiological data missing for some participants so they were excluded from those analyses. All other analyses appear complete	+ Missing data not reported but unlikely due to nature of the study	+ Missing data not reported but unlikely due to nature of the study
3.3 Were all important outcomes assessed?	++ Outcomes seemed appropriate and comprehensive	++ All outcomes appear to be appropriate	++ The outcome measures set seem appropriate to answer the research question	++ The important outcomes were assessed	++ Outcomes included seem appropriate	++ Outcomes included seem appropriate
3.4 Were outcomes relevant?	++ Outcomes seemed appropriate and set out to measure what was intended	++ All outcomes appear relevant	+ Some outcome measures seem inappropriate to the research question (e.g. sensation seeking)	++ The outcomes were relevant	+ Outcomes included seem relevant, however validated measures do exist	+ Outcomes included seem relevant, however validated measures do exist

Study ID	Barker 2003	Buttelmann 2014	Cole 2000	Cracknell 2016	Cracknell 2017 Study 1	Cracknell 2017 Study 2
3.5 Were there similar follow-up times in exposure and comparison groups?	NA No follow-up	++ All groups were treated similarly	NA Only one group	NA No follow-up	NA No follow-up	NA No follow-up
3.6 Was follow-up time meaningful?	NA No follow-up	+ A longer follow-up is unlikely to have resulted in differences in outcome, however it was not clear exactly how soon after the intervention the participants were assessed (beyond 'immediately')	- Follow-up was eleven days which is probably insufficient	NA No follow-up	NA No follow-up	NA No follow-up
4.1 Were exposure and comparison groups similar at baseline? If not, were these adjusted?	NA All participants completed both conditions	+ Authors report that groups were similar at baseline, due to allocation method. However, this data were not reported so cannot be confirmed. Also not clear if outcome measures were similar at baseline	NA All participants in the same group	- There were differences in outcome measures at baseline	NA Participants undertook all conditions which were randomised; no baseline assessment	NA Participants undertook all conditions which were randomised; no baseline assessment
4.2 Was intention to treat (ITT) analysis conducted?	NA Not relevant to this study design	NA Not relevant to this study design	NA All participants in the same group	NA Not relevant to this study design	NA Only one measurement time point and participants required to rate all images	NA Only one measurement time point and participants required to rate all images
4.3 Was the study sufficiently powered to detect an intervention effect (if one exists)?	- Power analyses were conducted on a post hoc basis which is of little value	NR No power analysis reported, although authors acknowledge potential underpowering	NR No power analysis reported	NR No power analysis reported	NR No power analysis reported	NR No power analysis reported
4.4 Were the estimates of effect size given or calculable?	NR Effect sizes were not reported	++ Effect sizes were reported for all analyses	NR Effect sizes were not reported	+ Effect sizes were reported for some, but not all, outcomes	NR Effect sizes were not reported	NR Effect sizes were not reported

Study ID	Barker 2003	Buttelmann 2014	Cole 2000	Cracknell 2016	Cracknell 2017 Study 1	Cracknell 2017 Study 2
4.5 Were the analytical methods appropriate?	+ Some concerns over analysis and whether there were multiple observations per participant, per condition, rather than average scores - this is unclear. However, covariates were pre-specified	- Statistical analysis methods not described. It appears that a one-way ANOVA was performed but this is not appropriate for the multiple groups and multiple time points	- Questionable whether the statistical methods proposed are appropriate. Confounders not adjusted for however the sample size was probably too small for this. Results were not well presented	- Data analysis seems incorrect or excessive - mixed ANOVA would be sufficient. Also questionable whether ANOVA should be used for Likert data	+ Some of the statistical tests used were incorrect/excessive and a mixed ANOVA is preferable, also questionable whether an ANOVA is appropriate for Likert type data	+ Some of the statistical tests used were incorrect/excessive and a mixed ANOVA is preferable, also questionable whether an ANOVA is appropriate for Likert type data
4.6 Was the precision of intervention effects given or calculable? Were they meaningful?	NR No confidence intervals included	+ Confidence intervals presented in graphical form for one analysis, but no values reported	NR No confidence intervals included	+ Confidence intervals provided in graphical form for most outcomes	NR No confidence intervals included	NR No confidence intervals included
5.1 Are the study results internally valid (i.e. unbiased)?	+ Some bias has been minimised but allocation was not randomised and nurses were not blinded	- Due to lack of randomisation, this study is heavily biased. Also issues with blinding and statistical analyses	- No control group and lack of blinding are significant biases	- High likelihood of confounders affecting study outcomes	++ Photographs presented in a random order and unlikely to have been influenced by other sources of bias	++ Photographs presented in a random order and unlikely to have been influenced by other sources of bias
5.2 Are the findings generalizable to the source population (i.e. externally valid)?	+ Additional participant demographics and inclusion criteria should have been included to make the findings more generalizable	- Participant detail not sufficient to determine if results generalizable. Predominantly female sample likely to skew results	- Sample size too small to be generalizable (although it was a pilot study). Recruitment and selection not well described	- There is insufficient detail about the study population to identify whether the findings are generalizable	- Not sufficient information provided to determine if externally valid	- Not sufficient information provided to determine if externally valid
Overall study grading	+	-	-	-	+	+

Study ID	DeSchrivier 1990	Edwards 2002	Edwards 2013	Edwards 2014	Katcher 1984
1.1 Is the source populations or source area well described?	++ Location and setting well described	+ Some description but lacking detail	+ Some description but lacking detail	++ Setting well described	- No details of the source population provided

Study ID	DeSchriver 1990	Edwards 2002	Edwards 2013	Edwards 2014	Katcher 1984
1.2 Is the eligible population or area representative of the source population?	+ Recruitment methods not stated and no information whether eligible population was representative	+ Recruitment was not well described	+ Recruitment was not well described	+ Recruitment was not well described	+ Recruitment method described but little information of the source or sample population
1.3 Do the selected participants or areas represent the eligible population or area?	+ Method of selection not stated and not clear what percentage agreed to participate	+ Selection was not described and although it is stated that all residents of the home were invited, we do not know what percentage agreed to participate. Inclusion/exclusion criteria not given	+ Selection was not described and although it is stated that all residents of the home were invited, we do not know what percentage agreed to participate	+ Method of selection from the eligible population not described and percentage who agreed to take part not stated. However, inclusion/exclusion criteria were stated	+ Selection process not described and percentage of potential participants who agreed to participate was not stated, but inclusion criteria explained
2.1 How was selection bias minimised?	+ Allocation was randomised but randomisation method not described	- Not clear how the control facility was selected, but unlikely to be random	NA No group allocation or cross-over	NA No group allocation and no cross-over	+ Randomised but method of randomisation not stated
2.2 Were the interventions (and comparisons) well described and appropriate?	+ Basic detail on the aquarium is provided but more description could have been included	+ Basic detail on the aquarium is provided but more description could have been included	+ The aquaria were described but more detail is needed, e.g. species	+ More detailed description needed	+ Intervention procedure was described but no description of the aquarium or poster
2.3 Was the allocation concealed?	NR Concealment was not reported	NR Concealment was not reported	NA No allocation	NA No allocation	NR Concealment was not reported
2.4 Were participants or investigators blind to exposure and comparisons?	- Neither participants nor assessors were blinded, however this would be impossible due to the nature of the study	- No blinding for the participants or researchers and staff, however this would be difficult to correct for due to the nature of the study	- No blinding for the participants or researchers and staff, however this would be difficult to correct for due to the nature of the study	- Neither participants nor investigators were blinded, although this was difficult due to the study design	+ Assessors were blinded but the participants were not; however blinding participants would not be possible due to the nature of the study

Study ID	DeSchriver 1990	Edwards 2002	Edwards 2013	Edwards 2014	Katcher 1984
2.5 Was the exposure to the intervention and comparison adequate?	+ Exposure was equal across conditions but may have been slightly short	++ Exposure time seems appropriate	++ Exposure time seems appropriate	+ Duration of the intervention probably adequate, but perhaps a little too short	++ Duration of the intervention seems appropriate
2.6 Was contamination acceptably low?	+ Contamination during testing was minimised, but all participants could access fish tank between testing sessions	++ For the one facility participating in both conditions, a 2-week washout period was used, which seems appropriate	NA There was only one condition	NA There was only one condition	+ Not explicitly stated but based on the short-term nature of the intervention this is unlikely
2.7 Were other interventions similar in both groups?	+ Duration of interventions the same, but it is not known if any participants in different groups received any additional interventions	+ The control/treatment group received longer contact with the researchers/programme due to the inclusion of the control phase, however the aquarium time was the same at all facilities	+ All participants received same study duration but different staff across each facility could have led to differences in the way participants were treated	+ All participants in the same group, however the intervention was delivered across 3 sites and it does not state whether there were any management differences between the sites	- Those in the intervention groups received additional procedures to those in the control group. Although this was part of the study it make interpretation difficult
2.8 Were all participants accounted for at study conclusion?	NR Drop out not reported	NR Drop out not reported	NR Drop out not reported	++ Drop out was reported and acceptable (<10%)	NR Drop out not reported
2.9 Did the setting reflect usual UK practice?	- Setting unlikely to reflect usual practice as was a purpose built laboratory	+ The setting appears to be similar to the UK but likely some local differences	+ The setting appears to be similar to the UK but likely some local differences	+ The setting appears to be similar to the UK but likely some local differences	++ It is unlikely that the setting varied from typical UK dental practice
2.10 Did the intervention or control comparison reflect usual UK practice?	NA Not a standard intervention.	NA Not a standard intervention.	NA Not a standard intervention.	NA Not a standard intervention	NA Not a standard intervention
3.1 Were outcome measures reliable?	+ All outcome measures seem reliable except the EMG which is known to have poor reliability scores	+ Body weight and nutritional intake can be reliable but the methods used to obtain these data were not described	+ Measures seem appropriate and staff were trained, but could still be subjective/inaccurate, especially considering environment	+ Reliability of the outcomes used was reported, however validity was not stated and not clear why measure was amended	- Methods of physiological data collection and equipment not stated. No comments on validity of the measures, and some outcomes were subjective (dentist ratings of compliance, observer ratings of anxiety)

Study ID	DeSchriver 1990	Edwards 2002	Edwards 2013	Edwards 2014	Katcher 1984
3.2 Were all outcome measures complete?	NR Missing data not reported, not clear if all participants completed all time points	+ Weight data is reported for all 62 participants but it is not clear if a full set of nutritional intake data are included	+ Weight data appears complete but it is not clear if a full set of nutritional intake data are included	+ Missing data were not explicitly reported but all participants appear to have been included in the analysis	NR Missing data not reported and it is not clear that all participants completed all data points
3.3 Were all important outcomes assessed?	++ All important outcomes assessed	+ As data collection was not well described this cannot be known. Also, in the discussion, the researchers refer to additional outcomes of importance (e.g. nutritional supplement use) but did not report whether this was recorded as part of the study	+ The authors note that other outcomes (e.g. nutritional supplement use) are important, but these are not assessed	++ All important outcomes appear to have been assessed	++ All important outcomes appear to have been assessed
3.4 Were outcomes relevant?	+ Most outcomes relevant, with the exception of EMG	+ Outcomes assessed appear to be relevant, however this is not clear as description of data collection was inadequate. Also may have been useful to consider quality rather than quantity of food intake	+ Outcomes assessed appear to be relevant, although may have been useful to consider quality rather than quantity of food intake	+ Outcomes appear relevant however the reason for adapting existing measures was not explained	++ Outcomes assessed appear to be relevant
3.5 Were there similar follow-up times in exposure and comparison groups?	NA No follow-up	- The control/treatment group were followed for longer	NA Only one group	NA No follow-up	NA No follow-up
3.6 Was follow-up time meaningful?	NA No follow-up	+ The time that the aquaria were in place seemed appropriate to detect changes in nutritional status, but perhaps not body mass	+ The time that the aquaria were in place seemed appropriate to detect changes in nutritional status, but perhaps not body mass	NA No follow-up	NA No follow-up

Study ID	DeSchriver 1990	Edwards 2002	Edwards 2013	Edwards 2014	Katcher 1984
4.1 Were exposure and comparison groups similar at baseline? If not, were these adjusted?	+ All groups were reported to be similar at baseline for age, but while the authors report gender to be similar at baseline, this might be debated. Also differences in outcomes at baseline which were not adjusted for correctly	++ No inter-facility difference were found, and all participants took part in the intervention	++ There was only one condition and no inter-facility difference were found	++ ANCOVA was used which can adjust for confounders	+ Unclear as this was not reported
4.2 Was intention to treat (ITT) analysis conducted?	NA Not relevant to this study design	+ Data on weight was reported for all participants but unclear if nutritional intake data comprises all participants. Also one participant discrepancy in body weight data	+ Data on weight was reported for all participants but unclear if nutritional intake data comprises all participants	- The one participant who did not complete the study was removed from the dataset	NA Not relevant to this study design
4.3 Was the study sufficiently powered to detect an intervention effect (if one exists)?	NR No power analysis reported	NR No power analysis reported	NR No power analysis reported	NR No power analysis reported	NR No power analysis reported
4.4 Were the estimates of effect size given or calculable?	NR Effect sizes were not reported	NR Effect sizes were not reported	NR Effect sizes were not reported	NR Effect sizes were not reported	NR Effect sizes were not reported
4.5 Were the analytical methods appropriate?	- Analysis methods not described so unclear	- No description of the statistical analysis included and didn't appear to account for clustering	- No description of the statistical analysis provided and didn't appear to account for clustering	- Due to the type of data collected (ordinal), ANCOVA generally not considered appropriate. Clustering was not considered	- Analysis methods not adequately described
4.6 Was the precision of intervention effects given or calculable? Were they meaningful?	NR No confidence intervals included	NR No confidence intervals included	+ Confidence intervals included in the figures for one analysis only, and no values reported.	NR No confidence intervals included	NR No confidence intervals included

Study ID	DeSchriver 1990	Edwards 2002	Edwards 2013	Edwards 2014	Katcher 1984
5.1 Are the study results internally valid (i.e. unbiased)?	- Potential bias lack of blinding, and irrelevant EMG, plus poor description of analysis methods so unclear if appropriate	- No blinding and the control group was non-equivalent by design, so findings are based large on pre-post change from intervention group	- No blinding and the study lacked a control group	- The study would benefit from a control group and follow-up. Lack of blinding is a significant source of bias, although difficult to control due to study design	+ Attempts made to reduce bias by blinding the assessor and randomising. However methods of randomisation not described and unclear whether analysis were appropriate
5.2 Are the findings generalizable to the source population (i.e. externally valid)?	+ More information about the participants and eligible population required	+ The sample was well described but unclear whether this is representative of eligible population	+ The sample was well described but unclear whether this is representative of eligible population	+ The sample was well described but unclear whether this is representative of eligible population	- Insufficient information given about the participants to determine whether generalizable
Overall study grading	-	-	-	-	-

Study ID	Maranda 2015	Riddick 1985	Sahrmann 2016	Sanchez 2015	Wells 2005
1.1 Is the source populations or source area well described?	++ Clinic that participants were recruited from was named, and inclusion/exclusion criteria given	++ Source population described in detail	+ Some description of the source population but more detail beneficial	- Poor description of the source population	+ Some information of the setting given but the source population would benefit from more description
1.2 Is the eligible population or area representative of the source population?	- Recruitment was not well described and unclear whether participants were representative of clinic (source) population	- Recruitment methods described, however control group participants identified by the centre manager, hence considerable selection bias	+ Recruitment and selection methods described but may not be representative as only adults measured, hence unlikely to be representative of the entire source population	+ Recruitment methods not described and not clear if representative	+ Recruitment was not well-described

1.3 Do the selected participants or areas represent the eligible population or area?	+ Selection process not described and percentage of potential participants who agreed to participate was not stated, but inclusion criteria clear	- Methods of selection from eligible participants not described except for the control group which was hand-picked by the centre manager. Percentage that agreed to take part included, and inclusion/exclusion criteria stated	+ The researchers refer to previous (albeit unpublished) research which examined the typical characteristics of visitors to the exhibit; the selected participants matched the eligible population on characteristics such as gender. However, not clear what percentage of the eligible population took part	+ Eligible population not described and method of selection not stated, but some inclusion/exclusion criteria given	+ Eligible population not described and method of selection not stated. However, the inclusion/exclusion criteria were given
2.1 How was selection bias minimised?	+ Randomised but method of randomisation not stated	- Majority of participants in intervention groups chose their preferred group, and control group was handpicked by centre manager, so considerable bias	NA There was only one condition	- Control group were randomly selected from those participating in the intervention group, but method of selection is not stated and order of interventions was not randomised	+ Randomised but method of randomisation not stated
2.2 Were the interventions (and comparisons) well described and appropriate?	+ Participants were given same fishbowl and equipment, but purchased their own fish (with funds from researchers), so unclear if they adhere to instructions to by specific species	+ Some description but the aquarium but more detail would have been beneficial	+ Intervention mostly well described but some additional information beneficial, e.g. stocking	++ Intervention described well and images were included to support this	++ Fairly well explained and comparisons appropriate
2.3 Was the allocation concealed?	+ States that randomisation sequence was concealed but it is unclear how this was achieved	- Concealment unlikely as allocation was mostly by preference	NA No allocation	NR Concealment was not reported	NR Concealment was not reported
2.4 Were participants or investigators blind to exposure and comparisons?	- Impossible to blind participants, and investigators were not blinded either	- Participants and assessors not blinded, but this would be hard to achieve due to design of study	- Participants and assessors not blinded, but this would be hard to achieve due to design of study	- Participants not blinded and unclear if researchers/assessors were blinded	+ Participants nor researchers blinded to conditions, although participants were not aware of study aims or other conditions

2.5 Was the exposure to the intervention and comparison adequate?	+ Length of intervention is appropriate, but unclear how well participants adhered to daily/weekly tasks	++ Exposure was appropriate	+ The exposure was probably adequate; however 10 minutes is not representative of average visit time (20 mins)	++ Duration of exposure adequate and equal between conditions	++ Duration of exposure adequate and equal between conditions
2.6 Was contamination acceptably low?	++ Authors reported that one participant was excluded due to buying a fish while in control group	- It is not known if contamination occurred, as residents in the complex could have visited someone with a fish tank	NA There was only one condition	- The control group had previously participated in the intervention group, so were already familiar with the procedure - contamination likely	+ Contamination unlikely but not explicitly stated that participants didn't take part in more than one condition, and as participants were probably known to one another they could have discussed participation
2.7 Were other interventions similar in both groups?	++ Groups were treated equally apart from planned intervention	+ Participants in each group were treated similarly by researchers, but not clear if other interventions were similar across groups	NA There was only one condition	- The control group were followed for longer as they had already participated in the intervention group	++ Interventions were similar and same procedure was used
2.8 Were all participants accounted for at study conclusion?	++ Does not appear that any participants were lost to follow-up	+ Drop out was reported and acceptable (<10%) but all from control group	NR Drop out not reported	NR Drop out not reported	NR Drop out not reported
2.9 Did the setting reflect usual UK practice?	NA Home setting	+ Likely to be some differences due to age and location of study	NA Public aquarium setting	NA Not a standard intervention	NA University setting
2.10 Did the intervention or control comparison reflect usual UK practice?	NA Not a standard intervention	NA Not a standard intervention	NA Public aquarium setting	NA Not a standard intervention	NA University setting
3.1 Were outcome measures reliable?	+ Validity and reliability not reported, but measures appear to be used in clinical practice/research	+ Measures obtained have reliability and validity reports but psychological assessments were interview administered which may have introduced bias	+ No reports of reliability but physiological methods are generally reliable and psychological assessment has been validated	+ Authors state that the pain assessment method is highly reliable, but no data given	+ Outcomes generally reliable, although the specific reliability of the devices used was not stated

3.2 Were all outcome measures complete?	NR Missing data not reported and it is not clear that all participants completed all data points	NR Missing data not reported	+ Physiological data were missing due to technical problems, but these were excluded. Not explicitly stated that all other measures are complete	NR Missing data were not reported and not clear whether all participants completed all time points	NR Missing data were not reported and not clear whether all participants completed all time points
3.3 Were all important outcomes assessed?	++ All important outcomes appear to have been assessed	++ All important outcomes appear to have been assessed	++ Outcome measures obtained seem appropriate	- Other parameters such as heart rate could have been measured	+ Would have been beneficial to measure some psychological outcomes
3.4 Were outcomes relevant?	++ Outcomes were relevant	++ Outcomes were relevant	++ Outcomes were relevant	+ The outcomes used were relevant, but not insulation	++ Outcomes were relevant
3.5 Were there similar follow-up times in exposure and comparison groups?	++ No differences in follow-up time between groups	NA No follow-up	NA No follow-up	- Control group 'followed' for longer as they participated in both conditions	NA No follow-up
3.6 Was follow-up time meaningful?	++ Follow-up seems appropriate	NA No follow-up	NA No follow-up	++ Duration of follow-up is appropriate for this study	NA No follow-up
4.1 Were exposure and comparison groups similar at baseline? If not, were these adjusted?	++ Groups were equivalent at baseline	- Differences between groups at baseline were not adjusted for. Also differences due to allocation by preference	NA There was only one condition	- Unclear as not reported, but control group was a small subset of the intervention group so unlikely that they were similar	+ Unclear as not described. Also a discrepancy as authors state 10 male and 10 female participants were assigned to each group but also that 58% were male
4.2 Was intention to treat (ITT) analysis conducted?	- Only participants with complete data were analysed	- Participants who dropped out were not included in analysis	NA Not relevant to this study design	NA Not relevant to this study design	NA Not relevant to this study design
4.3 Was the study sufficiently powered to detect an intervention effect (if one exists)?	- Power analysis was conducted, but this was poor and so may not be meaningful	- No power analysis reported, and methods used to account for being underpowered are inappropriate	NR No power analysis reported	NR No power analysis reported	NR No power analysis reported

4.4 Were the estimates of effect size given or calculable?	++ Effect sizes were given	NR Effect sizes were not reported	NR Effect sizes were not reported	NR Effect sizes were not reported	NR Effect sizes were not reported
4.5 Were the analytical methods appropriate?	- Analysis methods not appropriate, mixed ANOVA should have been used and sub-group analysis specified	- Statistical analysis not appropriate and poorly reported	++ Appropriate statistical analysis	- Analysis methods not appropriate due to use of multiple tests rather than omnibus test	++ Analysis methods appropriate
4.6 Was the precision of intervention effects given or calculable? Were they meaningful?	++ Confidence intervals reported	NR No confidence intervals included	+ Some confidence intervals stated in the figures but no numerical values provided	NR No confidence intervals included	NR No confidence intervals included
5.1 Are the study results internally valid (i.e. unbiased)?	+ Some sources of bias were minimised (e.g. contamination, similarity of groups at baseline,) and there was an attempt at randomisation and allocation concealment, although these are not well described	- Considerable flaws in study design, particularly with regards to selection bias	- Well reported but bias present due to lack of blinding and the study would benefit from a control group	- Main flaws were the inappropriate control group and lack of blinding	+ Overall well designed but some bias still present due to lack of blinding
5.2 Are the findings generalizable to the source population (i.e. externally valid)?	- As a pilot study it is probably not generalizable	- Recruitment well described but selection process unclear, with exception of control group who were handpicked by centre manager	+ Recruitment and selection fairly well described, but more detail could have been given about participants	- Recruitment and selection not well described and more details regarding sample needed. Also study is investigating an intervention for children, and although ethical issues prevent using child participants for this preliminary research, the findings can't be generalized to children	+ Likely to be generalisable to source population, but more information is needed
Overall study grading	+	-	-	-	+

Qualitative studies

Study ID	Kidd 1999	Langfield 2009
1. Is a qualitative approach appropriate?	Inappropriate Although the title refers to "benefits and problems", which is indicative of a qualitative approach, the design of the questionnaire (open/closed) is unclear. The authors also refer to hypotheses which suggests a quantitative approach	Appropriate Looks at meaning and value participants attribute to keeping pet fish
2. Is the study clear in what it seeks to do?	Unclear The aims are not clearly stated	Clear Aims clearly stated and clear rationale given
3. How defensible/ rigorous is the research design/methodology?	Indefensible The method was not clearly described but appears inappropriate	Not sure Method for recruitment likely to introduce bias
4. How well was the data collection carried out?	Not sure/not reported Data collection is not adequately described	Appropriately Study appears well conducted and methods are robust
5. Is the role of the researcher clearly described?	Not described No information given	Clearly described The relationship of the researcher to participants is clearly explained and a reflective journal was kept throughout
6. Is the context clearly described?	Clear Some information is given about participants and setting, although this could have been developed further	Clear Participant characteristics and context clearly defined; researchers own biases are acknowledged
7. Were the methods reliable?	Unreliable The aims and methods are not adequately described, but the study refers to understanding the benefits and problems of keeping home aquaria - a qualitative approach is therefore appropriate, but the researchers refers to hypothesis testing which is inappropriate	Reliable Data from in-depth interviews, reflective journal and member checking were triangulated. Constant comparison method was used, with two coders involved for at least part of the process
8. Is the data analysis sufficiently rigorous?	Not sure Only descriptive statistics are provided but not clear how these were obtained (i.e. coded from open answers, or closed questionnaire). Analyses performed are however appropriate for descriptive statistics	Not sure Unclear whether a second coder was involved throughout the analytical process, which could have increased rigor
9. Is the data "rich"?	Poor Only descriptive statistics are presented	Not sure/not reported Some quotes presented but not many, so not clear if these are representative. Only provides perspective of current pet fish owners, other perspectives (i.e. past pet fish owners) could have provided richer data. Does not represent minority groups

10. Is the analysis reliable?	Not sure/not reported Not clear how data was obtained or analysis was conducted, inadequate information	Not sure/not reported Not clear whether two coders were involved in entire process, which could have improved reliability
11. Are the findings convincing?	Not sure There is not enough information about the methods etc. to determine if findings are convincing	Convincing The findings are clear and coherent, evidenced fairly well with extracts/quotes, and are appropriately referenced
12. Are the findings relevant to the aims of the study?	Irrelevant As aims were not stated, it is not possible to know if they were relevant	Relevant They address the aims well
13. Conclusions	Inadequate No specific conclusions are presented	Adequate Conclusions reflect the research findings well
14. How clear and coherent is the reporting of ethics?	Not sure/not reported Unclear whether ethical approval was obtained, reference to "permission" but not informed consent	Appropriate Ethical approval and informed consent were obtained. Although ethics are not discussed in great detail, the study is unlikely to raise major ethical concerns
Overall assessment	-	+

Appendix E: Copies of materials used (Chapter 3)

Demographic Questionnaire

Please answer the following questions. If there are any questions which you would prefer not to answer then just leave the response blank.

1. What is your age? _____
2. What is your gender?
 - Male
 - Female
3. What is your job role?
 - Academic
 - Other (*please state department*):

4. Have you ever had any pets?
 - Yes
 - No
5. If yes, what type of pets did you have?
 - Dogs
 - Cats
 - Other small mammals (rabbits, guineas pig etc.)
 - Reptiles
 - Fish
 - Other (*please state*)

6. If you have ever kept fish, please indicate when this was:
 - I currently have pet fish
 - I have kept fish as adult, but don't currently have any
 - I had pet fish as a child

Thank you for completing this questionnaire.

Positive and Negative Affect Schedule

Please see Watson, Clark and Tellegen (1998) for complete scale.

Perceived Arousal Scale

Please see Anderson, Deuser and DeNeve (1995) for scale.

Digit Span Test

Forwards Instructions: *"I am going to say some numbers. Listen carefully and repeat them straight back to me. For example, if I say 7-1-9, what would you say?"*

Backwards Instructions: *"I am going to say some numbers. Listen carefully and repeat them straight back to me, but in the reverse order. For example, if I say 3-8-6, what would you say?"*

Item		Digit Span	Pass (✓) or Fail (x)
1	A	2 – 6	
	B	5 – 7	
2	A	2 – 4 – 9	
	B	3 – 6 – 7	
3	A	4 – 5 – 2 – 1	
	B	8 – 6 – 5 – 4	
4	A	9 – 6 – 4 – 1 – 2	
	B	8 – 7 – 3 – 2 – 1	
5	A	3 – 9 – 4 – 5 – 1 – 8	
	B	2 – 7 – 5 – 3 – 4 – 8	
6	A	7 – 4 – 5 – 3 – 8 – 9 – 6	
	B	8 – 2 – 1 – 5 – 4 – 3 – 7	
7	A	3 – 6 – 4 – 5 – 2 – 1 – 7 – 9	
	B	9 – 1 – 6 – 3 – 4 – 5 – 2 – 7	
8	A	3 – 2 – 6 – 4 – 7 – 8 – 1 – 9 – 5	
	B	5 – 8 – 9 – 3 – 6 – 7 – 4 – 1 – 2	

Stroop Colour-Word Task

green	purple	blue	brown	brown	green	green	purple	red	green
purple	red	brown	brown	red	blue	blue	blue	purple	red
brown	blue	red	purple	purple	brown	green	blue	red	green
blue	green	brown	red	green	purple	red	blue	purple	brown
brown	green	brown	brown	red	purple	brown	purple	purple	green
blue	blue	blue	blue	green	green	red	purple	red	red
brown	blue	red	purple	red	purple	red	red	purple	blue
brown	purple	green	green	blue	blue	green	brown	brown	green
purple	purple	red	green	purple	red	green	blue	blue	purple
blue	brown	brown	red	brown	brown	green	blue	red	green

Score Sheet

✓ or x							
	Brown		Red		Green		Brown
	Green		Brown		Purple		Blue
	Purple		Green		Brown		Green
	Red		Purple		Red		Purple
	Blue		Blue		Blue		Red
	Red		Brown		Brown		Green
	Blue		Red		Green		Brown
	Brown		Blue		Red		Purple
	Green		Green		Blue		Blue
	Purple		Purple		Purple		Red
	Red		Brown		Blue		Green
	Brown		Blue		Red		Brown
	Purple		Purple		Purple		Purple
	Green		Red		Brown		Red
	Blue		Green		Green		Blue
	Green		Blue		Green		Brown
	Brown		Purple		Brown		Red
	Red		Red		Blue		Green
	Blue		Green		Red		Blue
	Purple		Brown		Purple		Purple
	Purple		Green		Red		Blue
	Red		Purple		Blue		Red
	Brown		Blue		Purple		Green
	Green		Brown		Brown		Brown
	Blue		Red		Green		Purple

Time taken to complete: _____

Depression, Anxiety, Stress Scales

Please see Lovibond and Lovibond (1995) for scale.

Job-related Affective Well-being Scale, JAWS

Please see Van Katwyk, Fox, Spector, and Kelloway (2000) for scale.

Job Satisfaction Survey

Please see Spector (1985) for scale.

Semi-structured focus group schedule

Activity	Description	Timings
Informed consent and demographics	Participants complete consent form and demographic questionnaire. Confirm all participants are happy with audio recording.	0-5 minutes
Introductions	Participants introduce themselves to the group, including whether they have any pets.	5-10 minutes
Experiences	<p>Activity: think about your experience of the three activities, then for each activity please write down 2-3 words which describe this experience. Discuss.</p> <p><i>Prompts:</i></p> <p><i>“What do you remember thinking about during the activities?”</i></p> <p><i>“What did you think about the length of each activity?”</i></p> <p><i>“Did you have any preferences with regards to the three activities?”</i></p> <p><i>“How did you feel returning to work after each activity?”</i></p>	10-25 minutes
HAI in the workplace	<p>“In this research you completed the activity (e.g. watching the fish tank) in your workplace, but outside of your own office. What are your thoughts about the presence of animals within your office, e.g. a fish tank in the office?”</p> <p><i>Prompts:</i></p> <p><i>“What benefits might there be?”</i></p> <p><i>“What disadvantages might there be?”</i></p> <p><i>“What do you think about the presence of other animals – such as dogs – in the workplace?”</i></p>	25-35 minutes
“Non-live” interventions	<p>“One of the activities you completed during this research was watching a video of the fish. How do you think this compared to watching the live animals?”</p> <p><i>Prompts:</i></p> <p><i>“How do you think the presence of a screen showing a video of fish might compare to the presence of a fish tank within your office?”</i></p>	35-45 minutes
Closing comments	Ask participants if there is anything else they would like to mention. Thank them for their participation.	45-55 minutes

Semi-structured interview schedule

Participant provides written informed consent (or verbal if via telephone), confirm they are happy with audio recording. Participant completes demographic questionnaire (read verbally if via telephone).

1. Think back to the three activities you participated in; how would you describe your experience of these activities?

Prompts:

“What do you remember thinking about during the activities?”

“What did you think about the length of each activity?”

“Did you have any preferences with regards to the three activities?”

“How did you feel returning to work after each activity?”

2. In this research you completed the activities while at work, but outside of your own office. What are your thoughts on the presence of animals, particularly fish, in the workplace?

Prompts:

“What benefits might there be?”

“What disadvantages might there be?”

“What do you think about the presence of other animals – such as dogs – in the workplace?”

3. “One of the activities you completed during this research was watching a video of the fish. How do you think this compared to watching the live animals?”

Prompts:

“How do you think the presence of a screen showing a video of fish might compare to the presence of a fish tank within your office?”

4. Is there anything else you would like to mention? Do you have any questions for me?

Appendix F: Ethics Approvals

15/06/2018

Dear Heather Clements,

Your application 4940: Human-animal interaction in the workplace, submission reference 3636, has been approved, with conditions, by the Science and Sport SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below.**

Title	Comment
Supervisor/Director of Studies	The supervisor name and email address do not match.
Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship)?	It should be noted that this study is collecting some highly personal information about participants mental health status and feeling towards their job, in their actual place of work. All information collected should be dealt with in an appropriately sensitive manner.
Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application	Just a suggestion, but in the email invite you say that participants will take part in "some tasks". While these have been appropriately specified in the Participant Information Sheet, it is a little vague in the invite and may not give potential participants enough information at this stage.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Personal details withheld.

Dr Gary Boyd

28/06/2019

Dear Heather Clements,

Your application 8301: Can human-animal interaction in the workplace promote employee well-being? A qualitative study to further explore the role of fish aquaria , submission 6859, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Personal details withheld.

Dr Gary Boyd

22/05/2020

Dear Heather Clements,

Your application 12045: The influence of companion animals on mental well-being and loneliness during the Covid-19 pandemic, submission 10319, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Personal details withheld.

Dr Gary Boyd

11/01/2021

Dear Heather Clements,

Your application 13562: The impact of companion animals on the well-being and productivity of people working from home, submission 12161, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC, though you may wish to consider the reviewer comments below. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Title	Comment
Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect.	Will it be made clear to the participants that the outcomes of the study are available to them upon request? I might suggest that a further incentive to take part in the study would be to inform participants at the outset that you will provide a short report on the outcomes of the study to each participant. In my experience, this type of dissemination increases the uptake by volunteers to take part in this type of study.
Will participants be from any of the following groups? (Please tick all that apply)	These groups will not be specifically selected for, but they may still take part in the survey (e.g. terminal illness patients) - unless you specifically exclude them from the outset?
Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)	The information here is detailed and clear but I wonder if having information on who and why the study is being carried out near the top might help encourage participation i.e. University and Mars support for PhD research. Just for consideration by the team.
Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application	Same comment as before can the team consider if the 'we' referred to in the social media call should be more explicit on who is conducting this research.

Good luck with your research.

Personal details withheld.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix G: Copies of materials used (Chapter 4)

Demographic questionnaire

Please answer the following questions. If there are any questions which you would prefer not to answer then just leave the response blank.

7. What is your age? _____
8. What is your gender?
 Male
 Female
9. What is your job role?
 Academic
 Other (*please state department*):

10. Have you ever had any pets?
 Yes
 No
11. If yes, what type of pets did you have?
 Dogs
 Cats
 Other small mammals (rabbits, guineas pig etc.)
 Reptiles
 Fish
 Other (*please state*)

12. If you have ever kept fish, please indicate when this was:
 I currently have pet fish
 I have kept fish as adult, but don't currently have any
 I had pet fish as a child

Thank you for completing this questionnaire.

Semi-structured focus group schedule

Activity	Description	Timings
Informed consent and demographics	Participants complete consent form and demographic questionnaire. Confirm all participants are happy with audio recording.	0-10 minutes
Introductions	Participants introduce themselves to the group, including whether they have any pets.	10-15 minutes
Perceptions	“When you first heard that a fish tank was being installed in your office, what did you think?”	15-25 minutes
Positives	Activity: Participants write down three benefits of the fish tanks that they have experienced. Discuss.	25-40 minutes
Negatives	Activity: Participants write down three downsides to the fish tanks that they have experienced. Discuss.	40-55 minutes
Alternatives (other HAIs)	“Other research has focused on things like pet-friendly workplaces, and take your dog to work schemes. What are your thoughts on these, and how they compare to the presence of fish tanks?”	55-65 minutes
Alternatives (non-live)	“Another means of human-animal interaction is through virtual or “non-live” alternatives, such as robotic animals or – in the case of fish tanks – videos of the animals. What are your thoughts on these interactions, and how they would fit into a working environment?”	65-75 minutes
Closing comments	Ask participants if there is anything else they would like to mention. Thank them for their participation.	75-85 minutes

Semi-structured interview schedule

Participant provides written informed consent (or verbal if via telephone), confirm they are happy with audio recording. Participant completes demographic questionnaire (read verbally if via telephone).

1. When you first heard that a fish tank was being installed within your office, what were your thoughts?
2. Now that the fish tank has been installed for a few weeks, what – if anything – do you like about it being in your office?
Prompt: research – stress and relaxation
3. Is there anything you don't like about having the fish tank in your office?
Prompt: animal welfare, time commitment of caring for animal
4. Other research has looked at things such as pet-friendly workplaces, or take your dog to work schemes. What are your thoughts on these and how they compare to the presence of fish tanks?
Prompt: how interactions are different (physical contact), social aspect
5. Another means of human-animal interaction is through virtual or “non-live” alternatives, such as robotic animals, or in the case of fish tanks, videos of the animals. What are your thoughts on these interactions, and how they would fit into a work environment?
Prompt: live animal versus distraction, pleasant/relaxing images
6. Is there anything else you would like to mention? Do you have any questions for me?

Appendix H: Copies of materials used (Chapter 5)

Survey questions

Section 1: Demographic details:

Please answer the following questions about yourself. If you would rather not answer a question, please select “Prefer not to say”

1. What is your age?
18-34 years/35-50 years/51-69 years/70+ years/Prefer not to say
2. What gender do you identify as?
Male/Female/Other/Prefer not to say
3. What is your ethnicity?
White/Black or African American/Hispanic or Latino/Asian/Two or More/Other (please specify)/Prefer not to say
4. What is your highest level of education?
No education completed/Elementary or primary school/High school/Undergraduate degree or equivalent/Master’s degree or equivalent/Doctoral degree or equivalent/I don’t know/Prefer not to say
5. What is your marital status?
Single/Married or living with partner/Partner, not living together/Separated, Divorced, Widow or Widower/Other (please specify)/Prefer not to say
6. Including yourself, how many adults live in your household?
7. How many children live in your household (please include anyone under 18 years of age)?
8. What is your country of residence?
United Kingdom/United States/Australia or New Zealand/Canada/Other/Prefer not to say (please specify)
[If UK] England/Scotland/Wales/Northern Ireland
[If US] Please specify state

Section 2: Behaviour during pandemic

The following questions relate specifically to your life during the COVID-19 pandemic and how it compares to your life before the pandemic. There are no right or wrong answers and your responses are completely anonymous, so please answer as honestly as possible. For clarity, consider the start of the COVID-19 pandemic to be the date on which the first case was confirmed in your country, or if you are unsure, from the time that social distancing was put in place. If you would prefer not to answer any questions please select “Prefer not to say”

1. During the COVID-19 pandemic, on average, how often have you communicated with friends and family who are not part of your household *via* written communications (e.g. text messaging, WhatsApp, email, post/mail, etc.)?
More than once a day/Once a day/A few times a week/Once a week/Less than once a week/Less than once a month/Never/Prefer not to say
2. During the COVID-19 pandemic, on average, how often have you communicated with friends and family who are not part of your household *via* verbal communications (e.g. telephone, video calls)?
More than once a day/Once a day/A few times a week/Once a week/Less than once a week/Less than once a month/Never/Prefer not to say
3. During the COVID-19 pandemic, on average, how often have you communicated face-to-face with friends and family who are not part of your household (including when maintaining social distancing)?
More than once a day/Once a day/A few times a week/Once a week/Less than once a week/Less than once a month/Never/Prefer not to say
4. During the COVID-19 pandemic, on average, how often have you left your house to run essential errands (e.g. buy food and medicine)?
More than once a day/Once a day/A few times a week/Once a week/Less than once a week/Less than once a month//Never/Prefer not to say
5. During the COVID-19 pandemic, on average, how often have you left your house to exercise?
More than once a day/Once a day/A few times a week/Once a week/Less than once a week/Less than once a month/Never/Prefer not to say
6. Which of the below best describes your employment status during the COVID-19 pandemic?
Working onsite (full-time)/Working onsite (part-time)/Working from home (full-time)/Working from home (part-time)/Self-employed (working full-time)/Self-employed (working part-time)/Self-employed (unable to get work)/Furloughed/Unemployed/Student/Retired/Other (please state)/Prefer not to say
7. During the COVID-19 pandemic have you had a period of self-isolation greater than one week?
Yes/No/Prefer not to say
[If yes] How long was your period isolation (if still isolating please state how long it has been so far)?

Section 3: Companion animal guardianship

The following questions relate to your pets/companion animals . If you indicate “yes” to the companion animals question, you will be asked whether you own different type of companion animals and how you interact with them. If you have lots of companion animals this may take some time and feel a little repetitive, but please bear with it as this is important.

For any questions relating to the COVID-19 pandemic, remember to consider the start to have been the date of the first confirmed case in your country.

1. Do you currently keep any companion animals (pets)?
Yes/No

IF YES:

2. Do you have any dogs?
Yes/No

IF YES:

3. Please specify the number of dogs you currently have
4. Does your dog(s) live in your home with you?
Yes/No
5. Where does your dog(s) sleep?
In my bed with me/In my bedroom but not in my bed/Elsewhere in my house/Outside my home
6. Would you consider yourself the primary caregiver for your dog(s)?
Yes/No/Responsibility is shared equally with another person(s)
7. Using the scale provided, please indicate how much time you have spent engaging in the following activities on a typical day during the COVID-19 pandemic (please only include activities you have undertaken, e.g. if your dog is always fed by someone else, please select “none” for this activity):

	None	Less than 5 mins	5-15 mins	15-30 mins	30-60 mins	1-2 hours	2-4 hours	More than 4 hours
Walking your dog(s)								
Feeding your dog(s)								
Petting/stroking/grooming/ playing with your dog(s)								
Talking to your dog(s)								
Undertaking any other activities with your dog(s)								
Being around your dog(s) but not actively interacting with them (e.g. watching television with your dog(s) in the same room)								

8. Would you say the COVID-19 pandemic has influenced how you interact with or care for your dog(s) in any way (e.g. spending more/less time with your dog)?
No/Yes (please give brief description)
9. How would you rate the influence your dog(s) have had on your mental well-being (such as your thoughts, feelings, and emotions) during the COVID-19 pandemic?

Extremely negative effect	Moderately negative effect	Slight negative effect	No effect	Slight positive effect	Moderately positive effect	Extremely positive effect
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10. Do you have any cats?
Yes/No

IF YES:

Repeat questions 3-9 for cats, statements for question 7:

- Feeding your cat(s)
- Petting/stroking/grooming/
- playing with your cat(s)
- Talking to your cat(s)
- Undertaking any other activities with your cat(s)
- Being around your cat(s) but not actively interacting with them (e.g. watching television with your cat(s) in the same room)

11. Do you have any fish?

Yes/No

IF YES:

Do you keep any of your fish in tanks/aquariums?

Yes/No

IF YES:

How many tanks do you have?

How many individual fish do you have in these tanks (if unsure please provide best estimate)?

Do you keep any of your fish in ponds?

IF YES:

How many ponds do you have?

How many individual fish do you have these ponds (if unsure please provide best estimate)?

Repeat questions 6-9 for fishes, statements for question 7:

- Feeding your fish
- Conducting tank/pond maintenance (e.g. water changes, removing algae)
- Watching your fish
- Talking to your fish
- Undertaking any other activities with your fish
- Being around your fish but not actively interacting with them (e.g. watching television in the same room as a fish tank)

12. Do you have any exotic animals?

Yes/No

IF YES: Repeat questions 3,4,6-9 for exotic animals. Statements for question 7:

- Feeding your exotic animal(s)

- Petting/stroking/grooming/playing with your exotic animal(s)
- Talking to your exotic animal(s)
- Undertaking any other activities with your exotic animal(s)
- Being around your exotic animal(s) but not actively interacting with them (e.g. watching television with your exotic animal(s) in the same room)

13. Do you have any birds?

Yes/No

IF YES: Repeat questions 3,4,6-9 for birds. Statements for question 7:

- Feeding your bird(s)
- Petting/stroking/grooming/playing with your bird(s)
- Talking to your bird(s)
- Undertaking any other activities with your bird(s)
- Being around your bird(s) but not actively interacting with them (e.g. watching television with your bird(s) in the same room)

14. Do you have any small mammals (rabbits, rats, guinea pigs, mice, etc.)?

Yes/No

IF YES: Repeat questions 3,4,6-9 for small mammals. Statements for question 7:

- Feeding your small mammal(s)
- Petting/stroking/grooming/playing with your small mammal(s)
- Talking to your small mammal(s)
- Undertaking any other activities with your small mammal(s)
- Being around your small mammal(s) but not actively interacting with them (e.g. watching television with your small mammal(s) in the same room)

15. Do you have any other types of companion animals?

Yes/No

IF YES: Repeat questions 3,4,6-9 for other companion animals. Statements for question 7:

- Feeding your companion animal(s)
- Petting/stroking/grooming/playing with your companion animal(s)
- Talking to your companion animal(s)
- Undertaking any other activities with your companion animal(s)
- Being around your companion animal(s) but not actively interacting with them (e.g. watching television with your companion animal(s) in the same room)?

16. During the COVID-19 pandemic, have you had any problems accessing supplies for any of your companion animal(s) (e.g. food, pet care items)?

No/No supplies required/Yes (please give brief description)

17. During the COVID-19 pandemic, have you had any problems accessing emergency or routine medical treatment for any of your companion animal(s)?

No/No supplies required/Yes (please give brief description)

18. Has the COVID-19 pandemic affected your ability to meet the needs of any of your companion animal(s) in any other ways?

No/Yes (please specify)

19. Did you adopt or purchase any of your companion animals after the start of the COVID-19 pandemic?
Yes/No

IF YES:

Please specify the type and number of companion animals adopted/purchased since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic

Did you adopt or purchase this companion animal(s) because of the pandemic?
Yes/No

20. How concerned have you been about the possibility of contracting SARS-CoV-2 from your companion animals/pets, if at all?
Not at all concerned/A little concerned/Somewhat concerned/Extremely concerned

21. How concerned have you been about the possibility of your companion animals/pets contracting SARS-CoV-2 from you, if at all?
Not at all concerned/A little concerned/Somewhat concerned/Extremely concerned

Section 4: Mental well-being measures

The following few pages include some questionnaires about how you've been feeling recently. There are instructions given at the start of each page. There are no right or wrong answers, so please answer as truthfully as possible.

22. [UCLA Loneliness Scale, 3-item version (Please see Hughes, Waite, Hawkley and Cacioppo, 2004)]

23. [DeJong Gierveld Loneliness Scale, 6-item version, (Please see DeJong Gierveld and Tilburg, 2006)]

24. [DASS-21 (Please see Lovibond and Lovibond, 1995; Henry and Crawford, 2005)]

25. [The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) ©NHS Health Scotland, University of Warwick and University of Edinburgh, 2006, all rights reserved. (Please see Tennant et al., 2007)]

Section 5: Rating scales

26. The next questions are about how you have felt during the Covid-19 pandemic, compared to how you usually feel. Please respond by selecting the button in the relevant column. There are no right or wrong answers. Do not spend too much time on any one statement.

	Much less than normal	Somewhat less than normal	A little less than normal	About the same as normal	A little more than normal	Somewhat more than normal	Much more than normal
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During the Covid-19 pandemic I have felt stressed...							
During the Covid-19 pandemic I have felt anxious...							
During the Covid-19 pandemic I have felt low or depressed...							
During the Covid-19 pandemic I have felt lonely....							

27. In comparison to how you usually feel, how would you rate your overall mental well-being during the Covid-19 pandemic? Please respond using the scale below

Much worse than usual	Somewhat worse than normal	A little worse than usual	About the same as usual	A little better than usual	Somewhat better than normal	A lot better than usual
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Section 6: Open-ended questions

28. What, if anything, do you feel has helped to support your mental well-being during the pandemic?

29. If you have companion animals, in what ways, if any, do you feel your companion animals have influenced your mental well-being during pandemic?"

Semi-structured interview schedule

[Participant will have provided written informed consent prior to the interview. Reassess consent verbally and double check they are happy with audio recording].

Demographic questions:

“First I’m going to ask you some questions about yourself. You don’t have to answer these questions if you don’t want to. If you don’t want to answer a question please say “prefer not to say” and I will move onto the next question. I’m not going to audio record these responses, but I will write them down.”

1. What age range do you fall into?

18-34 years

35-50 years

51-69 years

70+ years

Prefer not to say

2. What gender do you identify as?

Male

Female

Other

Prefer not to say

3. What country do you live in? [If UK, ask which domain; if US, ask which state]

4. How many people live in your home, including you?

5. What types of companion animals do you own? How many of each do you own (if fish, how many tanks/ponds)?

Dogs

Cats

Fish (in tanks/in ponds)

Birds

Rabbits or small mammals

Exotic animals

Any others [what type]

6. Do you consider yourself the primary caretaker for any of these animals? Which ones?

Yes

No

Responsibility is equally shared with another person or persons

Semi-structured questions

“I’m now going to start the audio recording, are you happy with this? I’m now going to ask you some questions about your experience of being a companion animal guardian, including during the coronavirus pandemic. If you get upset or want to stop at any stage please just let me know and we can take a break or end the interview.”

7. First, can you just tell me a little bit about your companion animals?
 - How long have you had your companion animal? Did you adopt or purchase any of them after the start of the coronavirus pandemic?
 - Prompt: [If yes] So what made you decide to get a companion animal at that time?
8. Can you remember what made you want to get a companion animal in the first place?
 - Prompt: If response relates to companionship/well-being/physical activity/other aspect of well-being, follow up with question about how this has been affected during the pandemic.
9. Thinking about life generally during the pandemic, how have you found adjusting to that?
 - Is there anything specific you've struggled with?
 - Would you say your well-being has been impacted in any way? How so?
10. How would you say keeping companion animals has influenced how you've dealt with the pandemic?
11. Thinking about a typical day, how has this changed from before the pandemic to now?
 - How has that affected how you interact with your companion animals, if at all?
 - Prompts: Would you say you spend more or less time with your companion animal, or is it about the same? Do you think this has been positive or negative for your relationship with your companion animal?
 - Have you noticed any changes in your companion animal's behaviour?
 - Prompt: Has your relationship with your companion animal altered in anyway due to the pandemic?
 - Prompt: What do you think will happen when the pandemic is over, and we start getting back to "normal" life?
12. Have you experienced any downsides to keeping a companion animal during the pandemic?
13. Has the coronavirus pandemic hindered you from meeting the needs of your companion animal in anyway?

Fish questions - only for participants who keep fish in tanks (if questions have not already been covered)

"I'd like to ask you some questions specifically about how you interact with your fish if that's ok?"

14. How long have you kept fish?
15. Have you purchased any fish since the start of the pandemic?
 - Prompt: [If yes] What made you decide to get them at that time?
16. What first made you want to get fish?

- Prompt: If response relates to companionship/well-being/other aspect of well-being, follow up with question about how this has been affected during the pandemic.

17. Thinking about life during the pandemic, how have you found adjusting to that?

- Is there anything specific you've struggled with?
- Would you say your well-being has been impacted in any way? How so?

18. How would you say keeping fish has influenced your experience of the pandemic, if at all?

19. Thinking about a typical day, how has this changed from before the pandemic to now?

- How has that affected how you interact with your fish, if at all?
- Prompt: Have you maintained the same cleaning schedule for your tank? What about feeding your fish?

20. Have you experienced any downsides to keeping fish during the pandemic?

21. Has the coronavirus pandemic hindered you from meeting the needs of your fish in anyway?

Final question – all participants

22. Do you have anything else you'd like to say about being a companion animal guardian during the coronavirus pandemic?

[Thank participant for taking part, ask if they have any questions, remind them they can withdraw for up to two weeks by emailing you].

Male	1.18	0.80	1.48	0.140	-0.22	0.14	-1.57	0.118	-1.10	0.65	-1.70	0.089
Highest level of education (0=School or below)												
Undergraduate	1.76	0.98	1.80	0.073	-0.17	0.17	-0.97	0.334	-0.82	0.78	-1.05	0.293
Masters	2.07	1.03	2.01	0.045	<0.01	0.18	0.02	0.981	-1.05	0.83	-1.26	0.208
Doctorate	2.08	1.13	1.83	0.067	-0.14	0.20	-0.70	0.487	-1.39	0.91	-1.53	0.128
Marital status (0=Single, separated, divorced, widowed)												
Partnered, not living together	2.50	1.30	1.93	0.054	-0.60	0.24	-2.56	0.011	0.64	1.06	0.61	0.544
Married or living with partner	2.72	0.67	4.06	<0.001	-1.17	0.12	-9.77	<0.001	-1.72	0.55	-3.14	0.002
Live with children (0=No)												
Yes	1.18	0.75	1.57	0.116	-0.11	0.13	-0.84	0.404	-1.88	0.61	-3.08	0.002
Country (0=United Kingdom)												
United States	1.43	0.73	1.97	0.049	-0.11	0.13	-0.83	0.407	-2.38	0.59	-4.02	<0.001
Other	2.36	0.87	2.71	0.007	-0.20	0.15	-1.27	0.203	-2.63	0.71	-3.71	<0.001
Communicated via verbal means (0=Average)												
Less than average	-1.80	0.73	-2.45	0.014	0.17	0.13	1.30	0.195	0.97	0.59	1.63	0.104
More than average	-0.14	0.71	-0.19	0.847	0.15	0.13	1.14	0.254	0.13	0.58	0.22	0.824
Communicated face-to-face (0=Average)												
Less than average	-0.85	0.78	-1.09	0.275	0.08	0.14	0.59	0.553	-0.07	0.64	-0.11	0.910
More than average	0.42	0.75	0.56	0.574	-0.29	0.14	-2.15	0.032	-0.62	0.62	-1.01	0.312
Left the house to exercise (0=Average)												
Less than average	0.33	0.82	0.41	0.685	-0.28	0.15	-1.90	0.058	-0.32	0.67	-0.47	0.637
More than average	2.64	0.74	3.57	<0.001	-0.39	0.13	-2.94	0.003	-2.26	0.60	-3.76	<0.001
Working during pandemic (0=No)												
Yes	1.91	0.79	2.42	0.016	-0.11	0.14	-0.79	0.432	-1.87	0.64	-2.92	0.004
Period of isolation >1 week (0=No)												
Yes	-0.53	0.68	-0.79	0.431	0.49	0.12	4.08	<0.001	0.93	0.55	1.68	0.093

	Mental well-being (n = 1031)				UCLA Loneliness Scale (n = 1074)				Depression (n = 1046)			
	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	t	p	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	t	p	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	t	p
Step 3	$\Delta R^2 = 0.008$ $\chi^2(5) = 8.52, p = 0.130$				$\Delta R^2 = 0.001$ $\chi^2(5) = 1.40, p = 0.925$				$\Delta R^2 = 0.008$ $\chi^2(5) = 8.29, p = 0.141$			
Intercept	38.82	1.63	23.77	<0.001	6.43	0.29	22.28	<0.001	15.59	1.32	11.83	<0.001
Age (0=18-34 years)												
35-50 years	1.09	0.75	1.45	0.148	-0.42	0.13	-3.10	0.002	-1.94	0.61	-3.19	0.001
51-69 years	3.15	0.82	3.83	<0.001	-0.40	0.15	-2.74	0.006	-3.03	0.67	-4.54	<0.001
70+ years	7.30	1.73	4.23	<0.001	-0.84	0.31	-2.74	0.006	-5.34	1.38	-3.88	<0.001
Gender (0=Female)												
Male	0.90	0.82	1.10	0.273	-0.24	0.15	-1.67	0.095	-0.91	0.66	-1.37	0.171
Highest level of education (0=School or below)												
Undergraduate	1.71	0.98	1.74	0.082	-0.17	0.17	-0.96	0.337	-0.67	0.79	-0.85	0.395
Masters	1.95	1.04	1.87	0.062	0.01	0.18	0.05	0.959	-0.81	0.84	-0.97	0.334

Doctorate	2.02	1.15	1.77	0.078	-0.13	0.20	-0.66	0.508	-1.14	0.92	-1.24	0.217
Marital status (0=Single, separated, divorced, widowed)												
Partnered, not living together	2.22	1.30	1.70	0.089	-0.62	0.24	-2.63	0.009	0.77	1.06	0.73	0.467
Married or living with partner	2.84	0.68	4.21	<0.001	-1.16	0.12	-9.62	<0.001	-1.84	0.55	-3.34	0.001
Live with children (0=No)												
Yes	1.13	0.77	1.46	0.144	-0.13	0.14	-0.94	0.349	-2.03	0.62	-3.26	0.001
Country (0=United Kingdom)												
United States	1.88	0.75	2.50	0.013	-0.08	0.13	-0.60	0.547	-2.72	0.61	-4.47	<0.001
Other	2.89	0.90	3.22	0.001	-0.16	0.16	-0.99	0.325	-3.01	0.73	-4.13	<0.001
Communicated via verbal means (0=Average)												
Less than average	-1.62	0.74	-2.20	0.028	0.18	0.13	1.35	0.177	0.86	0.60	1.45	0.148
More than average	-0.09	0.72	-0.13	0.897	0.16	0.13	1.21	0.227	0.18	0.58	0.31	0.759
Communicated face-to-face (0=Average)												
Less than average	-0.91	0.78	-1.17	0.244	0.08	0.14	0.56	0.578	-0.06	0.64	-0.10	0.920
More than average	0.46	0.76	0.61	0.544	-0.29	0.14	-2.15	0.031	-0.71	0.62	-1.15	0.249
Left the house to exercise (0=Average)												
Less than average	0.39	0.82	0.47	0.639	-0.28	0.15	-1.88	0.060	-0.43	0.67	-0.64	0.525
More than average	3.10	0.76	4.06	<0.001	-0.36	0.14	-2.66	0.008	-2.60	0.62	-4.21	<0.001
Working during pandemic (0=No)												
Yes	1.90	0.79	2.40	0.017	-0.10	0.14	-0.72	0.474	-1.82	0.64	-2.83	0.005
Period of isolation >1 week (0=No)												
Yes	-0.57	0.68	-0.84	0.402	0.49	0.12	4.02	<0.001	0.95	0.55	1.72	0.087
Companion animal guardian (0=No)												
Yes	-1.20	1.19	-1.01	0.315	-0.06	0.21	-0.29	0.771	0.07	0.97	0.07	0.944
Dog guardian (0=No)												
Yes	-1.08	0.80	-1.35	0.179	-0.07	0.14	-0.47	0.640	1.38	0.65	2.13	0.034
Cat guardian (0=No)												
Yes	0.44	0.73	0.60	0.549	0.02	0.13	0.19	0.852	0.55	0.59	0.93	0.355
Fish guardian (0=No)												
Yes	1.03	0.82	1.25	0.212	0.12	0.15	0.79	0.432	0.13	0.66	0.20	0.842
Other companion animal guardian (0=No)												
Yes	-0.56	0.79	-0.71	0.478	0.05	0.14	0.33	0.742	0.51	0.64	0.79	0.427

Partnered, not living together	1.02	0.64	1.59	0.113	1.35	1.14	1.18	0.238
Married or living with partner	-0.63	0.32	-1.94	0.052	<0.01	0.59	<0.01	0.999
Live with children (0=No)								
Yes	-0.31	0.37	-0.83	0.406	0.38	0.67	0.56	0.574
Country (0=United Kingdom)								
United States	-0.25	0.36	-0.68	0.494	-1.42	0.66	-2.16	0.031
Other	-0.68	0.43	-1.59	0.113	-2.28	0.79	-2.90	0.004
Communicated via verbal means (0=Average)								
Less than average	0.57	0.35	1.63	0.104	1.10	0.64	1.71	0.088
More than average	0.92	0.34	2.68	0.008	1.39	0.63	2.21	0.028
Communicated face-to-face (0=Average)								
Less than average	0.20	0.38	0.53	0.594	-0.28	0.69	-0.41	0.682
More than average	0.01	0.37	0.03	0.980	-1.62	0.67	-2.42	0.016
Left the house to exercise (0=Average)								
Less than average	-0.22	0.40	-0.55	0.581	-1.04	0.72	-1.44	0.150
More than average	-0.82	0.37	-2.25	0.025	-2.14	0.67	-3.20	0.001
Working during pandemic (0=No)								
Yes	-0.54	0.38	-1.42	0.156	-0.25	0.69	-0.37	0.713
Period of isolation >1 week (0=No)								
Yes	1.09	0.33	3.30	0.001	0.90	0.59	1.51	0.131
Companion animal guardian (0=No)								
Yes	-0.20	0.57	-0.36	0.720	0.88	1.05	0.84	0.400
Dog guardian (0=No)								
Yes	-0.01	0.38	-0.03	0.980	<0.01	0.70	<0.01	0.996
Cat guardian (0=No)								
Yes	0.33	0.35	0.94	0.349	0.29	0.64	0.45	0.656
Fish guardian (0=No)								
Yes	0.63	0.39	1.60	0.111	<0.01	0.72	<0.01	1.000
Other companion animal guardian (0=No)								
Yes	0.81	0.38	2.15	0.032	0.65	0.68	0.94	0.345

Note: $\hat{\beta}$ are unstandardised regression coefficients, results in bold are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Table S2 Results of robust hierarchical regression analyses to examine the influence of level of engagement with companion animals on loneliness and mental well-being among companion animal guardians

	Mental well-being				UCLA Loneliness Scale				Depression			
	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Fishes	$R^2 = 0.029$ $\chi^2(10) = 5.37, p = 0.865, n = 200$				$R^2 = 0.048$ $\chi^2(10) = 9.45, p = 0.450, n = 208$				$R^2 = 0.026$ $\chi^2(10) = 5.33, p = 0.868, n = 204$			
Intercept	44.67	4.74	9.42	<0.001	5.59	0.88	6.35	<0.001	8.58	3.99	2.15	0.033
Primary caregiver (0=No)												
Responsibility equally shared with another	2.22	4.05	0.55	0.585	-0.20	0.75	-0.27	0.788	-0.60	3.40	-0.18	0.860
Yes	-0.34	3.91	-0.09	0.931	0.07	0.73	0.09	0.926	1.03	3.31	0.31	0.756
Time spent daily on tank/pond maintenance (0= An average amount)												
Less than average	0.47	2.29	0.20	0.838	-0.17	0.42	-0.40	0.690	2.48	1.91	1.30	0.196
More than average	0.90	2.19	0.41	0.683	-0.44	0.41	-1.08	0.282	-0.68	1.83	-0.37	0.712
Time spent daily feeding fishes (0= An average amount)												
Less than average	2.07	4.14	0.50	0.618	-0.61	0.77	-0.79	0.431	-1.21	3.47	-0.35	0.727
More than average	0.66	1.99	0.33	0.740	0.10	0.37	0.27	0.791	-0.42	1.68	-0.25	0.801
Time spent daily watching fishes (0= An average amount)												
Less than average	2.22	2.28	0.97	0.332	0.08	0.43	0.19	0.848	-2.51	1.92	-1.31	0.193
More than average	-1.04	2.10	-0.49	0.623	0.18	0.39	0.46	0.647	0.01	1.75	0.01	0.996
Time spent daily talking to fishes (0= An average amount)												
Less than average	0.26	2.06	0.13	0.900	-0.76	0.38	-1.98	0.049	0.87	1.74	0.50	0.618
More than average	0.90	2.28	0.39	0.694	-0.46	0.42	-1.08	0.280	0.68	1.91	0.36	0.721
	Mental well-being				UCLA Loneliness Scale				Depression			
	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Dogs	$R^2 = 0.053$ $\chi^2(12) = 30.65, p = 0.002, n = 581$				$R^2 = 0.063$ $\chi^2(12) = 38.41, p < 0.001, n = 609$				$R^2 = 0.056$ $\chi^2(12) = 34.89, p < 0.001, n = 592$			
Intercept	39.48	2.62	15.08	<0.001	5.40	0.46	11.71	<0.001	14.17	2.12	6.67	<0.001
Primary caregiver (0=No)												
Responsibility equally shared with another	7.82	2.27	3.45	0.001	-1.33	0.40	-3.35	0.001	-6.46	1.84	-3.50	0.001
Yes	6.97	2.28	3.06	0.002	-0.92	0.40	-2.31	0.021	-6.73	1.85	-3.64	<0.001
Time spent daily walking dogs (0= An average amount)												
Less than average	-0.92	0.97	-0.95	0.343	0.41	0.17	2.35	0.019	1.05	0.80	1.31	0.189
More than average	-0.20	1.05	-0.19	0.851	0.22	0.19	1.16	0.245	0.25	0.86	0.29	0.775
Time spent daily feeding dogs (0= An average amount)												
Less than average	1.75	1.00	1.76	0.080	-0.06	0.18	-0.36	0.716	-0.33	0.81	-0.41	0.685
More than average	0.34	1.06	0.32	0.748	-0.08	0.19	-0.45	0.651	-0.72	0.87	-0.84	0.403

Time spent daily petting dogs (0= An average amount)														
Less than average	-0.33	1.25	-0.27	0.790	-0.08	0.22	-0.36	0.723	-0.91	1.02	-0.89	0.374		
More than average	-2.22	1.08	-2.07	0.039	0.09	0.19	0.45	0.656	1.78	0.88	2.03	0.043		
Time spent daily talking to dogs (0= An average amount)														
Less than average	2.41	1.22	1.97	0.050	-0.33	0.22	-1.49	0.138	-1.28	1.00	-1.28	0.202		
More than average	1.02	1.19	0.85	0.395	0.14	0.21	0.66	0.513	-0.08	0.98	-0.08	0.936		
Time spent daily on other activities with dogs (0=An average amount)														
Less than average	-1.80	1.15	-1.56	0.119	0.49	0.20	2.40	0.017	0.97	0.94	1.03	0.302		
More than average	-0.31	1.10	-0.28	0.778	0.34	0.20	1.71	0.087	0.74	0.90	0.82	0.413		
			Mental well-being				UCLA Loneliness Scale				Depression			
			$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Cats			$R^2 = 0.036$ $\chi^2(10) = 14.24, p = 0.162, n = 415$				$R^2 = 0.035$ $\chi^2(10) = 14.83, p = 0.139, n = 442$				$R^2 = 0.052$ $\chi^2(10) = 23.39, p = 0.009, n = 429$			
Intercept	43.88	2.77	15.85	<0.001	5.57	0.54	10.31	<0.001	12.65	2.28	5.54	<0.001		
Primary caregiver (0=No)														
Responsibility equally shared with another	2.04	2.26	0.90	0.369	-0.76	0.44	-1.72	0.086	-2.78	1.86	-1.49	0.137		
Yes	0.74	2.25	0.33	0.742	-0.28	0.44	-0.62	0.535	-2.04	1.86	-1.10	0.273		
Time spent daily feeding cats (0= An average amount)														
Less than average	1.76	1.16	1.52	0.130	-0.17	0.22	-0.78	0.437	-0.29	0.95	-0.31	0.761		
More than average	-0.42	1.34	-0.32	0.751	-0.06	0.25	-0.25	0.803	0.13	1.11	0.12	0.907		
Time spent daily petting cats (0= An average amount)														
Less than average	-0.46	1.31	-0.35	0.724	0.13	0.25	0.52	0.603	1.42	1.08	1.32	0.188		
More than average	-1.05	1.42	-0.74	0.461	0.46	0.27	1.69	0.093	1.31	1.18	1.11	0.268		
Time spent daily talking to cats (0= An average amount)														
Less than average	2.58	1.40	1.85	0.065	-0.38	0.27	-1.43	0.154	-4.29	1.15	-3.73	<0.001		
More than average	1.14	1.48	0.77	0.441	-0.49	0.28	-1.72	0.087	-2.42	1.23	-1.96	0.050		
Time spent daily on other activities with cats (0= An average amount)														
Less than average	-1.50	1.38	-1.09	0.278	0.15	0.26	0.59	0.558	0.24	1.13	0.21	0.833		
More than average	-0.43	1.50	-0.29	0.772	0.07	0.28	0.26	0.796	0.66	1.22	0.54	0.591		

Less than average	-1.59	0.58	-2.74	0.006	-1.33	1.10	-1.21	0.226	
More than average	-0.19	0.51	-0.37	0.711	0.62	0.94	0.66	0.511	
Time spent daily talking to dogs (0= An average amount)									
Less than average	-0.89	0.57	-1.56	0.120	-1.57	1.07	-1.46	0.144	
More than average	-0.51	0.56	-0.91	0.363	-1.30	1.04	-1.25	0.213	
Time spent daily on other activities with dogs (0=An average amount)									
Less than average	0.17	0.54	0.31	0.754	0.38	1.01	0.38	0.704	
More than average	0.95	0.52	1.83	0.067	1.35	0.97	1.40	0.162	
		Anxiety				Stress			
		$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	$\hat{\beta}$	SE	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Cats		$R^2 = 0.045$				$R^2 = 0.049$			
		$\chi^2(10) = 20.48, p = 0.025, n = 430$				$\chi^2(10) = 21.25, p = 0.019, n = 428$			
Intercept	4.94	1.41	3.51	<0.001	15.76	2.53	6.23	<0.001	
Primary caregiver (0=No)									
Responsibility equally shared with another	-1.12	1.16	-0.96	0.336	-2.73	2.07	-1.32	0.188	
Yes	-0.83	1.16	-0.72	0.474	-3.65	2.07	-1.77	0.078	
Time spent daily feeding cats (0= An average amount)									
Less than average	0.40	0.58	0.70	0.486	-1.05	1.04	-1.02	0.310	
More than average	-0.08	0.68	-0.12	0.904	0.04	1.21	0.04	0.972	
Time spent daily petting cats (0= An average amount)									
Less than average	1.19	0.65	1.83	0.068	1.32	1.17	1.13	0.261	
More than average	1.34	0.71	1.88	0.061	1.45	1.29	1.13	0.260	
Time spent daily talking to cats (0= An average amount)									
Less than average	-1.35	0.70	-1.94	0.053	-3.65	1.25	-2.92	0.004	
More than average	-1.76	0.75	-2.35	0.019	-3.01	1.35	-2.23	0.026	
Time spent daily on other activities with cats (0= An average amount)									
Less than average	-0.73	0.68	-1.07	0.285	0.07	1.23	0.06	0.956	
More than average	0.96	0.74	1.29	0.197	1.39	1.34	1.04	0.299	

Note: $\hat{\beta}$ are unstandardised regression coefficients, results in bold are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Appendix J: Copies of materials used (Chapter 6)

Pre-study questionnaire

1. What is your age (please state)?
2. What gender do you identify as?
Male/Female/Other/Prefer not to say
3. What is your ethnicity?
White/Asian or Asian British/Black or Black British/Mixed or Multiple/Other Ethnic Group/Prefer not to say
4. What is your marital status?
Married/Co-habiting/Separated/Divorced/Widowed/Single/Other/Prefer not to say
5. Do you have any children (aged 16 years or under)?
Yes/No

IF YES: Please state number and ages of children
6. Do you have any pets?
Yes/No
7. Where in the United Kingdom do you live?
England/Scotland/Wales/Northern Ireland
8. Which category does your occupation fall into?
Manager, director or senior officials/Professional occupations/Associate professional and technical occupations/Administrative and secretarial occupations/Skilled trades occupations/Caring, leisure and other service occupations/Sales and customer service occupations/Process, plant, and machine operatives/Elementary occupations/Prefer not to say
9. Did you ever work from home before the COVID-19 pandemic?
Yes/No

IF YES: How often did you work from home before the COVID-19 pandemic?
Once a month or less/A few times a month/Once a week/A few times a week/Most days/Always
10. How often do you work from home right now?
Once a month or less/A few times a month/Once a week/A few times a week/Most days/Always
11. Do you work fixed or flexible hours?
Fixed/Flexible

12. Perceived Stress Scale (Please see Cohen and Williamson, 1988)
13. Work Protection Preference (Please see Methot and LePine 2016)
14. Home Protection Preference (Please see Kreiner 2006)

Assessments

To be completed three times per day (at start, middle and end of working day)

1. Stress Visual Analogue Scale

“How much stress do you feel right now at this moment?”

(None – The most severe imaginable)

2. Digit Span Tasks

Participants were be presented with a series of digits on screen and required to repeat them back either in the same order (i.e. “3, 1, 9” as “3, 1, 9”) or backwards (i.e. “3, 1, 9” as “9, 1, 3”). As the task was completed online, responses were made using buttons on keyboard rather than verbally. A trial run was completed before each task.

Post-study questionnaire

1. How many hours did you work today?
2. How productive do you feel you have been today?
(Not at all productive – The most productive I could have been)
3. How would you rate the quality of the work you completed today?
(Lowest quality – Highest quality)
4. It is recommended that people using display screen equipment (e.g. computers) take short, frequent breaks from looking at the screen (e.g. 5 minutes once per hour). This could be to complete other work-related tasks or be non-work related. How much would you agree that you did this today?
(Not at all – Very much so)
5. Today, how often would you say you have been distracted from your work?
(Not at all – Extremely often)
6. From the list of potential distractions below, please select the three options which you feel were most distracting to you today. You may add additional options if you wish.
 - a. Other adults living in my house
 - b. Children living in my house
 - c. Animals living in my house
 - d. Worry about personal issues (e.g. financial, medical etc.)
 - e. Social media
 - f. Colleagues
 - g. Work-related issues (e.g. responding to emails)
 - h. Friends/family from outside my household (e.g. *via* telephone)
 - i. Neighbours (e.g. noise disturbances)
 - j. Current events/news media
 - k. Other option 1 (please state)
 - l. Other option 2 (please state)
 - m. Other option 3 (please state)
7. Daily home-to-work conflict (Adapted version of Work-Family Conflict Scale (Carlson et al. 2000) used by Delanoeije et al. 2019)
8. While you were working from home today, were there any other adults (anyone 18+ years) present in your home? (Yes/No)

IF YES: How long was another adult present in your home today?
 - a. All/most of the time (for at least half of your working hours)
 - b. Some of the time (up to half of your working hours)
- 9-12. Repeat question 8 for: young adults (17-18 years), children aged 12-16 years, children aged 5-12 years and children under 5 years.

13. Thinking about both your work and your personal life, what (if anything) would you say are the benefits of working from home?
14. Thinking about both your work and your personal life, what (if anything) would you say are the disadvantages of working from home?
15. Do you have any pets (please tick all that apply)?
 - a. No pets
 - b. Dogs
 - c. Cats
 - d. Fish
 - e. Other (please state)

[These questions only for people who keep dogs/cats/fishes]

16. During your working hours today (inclusive of breaks), how often did you interact with your **dogs** (e.g. stroke them, talk to them, walk them etc.)?
(Not at all – Extremely often)
17. “During your working hours today (inclusive of breaks), where were your **dogs** most of the time?”
In the same room as me/Elsewhere in my house/Outside my house
18. When working in the office, do you have the option to take your dog to work?

Yes, and I take my dog to work often or always/Yes, and I take my dog to work occasionally/Yes, but I never take my dog to work/No, I do not have this option/Not applicable, I always work from home
19. During your working hours today (inclusive of breaks), how often did you interact with your **cats** (e.g. stroke them, talk to them, let them inside/outside etc.)?
(Not at all – Extremely often)
20. During your working hours today (inclusive of breaks), where were your **cats** most of the time?
In the same room as me/Elsewhere in my house/Outside my house
21. During your working hours today (inclusive of breaks), how often did you interact with your **fish** (e.g. watch them, feed them, talk to them etc.)?
(Not at all – Extremely often)
22. In relation to where you are when working from home, where are your fish?
In the same room as me/Elsewhere in my house/Outside my house

[These questions only for people who keep companion animals (any type)]

23. Thinking about your work, your personal life and your pets, what (if anything) would you say are the benefits of working from home with pets?
24. Thinking about your work, your personal life and your pets, what (if anything) would you say are the disadvantages of working from home with pets?

[These questions only for people who do not keep companion animals]

25. You have indicated that you do not currently keep any companion animals (pets), but what do you think might be the advantages (if any) of working from home with pets?

26. What do you think might be the disadvantages (if any) of working from home with pets?

Bound copies of publications

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The effects of interacting with fish in aquariums on human health and well-being: A systematic review

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Abstract

Background

Most research into the health benefits of human-animal interaction has focused on species that interact physically with humans, such as dogs. This may be unsuitable for certain populations for reasons including accessibility and the risk of negative consequences to both the person and the animal. However, some research has associated viewing fish in aquariums with positive well-being outcomes; as there is no physical contact with the animal, this form of interaction carries less risk. At present, little is known about the specific benefits of human-fish interaction.

Objectives

To explore current evidence relating to the psychological and physiological benefits of interacting with fish in aquariums.

Methods

Systematic searches were conducted to identify relevant primary research of any design. All forms of interaction were considered, including keeping fish as companion animals and fish aquarium-based interventions. "Non-live" alternatives, such as videos, were also considered. This review was conducted according to a registered protocol (PROSPERO ID: CRD42018090466).

Results

Nineteen studies were included. Two provided tentative evidence that keeping home aquaria is associated with relaxation. The remaining studies involved novel interactions with fish in home or public aquariums. Outcomes relating to anxiety, relaxation and/or

drafts of the manuscript. Mars Petcare UK played no role in study design, data collection, or analysis, but approved the final manuscript before publication. The remaining funding for the PhD was secured from the University of the West of Scotland.

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physiological stress were commonly assessed; evidence was mixed with both positive and null findings. Preliminary support was found for effects on mood, pain, nutritional intake and body weight, but not loneliness. All studies had methodological issues and risk of bias was either high or unclear.

Conclusions

Review findings suggest that interacting with fish in aquariums has the potential to benefit human well-being, although research on this topic is currently limited. Future research should aim to address gaps in the evidence, such as whether and how the type of human-fish interaction can influence well-being outcomes. Researchers should also aim to address the methodological concerns highlighted in this review.

Introduction

Interacting with non-human animals (hereafter "animals") has been associated with a range of well-being benefits among humans. Companion animal guardianship has been linked with improved physical and psychological outcomes, including lower blood pressure [1,2], reduced risk of cardiovascular disease and lower rates of mortality [3,4], reduced loneliness [5], and increased emotional support during mental health crisis [6]. In fact, research has indicated that many people choose to keep companion animals for reasons associated with well-being, such as companionship, emotional support, and improved physical health [7,8]. Similarly, animal-assisted interventions (AAI) are initiated with the specific purpose of improving one or more aspects of human well-being; they include goal-oriented animal-assisted therapies delivered by healthcare professionals, and animal-assisted activities which are often volunteer-led and may lack specific treatment goals [9]. These interventions have been used to support improvements in physical, psychological, and behavioural outcomes for a wide range of populations across the lifespan [10–14].

Despite these positive findings, research into the benefits of human-animal interaction (HAI) is far from conclusive. Some studies have shown no relationship, or a negative relationship, between keeping companion animals and physical or mental health outcomes [15–20]. Furthermore, as most research in this area is correlational it is difficult to determine causality; better health may increase the likelihood of adopting a companion animal, rather than the reverse [21], or health and companion animal guardianship may be linked by other factors, such as sociodemographic characteristics or health-related behaviours [19,22,23]. Similarly, while AAI are commonly perceived as beneficial, especially among those with a positive attitude towards companion animals, some authors suggest that these benefits have been overstated [24]. In reality, research concerning these interventions is frequently anecdotal or descriptive in nature, with high levels of heterogeneity in factors such as the type of animal, the nature of the interaction, and the setting [25,26]. Methodological issues are also commonplace and include the absence of appropriate comparison groups, reliance on small samples, failure to randomise participants to conditions, and a lack of blinding for both participants and assessors [25–28]. It is therefore difficult to draw firm conclusions about the efficacy of these interventions [26–28].

These inconsistencies are further confounded by a lack of consensus about the mechanisms through which HAI may improve human well-being [9]. Researchers have often referred to

the biophilia hypothesis [29,30], which proposes that humans have an innate affiliation with other forms of life. This perspective suggests that because human evolution occurred almost exclusively in natural environments, people are predisposed to respond positively to aspects of nature that would have increased fitness in the ancestral environment, and negatively to those which would have decreased fitness [31]. For example, people typically respond positively to natural landscapes providing sources of food, water or shelter, and negatively to animals which pose a threat, such as spiders or snakes [31]. Although the biophilia hypothesis has been criticised for offering too broad a perspective and for lacking falsifiability [32], researchers have drawn on these ideas to develop theories with more explanatory power. For example, the biophilia-effect suggests that because the behaviour of animals is indicative of the presence or absence of threats in the environment, interaction with a calm or friendly animal may support human well-being by promoting relaxation and reducing physiological arousal [33,34].

Other popular explanations centre on the social support provided by companion animals. In the context of attachment theory [35–37] for example, humans are argued to form bonds with their companion animals which are comparable to those formed within close interpersonal relationships [38]. This theory suggests that humans form strong emotional attachments with certain individuals, or “attachment figures”. These attachments are characterised by the presence of proximity seeking behaviours, distress at separation, and the provision of unique emotional support that cannot be replicated within other interpersonal relationships. Although attachment theory originally focused on the relationship between an infant and their primary caregiver (usually their mother), it was later expanded to incorporate the bonds which form in other close relationships, such as with siblings or romantic partners [39,40]. More recently, attachment theory has been applied to human-animal relationships, with findings suggesting that both the human and animal can serve as the attachment figure and provide feelings of comfort and safety during times of uncertainty or stress [20,38]. Furthermore, support provided by animals may be particularly effective, as it is unconditional and non-judgemental [41], and because physical touch—an important component of emotional support—is often discouraged with other humans but not with animals [42].

Alternatively, HAI may operate via distraction, whereby attention is diverted away from a perceived stressor to lessen the experience of negative mental states; this may be of most relevance in the context of AAI [25]. Research has indicated that young children preferentially attend to images or videos of animals compared to non-living objects [43], and will choose to interact with real (but caged) animals over toys resembling those animals [44]. Similarly, adults have been found to more rapidly identify changes in the location of living targets (animals and people), compared to inanimate objects [45]. These findings suggest that animals may be particularly effective at attracting human attention. However, animals are not unique in being an effective source of distraction, and so similar benefits may be achieved through the use of alternative, and possibly more cost effective, stimuli [25,42].

This brief overview is by no means exhaustive and several other theories have been proposed [9,33,42]. Despite these divergent approaches however, one model provides a framework which may potentially incorporate some, or all, of the above discussed mechanisms. The biopsychosocial model [46] proposes that health is a continuum influenced by interacting biological, psychological and social factors; changes in one factor may influence the others and in turn impact health. For example, psychosocial stresses may lead to physiological responses including increased heart rate and blood pressure, or reduced immune function. Ultimately, these responses may have a negative effect on health, resulting in increased morbidity and mortality [47,48]. Equally however, some psychological and social factors may have a protective influence on health; higher levels of social support for example, have been linked to a reduced risk of cardiovascular disease [47]. In the context of this model, there are numerous

ways in which interaction with companion animals may impact human health. For example, owning a dog may lead to improved health through increased physical activity, while animals may provide social support either directly, or indirectly by facilitating social interactions with other individuals [49,50]. Conversely however, the grief associated with the loss of a companion animal may have a detrimental effect on human well-being [50]. Thus, while the biopsychosocial model provides a potential framework for integrating multiple theories, it also highlights the likelihood that no one mechanism can account for the diverse effects of HAI. One area which warrants further consideration is whether the observed benefits are influenced by the type of animal involved in the interaction [26,51].

Multiple reviews and meta-analyses have noted that dogs are the animal most frequently involved in AAI (although other species such as horses are also commonly involved) [10,12,51]. Similarly, much research into companion animals has focused on those animals that can interact physically with humans, such as dogs and cats [3,52]. This type of interaction may not however, be suitable among all populations. For instance, people in rented accommodation are often restricted in the types of companion animal they may keep in their home, and physical interactions may be inappropriate for people with declining health or limited physical capacity [52]. Similarly, dog-assisted (or similar) interventions often rely on volunteer services [51] and may require supervision of the client and animal to minimise risk, which can lead to infrequent and inconsistent exposure [53,54]. Issues may also arise where there is potential for aggression from the animal, where individuals have allergies, compromised immune systems, or phobias, or where contact with the animal could lead to accidental injury (e.g. scratches, falls) [51,55,56]. Animal welfare is also a concern, as some clients may behave aggressively or unpredictably towards the animal, or the animal may become stressed during the interaction [51,57]. Therefore, research into the effects of HAI with less physically interactive animals is needed to determine whether benefits may be experienced.

One form of HAI which has attracted relatively little investigation is the role of fish aquariums. Early research indicated a link between viewing fish in aquariums and benefits such as reduced blood pressure and increased relaxation [58–60], perhaps contributing to the widespread notion that aquariums are beneficial in healthcare settings [61]. More recently, research has linked interaction with fish in aquariums to outcomes such as reduced anxiety [62], increased tolerance to pain [63], and improvements in nutritional intake and body weight among residents of specialised dementia units [64,65]. As with HAI research more broadly, the mechanisms underlying these benefits are unclear. Research with people who keep home aquaria has indicated that some individuals consider their fish to be a source of companionship, and feel an emotional bond with the animals [52]; this suggests social support and attachment may play a role in the beneficial effects of human-fish interaction. However, while research has shown the presence of attachment behaviours in other human-animal relationships, such as with dogs [66,67], it is not evident that fish exhibit behaviours such as proximity seeking or separation distress. Thus, while individuals may believe there to be an emotional bond between themselves and their fish, it is unclear whether this constitutes a true attachment bond as described by attachment theory [35–37]. Alternatively, watching fish swimming may simply be a source of distraction; this is supported by research which has shown positive physiological effects associated with viewing videos of animals, including fish [68].

An alternative perspective still comes from theories concerning the restorative value of nature. These theories suggest that exposure to unthreatening nature can help restore depleted cognitive resources, and support rapid emotional and physiological recovery from stressful events [62]. Although most of this research has focused on natural or “green” landscapes, some studies have directly explored the role that encounters with wildlife play in human well-being. For example, research has suggested that many people feed wild birds because doing so

brings them pleasure [70], while watching wild birds feeding is associated with increased relaxation and connectedness to nature [71]. Similarly, improvements in self-reported control, happiness, and activity were observed among a sample of nursing home residents who were given the responsibility of caring for a bird feeder, while no changes were observed among residents who did not receive such an opportunity [72]. Furthermore, research has suggested that for some individuals, wildlife encounters are a key motivation for visiting natural (coastal) environments [73], and are associated with a range of benefits to human psychological well-being [74]. Given that the ways in which people interact with birds and other forms of wildlife are similar to the ways in which people interact with fish in aquariums (i.e. the interaction is largely visual), it may be that watching fish swimming promotes human well-being because this activity provides exposure to unthreatening nature, leading to restoration.

Irrespective of the mechanism, these findings suggest that human-fish interactions may be a viable alternative to more commonly researched forms of HAI. Furthermore, aquariums may overcome some of the issues associated with these forms of interaction. As a constant feature within the environment, fish aquariums are available to the client at any time and for as long as required, thus may provide greater flexibility in exposure than AAI which rely on visitation programmes [53]. Even other types of resident animal cannot provide constant interaction, as this would be detrimental to their welfare [51]. The monetary cost associated with installation and upkeep of a fish tank is also much smaller than that associated with other companion animals [51], although regular maintenance of the aquarium is needed, and requires an individual with knowledge of the necessary processes to ensure the welfare of the fish is not compromised. Aside from the person responsible for maintaining the fish tanks however, the passive nature of viewing fish in an aquarium means that even individuals with limited physical capacity are able to interact with the animals [52]. There are no significant risks from aggression or allergies, and fewer risks associated with accidental injury due to the lack of physical contact with the animal (although possible injury could be sustained while installing or maintaining the tank, or if someone or something damages the tank, causing a break). While there is a small risk of bacterial infection associated with keeping home aquaria, this is rare and requires physical contact with the fish or water, so can be effectively minimised through careful hygiene practices [75].

Despite the potential benefits however, research in this area is limited, and to date only one review has sought to explore the potential benefits of fish aquariums to human health and well-being [26]. However, this narrative review explored these benefits in the context of restorative environments and biodiversity, with a focus on the value of public aquariums; although there was reference to research conducted with home aquaria, this overview was not comprehensive. Furthermore, consideration should be given to the quality and strength of evidence when drawing conclusions from existing research findings; for this purpose, a systematic review of the literature is needed.

Review questions

Through a systematic review of the literature, this article aims to explore the psychological and physiological benefits of interacting with fish in aquariums. Given that previous research has highlighted potential benefits associated with viewing videos of fish [68], simulated or "non-live" alternatives will also be considered. The following research questions will be addressed:

1. What influence does interaction with fish in aquariums (live or non-live) have on the psychological well-being of human participants?
2. What influence does interaction with fish in aquariums (live or non-live) have on the physiological well-being of human participants?

In addition, this review will aim to identify:

- The attitudes of human participants regarding the benefits and challenges of interacting with fish in aquariums;
- Any adverse effects which may be experienced by humans when interacting with fish in aquariums;
- Any concerns regarding animal welfare which may be encountered during human interaction with fish in aquariums.

Methods

This systematic review was conducted according to a registered protocol (PROSPERO ID: CRD42018090466), and adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis (PRISMA) statements [77]. Prior to commencing the review, the PROSPERO register was searched to ensure no similar reviews were currently underway; the following terms were used: "fish", "aquarium", "animal assisted intervention", "animal assisted therapy", "pet therapy", "human-animal interaction" and "companion animal".

Search strategy

Systematic searches conducted in January 2018 identified peer-reviewed evidence and grey literature on the topic of fish aquarium-based HAI. A four-step search strategy was developed through discussion between the authors, and consulting previous systematic reviews in the field of HAI. Searches were conducted in the following electronic databases: Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Education Source, ERIC, Health Source—Nursing/Academic Edition, MEDLINE, PsycARTICLES, Psychology and Behavioural Sciences Collection, PubMed, SAGE Journals ONLINE, Science Direct, and Web of Science (Core Collection). Steps one to three involved identifying all records relating to 1) HAI and related theories, 2) relevant health and well-being outcomes, and 3) fish and/or aquariums. Steps one and two were conducted in all fields to maximise identification of relevant literature. However, as much research in this field is conducted with other species, step three was limited to title, abstract and keywords only (or the nearest alternative). Step four combined the results from these searches; an example search strategy is shown in Table 1. Results from electronic databases were supplemented with searches in Google Scholar, ETHOS, and websites on HAI (WALTHAM Science, HABRI-Central, and Animals and Society Institute), and by hand-searching the reference lists of included studies and relevant review articles for additional references.

Inclusion criteria

Based on preliminary searches, research in this area was anticipated to be both limited in quantity and varied in design. Therefore, the inclusion criteria were deliberately broad to incorporate the full scope of research related to effects of interacting with fish in aquariums on human health and well-being. The inclusion criteria were as follows:

Participants: there was no limitation on the participant populations of included studies. Studies involving both healthy and clinical samples of any age were included.

Intervention/exposure: any form of human interaction with fish in aquariums was included, from passive exposure to fish tanks, actively viewing fish swimming, to caring for fish in aquariums. Non-live alternatives (e.g. videos) were also considered. There were no limitations

Table 1. Example search strategy (PubMed).

Step 1 (all fields):	#1	"human/animal interaction"
	#2	"human/animal relationship"
	#3	"human/animal bond"
	#4	"animal facilitated intervention"
	#5	"animal facilitated therap"
	#6	"animal facilitated activit"
	#7	"pet therap"
	#8	"pet facilitated therap"
	#9	"pet interaction"
	#10	"pet ownership"
	#11	"companion animal"
	#12	attachment
	#13	biophilia
	#14	biopsychosocial
	#15	"social support"
	#16	"social mediation"
	#17	"prepared learning theory"
	#18	"self-efficacy"
	#19	modelling
	#20	"role theory"
	#21	"polyval theory"
	#22	"attention restoration theory"
	#23	"stress recovery theory"
Step 2 (all fields):	#24	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12 OR #13 OR #14 OR #15 OR #16 OR #17 OR #18 OR #19 OR #20 OR #21 OR #22 OR #23
	#25	health
	#26	wellbeing
	#27	anxiety
	#28	arousal
	#29	stress
	#30	relaxation
	#31	"quality of life"
	#32	"life satisfaction"
	#33	restoration
	#34	recovery
	#35	pain
	#36	loneliness
	#37	#25 OR #26 OR #27 OR #28 OR #29#31 OR #32 OR #33 OR #34 OR #35 OR #36
Step 3 (title/abstract):	#38	aquarium
	#39	"aquatic environment"
	#40	aquaria
	#41	"fish"
	#42	"fish tank"
	#43	#38 OR #39 OR #40 OR #41 OR #42
Step 4:	#44	#24 AND #37 AND #43

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regarding the length, frequency or duration of exposure, or the setting. Studies were not excluded on the basis that other animals (e.g. corals) were also present in the aquariums.

Comparator: studies both with and without a control group were included. For those with a control group, any type of comparator was considered, including no treatment controls, alternative AAI, and alternative interventions without animal involvement.

Outcomes: the primary outcomes were psychological (e.g. anxiety, depression, behaviour change, social interaction) and physiological (e.g. blood pressure, heart rate, motor skills) well-being. Secondary outcomes were any adverse events experienced by human participants and any issues regarding animal welfare; participants' attitudes towards human-fish interaction were also considered, such as any benefits or limitations they had observed, or any evaluations of fish aquarium-based interventions.

Study Design: included studies were limited to primary research, but there were no limitations on study design; both quantitative and qualitative studies were included.

Exclusion criteria

Research was limited to articles published in the English language, with no limitations on date of publication. To enhance the quality of included studies, articles were limited to those published in peer reviewed journals and doctoral theses. Only research involving live fish or non-live alternatives (e.g. videos of fish) was included. Research relating to the health benefits of fish consumption, studies involving invasive research conducted on fish, and those relating to fishing/angling were excluded.

Study selection

The study selection process is outlined in Fig 1. All records identified via electronic databases ($n = 7248$) were exported into a single EndNote library and duplicates were removed. All remaining records ($n = 6978$) were then screened for inclusion in a two-stage process. Initially, the titles and abstracts of all records were assessed for relevance by two independent reviewers (HC/KS); the full-text of all remaining articles was then obtained and screened against the inclusion/exclusion criteria by two independent reviewers (HC/SV). At each stage, disagreements were resolved through discussion. Hand-searching of reference lists and supplementary searches on Google Scholar, EThOS, and HAI websites were also conducted to identify any additional studies of relevance ($n = 69$). The full-text of two records, including one unpublished thesis, could not be accessed and attempts to identify up to date contact details for the authors were unsuccessful, so these studies could not be included in the review. A third record (an unpublished thesis) could not be included for copyright reasons, as attempts at gaining the author's permission to cite the research were unsuccessful.

Data extraction & quality appraisal

Data from included studies were extracted by two independent reviewers (HC/SV) using a purpose-developed data extraction form (see S3 Appendix). The following data were extracted: general information (author, year, publication type and source, country, funding, conflicts of interest); study details (aims/objectives, dates of data collection, theoretical framework); methods (design, participant recruitment and characteristics, intervention, control, allocation to conditions, setting/context, primary outcomes, secondary outcomes); results (method of analysis, psychological outcomes, physiological outcomes, secondary outcomes); author conclusions; and reviewer comments. All discrepancies were resolved through discussion. To reflect the inclusion of both quantitative and qualitative research, risk of bias was assessed using the National Institute for Health & Care Excellence (NICE) Quality Appraisal Checklists for quantitative intervention studies, quantitative studies reporting a correlation, and qualitative studies

Fig 1. PRISMA flow diagram of study selection.

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[78]. Quality appraisal was conducted by two independent reviewers (HC/SV) and disagreements were resolved through discussion.

Reporting bias

To assess for selective reporting of outcomes, the methods section of included studies was compared to the presented results to identify any discrepancies and determine whether an adequate description of the results was provided. As no studies were conducted according to a published or registered protocol, it was not possible to draw comparisons between the study protocols and published results. Furthermore, as there was much heterogeneity in study outcomes it was not possible to assess for publication bias using funnel plots, as this is not recommended for use on outcomes assessed in fewer than ten studies [79].

Strength of evidence

The strength of the evidence was assessed using the Weight of Evidence approach [80] for each of the two review questions independently. This approach involves assessing each study against four criteria. *Weight of Evidence A* is a generic assessment of study quality, while *Weight of Evidence B* and *C* are review-specific, and relate respectively to the appropriateness of the research design and the relevance of the evidence in addressing the review question(s). The final criterion (*Weight of Evidence D*) is an overall assessment of the extent to which the study addresses the review question(s), and was calculated as the most common rating from the first three criteria (where assessments were "low", "medium" and "high" for the first three criteria, an overall weighting of "medium" was given). Assessments were made independently by two reviewers (HC/SV), with all disagreements resolved through discussion.

Results

Nineteen studies published in eighteen articles met the inclusion criteria and were included in the review (see Tables 2 and 3 for overview of included studies). All studies were published as peer reviewed journal articles, with publication years ranging from 1984 to 2017. Two articles [54,65] reported research conducted as part of the same project but it is unclear whether the same sample was used for both studies; as the articles reported different outcomes they were treated independently in this review. Most research was conducted in the USA ($n = 11$), with four studies conducted in the UK and one each in Germany, France, Taiwan and Australia.

The broad inclusion criteria meant there was substantial clinical and methodological heterogeneity between included studies, and so statistical meta-analysis was deemed inappropriate. Therefore, a narrative synthesis of the evidence was conducted using techniques described by Popay et al. [89]. A preliminary synthesis was developed using textual descriptions, tabulation, groupings and clusters; the relationships within and between studies were then explored through qualitative case descriptions and the use of idea webbing/conceptual mapping. The robustness of the synthesis was assessed by reflecting on the methods used in the review, and by considering the quality of included studies and the strength of the evidence. Findings from studies conducted with existing home aquaria owners ($n = 2$), and those using correlational designs ($n = 1$), are discussed independently from those involving novel interactions with fish in aquariums ($n = 16$); as four studies in the latter group related specifically to public aquariums they are also considered separately.

Fish as companion animals

Two studies were conducted with individuals who currently kept fish as companion animals to gain an understanding of their experiences. One was a phenomenological study which explored experiences of pet fish ownership through in-depth interviews ($n = 9$, M age = 34.9 years, 33% female) [52], while the second utilised a survey design and provided descriptive statistics on qualitative aspects of keeping home aquaria ($n = 100$, M age = 37.1 years, 50% female) [81]. Both studies identified relaxation and stress reduction as potential benefits of keeping fish as companion animals; this appeared to be primarily associated with watching the movements of the fish, although the sound of running water was also mentioned by some participants in one study [52]. Companionship was also identified as a potential benefit of keeping fish, although this was experienced to a much lesser extent than relaxation, with only a minority (5%) of participants in one study reporting this benefit. Other benefits associated with keeping fish included happiness [52], entertainment, and education [81]. A small number of participants (6%) in one study viewed their fish tanks as room decoration only [81]. Limitations to keeping fish were also identified. In one study, it was noted that fish cannot provide

Table 2. Summary of study characteristics of included studies.

First author and year	Design	Participants				Aquarium Intervention(s)	Comparator(s)	Setting (Country)
		Population	Total sample size (n)	Age (Mean)	Gender (% female)			
<i>Fish as companion animals</i>								
Kidd 1999 [81]	Survey	Pet fish owners	100	37.1 years	50%	-	-	Not applicable (USA)
Langford 2009 [52]	Phenomenological study, in-depth interviews	Pet fish owners	9	34.9 years	33%	-	-	Not applicable (Australia)
<i>Correlational studies</i>								
Iin 2013 [82]	Survey	Medical directors at accredited hospitals	737	49 years	8%	Presence of aquarium in workplace	Presence of other interior amenities (indoor plants, music, art and exhibitions; private or personalised spaces)	Accredited hospitals (Taiwan)
<i>Intervention studies</i>								
Barker 2003 [53]	Within-subjects ("cross over") study	Patients awaiting electroconvulsive therapy treatment	42 (only 30 included in analysis)	48.4 years	74%	10-gallon aquariums containing around five African cichlids, approx. 20-minutes of passive exposure (n = 30)	No aquarium (n = 30)	Folding/ waiting rooms at outpatient treatment centre (USA)
Buttelmann 2014 [62]	Between-subjects study without randomisation	Undergraduate students	71	22.5 years	92%	Five-minute interaction with one veiltail goldfish in 5.5l goldfish bowl, to "try and accustom it to humans" (n = 18)	Five-minute interaction with dog (n = 18) or plant (n = 17), or no activity (n = 18)	University laboratory (Germany)
Cole 2000 [83]	Before-and-after pilot study	Patients awaiting heart transplantation	10	55.9 years	20%	15-gallon saltwater tank containing four colourful fish, 11 days (n = 10)	-	Hospital rooms (USA)
Dechriver 1990 [84]	Between-subjects study with randomisation	Older adults in publicly subsidised housing	27	Median per condition = 73–76 years	78%	Eight minutes viewing 10-gallon tank with nine fish (2 black mollies, 2 red wag swordtails, 2 gold wag mollies, 2 pineapple swordtails, 1 catfish) (n = 9), or video of tropical fish in an aquarium (n = 9)	Eight minutes viewing "placebo" video of television lines/static (n = 9)	Purpose-built laboratory in publicly subsidised housing complex (USA)
Edwards 2002 [64]	Interrupted time-series with non-equivalent control	Residents of specialised dementia units	62	80.1 years	61%	Aquariums containing eight large colourful fish, up to four months (n = 62)	Scenic ocean picture, two weeks (n = 17)	Dining rooms of specialised dementia units (USA)
Edwards 2013 [65]	Interrupted time-series	Residents of specialised dementia units	70	82.2 years	74%	As above (n = 70)	-	As above
Edwards 2014 [54]	Before-and-after study	Residents of specialised dementia units	72	80.3 years	71%	Aquariums containing eight to ten large colourful fish, 10 weeks (n = 72)	-	As above
		Staff of specialised dementia units	71	NR	82%	Aquarium as above, 10 weeks (n = 71)	-	As above

(Continued)

Table 2. (Continued)

First author and year	Design	Participants				Aquarium Intervention(s)	Comparator(s)	Setting (Country)
		Population	Total sample size (n)	Age (Mean)	Gender (% female)			
Katcher 1984 [85]	Between-subjects study with randomisation	Patients undergoing elective dental surgery	42	NR	NR	40-minute contemplation of aquarium with (n = 8) or without (n = 8) hypnosis	40-minute contemplation of poster with (n = 8) or without (n = 8) hypnosis, or no intervention (n = 10)	Dental surgery (USA)
Maranda 2015 [86]	Pilot Randomised Control Trial	Adolescents with type 1 diabetes mellitus	29	14.2 years	64%	Fishbowl containing <i>Betta splendens</i> fish, and instructions to pair diabetes self-management tasks with daily and weekly fish care duties, approximately 3 months	Usual care (n = 12)	At home (USA)
Riddick 1985 [60]	Between-subjects study without randomisation	Older adults in publicly subsidised housing	24	Range 57-94 years	71%	2.5-gallon tanks containing two goldfish, plus nine visits from researcher over six-months (n = 7)	Ten visits from the researcher over six-months (n = 8), or no intervention (n = 7)	Publicly subsidised housing (USA)
Sanchez 2015 [63]	Before-and-after study with control group	Students/trainees in paediatric orthopaedics	69	28.2 years	58%	30-minutes viewing 26.5-gallon saltwater aquarium with >25 fish, including several species of surgeonfish (n = 69)	30-minutes viewing white wall (n = 12)	Hospital waiting room (France)
Wells 2005 [68]	Between-subjects study with randomisation	University students	100	19.7 years	42%	10-minute video of 10 neon tetras swimming in a tank (n = 20)	10-minute video of birds in an aviary, primates in a zoo enclosure, a popular soap opera, or a blank screen (all n = 20)	University laboratory (UK)
<i>Public aquariums</i>								
Cracknell 2016 [87]	Between-subjects study, quasi-experimental	University students	84	24 years	76%	10-minutes viewing above exhibit when fully stocked (n = 29) or partially stocked (n = 26)	10-minutes viewing exhibit when unstocked (n = 29)	Public aquarium exhibit (UK)
Cracknell 2017, Study 1 [61]	Within-subjects study	University students	39	19.5 years	74%	Images of public aquarium exhibits (n = 39)	Images of built, green, aquatic or sub-aquatic environments (all n = 39)	University laboratory (UK)
Cracknell 2017, Study 2 [61]	Within-subjects study	University students	40	20.8 years	68%	Images of public aquarium exhibits differing in species richness, abundance of individuals, and content (tropical/temperate) (all n = 40)	-	University laboratory (UK)

(Continued)

Table 2. (Continued)

First author and year	Design	Participants				Aquarium Intervention(s)	Comparator(s)	Setting (Country)
		Population	Total sample size (n)	Age (Mean)	Gender (% female)			
Sahrmann 2016 [88]	Before-and-after study	General public	165	Range 18-68 years	72%	10-minute interaction with stingrays at touch-tank (n = 165)	-	Public aquarium exhibit (USA)

NR: not reported

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0220524.t002>

the same level of emotional support as other types of animal, and that participants had to deal with the death of their animals on a regular basis [52]. These factors were associated with variation in the level of attachment participants felt to their fish, with some reporting being highly attached, and others viewing their fish as replaceable [52]. Other limitations that were identified were associated with the maintenance, cost and time commitments of keeping home aquaria.

Correlational studies

One study used a correlational design to assess whether the presence of aquariums in the workplaces of hospital medical directors was associated with their self-rated health. Participants ($n = 737$, mean age = 49 years, 8% female) were mailed a questionnaire to assess their patient-related work stress, and the presence of five interior amenities (aquariums, indoor plants, music, art and exhibitions, and private or personalised workspaces) within their working environment. Four dimensions of self-rated health were also assessed, specifically: how participants rated their own health against that of the same age population and their medical peers, and their experience of various health complaints during the past month (short-term) and six months (long-term). Both physiological and psychological health complaints were included. The analyses indicated that after controlling for personal characteristics, work status and work stresses, the presence of interior amenities was associated with an improvement in participants' self-rated health. However, the presence of aquariums alone was not significantly related to any dimension of medical directors' self-rated health.

Intervention studies

Sixteen studies involved novel interactions with fish in aquariums, however, four of these related specifically to public aquariums so are discussed separately below. Of the twelve remaining studies, three involved student or trainee samples [62,63,68] and nine involved clinical populations, specifically: residents of specialised dementia units [54,64,65], dental patients [85], electroconvulsive therapy patients [53], hospitalised patients awaiting heart transplantation [83], older adults [60,84], and adolescents with type 1 diabetes mellitus [86]. One study also explored how staff were affected by the intervention [54]. Most studies involved adult populations, and where reported, mean ages ranged from 19.7 to 82.2 years, although student samples were typically younger than those drawn from clinical populations. One study involved adolescents and reported the mean age to be 14.2 years. All samples included male and female participants (20 to 92% female), with the exception of one study which did not report gender [85]. Ethnicity was reported in four studies; in three cases the sample was predominantly Caucasian (72.8 to 98.5%) [54,64,65]; the fourth consisted 56% Caucasian and 44% African American in the intervention group, and 33% Caucasian, 58% African American, and 9% other

Table 3. Summary of key findings of included studies.

First author and year	Procedure	Psychological outcomes	Physiological outcomes	Risk of bias*
<i>Fish as companion animals</i>				
Kidd 1999 [81]	Customers of shop selling fish and aquarium equipment completed survey.	Benefits of aquarium ownership reported by 94% of respondents and included relaxation (n = 47), watching movements (n = 32), stress reduction (n = 23), companionship (n = 5), entertainment (n = 4) and education (n = 1).	-	-
Langfield 2009 [52]	Semi-structured interviews conducted with current pet fish owners; the data were analysed using the constant comparison method.	Four themes identified: reasons for owning fish as pets; the environment; caring for pet fish; and benefits and limitations of owning fish as pets.	-	+
<i>Correlational studies</i>				
Lin 2013 [82]	Medical directors from all accredited hospitals in Taiwan were mailed a questionnaire, which assessed patients related work stress, the presence of five interior amenities in the workplace (including aquariums), and self-rated health status.	Self-rated health (compared to same age population, compared to medical peers, short-term health complaints, long-term health complaints); no relationship between presence of an aquarium in the workplace, and any dimension of self-rated health was found.	Self-rated health (short-term health complaints, long-term health complaints); no relationship between presence of an aquarium in the workplace, and any dimension of self-rated health was found.	+
<i>Intervention studies</i>				
Barker 2003 [53]	Patients assigned to rooms with/without aquarium on subsequent visits. Physiological outcomes assessed immediately after assignment and before treatment, psychological outcomes assessed before treatment only.	Anxiety, depression, fear & frustration (VAS); no significant differences between aquarium and no aquarium conditions; trend towards a greater reduction in anxiety in the aquarium condition (p = 0.08).	HR/DBP/SBP: no significant differences found between aquarium and no aquarium condition before or after treatment.	+
Buttelmann 2014 [62]	Participants about to give spontaneous presentation interacted with fish/dog/plant/ nothing for 5-minutes. Outcomes assessed at baseline, following induction of anxiety (being informed of the presentation task) and after the interaction.	Anxiety (STAI-S) reduced significantly more in fish, dog and plant groups than no activity group; no significant differences between experimental groups. More participants in the dog group experienced a reduction to below baseline levels than those in control group; no differences between other groups. Laughter (yes/no): more participants in the dog group laughed during the intervention than in all other groups; no differences between the other groups.	DBP/SBP/NR as influenced by participants' movement/speech.	-
Cole 2000 [83]	Aquariums installed into the hospital rooms of patients awaiting heart transplantation. Outcomes assessed at baseline then after 3 and 11 days.	Anxiety, depression, hostility, dysphoria, sensation seeking & positive affect (MAACL-R); no significant differences between baseline and follow-up.	-	-
DeSchriner 1990 [84]	Participants seated comfortably and watched live fish/fish video/placebo video for eight minutes. An emotive article was read aloud to induce stress. Outcomes assessed every minute during procedure.	Treatment evaluation (adapted LSS) all conditions were perceived as equally relaxing.	HR, skin temperature (°F), muscle tension (μV); no significant differences between conditions.	-
Edwards 2002 [64]	Aquariums/picture installed into dining rooms of specialised dementia units. Nutritional intake assessed daily for two weeks before and after installation, then weekly for six weeks. Body mass assessed at baseline then monthly for four months.	-	Nutritional intake (grams consumed/meal) significantly increased in two weeks after installation, then again in following six weeks. No significant changes in control group two weeks after installation. Body mass (lbs): significantly increased in month after installation, then continued to increase until end of study (total M gain = 1.65lb).	-

(Continued)

Table 3. (Continued)

First author and year	Procedure	Psychological outcomes	Physiological outcomes	Risk of bias*
Edwards 2013 [65]	Aquariums installed into dining rooms. Nutritional intake assessed daily for two weeks before and after installation, then weekly for six weeks. Average body mass was calculated for three months prior to installation (baseline), the intervention period (weeks 3–5), and follow-up (week 10 to 3-months post-intervention).	-	Nutritional intake (grams consumed/meal): significantly increased in the two weeks after installation, but not in following six weeks. Body mass (lbs): significantly increased from baseline to intervention but not from intervention to follow-up (total M gain = 2.2lbs).	-
Edwards 2014 [64]	Aquariums installed into dining rooms and outcomes assessed at baseline and after 10 weeks.	BPSD (Nursing Home Disruptive Behaviour Scale): significant improvements on domains of uncooperative, irrational, sleep and inappropriate behaviours but not annoying or dangerous behaviours. Significant overall improvement. Job satisfaction (Assessment of Work Environment Scale): significantly improved following introduction of the aquarium.	-	-
Katcher 1984 [63]	Participants received intervention immediately prior to treatment. Physiological measures assessed throughout intervention/procedure; psychological measures assessed during/after procedure.	Treatment comfort (Treatment Comfort Index): patients rated comfort as significantly higher after aquarium contemplation than poster contemplation. Also higher in both aquarium groups and the poster with hypnosis group than the no contemplation group. Anxiety (assessed by blind observer using a checklist) & patient compliance (assessed by dentist): no significant effect of aquarium observed.	DBP/SBP: no significant differences during intervention or procedure. HR: NR.	-
Maranda 2015 [66]	Participants obtained pet fish and were instructed to pair twice daily feeds with blood glucose readings, and weekly water changes with a parental review of their glucose logs. Outcomes assessed at baseline and follow-up (approximately 3 months).	Quality of life (PedsQoL Generic and Diabetes modules): no significant effects were found for generic or health-related quality of life.	Glycaemic control (A1C): significant reduction in A1C level for those in the intervention group compared to those in the control group. Younger participants (10–13 years) had a significantly greater response to the intervention than older participants (14–17 years).	+
Riddick 1985 [60]	Aquarium/visitor interventions were provided over six months. Outcomes were assessed via interview at baseline and six months.	Leisure satisfaction (LSS): no significant difference between groups; one component (relaxation) bordered on significance ($p = 0.06$). Loneliness (UCLA Loneliness Scale), happiness (MUNSH), anxiety (STAI-T): no significant differences between groups.	DBP: analysed as change from baseline to six-months for each group separately, due to differences at baseline. Only aquarium group underwent significant reduction. SBP: no significant differences between conditions.	-
Sanchez 2015 [63]	Participants watched aquarium continuously for 30-minutes. Outcomes assessed at 5, 10, 20 and 30-minutes, then at 10-minutes post-viewing.	-	Pain threshold (measured using electrical stimulation device): significantly higher 5, 10, 20, and 30-minutes after viewing, compared to the initial value and remained elevated 10-minutes after viewing ended. No significant changes in the control condition.	-
Wells 2005 [64]	Participants watched one of the videos for 10-minutes then completed a reading aloud task designed to induce stress. Outcomes assessed at baseline (phase 1), after watching video (phase 2), and after reading task (phase 3).	-	HR/SBP: significantly lower in phase 3 in animal video groups compared to control video groups. No difference between animal video groups. DBP: significantly lower in phases 2 & 3 in animal video groups compared to control video groups. No difference between animal video groups.	+

Public aquariums

(Continued)

Table 3. (Continued)

First author and year	Procedure	Psychological outcomes	Physiological outcomes	Risk of bias ^a
Cracknell 2016 [87]	Participants viewed aquarium exhibit for 10-minutes; outcomes were assessed at baseline, 5-minutes and 10-minutes.	<i>Valence (Feeling Scale)</i> : a significant effect of time showed that valence increased with viewing; there was no significant effect of stocking level. <i>Arousal (Felt Arousal Scale)</i> : a significant effect of time showed that arousal significantly decreased with viewing; there was no significant effect of stocking level.	<i>DBP/SBP</i> : no significant differences were found between different stocking levels. <i>HR</i> : a significant effect of stocking level indicated that participants in the two stocked conditions had greater reductions in HR than those in unstocked condition.	-
Cracknell 2017, Study 1 [61]	Participants viewed each image and rated them on four dimensions.	<i>Attractiveness, willingness to display & affect</i> : built environments rated lower than all others, aquatic environments and aquariums rated highest. <i>Perceived restorativeness</i> : built environments rated lower than all others, aquariums rated higher than sub-aquatic and green environments, aquatic environments rated higher than aquariums.	-	+
Cracknell 2017, Study 2 [61]	As above.	<i>Attractiveness, willingness to display, affect & perceived restorativeness</i> : vertebrates rated higher than invertebrates; tropical exhibits rated more highly than temperate exhibits; high abundance rated higher than low abundance; high species richness rated higher than low species richness in tropical scenes but lower in temperate scenes.	-	+
Sahemans 2016 [88]	Participants interacted with stingrays at the touch-tank. Physiological outcomes assessed throughout, psychological outcomes assessed pre- and post-interaction.	<i>Hedonic tone</i> : significantly improved from pre- to post-touch. <i>Energetic arousal</i> : significantly increased from pre- to post-touch. <i>Tense arousal</i> : significantly decreased from pre- to post-touch. (All assessed using the UMACI)	<i>HR</i> : significant quadratic trends showed that HR became more elevated and less variable during touch, then began to return to normal towards the end of the touch period (but did not reach baseline levels).	-

NR, not reported; BPSD: behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia; DBP: diastolic blood pressure; HR: heart rate; LSS: Leisure Satisfaction Scale; MAACL-R: Multiple Affect Adjective Checklist-Revised; MUNSH: Memorial University of Newfoundland Scale of Happiness; SBP: systolic blood pressure; STAI-S: State-Trait Anxiety Inventory State Scale; STAI-T: State-Trait Anxiety Inventory Trait Scale; UMACI: University of Wales Institute of Science and Technology Mood Adjective Checklist; VAS: visual analogue scales

^aRisk of bias was assessed using the NICE (2012) Quality Appraisal Checklists for quantitative intervention studies and qualitative studies. ++ indicates all/most criteria were fulfilled and conclusions are unlikely to alter; + indicates some criteria were fulfilled and conclusions are unlikely to alter; - indicates few or no checklist criteria were fulfilled, and conclusions are likely or very likely to alter.

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ethnicity in the control group [86]. Estimates of socio-economic status were reported in five studies; two reported level of education (65 to 68% high school educated or above) [54,64], one reported marital status (43% married) [53], one reported ZIP code-based annual household income (intervention group: \$54,800; control group: \$51,800) [86], and one reported that all participants qualified for "low income" publicly subsidised housing [60].

There was substantial variation in study setting and design. Two studies were conducted in university laboratories [62,68], one in a purpose-built laboratory in a housing complex [84], one in a hospital waiting room but under laboratory conditions [63], two in participants' homes [60,86], and six in clinical or therapeutic settings [53,54,64,65,83,85]. Design of studies included before-and-after studies [54,83]; controlled before-and-after studies [63]; interrupted time series with [64] or without [65] control groups; within-subjects or crossover studies [53]; between-subjects studies with [68,84,85] or without [60,62] randomisation; and a pilot

randomised control trial [86]. Where comparators were used they included no treatment or usual care controls, viewing alternative stimuli such as posters, and interacting with other animals (see Table 2 for further details).

The majority of studies used home aquaria containing between one and nine fish, with the exception of one study which used a 265-gallon aquarium with over 25 fish, installed in a hospital waiting room [63]. One study did not report details of the aquarium set-up [85], and while another study specified the species of fish which participants were to purchase (*Betta splendens*), it was not clear whether all participants adhered to these instructions [86]. Two studies used videos of fish in aquariums [68,84] and did not specify the size of the aquariums shown, although one was reported to contain ten neon tetras [68]. The type of interaction differed between studies and included: passive exposure [53,54,64,65]; actively watching the fish swimming [63,68,84,85]; interacting with a fish to "try and accustom it to humans" [62]; and caring for fish in an aquarium in either a hospital [83] or home [60,86] environment.

Anxiety & relaxation. Reflecting the findings of studies conducted with those who choose to keep home aquaria, several intervention studies ($n = 7$) assessed outcomes relating to anxiety or relaxation. A variety of instruments were used, and so meta-analytical techniques could not be applied. Two studies assessed whether brief exposure to an aquarium could alleviate anxiety associated with stress-provoking medical procedures. In Barker et al. [53], patients attending electroconvulsive therapy treatment were assigned to waiting rooms with or without aquariums. At the end of the waiting period (approximately 20 minutes) participants assessed their levels of anxiety using a visual analogue scale. Although participants reported lower levels of anxiety in the aquarium versus no aquarium condition, this did not reach a level of statistical significance. Katcher et al. [85] examined whether contemplation of an aquarium prior to dental surgery reduced anxiety during treatment; this was assessed by a blind observer who recorded overt signs of anxiety every five minutes throughout the procedure. Again, anxiety was lower in the aquarium groups compared to the comparator groups, but this difference was not statistically significant. However, scores from a Treatment Comfort Index indicated that patients who contemplated an aquarium before their dental surgery reported higher levels of comfort during the treatment than those who contemplated a poster or a blank wall. No differences were found in patient compliance as assessed by the dentist.

Buttelmann and Röpcke [62] also assessed short-term changes in anxiety, this time in relation to a public speaking task. Student participants were asked to complete a short presentation on an unfamiliar topic with just five-minutes to prepare; a five-minute intervention period followed the preparation time during which participants interacted with a fish, dog, or plant, or were simply told to wait. Anxiety was assessed at baseline, after the stressor, and after the intervention period using the State scale of the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI); a score for each participant was calculated as the percentage of induced anxiety that was reduced following the intervention, where induced anxiety was calculated as the change from baseline to post-stressor. Participants who interacted with the fish had a greater reduction in induced anxiety than participants who received no intervention, and this reduction was equivalent to that experienced by participants who instead interacted with a dog or a plant. However, significantly more participants in the dog group experienced a reduction in anxiety to below baseline levels, relative to the control group; there were no significant differences between the other groups with regards to this outcome.

Two studies assessed anxiety over longer intervention periods. No change in anxiety was found for patients awaiting heart transplantation three- or 11-days after fish tanks were installed in their hospital rooms, as measured using the Multiple Affect Adjective Checklist-Revised (MAACL-R) [83]. Similarly, older adults who were given fish to care for in their own home experienced no greater reduction in anxiety (measured using the Trait scale of the

STAI) after six-months, than those who received visits from the researcher, or no intervention [60]. In the latter study however, there was a borderline significant ($p = 0.06$) increase in relaxation (a component of the Leisure Satisfaction Scale) for residents in the aquarium group, compared to the comparator groups; there were no significant differences between groups for overall leisure satisfaction.

Outcomes relating to anxiety were assessed in two further studies. In DeSchriver and Riddick [84] participants viewed either a live fish aquarium, a video of fish swimming or a placebo video of television lines and static; participants' responses to a treatment evaluation questionnaire (adapted from the Leisure Satisfaction Scale) indicated that all activities were perceived to be equally relaxing. Finally, Edwards et al. [54] found that installation of aquariums into specialised dementia units was associated with a significant improvement in carer ratings of residents' behavioural and psychological symptoms, assessed using the Nursing Home Disruptive Behaviour Scale. This improvement in behaviour also coincided with an increase in job satisfaction among staff members, measured using the Assessment of Work Environment Scale.

Physiological stress. Six studies assessed indicators of physiological stress, although these outcomes were not reported in one study as the readings appeared to have been influenced by participants' movement and speech [62]. Heart rate and/or blood pressure were the most commonly assessed outcomes, and were typically measured using automated devices (although in one case the device used was not stated [60]). However, the number and timing of assessments varied across studies; combined with the heterogeneity in study and intervention design, this variation made the data unsuitable for meta-analysis.

Two studies assessed whether the presence or contemplation of an aquarium could reduce heart rate and blood pressure among people undergoing medical procedures [53,85], with neither study finding a significant effect on either variable (one study did not report the findings related to heart rate [85]). DeSchriver and Riddick [84] assessed differences in heart rate, skin temperature and muscle tension between participants who viewed a live fish aquarium, a fish video, or a placebo video. Heart rate was measured as beats per minute using an automated device, skin temperature in degrees Fahrenheit using a temperature meter mounted on the participant's finger, and muscle tension in microvolts using bicep electromyography (EMG); no significant differences were found between conditions for any of these variables. Wells [68] however, found that participants who watched an animal video (fish, bird or primate) had lower heart rate and blood pressure (systolic and diastolic) after a subsequent reading aloud task than participants who watched a control video (soap opera or blank screen). Diastolic blood pressure was also significantly lower immediately after viewing the video for participants in the animal video groups compared to the control groups; there were no differences between the animal video conditions. One study examined changes in blood pressure over longer periods and found that diastolic (but not systolic) blood pressure was significantly reduced after six months for participants who were given fish to keep in their own home, but not for those who received visits from the researchers, or had no intervention [60].

Affective state. Four studies assessed a range of outcomes relating to participants' current mood or affective state. The presence of an aquarium in waiting rooms had no effect on fear, frustration or aggression (assessed using visual analogue scales) for participants awaiting ECT treatment [53]. Similarly, responses to the MAACL-R showed no change in depression, hostility, dysphoria, sensation seeking, or positive affect among patients awaiting heart transplantation three- or 11-days after aquariums were installed in their hospital rooms [83]. One study assessed whether happiness (assessed using the Memorial University of Newfoundland Scale of Happiness) increased after six months for older adults who were given fish to care for in their own home, but no significant differences were found between participants in the fish group and those who were visited by the researcher, or received no intervention [60]. In

Buttelmann and Römpke [62], videotapes of the intervention period were coded for occurrence of laughter (yes/no); significantly more participants in the dog group were observed laughing compared to all other groups, with no significant differences between the fish, plant and control groups.

Loneliness. Riddick [60] used the UCLA Loneliness Scale to assess whether loneliness improved for participants who were given a fish versus those who received visits from the researcher, or had no intervention. No significant difference was found between the three groups after six-months, although a trend towards reduced loneliness was seen for those in the visitor group ($p = 0.08$).

Nutritional intake & body mass. As weight loss is a risk factor for people with dementia [90], two studies examined whether introducing fish aquariums into the dining rooms of specialised dementia units could influence residents' nutritional intake, and subsequently improve their body mass [64,65]. Nutritional intake was measured as the amount of food (in grams) consumed at each meal during the intervention period, and in both studies, was found to significantly increase in the two weeks following installation. This increase also continued over the following six weeks, but only to a statistically significant level in one study [64]. In addition, body mass significantly increased during the months following installation of the aquarium, with average weight gains of 1.65lbs [64] and 2.2lbs [65] at four months post-installation. No changes in nutritional intake were observed after two weeks in a non-equivalent control group ($n = 17$) used in the earlier study [64].

Pain. One study involving healthy adults explored whether watching fish in an aquarium could increase participants' pain threshold [63]. Participants ($n = 69$) were seated in front of the aquarium and gripped an electrical stimulation device between their fingers; the device increased in intensity until participants indicated that they could feel the sensation. The procedure was then repeated, and participants instead indicated when they first experienced pain. Assessments made throughout the 30-minute viewing period indicated that, although there were no changes in sensation threshold, participants' pain thresholds were significantly increased after 5-, 10-, 20-, and 30-minutes compared to baseline readings. They also remained elevated 10-minutes after viewing ended. No changes in pain threshold were detected among a subset of participants who were retested while viewing a blank wall for the same amount of time ($n = 12$).

Glycaemic control. One study assessed whether pairing fish care duties with diabetes self-management tasks could lead to improved glycaemic control for adolescents with type 1 diabetes mellitus [86]. Participants randomly assigned to the intervention group were provided with a fishbowl and related equipment, and purchased a fish using a gift card provided by the researchers. They were then instructed to pair twice daily feeds (morning and evening) with blood glucose readings, and weekly water changes with a caregiver review of their glucose logs. Glycaemic control was assessed via A1C (an indicator of average blood glucose levels over the preceding three months) at baseline and follow-up (approximately three months). A significant improvement was found for the intervention group compared to the control group (usual care), with younger participants (10–13 years) having a greater response to the intervention than older participants (14–17 years). This study also assessed whether the intervention had an effect on generic and health-related quality of life, but no significant changes were observed from baseline to follow-up.

Secondary outcomes. Most intervention studies reported procedures that were in place to ensure animal welfare. In the three studies by Edwards and colleagues [54,64,65], the aquariums were specifically designed for use on a dementia unit; they were self-contained and locked to ensure the safety of fish and residents, and were automated to reduce the burden on staff. Two studies used aquarium servicing companies [53,83], with one also stating that participants

were responsible for feeding the fish and had to place their initials on a feeding calendar to prevent under/over-feeding [83]. Buttelmann and Römpler [62] reported that when data collection was underway, one of five fish was taken from a communal tank and placed in a smaller goldfish bowl for the duration of the intervention, with the fish used in rotation to reduce stress; procedures were also in place to minimise stress experienced by the dog used as a comparator. Of the two studies in which participants kept fish in their own home, one reported that the tanks were initially maintained by the researchers and the participants, with the participants taking greater responsibility for fish care over the course of the study. Participants were also provided with information and literature on feeding and signs of fish illness, and could contact the researchers via telephone 24-hours a day [60]. The second study stated that participants were provided with instructions on how to care for their fish, but did not report any involvement in fish care on the part of the researchers [86]. This study also reported that the fish of two participants had to be replaced due to them dying during routine fish care, although it was not reported whether the cause of these deaths was known, or whether steps were taken to prevent future mortalities. Otherwise, no studies reported whether the welfare of the fish was affected due to their involvement in the research, so it is unclear whether these procedures were effective in practice. Similarly, no studies reported whether participants experienced adverse effects because of the interventions. Several studies provided anecdotal reports that participants responded positively to the interventions, however, none collected and reported these data in a rigorous and systematic manner.

Public aquariums

Four studies reported in three papers related specifically to public aquariums. Two were conducted within an aquarium setting [87,88] and two (published in the same paper) used images of public aquarium exhibits [61]. Participants were either student samples [61,87] or healthy adults [88]. Sample sizes ranged from 39 to 165 ($M = 82$); all samples included male and female participants (68 to 76% female) and mean ages ranged from 19.5 to 24.0 years (one study reported only the age range of participants as 18 to 68 years [88]). Two studies were within-subjects designs with control groups [61], one was a before-and-after study [88], and one was between-subjects with pseudo-randomisation [87]. Interactions included very brief exposure to images [61], viewing a 550,000-litre exhibit at various levels of stocking [87], and physically interacting with stingrays at a touch-tank [88].

Two studies [87,88] examined changes in self-reported mood and physiological outcomes after interacting with fish at public aquarium exhibits. In Cracknell et al. [87], assessments using the Feeling Scale and Felt Arousal Scale indicated that participants' affective state significantly improved, and their levels of arousal significantly reduced after viewing an aquarium exhibit for 10-minutes, with no significant differences between three levels of stocking (unstocked, partially stocked and fully stocked). Similarly, blood pressure reduced in all conditions but there were no significant differences between the stocking conditions. However, heart rate was influenced by level of stocking, with significantly greater reductions observed in the partially and fully stocked conditions compared to the unstocked condition. In Sahrman et al. [88], heart rate was found to be elevated and less variable while interacting with stingrays at a touch-tank, compared to before or after contact with the animals. Three dimensions of mood were assessed using the University of Wales Institute of Science and Technology Mood Adjective Checklist (UMACL); hedonic tone and energetic arousal were significantly increased, and tense arousal was significantly decreased, after the 10-minute interaction period compared to before contact. This is indicative of a short-term increase in physiological stress when touching the animals, but a decrease in mental stress after leaving the exhibit.

In two studies [61], participants rated photographs of different environments on four dimensions of preference; the pleasantness of the scene, how willing they would be to display the image, how the image made them feel, and—of most relevance to this review—the perceived restorativeness of the scene. In study 1, public aquarium exhibits were compared to different natural and manmade environments. Aquariums were rated equally to, or higher than all other environments for all dimensions except perceived restorativeness, which was higher for aquatic environments (e.g. coastal landscapes). In study 2, different aquarium exhibits were compared. The findings indicated that tropical exhibits were preferred over temperate ones, and vertebrates were preferred over invertebrates; higher levels of biota were also preferred, but preference for species richness differed according to whether the exhibit was tropical or temperate (see Table 3 for further details).

Secondary outcomes. Of the studies relating to public aquariums two involved live animals; both used procedures which reflected typical visitor behaviours, and so animal welfare concerns were unlikely to be increased as a result of the research. Furthermore, Sahrman et al. [88] reported that participants were shown proper touch techniques before being allowed to interact with the stingrays. Additionally, both studies asked participants about their feelings towards the exhibits. In Cracknell et al. [87] participants' responses to evaluative statements indicated that they enjoyed watching the exhibit, found it interesting, felt better after watching, and would be happy to watch again. Furthermore, as the levels of stocking increased, participants' responses became more positive. In Sahrman et al. [88], 80% of participants gave positive responses to an open-ended question about their experience of the exhibit. Adverse events to participants were not reported in either study, however, Sahrman et al. [88] stated that 7% of participants indicated they felt nervous, anxious or unsure when touching the animals. As the two studies by Cracknell et al. [61] used photographs in a laboratory setting, adverse events to participants were unlikely to have occurred, and there were no animal welfare concerns.

Risk of bias in included studies

Qualitative studies. Two studies were assessed using the NICE Quality Appraisal Checklist for qualitative studies [78]. Of these two studies, one used methods appropriate to the study aims and took steps to ensure rigor and trustworthiness [52]. However, the use of snowball sampling and a lack of clarity regarding whether two researchers were involved in the entire analytical process introduced some risk of bias to this study. By contrast, the second study consistently lacked sufficient detail to make sound judgements about risk of bias and the defensibility of conclusions [81]. The study aims were not clearly stated, and there was insufficient description of the methods and data analyses to determine whether these were appropriate. As such, the findings of this study should be treated with caution. Further details are provided in [S4 Appendix](#).

Quantitative studies reporting a correlation. One study [82] was assessed using the NICE Quality Appraisal Checklist for quantitative studies reporting correlation/association [78]. This study involved a survey design to assess whether the presence of interior amenities (including aquariums) is related to self-rated health among hospital medical directors; therefore, the research relied on self-report data which can be highly subjective. Additionally, while the study controlled for personal characteristics, work status and work stresses, it is unlikely that all possible confounders were considered; health-related behaviours and pre-existing medical conditions for instance, were not assessed but are likely to impact self-rated health status. Finally, the response rate was fairly low (32.83%), so it is unclear whether the included participants were representative of the source population.

Quantitative intervention studies. The remaining sixteen studies were assessed using the NICE Quality Appraisal Checklist for quantitative intervention studies [28]. One study was reported as a (pilot) randomised controlled trial (RCT)—usually considered the most rigorous form of experimental study design—and three others used between-subjects designs with random allocation [68,84,85]. Each of these studies had high or unclear risk of bias (see [S4 Appendix](#) for further details). One study reported that a randomisation schedule was developed using a computerised random number generator, and that this sequence was concealed until allocation, however, it was not clear how participants were allocated to this sequence [86]. No other studies reported the method of randomisation or whether allocation was concealed. One study reported that participants in the intervention and control groups were similar at baseline [86], and a second stated that groups were balanced in terms of age and gender, although participants' baseline scores appeared to differ across conditions [84]. The remaining two studies did not report whether groups were similar at baseline [68,85].

Non-randomised, between-subjects designs were used in three studies [60,62,87]. One allocated participants on the basis of specific characteristics to ensure similarity between groups at baseline; whether balance was truly achieved is unclear however, as the authors did not provide descriptive statistics to support this statement [62]. Allocation could not be randomised in the second study due to the demands of the study site, and some differences between groups were observed at baseline [87]. In the final study, the control group was handpicked by the centre manager, and allocation to intervention conditions was based primarily on participants' preferences; thus this study is subject to substantial bias [60].

Within-subjects or crossover designs were used in three studies, reported in two papers [53,61]. In two studies, the order of presentation was randomised and determined by a computer, thus concealing allocation [61]. In the third, participants were allocated on a first-come basis due to the needs of the service and allocation was not concealed [53].

Six studies used before-and-after [54,63,83,88] or time series [64,65] designs. Although two [63,64] included a small number of participants from the treatment group in a control group, both analysed results from each group separately and based conclusions predominantly on findings from the treatment group in isolation, therefore, these two studies are considered alongside those without a comparator. Uncontrolled designs are typically considered to have low internal validity, and as only two studies interpreted results in relation to existing trends [64,65], it is unclear whether the results observed in these studies differ from those which would have been observed naturally over time.

Several potential sources of bias were present across included studies, irrespective of design. Blinding of participants was impossible due to the nature of the interventions (as people can see the fish), although some studies did report that participants were unaware of the study aims during data collection [53,68,87]. Three studies reported blinding of study personnel [53,62,85] but in two cases this applied only to certain aspects of data collection, specifically, scoring of visual analogue scales [53] and coding of videos [62]. Only one within-subjects study reported using a sufficient washout period between conditions [64], and contamination may have been an issue in studies where participants had access to the fish tank between testing sessions [84], or could have visited neighbours assigned to the aquarium group [60]. Most studies provided an adequate description of the aquariums, although additional details such as the species of fish used would have been beneficial in some cases; only one study provided no details of the aquarium set-up [85]. In two studies, adequacy of exposure could be questioned; Sahrman et al. [88] reported that visits to the touch-tank typically last around 20 minutes, but the intervention period lasted only ten, while Cole and Gawlinski [83] stated that the type of patients included in their study usually experience a waiting time of two months, but the longest follow-up was just 11-days (although it is noteworthy that this was a pilot study). In one

study, exposure to the intervention and control were non-equivalent by design of the research [64], and in another it was unclear if length of exposure was standardised, or determined by the participant [61].

In some studies, methods of statistical analysis were unclear or inadequately reported [53,60,62,83–86]. Several inappropriately used multiple comparisons in place of a single omnibus test [61,63–65,87] and some also used parametric tests for Likert-type data which may be considered inappropriate (although this is highly debated) [54,61,87]. Only two studies reported conducting power analyses. In one study these were conducted on a *post-hoc* basis and so are of limited value [53], while in the second the data used as a basis for the power analysis was not clearly described [86]. Dropout rates were reported in only two studies [54,60] and while both were at an acceptable level (<10%), neither conducted an intention-to-treat analysis. One study reported excluding a participant because they bought a fish when assigned to the control group [86]. The problem of missing data was discussed in a further four studies [53,62,87,88] and was typically dealt with by excluding participants with incomplete data from the analyses.

Only two studies adequately described the recruitment and selection process [60,88], but one of these reported that participants for the control group were handpicked by the service manager (thus risk of bias was high) [60]. Most other studies provided some details such as the inclusion/exclusion criteria, but these were insufficient to determine whether risk of bias was minimised. Descriptions of participant characteristics were limited in most studies, with one providing no information about the sample [85]. For these reasons, it is unclear whether the findings from most studies are generalizable to the source populations.

Reporting biases

Evidence of potential selective reporting was identified in some studies. Katcher et al. [85] reported collecting heart rate data but this outcome was not included in the results section of the article. Similarly, in discussion of their research findings, Edwards and Beck [64] referred to data which indicated reduced use of nutritional supplements among participants, but this outcome was not discussed in either the methods or results sections. A third study [62] did not present data collected regarding heart rate and blood pressure, however the authors explained the reason for this exclusion; the data failed to show successful anxiety induction in over 50% of participants, and may have been influenced by participants' movements and speech. Aside from omission of specific outcomes, some studies did not sufficiently report results, for instance failing to provide full details of the statistical test and significance levels [83], or not reporting the results of *post hoc* testing [60]. For one study, a lack of detail regarding the methodology made it difficult to determine whether results were presented in full [81]. Due to heterogeneity in study outcomes it was not possible to assess for evidence of publication bias using statistical methods (i.e. funnel plots). However, given that included studies were limited to those published in the English language, and that additional research was identified during the search but could not be accessed, it is probable that some relevant research was unintentionally omitted.

Strength of evidence

Strength of evidence assessments were made using the Weight of Evidence approach [80]. For this review, ratings of study quality (*Weight of Evidence A*) corresponded directly to the assessments made using the NICE Quality Appraisal Checklists [78] (see Table 3). Studies with high risk of bias (-) were rated as 'low' ($n = 12$) and studies with unclear risk of bias (+) were rated

as 'medium' ($n = 7$). As no studies were assessed as having low risk of bias (++), no studies were rated as 'high' for this criterion (see Tables 4 and 5 for more details).

With regards to study design (*Weight of Evidence B*), studies were rated as 'high' if they used randomised experimental designs ($n = 6$), and 'medium' if they used other experimental designs ($n = 9$). The exception was the study by Riddick [60] which was rated as 'low' despite using a non-randomised experimental design; this was due to the inappropriate methods of allocation (participant choice and hand selection by the centre manager). Studies using qualitative or correlational designs ($n = 3$) were rated as 'low' because these studies did not directly assess how interacting with fish in aquariums influences well-being outcomes.

The majority ($n = 14$) of studies received a rating of 'high' for relevance (*Weight of Evidence C*), as the findings related directly to the review question(s). Two studies were downgraded to 'medium' as they used photographs and assessed the perceived restorativeness of various public aquarium exhibits, rather than measuring actual changes in restoration outcomes (e.g. mood, physiological stress) [61]. One qualitative study [52] was also downgraded to 'medium' as, while an insight into the psychological benefits of interacting with fish in aquariums was given, well-being outcomes were not directly assessed. The second qualitative study [81] was rated as 'low' because the data were extremely limited, and there was inadequate description of the aims, design and results to determine the relevance of the study. Finally, the one study using a correlational design [82] was given a rating of 'low' for relevance because aquaria were a very small part of the study, and no description was given regarding the nature of the aquariums or the ways in which participants interacted with the fish they contained.

The overall weight for each study (*Weight of Evidence D*) was assigned based on the most common rating from the first three criteria. Most studies ($n = 12$) achieved an overall weight of 'medium', with three rated as 'low' [60,81,82] and four as 'high' [68,84–86]. The lowest weighted evidence came from studies using correlational designs, or involving individuals who already kept fish as companion animals; two studies were rated as 'low' and one as 'medium'. By comparison, evidence from the intervention studies was weighted more strongly; one study was rated as 'low', seven as 'medium' and four as 'high'. Evidence from public aquarium studies was more consistent, with all four studies achieving an overall weight of 'medium'.

With respect to the two review questions, psychological and physiological well-being were explored in fifteen and twelve studies, respectively. In both cases the majority of studies were assigned an overall weight of 'medium' ($n = 9$ for psychological outcomes, $n = 6$ for physiological outcomes). However, three studies relating to psychological well-being were rated as 'low' and three as 'high', whereas four studies assessing physiological well-being achieved an overall weight of 'high', with only two rated as 'low'. This suggests that the evidence relating to the physiological benefits of interacting with fish in aquariums may be slightly stronger than that relating to the psychological benefits. It is noteworthy however, that many studies relating to both types of outcome were 'upgraded' due to the high relevance of the evidence and the suitability of research designs, but had a high risk of bias (see Tables 4 and 5 for details). Thus, while research related to physiological outcomes may be slightly stronger than that relating to psychological outcomes, overall the strength of evidence was fairly low and substantial limitations were present in both evidence bases.

Discussion

The purpose of this review was to investigate the psychological and physiological benefits of interacting with fish in aquariums. Nineteen studies were included in the review, encompassing those relating to the benefits of keeping fish as companion animals, correlational studies, and research involving novel interactions with fish in home or public aquariums. The strength

Table 4. Weight of evidence assessments for psychological outcomes.

First author and year	Weight of Evidence A: Quality	Weight of Evidence B: Research design	Weight of Evidence C: Relevance	Weight of Evidence D: Overall weight
<i>Fish as companion animals</i>				
Kidd 1999 [81]	Low	Low	Low	Low
Langfield 2009 [52]	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium
<i>Correlational studies</i>				
Lin 2013 [82]	Medium	Low	Low	Low
<i>Intervention studies</i>				
Barker 2003 [53]	Medium	Medium	High	Medium
Buttelmann 2014 [62]	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Cole 2000 [83]	Low	Medium	High	Medium
DeSchriver 1990 [84]	Low	High	High	High
Edwards 2014 [54]	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Katcher 1984 [85]	Low	High	High	High
Maranda 2015 [86]	Medium	High	High	High
Riddick 1985 [60]	Low	Low	High	Low
<i>Public aquariums</i>				
Cracknell 2016 [87]	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Cracknell 2017, Study 1 [61]	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
Cracknell 2017, Study 2 [61]	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
Sahrmann 2016 [88]	Low	Medium	High	Medium

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of evidence relating to physiological outcomes was slightly higher than for psychological outcomes, however both evidence bases had mixed results. Of the fifteen studies that explored psychological outcomes, four studies of medium weight observed positive effects associated with human-fish interactions [52,54,62,88], but six ($n = 1$, high; $n = 3$, medium; $n = 2$, low)

Table 5. Weight of evidence assessments for physiological outcomes.

Study ID	Weight of Evidence A: Quality	Weight of Evidence B: Research design	Weight of Evidence C: Relevance	Weight of Evidence D: Overall weight
<i>Correlational studies</i>				
Lin 2013 [82]	Medium	Low	Low	Low
<i>Intervention studies</i>				
Barker 2003 [53]	Medium	Medium	High	Medium
DeSchriver 1990 [84]	Low	High	High	High
Edwards 2002 [64]	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Edwards 2013 [65]	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Katcher 1984 [85]	Low	High	High	High
Maranda 2015 [86]	Medium	High	High	High
Riddick 1985 [60]	Low	Low	High	Low
Sanchez 2015 [63]	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Wells 2005 [68]	Medium	High	High	High
<i>Public aquariums</i>				
Cracknell 2016 [87]	Low	Medium	High	Medium
Sahrmann 2016 [88]	Low	Medium	High	Medium

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found only partial support [60,61,81,85,87] and five ($n = 2$, high; $n = 2$, medium; $n = 1$, low) found no effect [53,83,84,86]. Similarly, a positive effect on physiological outcomes was observed in six of twelve studies ($n = 2$, high; $n = 4$, medium) [61–65,68,86,88], but partial support was found in two ($n = 1$, medium; $n = 1$, low) [60,87], and no effect in four ($n = 2$, high; $n = 2$, low) [53,84,85]. Furthermore, there was substantial clinical and methodological heterogeneity between included studies, and risk of bias was either high or unclear. These factors must therefore, be considered when drawing conclusions from this collection of studies.

Reflecting the widespread belief that watching fish swimming is relaxing, there was tentative evidence from two studies (rated 'low' and 'medium' for weight of evidence) that keeping fish as companion animals is associated with benefits such as stress reduction and increased relaxation. Other benefits were also identified, including happiness and companionship. Not all participants shared these experiences however, with some reporting no benefits from keeping home aquaria. This reflects the inconsistency of research findings more widely in the field of HAI, specifically, the lack of conclusive evidence to demonstrate a direct link between companion animal guardianship (irrespective of the type of animal) and improved well-being [21].

One possible explanation for these inconsistent findings is that the benefits of companion animal guardianship are mediated by the strength of the attachment between a human and their companion animal [41,91,92]. In both studies, variation was apparent in the level of attachment fish owners had to their animals; some participants indicated a strong attachment bond, while others indicated difficulty in forming attachments due to a lack of reciprocal affection from their fish. This variation may therefore account for the divergent experiences of those who keep fish as companion animals. Similarly, there were differences between participants in the degree to which they were involved in the care of their fish. One study noted that most participants were responsible for feeding the fish themselves, but some shared this responsibility with other family members [81]; participants in the second study noted that different species require different levels of care [52]. As increased effort can lead to people placing greater value on the product of that effort [93], home aquaria owners who take a greater role in the care of their fish may perceive more benefits from their animals than those who take a lesser role. Alternatively, as research has indicated that the beneficial effects of companion animal guardianship may be mediated by factors such as sociodemographic characteristics and health-related behaviours [19,22,23], individual differences between people who keep fish may explain some of the variation in findings. Future research should therefore, consider how differences in attachment, involvement in companion animal care, and population characteristics may account for variation in the experiences of those who keep fish as companion animals.

The findings from intervention studies were largely inconclusive. In contrast to research with other animals such as dogs and cats (for meta-analysis see Ein et al. [94]), there was little evidence that fish aquarium-based interventions help to reduce psychological and physiological stress or anxiety. Promisingly, one highly weighted and two medium weighted studies found significant positive effects on outcomes related to physiological stress and anxiety or related outcomes [54,62,68]. However, two studies (one weighted high, one low) found only partial support [60,85] and three studies (one high, two medium) found no significant effects [53,83,84]. Similarly, while previous research has linked contact with animals to reduced loneliness [5,95], acquisition of a fish tank had no effect this outcome among older adults after six months (although the only study to explore this outcome was weighted low for strength of evidence, and had substantial risk of bias) [60]. As is common with research into HAI [25,26] however, many studies had small sample sizes and thus may have been underpowered. As several studies with smaller samples observed greater improvements in the aquarium versus comparator groups, the possibility that these differences may have become statistically significant given sufficient power cannot be rejected.

Alternatively, individual differences in participant characteristics may account for some of the variation in study findings. Ein et al. [94] for example, observed that pet therapy (with dogs and cats) reduced heart rate for healthy adults but not clinical samples and reduced subjective stress/anxiety among adults but not older adults. It was argued that these moderating effects may be due to the use of medication among clinical samples, and greater emotional stability in older adults. Although substantial clinical and methodological heterogeneity precluded the use of moderator and subgroup analyses in the current review, it is plausible that participant characteristics may have had similar moderating influences on the effectiveness of human-fish interaction. For instance, of the five studies assessing physiological stress, four involved clinical populations or older adults, and found either no effect [53,84,85] or only mixed evidence [60]. Conversely, the final study involved a student sample and found significant improvements in heart rate and blood pressure associated with watching videos of fish [68]. While medication usage was not considered within these studies, it is possible this discrepancy in results may be at least partially accounted for by a higher level of medication use among the clinical and older adult samples, compared to student samples.

There was some support for the effectiveness of fish aquarium-based interventions on pain [63], nutritional intake and body mass [64,65], but attribution of these effects to human-fish interaction is limited by poor study design. For instance, in the two studies by Edwards and Beck [64,65], staff members were required to track residents' food intake by physically weighing their food at mealtimes; as nursing home staff often overestimate food intake among residents [96], tracking levels of consumption in this manner may have led to increases in residents' nutritional intake simply by raising staff members' awareness of under-eating. As these (and other) studies lacked appropriate control groups, it is not possible to separate any effects of the aquarium from other factors associated with the research, or from any changes that would have occurred naturally over time [26]. Other common methodological concerns were the lack of randomisation, allocation concealment, and blinding of study personnel; it is noteworthy however, that these methodological concerns are not uncommon in other areas of HAI research [25,26].

In some intervention studies the observed benefits may have been attributable to factors other than human-fish interaction. For instance, one study found that pairing diabetes self-management tasks with routine fish care activities led to improved glycaemic control among adolescents with type 1 diabetes [86]. Arguably however, the fish may not have been an integral component of this intervention; self-management behaviours may be paired with any regular activity, such as mealtimes, and waking or sleep routines [97]. While it is possible that adolescents may have greater motivation to adhere to an intervention because it involves interaction with live animals [33], without direct comparison of fish care tasks to other routine activities, it is impossible to determine whether the fish were a necessary component of this intervention. Likewise, while Buttellmann and Röpcke [62] found that interacting with a single fish in a goldfish bowl reduced anxiety to a greater extent than no intervention, this effect was equivalent for participants who instead interacted with a dog or a plant. Although a substantial body of research would predict benefit from interacting with a dog, it is less clear that these benefits should be observed from interacting with a single plant (although there is some evidence that the presence of indoor plants has psychological benefits (for overview see Bringslimark et al. [98]), this research usually focuses on passive exposure and so the interaction within the current study—brushing the leaves of the plant with water—was not typical). As such, the authors acknowledged that these findings may be attributed to simple distraction, and so could be achieved with a variety of other activities provided they are engaging for the individual [33,42].

Similarly, while the findings related to public aquariums were generally quite positive, it was not always clear whether these benefits were the direct effect of human-fish interaction.

Cracknell et al. [87] observed improvements in all participants irrespective of whether any fish species were present in the public aquarium exhibit. This suggests that benefits may be experienced from exposure to underwater scenes even in the absence of live animals, a finding which better aligns with theories of restorative environments than HAI. Interestingly however, heart rate did improve to a greater extent as the abundance of fish increased, and higher stocking levels were associated with longer viewing times in a separate sample of participants [87]. Furthermore, photographs of aquariums were rated more highly when displaying a higher abundance of fish, although preference for diversity of species differed between tropical and temperate exhibits [61]. These findings suggest that there may be additional benefits to interacting with live animals compared to other stimuli as there are risks and animal welfare concerns associated with HAI [12,51], additional research is needed to corroborate these findings.

Strengths

The major strength of this review is that it is the first attempt to systematically examine the psychological and physiological benefits of interacting with fish in aquariums. One previous review has addressed this topic [76], but the narrative account focused on research from a restorative environments perspective and did not use a systematic approach. Consequently, evidence relevant to the current research questions was excluded, whereas the systematic approach used in the current review led to a more comprehensive overview of the research findings. The specification of inclusion/exclusion criteria also ensured that research met a minimum standard for inclusion; HAI research has often relied on evidence from poor quality sources that lack stringent peer review, such as books and conference proceedings [99], but evidence from these sources was excluded from the current review. While studies of any design were included, assessing risk of bias and the strength of the evidence ensured that the research findings were considered in the context of methodological limitations. Overall, by using a systematic approach and adhering to PRISMA guidelines [77], this review provided a more rigorous and reliable synthesis of the research evidence, while aiming to meet the standards of transparency and reporting widely expected in other areas of health-related research.

Limitations

There are a number of limitations to this review which should be acknowledged. Firstly, bias may have been introduced by limiting included studies to those published in the English language. Furthermore, three potentially relevant studies could not be included due to issues in gaining access to the full-text, or for copyright reasons (in all cases attempts to identify/contact the authors were unsuccessful). As two of these studies were unpublished theses, this may signify the presence of publication bias; however, it was not appropriate to assess for publication biases statistically due to heterogeneity in study outcomes.

The major limitations of this review were however, the scope and quality of the current research evidence. While the inclusion criteria were deliberately broad to maximise results, only nineteen studies were included in the review; however, despite this small number of included studies, there was substantial clinical and methodological heterogeneity, which made it difficult to draw comparisons across research findings. Furthermore, in all studies risk of bias was either high or unclear, and the strength of evidence was fairly low, with only four of nineteen studies achieving a rating of 'high' for weight of evidence. While the identification of these limitations is crucial to support the development of future research, these inconclusive findings are unhelpful to practitioners wishing to provide their clients with evidence-based advice or interventions.

Future directions

Reflecting the field of HAI more broadly, there is a need for future research to address the discussed methodological limitations, and minimise sources of bias. Intervention studies should aim to meet the "gold standard" of RCTs, or use appropriate alternatives where this is not a possibility (for overview see Kazdin [26]). Given the particularly low strength of evidence relating to keeping fish as companion animals, there is also a need for large-scale observational research to better explore the effects of home aquaria ownership on well-being; this could be achieved through the incorporation of questions about companion animal guardianship into existing longitudinal studies [19,28]. Both experimental and observational research should take into consideration any mediating effects of attachment, sociodemographic characteristics, and health-related behaviours. Furthermore, as examining commonalities in qualitative research findings may be key in identifying the mechanisms underlying HAI [26], there is a need for additional qualitative research on the topic of human-fish interaction.

Aside from addressing methodological limitations, there are several opportunities for future research highlighted by this review. While most of the intervention studies were conducted within specific clinical populations, there was preliminary evidence that human-fish interaction may be beneficial among non-clinical samples. For example, one study found that student anxiety decreased following brief interactions with a single fish in an aquarium [62], and another observed an improvement in job satisfaction among staff working in dementia units following the installation of fish aquariums (although it is unclear whether this was due to the presence of the aquariums or improvements in residents' behaviour) [54]. These findings reflect research with dogs which has indicated that HAI may be beneficial in educational [100,101] or workplace environments [102]. Future research may therefore, wish to explore the influence of interaction with fish in aquariums on student or employee well-being, although it is noteworthy that one study found no relationship between hospital medical directors self-rated health and the presence of aquariums in their working environment [82]. Additionally, as all but one of the included studies were conducted within adult populations, it would be of interest to further explore whether interacting with fish in aquariums is beneficial for the well-being of child or adolescent participants.

Another potential avenue of investigation is to explore which aspects of fish aquariums contribute to improved well-being. Research in public aquariums indicated that the abundance of fish and diversity of species may have a positive impact on well-being outcomes [61,87], but it is currently unclear whether this translates into home aquaria. Furthermore, as this research observed benefits associated with exposure to an unstocked aquarium exhibit [87], future research should take into consideration the presence of additional aquarium features, such as other animals (e.g. snails, shrimp, corals), plants or ornaments, and whether the sound of running water produced by a fish tank plays a role in relaxation [52]. Similarly, consideration should also be given to the type of human-fish interaction. For instance, one study found positive effects associated with interacting with stingrays at an aquarium touch tank [88], but this interaction is very atypical in the context of this review. Thus, while the study furthers the evidence base regarding the benefits of human-fish interaction, it is unclear whether these effects will translate to the benefits of fish aquaria more broadly. Moreover, variation also exists within more common forms of interaction; being involved in the care of the animals may for example, lead to different effects than simply watching fish swimming, and the effectiveness of interventions may be influenced by intensity of exposure, such as the duration and frequency of the human-fish interaction.

Finally, future research should consider the impact of human-fish interactions on the animals involved. At present, much research into the health benefits of HAI has focused on

human well-being, an approach which has been criticised as being human-centred [103,104]. Some researchers have therefore argued for a greater emphasis on the reciprocal nature of HAI, with animals considered active participants in human-animal encounters [20,104]. While research with other species (typically dogs) has begun to investigate the impact of HAI on the animals involved, the effects of human-fish interaction on the fish involved were largely absent from the studies in this review. One paper reported that the fish of two participants died during routine fish care and were replaced [86], but did not specify whether the cause of these deaths was known, or whether steps had been taken to prevent future mortalities. No other studies reported whether the fish experienced any adverse effects of the interactions, and no studies directly assessed fish welfare. Therefore, future research exploring the health benefits of interacting with fish in aquariums should at minimum report whether (or not) any adverse effects to animal welfare are experienced as a result of human-fish interactions.

Parallel to this, additional research is needed to determine the effectivity of non-live alternatives, such as videos of fish swimming. As such interactions provide exposure to animals (albeit in simulated form) while eliminating animal welfare concerns, they may provide a suitable substitution for live fish aquariums. At present only two studies (to our knowledge) have investigated the benefits of watching fish videos [68,84], with conflicting findings. More broadly however, research has identified that robotic animals may have positive effects on well-being outcomes, such as loneliness, depression, and anxiety in older adults [105,106]. Thus, it is possible that non-live alternatives to fish aquaria, such as videos, robotic fish, or computer simulations, may benefit human well-being while eliminating risks to both the human and the animal. However, more research is needed before conclusions can be drawn.

Conclusion

The findings of this review provide tentative support that interacting with fish in aquariums may be beneficial for psychological and physiological well-being among humans. Although findings were mixed, many studies had small sample sizes, so it is possible significant effects would have been detected given adequate power. Conversely however, many studies were subject to methodological limitations and had high or unclear risk of bias. Therefore, more research is needed before firm conclusions can be drawn. Future research on this topic should be well powered, and aim to use robust methodologies that minimise potential sources of bias. Consideration should also be given to any factors which may influence the effects of human-fish interaction, such as participant characteristics, features of the aquarium, or the type of interaction between the human and the animals. Finally, the details of the study design, and in particular the human-fish interaction, should be clearly described to allow for replication.

Supporting information

S1 Appendix. PRISMA checklist.
(PDF)

S2 Appendix. Protocol.
(PDF)

S3 Appendix. Data extraction form.
(PDF)

S4 Appendix. Quality appraisal.
(PDF)

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Article

Companion Animal Type and Level of Engagement Matter: A Mixed-Methods Study Examining Links between Companion Animal Guardianship, Loneliness and Well-Being during the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Simple Summary: Companion animals (pets) may reduce loneliness and promote the well-being of their guardians (owners). This is important in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, as companion animal guardians may be less negatively affected by the pandemic. This research examined the influence of companion animals, and specifically ornamental fishes, on mental well-being and loneliness during the pandemic. Data were collected via an online survey and interviews with companion animal guardians. Companion animal guardianship alone was not linked to loneliness or well-being during the pandemic, but there was evidence that people who interacted more with their dogs (and to a lesser extent cats) were lonelier and had poorer well-being; possibly, these individuals spent more time with their dogs/cats because they were more isolated. Open-ended survey responses and interview data identified that most people felt their companion animals were a positive influence during the pandemic, but ornamental fishes were perceived as having a less positive effect than other companion animals, possibly because they cannot provide comfort via physical touch. Consistent with past research, these findings indicate that people believe their companion animals positively influenced their lives during the pandemic, but there is a lack of quantitative evidence to support these beliefs.

Abstract: To reduce the spread of COVID-19, countries worldwide placed limitations on social interaction, which is anticipated to have severe psychological consequences. Although findings are inconsistent, prior research has suggested that companion animals may positively influence human well-being and reduce loneliness. In the context of COVID-19, this has important implications, as companion animal guardians may be less negatively affected by the pandemic. The primary aim of this research was to investigate the influence of companion animals on mental well-being and loneliness during the pandemic, with specific interest in the role of ornamental fishes. A mixed-methods study was conducted, using an international sample. Quantitative data were collected via an online survey ($n = 1199$) and analysed using robust hierarchical multiple regression analyses; the influence of level of engagement with companion animals was examined for dogs, cats and ornamental fishes. There was no evidence that companion animal guardianship was associated with loneliness and mental well-being during the pandemic but spending more time engaging physically or socially with dogs (and to a lesser extent cats) was generally associated with poorer outcomes. Qualitative data were collected through open-ended survey responses ($n = 757$) and semi-structured interviews ($n = 25$) and analysed using reflexive thematic analysis. Two themes were developed—one related to companion animals as providers of social and emotional support,

and the other to companion animals as providers of purpose and perspective. Concerns regarding the impact of the pandemic on animal welfare were also identified. Compared to other animal types, more participants expressed indifference regarding the impact of their fishes on their well-being during the pandemic, possibly because fishes cannot provide comfort via physical touch. The findings of this study reflect the wider field of human–animal interaction; although qualitative data suggest guardians believe their companion animals are a positive influence in their lives, there is little convincing quantitative data to support these beliefs. This highlights the need to refine theories regarding which aspects of companion animal guardianship may influence human well-being; the findings from this research may be useful in the refinement of such theories.

Keywords: human–animal interaction; ornamental fishes; COVID-19; mixed methods; loneliness; mental well-being

1. Introduction

On 11 March 2020, the World Health Organisation (WHO) declared the COVID-19 outbreak to be a pandemic. The impact of this pandemic is catastrophic; at the time of writing, over 187 million cases and 4 million deaths have been recorded globally [1]. To inhibit the spread of the virus, countries worldwide adopted strategies to limit physical contact between individuals from different households; this included nationwide lockdowns, travel restrictions and social distancing [2].

The psychological consequences of the pandemic are potentially severe [3]. It is well established that social isolation and loneliness are detrimental to physical and mental health, with a risk of premature mortality comparable to that of factors such as obesity or substance abuse [4,5]. Worries related to the pandemic are also a cause of psychological distress. For example, one study conducted during the first six weeks of lockdown in the United Kingdom (UK) identified two aspects of anxiety associated with COVID-19—disease anxiety related to catching or transmitting the virus, and consequence anxiety related to the longer-term impacts of the pandemic, such as in relation to the economic cost [6]. Numerous studies from various countries have already reported psychological issues associated with the early stages of the pandemic [7–10].

Companion animals are widely believed to promote positive well-being. For instance, companionship and emotional support were among the most common reasons given for keeping companion animals among a sample of dog and cat guardians [11], while qualitative findings have indicated that companion animals are considered important sources of mental health support [12–15]. On the other hand, several cross-sectional studies have found no association, or a negative association, between companion animal guardianship and mental or physical health [16–21]. There is also no convincing evidence that companion animals directly influence loneliness [22], although an indirect effect may occur via social facilitation [23,24]. Furthermore, human–animal interaction (HAI) research frequently suffers from methodological issues, such as inadequate sample sizes, high levels of heterogeneity, and a lack of blinding [25–28], plus participants are likely to have positive attitudes towards companion animals, and so findings may not be generalisable [27]. Thus, the influence of companion animals on loneliness and mental well-being remains unclear, but if an effect exists, this may have important implications regarding the psychological impact of the COVID-19 pandemic; companion animal guardians may be less negatively affected in comparison to non-guardians.

However, companion animals may also have detrimentally impacted well-being during the pandemic. Previous research has highlighted negative aspects of keeping companion animals, such as the financial cost and the burden associated with their care [13]. It is possible that these negative aspects were amplified during the pandemic, for instance if restrictions on movement or loss of income impacted the ability of guardians to care for their companion animals. There is also evidence that some guardians are concerned about

the potential of companion animals to transmit or contract the SARS-CoV-2 virus [29]. Therefore, the primary aim of this research was to investigate the relationship between companion animal guardianship, and mental well-being and loneliness during the COVID-19 pandemic; at conception of this study, no published research on this topic was identified.

A secondary aim of this research relates to a broader question in the field of HAI; how any effects associated with companion animal guardianship are influenced by the type of companion animal. Much research has focused on animals that interact with humans in a physical or social manner, namely dogs, cats and horses. Comparatively few studies have examined the impact of other animal types, such as ornamental fishes [30]. Fishes represent a significant proportion of companion animals, for example they are the third most popular companion animal in the UK and are by far the most numerous, as one home aquarium may contain many fishes (www.pfma.org.uk, accessed on 26 February 2021). Only one study to date has examined the impact of fish guardianship on loneliness, and no effect was observed [31]. However, qualitative evidence has demonstrated that some fish guardians believe their fishes provide companionship, along with other psychological benefits such as relaxation [32]. Fishes have also been associated with positive outcomes such as reduced agitation, increased food intake and improved body mass among people with dementia [33–35], reduced anxiety among students preparing for an impromptu presentation [36], and improved mood among visitors to a public aquarium [37]. Thus, the secondary aim of this study was to investigate the specific relationship between keeping ornamental fishes and mental well-being and loneliness during the pandemic.

As the comparison of companion animal guardians and non-guardians may represent an oversimplification of the relationship between companion animal guardianship and well-being [38,39], factors such as sociodemographic characteristics are now widely accounted for in cross-sectional HAI research. Less well understood is how the type and amount of engagement between an individual and their companion animal may influence the relationship between companion animal guardianship and well-being [26,38]. Thus, the current study examined how these relationships may be influenced by the amount of time participants spent engaging in specific behaviours with their companion animal.

Finally, as it is possible that neither quantitative nor qualitative methods are sufficient to understand the relationship between companion animal guardianship and well-being when used in isolation, the current study used an embedded mixed-methods approach. The purpose of using this approach was to obtain qualitative data that could support the interpretation of quantitative findings.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Ethical Approval

This study was approved by the School of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee at the University of the West of Scotland (Ref:12045), and the Mars Research Review Board.

2.2. Design and Procedure

This study used an embedded mixed-methods design [40], with the qualitative component embedded within the larger quantitative study (Figure 1). A convergent approach was used. Quantitative data were collected from June to November 2020 via an online, cross-sectional survey, and qualitative data were collected from June 2020 to January 2021 via open-ended survey questions and in-depth interviews; all participants who completed both components completed the survey prior to the interview. Both datasets were analysed independently, with the qualitative findings used to inform the interpretation of the quantitative results.

Figure 1. Embedded mixed-methods design.

2.3. Participants and Recruitment

Survey participants ($n = 1199$) were an international sample of adults (18+ years) proficient in the English language. The sample comprised mainly individuals from the UK (51%) and USA (32%). Participants were recruited through opportunity sampling (e.g., via social media), with fish-specific organisations/networks purposively targeted. Interview participants ($n = 25$) were recruited either by them contacting the researcher following completion of the survey, or via the same process described above; they comprised individuals from either the UK (84%) or the USA (16%). Both companion animal guardians and non-guardians were eligible to participate in the survey, whereas only companion animal guardians could take part in an interview. Very few participants kept ornamental fishes as their only companion animal, thus data from fish guardians represent the experiences of those who keep ornamental fishes in addition to other companion animals. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their participation.

2.4. Materials

2.4.1. Survey

The survey consisted of a mix of open- and closed-ended questions split over six sections, as described in Table 1.

2.4.2. Interviews

A semi-structured interview schedule was used. Demographic information was collected via closed questions, after which participants were asked to tell the researcher “a little bit” about their companion animals. The rest of the interview focused on their experiences of being a companion animal guardian during the pandemic. All interviews were conducted remotely via phone ($n = 7$) or video conferencing ($n = 18$), and were audio recorded with the permission of the participant.

2.5. Data Analysis

2.5.1. Quantitative Data Management

Survey data were checked for accuracy and completeness prior to analysis; three participants provided inconsistent answers and so their data were removed. Ambiguous responses and those of “prefer not to say” were recorded as missing data but did not exceed 2% of responses per item. Where data were missing for the standardised assessments (<2% per scale), total scores were not calculated. Several demographic variables had low response rates for one or more categories. Where there was reasonable justification, these categories were combined prior to analysis (e.g., for country of residence “Australia or New Zealand” ($n = 39$) and “Canada” ($n = 19$) were collapsed into the category of “other” country). Where there was no reasonable justification, the original categories were retained unless cell sizes were too small to be included in the analyses (e.g., the category of “partner, not living together” ($n = 72$) for marital status was retained, but genders other than male or female ($n = 6$) could not be included).

Table 1. Description of survey questions by section of survey.

Section of Survey	Description
Section 1: Demographic details	Closed questions: age group, gender, ethnicity, highest level of education, marital status, country of residence, and number of adults and children living in the household.
Section 2: Social and lifestyle behaviours during the pandemic	Closed questions regarding the level of social interaction experienced during the pandemic; frequency of communication with friends and family outside the household via written methods (e.g., text messaging, email), verbal methods (e.g., phone or video calls) or face to face, and frequency of having left the home to exercise or complete essential errands (responses from 1 = "Never" to 7 = "More than once a day"); employment status during the pandemic; period of self-isolation greater than one week (yes/no).
Section 3: Companion animal guardianship and level of engagement	Mix of closed and open questions. Participants who kept companion animals indicated which types (dogs, cats, fish, small mammals, exotic animals, birds, and/or other), and for each type: The number of individuals (plus number of tanks/ponds for fishes). If they were the primary caregiver(s). Where the animal lived (inside the home/outside). Where the animal slept (dogs and cats only). Whether interaction with that animal type had been affected by the pandemic (open-ended question). The perceived influence of that animal type on their well-being during the pandemic (1 = "Extremely negative" to 7 = "Extremely positive"). Level of engagement, i.e., the amount of time spent undertaking different behaviours relating to that companion animal type on a typical day during the pandemic (1 = "None" to 8 = "More than four hours"); some behaviours were measured for all animal types (e.g., time spent feeding/talking to animals), some were species-specific (e.g., time spent walking dogs/conducting tank or pond maintenance). Level of engagement was measured rather than human-animal bond, as it is unclear how the latter applies within the fish guardianship dynamic. Additional questions regarding the general experience of companion animal guardianship during the pandemic included: Problems accessing supplies or veterinary treatment (yes/no). Other pandemic-related issues regarding care of companion animals. Level of concern about contracting/giving SARS-CoV-2 from/to companion animals (1 = "Not at all concerned" to 4 = "Extremely concerned"). Any new animals purchased/adopted during/because of the pandemic.
Section 4: Well-being assessments	Series of four validated scales to measure loneliness and well-being. The short-form UCLA Loneliness Scale (UCLA-LS) [41] measured overall loneliness. Thinking about their life "at the moment", participants gave responses to three items (e.g., "How often do you feel that you lack companionship?") on a 3-point scale from 1 = "Hardly ever" to 3 = "Often". Scores were calculated by summing responses (min = 3, max = 9). This scale is commonly used to measure loneliness in HAI research [22], and has satisfactory levels of reliability and validity [41]. The De Jong Gierveld Loneliness Scale is considered a reliable and valid instrument to measure social, emotional and overall loneliness [42]. Responses to six items (e.g., "I miss having people around me") could be "yes", "more or less" or "no". Participants responded with regard to how they were currently feeling. One point was given for items 1–3 if the response was "yes" or "more or less", and for items 4–6 if the response was "no" or "more or less". Emotional loneliness was calculated by summing items 1–3, social loneliness by summing items 4–6 (min = 0, max = 3 for each), and overall loneliness by summing all items (min = 0, max = 6). The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-Being Scale (WEMWBS) [43] measured mental well-being. Participants indicated how much 14 statements (e.g., "I've been feeling optimistic about the future") had applied to them over the past two weeks using a 5-point scale (1 = "None of the time" to 5 = "All of the time"). Scores were calculated by summing responses to all items (min = 14, max = 70). The WEMWBS is used extensively in psychological research and is considered psychometrically sound [43]. The long version was used as it covers both psychological functioning and positive affect, while the short version covers only psychological functioning. The short-form of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21) [44] required participants to respond to 21 statements (e.g., "I found it hard to wind down") using a scale from 0 = "Did not apply to me at all" to 3 = "Applied to me very much" to indicate how much each statement had applied to them over the past two weeks. The timescale for the DASS-21 is usually the past week but was altered to match the WEMWBS. A total score for each construct was calculated by summing responses to all items from the relevant scales (min = 0, max = 21 per subscale). The DASS-21 has high internal consistency and discriminant validity [45].
Section 5: Rating scales for change in well-being during the pandemic	Participants indicated how anxious, low or depressed, stressed, and lonely they had felt during the pandemic, on a scale from 1 = "Much less than normal" to 7 = "Much more than normal". Overall well-being during the pandemic was rated on a scale from 1 = "Much worse than usual" to 7 = "Much better than usual". These items were used to support the understanding of whether any relationships identified between companion animal guardianship and well-being related to the influence of companion animals during the pandemic or are tapping into existing differences in the populations.
Section 6: Open-ended questions	Two items allowed participants to describe in their own words how they had supported their mental well-being during the pandemic, and the specific contribution of their companion animals (if they had any).

The response categories for the social and lifestyle variables were also condensed to reduce the number of parameters in the analyses and provide greater balance in group sizes. For each variable, the median was identified and responses within the corresponding category were assigned a value of 'average'. Responses for the categories above and below the median were recorded as 'more than average' and 'less than average', respectively. For example, for frequency of exercise outside the home the median fell within the category "A few times a week" so these responses were recorded as average; responses of "Never" to "Once a week" were recorded as less than average, and responses of "Once a day" or "More than once a day" as more than average. Where the median fell within the highest or lowest category, that variable was not included in the analyses. Variables relating to the level of engagement with companion animals (e.g., time spent walking dogs) were condensed using the same procedure. Due to wide variation in employment status, participants were categorised as either "working" or "not working" during the pandemic.

2.5.2. Companion Animal Guardianship, Mental Well-Being and Loneliness

Separate hierarchical multiple regression analyses (as in [46]) were conducted to determine whether companion animal guardianship was related to scores on the standardised assessments of depression, anxiety, stress, mental well-being and loneliness. The model had three stages. Demographic characteristics were entered in stage one; it was not possible to include ethnicity as the sample was predominantly white ($n = 1096$, 91%). Social and lifestyle factors were entered at stage two; bivariate correlations were used to determine which variables significantly correlated with at least one dependent variable, and these variables were included in the model. Companion animal guardianship was entered in the final stage as separate dichotomous predictors for whether participants kept any type of companion animal, and whether they kept dogs, cats, fish or other types of companion animal (yes/no for each).

Data were analysed using R version 4.0.0 [47]. There was no evidence of multicollinearity, but in all cases, diagnostics indicated that assumptions were violated due to the presence of influential data points and non-normality of residuals. As robust analyses are recommended for data which violate model assumptions [48], robust regression analyses were conducted via the "lmer" function of the "robustbase" package [49], using the default settings recommended by Koller and Stahel [50]. At each stage a Wald-type test statistic was used to assess whether the inclusion of the additional predictors resulted in a significant change in robust deviance compared to the reduced model; p -values < 0.05 were deemed to be statistically significant.

Multiple scales were used to measure loneliness, but no differences were found with regard to influence of companion animal guardianship across these measures, so only results pertaining to the UCLA-LS are reported.

2.5.3. Level of Engagement with Companion Animals, Mental Well-Being and Loneliness

To examine the influence of level of engagement between a guardian and their companion animal, further robust multiple regression analyses were conducted for the subsets of participants who kept dogs, cats and fishes. Each model included both general and species-specific engagement variables, and whether the participant was the primary caregiver for their companion animal (yes, no or responsibility equally shared with another). All predictors were entered into the models simultaneously, otherwise the analyses were conducted as described above.

2.5.4. Qualitative Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using NVivo 12 Pro [51]. Interview data were combined with responses to the survey question "In what ways, if any, do you feel your companion animals have influenced your mental well-being during the pandemic?" ($n = 757$), and analysed using reflexive thematic analysis [52–54]. An essentialist approach was followed, assuming that participants' accounts reflected reality, and seeking to understand these

experiences to deepen understanding of the quantitative findings. The analysis was conducted by HC; KS read the entire dataset and the final report to ensure the analysis provided an accurate and complete representation of the data.

Familiarisation was achieved through verbatim transcription of the interviews and active re-reading of the dataset. Generation of codes was based on the semantic content of the data and followed a predominantly inductive approach; potential codes identified during familiarisation formed the basis of the analysis, but the researcher coded openly for any relevant features of the dataset. Following initial coding, themes were constructed by organising codes into groups to identify “patterns of shared meaning across the dataset” [53] (p. 592); thematic maps were used to support this process and visualise the structure of the analysis. Candidate themes were then ‘tested out’ against the data; all extracts coded onto each theme were examined to determine whether they formed a coherent pattern, and brief textual descriptions were produced and compared to identify areas of overlap. Adjustments were made as needed. Finally, the entire dataset was reviewed to ensure the themes accurately and fully represented the data. Each of the final themes represents a patterned response within the data that captures something of importance to the research question; they were not selected based on prevalence alone.

Data were analysed across all types of companion animal collectively. However, in line with the objective to focus on ornamental fishes, extracts were chosen to represent companion animal guardianship in general, with additional quotations from fish guardians provided where relevant.

3. Results

3.1. Sample Characteristics

3.1.1. Survey

Survey data were available for 1199 participants; 1159 (97%) responded to the question “Do you have any companion animals (pets)?” and 1069 (89%) reached the end of the survey. Most participants ($n = 1005$, 84%) kept at least one companion animal, with 42% ($n = 419$) of these individuals keeping a mix of companion animal types. Dogs were the most popular species both overall ($n = 661$, 66%) and where they were the only type of companion animal kept in the household ($n = 329$, 33%); cats were the second most popular (total $n = 469$, 47%; single species $n = 200$, 20%). Fewer individuals kept fishes ($n = 218$, 22%), small mammals ($n = 87$, 9%), exotic animals ($n = 77$, 8%), birds ($n = 65$, 6%) or other types of companion animal ($n = 47$, 5%), and in all cases 2% or less were kept as the only species. “Other” companion animals included horses, ponies or farm animals, insects/invertebrates, and wild birds. With regard to ornamental fishes, most participants kept their fishes in tanks ($n = 171$, 78%), or tanks and ponds ($n = 33$, 15%); only 10 participants (5%) kept fishes in ponds alone (four participants did not state whether their fishes were kept in tanks or ponds). Survey sample characteristics for companion animal guardians and non-guardians are summarised in Table 2; a breakdown of sample characteristics by type of companion animal can be found in Table S1.

3.1.2. Interviews

Twenty-five participants took part in an interview. Most identified as female ($n = 22$, 88%); 10 (40%) were aged 18–34 years, with slightly fewer aged 35–50 years ($n = 7$, 28%) or 51–69 years ($n = 8$, 32%). All resided in the UK ($n = 21$, 84%) or the USA ($n = 4$, 16%) and most lived with other people ($n = 21$, 84%). Dogs and cats were the most popular companion animals ($n = 13$ for both, 52%). Seven participants (28%) kept fishes, four (16%) kept small mammals, and three (12%) kept exotic animals; no participants kept birds or other companion animals. Some individuals did report keeping invertebrates, but these were always kept alongside fishes. Eleven participants (44%) kept a mix of companion animal types; all participants who kept fishes kept at least one other type of companion animal. Fourteen participants (56%) were the primary caregiver for at least one companion animal, and all other participants shared this responsibility with another person.

Table 2. Survey participant characteristics by companion animal guardianship status.

	All Companion Animal Guardians (n = 1005)	Non-Companion Animal Guardians (n = 154)	Total (n = 1159)
Age			
18–34	364 (36%)	74 (48%)	438 (38%)
35–50	353 (35%)	41 (27%)	394 (34%)
51–69	254 (25%)	27 (18%)	281 (24%)
70+	32 (3%)	12 (8%)	44 (4%)
Prefer not to say	2 (<1%)	0	2 (<1%)
Gender			
Female	839 (83%)	111 (72%)	950 (82%)
Male	154 (15%)	41 (27%)	195 (17%)
Other	4 (<1%)	2 (1%)	6 (1%)
Prefer not to say	8 (1%)	0	8 (1%)
Ethnicity			
White	920 (92%)	141 (92%)	1061 (92%)
Asian	18 (2%)	5 (3%)	23 (2%)
Black or African American	5 (<1%)	1 (1%)	6 (1%)
Hispanic or Latino	32 (3%)	3 (2%)	35 (3%)
Two or more	12 (1%)	1 (1%)	13 (1%)
Prefer not to say/unclear	18 (2%)	3 (2%)	21 (2%)
Education			
High school or below	135 (13%)	15 (10%)	150 (13%)
Undergraduate	415 (41%)	47 (31%)	462 (40%)
Masters	270 (27%)	37 (37%)	327 (28%)
Doctorate	172 (17%)	35 (23%)	207 (18%)
Prefer not to say/don't know	13 (1%)	0	13 (1%)
Marital			
Married/living with partner	620 (62%)	77 (50%)	697 (60%)
Partner, not living together	57 (6%)	14 (9%)	71 (6%)
Single, separated, divorced or widowed	320 (32%)	61 (40%)	381 (33%)
Prefer not to say/unclear	8 (1%)	2 (1%)	10 (1%)
Live with children			
Yes	244 (24%)	38 (25%)	282 (24%)
No	761 (76%)	116 (75%)	877 (76%)
Country			
United Kingdom	473 (47%)	113 (73%)	586 (51%)
United States	351 (35%)	24 (16%)	375 (32%)
Other	179 (18%)	16 (10%)	195 (17%)
Prefer not to say	2 (<1%)	1 (1%)	3 (<1%)
Frequency of written communication			
Less than an average amount	390 (39%)	64 (42%)	454 (39%)
An average amount	615 (61%)	90 (58%)	705 (61%)
Frequency of verbal communication			
Less than an average amount	305 (30%)	31 (20%)	336 (29%)
An average amount	404 (40%)	61 (40%)	465 (40%)
More than an average amount	296 (29%)	62 (40%)	358 (31%)
Frequency of face-to-face communication			
Less than an average amount	330 (33%)	48 (31%)	378 (33%)
An average amount	258 (26%)	38 (25%)	296 (26%)
More than an average amount	416 (41%)	67 (44%)	483 (42%)
Prefer not to say	1 (<1%)	1 (1%)	2 (<1%)
Frequency of exercise outside the home			
Less than an average amount	323 (32%)	44 (29%)	367 (32%)
An average amount	233 (23%)	50 (32%)	283 (24%)
More than an average amount	445 (44%)	60 (39%)	505 (44%)
Prefer not to say	4 (<1%)	0	4 (<1%)
Frequency of essential errands			
Less than an average amount	291 (29%)	41 (27%)	332 (29%)
An average amount	387 (39%)	69 (45%)	456 (39%)
More than an average amount	327 (33%)	44 (29%)	371 (32%)
Working			
Yes	756 (75%)	122 (79%)	878 (76%)
No	241 (24%)	32 (21%)	273 (24%)
Prefer not to say	8 (1%)	0	8 (1%)
Period of isolation greater than 1 week			
Yes	305 (30%)	31 (20%)	336 (29%)
No	697 (69%)	123 (80%)	820 (71%)
Prefer not to say	3 (<1%)	0	3 (<1%)

Note: 'Other' genders were recorded as missing data for analyses; examples of unclear responses include "human being" and "English" for ethnicity, and "boyfriend" and "engaged" for marital status.

3.2. Quantitative Findings

Participants who kept companion animals overwhelmingly rated them to have had a positive effect on their well-being during the pandemic (Figure 2). Most participants believed their dogs and cats had an extremely or moderately positive effect on their well-being, while fewer individuals believed they had a slightly positive effect or no effect at all. To a lesser extent, the same pattern of results was observed for guardians of other companion animals, whereas for fishes there was a more even split across these four categories. For all animal types, only a very small minority of participants rated their companion animals as having had any degree of negative effect on their well-being (<2%).

Figure 2. The percentage of participants who responded with each category across the scale by type of companion animal. ‘Other companion animal’ is inclusive of small mammals, exotic animals, birds and otherwise unspecified companion animals (e.g., horses). Dogs $n = 661$, cats $n = 469$, fish $n = 218$, and other companion animal $n = 276$.

Eighteen per cent of participants had experienced issues obtaining pet care supplies and 14% reported problems accessing veterinary treatment; 13% reported additional negative impacts associated with the pandemic (e.g., reduced frequency of dog walking, no access to professional grooming services). Twelve per cent of participants ($n = 125$) reported adopting or purchasing a new companion animal during the pandemic, with around a quarter (24%) agreeing that the pandemic was instrumental in their decision to adopt. Most participants (92%) reported being not at all concerned about contracting SARS-CoV-2 from their companion animals; 7% were a little concerned and less than 1% were somewhat or extremely concerned. More individuals reported being a little (20%), somewhat (6%) or extremely (1%) concerned about passing SARS-CoV-2 onto their companion animals. However, most (73%) were not at all concerned about this possibility.

3.2.1. Companion Animal Guardianship, Mental Well-Being and Loneliness

Correlations between participants’ scores on the standardised assessments and their subjective ratings of how the pandemic had influenced their loneliness and mental well-being ranged from medium to large in size ($r_s = 0.36$ – 0.51 , $p < 0.001$ in all cases). This suggests that scores on the standardised assessments likely reflected a combination of pre-existing mental states and pandemic-related changes.

Full results of the robust hierarchical regression analyses are shown in Table S2. Participants' demographic characteristics explained between 7.1% and 12.9% of variance in their scores on the standardised assessments. In all cases, this was a statistically significant improvement in the model fit ($\chi^2(12) = 74.94\text{--}150.85$, $p < 0.001$ in all cases). Social and lifestyle factors explained an additional 2.6% to 3.6% of variance; again, the model fit was significantly improved for all dependent variables ($\chi^2(8) = 27.66\text{--}42.54$, $p < 0.01$ in all cases). The addition of companion animal guardianship factors did not significantly improve the model fit for any dependent variable ($\chi^2(5) = 1.40\text{--}9.88$, $p > 0.05$ in all cases). Dog guardianship was found to be significantly associated with depression, and guardianship of other companion animals was found to be significantly associated with anxiety. However, in both cases there was no overall change in robust deviance, suggesting that these associations emerged because dog and other companion animal guardianship shared variance with a predictor or predictors already included in the model.

3.2.2. Level of Engagement with Companion Animals, Mental Well-Being and Loneliness

The results of the robust regression analyses are given in Table S3. Level of engagement with dogs explained between 4.8% and 7.1% of variance in scores on the standardised assessments, and in all cases this was a statistically significant improvement in the model fit ($\chi^2(12) = 28.19\text{--}48.03$, $p < 0.01$ in all cases). With respect to the contribution of individual predictors, spending less time than average talking to dogs was associated with higher mental well-being ($\beta = 2.41$, $SE = 1.22$, $t = 1.97$, $p < 0.05$). Lower mental well-being ($\beta = -2.22$, $SE = 1.08$, $t = -2.07$, $p = 0.039$) and higher depression ($\beta = 1.78$, $SE = 0.88$, $t = 2.03$, $p = 0.043$) were associated with a greater than average amount of time spent petting dogs, while spending less time than average petting dogs was associated with lower anxiety ($\beta = -1.59$, $SE = 0.58$, $t = -2.74$, $p = 0.006$). Walking dogs for less time than average per day was associated with both higher anxiety ($\beta = 1.38$, $SE = 0.46$, $t = 3.02$, $p = 0.003$) and higher loneliness ($\beta = 0.41$, $SE = 0.17$, $t = 2.35$, $p = 0.019$); loneliness was also associated with less time than average spent undertaking 'other' activities with one's dog ($\beta = 0.49$, $SE = 0.20$, $t = 2.40$, $p = 0.017$). Finally, being the primary caregiver for a dog, or sharing this responsibility with another person, was associated with more positive scores across all dependent variables relative to not being the primary caregiver ($p < 0.05$ in all cases).

The model for level of engagement with cats was a statistically significant improvement on the null model for depression, anxiety, and stress ($\chi^2(10) = 20.48\text{--}23.39$, $p < 0.05$ in all cases). These models explained between 4.5% and 5.2% of variance in the relevant dependent variable. Spending more time than average talking to cats was associated with lower anxiety ($\beta = -1.76$, $SE = 0.75$, $t = -2.35$, $p = 0.019$) whereas spending less time than average was associated with lower depression ($\beta = -4.29$, $SE = 1.15$, $t = -3.73$, $p < 0.001$); lower stress was associated with spending both more ($\beta = -3.01$, $SE = 1.35$, $t = -2.23$, $p = 0.026$) and less ($\beta = -3.65$, $SE = 1.25$, $t = -2.92$, $p = 0.004$) time than average talking to cats. For mental well-being and loneliness, level of engagement with cats did not significantly improve the model fit (mental well-being, $\chi^2(10) = 14.24$, $p = 0.162$; UCLA-LS, $\chi^2(10) = 14.83$, $p = 0.139$).

The model for level of engagement with fishes did not result in a significant improvement in model fit for any of the dependent variables (mental well-being, $\chi^2(10) = 5.37$, $p = 0.865$; loneliness, $\chi^2(10) = 9.45$, $p = 0.450$; depression, $\chi^2(10) = 5.33$, $p = 0.868$; anxiety, $\chi^2(10) = 7.34$, $p = 0.693$; stress, $\chi^2(10) = 9.46$, $p = 0.489$).

3.3. Qualitative Findings

Two themes were developed from the data. "Companion animals as providers of social support" related to the notion that companion animals offered an alternative to interpersonal connections during a time of isolation. "Companion animals as providers of purpose and perspective" related more to the practicalities of being a companion animal guardian, and how this helped participants retain a sense of normality and feel useful when they may have otherwise become dispirited. There was also evidence that animal

welfare may have been influenced by the pandemic, but these data did not relate to the current research question and so are not reported here. Example quotations are provided in Tables 3 and 4.

3.3.1. Theme 1: Companion Animals as Providers of Social Support

“It meant never being alone”

Most participants felt their companion animals had provided comfort and support, both prior to and during the pandemic. This support was experienced at two levels. At a basic level, participants were comforted by the mere presence of a companion animal as another living being in their home. At a deeper level, companion animals provided psychological and emotional support, helping their guardians cope with the uncertainty caused by the pandemic. Individuals experiencing a greater degree of isolation particularly appreciated the support provided by their companion animals, such as those who lived alone or had switched to remote working during the pandemic.

Table 3. Example quotations for “Companion animals as providers of social support”.

Subtheme	Example Quotations
It meant never being alone	<p><i>“They are company, comfort, a living presence in my empty home” (Survey, Participant 677)</i></p> <p><i>“... my husband his work is outside of the home, so during lockdown he had to be at home... when he left it was a big change because we were like three months, you know, we were on top of each other in a one bedroom flat and it was really, really nice because you know I’d get on with work and he’d be doing things around the house and yeah he was just there, but then when he started going back to work I was like “oh my gosh” you know, and then I’m not going back to work, I’m here at home still so I think at that point having the cats and dog became even more important” (Interview, Participant 21)</i></p> <p><i>“... having her for company in a time when I am very isolated has been not a perfect substitute for human interaction but it has been something...” (Survey, Participant 318)</i></p>
A substitute for human talk and touch	<p><i>“As I’ve had less face to face contact with friends and family my dog’s company has been exceptionally important. I think I would have felt very alone otherwise. I normally have a hug with friends/family, so it’s been good to have my dog curl up next to me for a cuddle.” (Survey, Participant 51)</i></p> <p><i>“They have been company for me and the only other beings I could have any physical contact with for three full months. They’re very loving and sweet, but I’ve still felt the lack of a human hug too—dog snuggles are lovely but it’s also not the same as being held.” (Survey, Participant 222)</i></p> <p><i>“... even though they don’t answer me back, to be able to speak with them in such a way that it’s humanising, yes it’s anthropomorphising them but that’s part of it, that yes you can talk with them and they do seem to respond and you know, a dog cocks his head when you’re talking to him and it’s because he’s confused but it’s still—you know he’s listening...” (Interview, Participant 14)</i></p>
Bridging interpersonal connections during social distancing	<p><i>“When I have taken my dogs out it has sometimes been because of them that strangers might at least say hello, this may have been my only interaction with a human some days” (Survey, Participant 96)</i></p> <p><i>“... it’s been really nice to sort of see everyone on zoom calls with their respective pets and random cats and dogs wandering into frame, so I think that’s been quite nice to see as well, it kind of builds a like ‘oh I didn’t know you had a dog’ or ‘what type of dog do you have’, so that’s been nice...” (Interview, Participant 19)</i></p> <p><i>“... I’ve really enjoyed learning new things about the fish or keeping the fish etc. I’ve also enjoyed—I use Instagram and I share pictures [of aquaria] and things on there, which has been cool because I’ve met and been speaking to new people...” (Interview, Participant 10)</i></p> <p><i>“... my son [son’s name] wants me to send photos of the dogs and things like that so, so yeah I think because maybe people have got more time on their hands—other people in the family—they’ve wanted to do more with them...” (Interview, Participant 24)</i></p>

Table 4. Example quotations for “Companion animals as providers of purpose and perspective”.

Subtheme	Example Quotations
They help maintain a normal routine	<p>“... one thing with the fish particularly, because they need quite a lot of ongoing care, you know they need regular water changes, you know, all the looking after of the water, you can't sort of think 'oh I really can't be bothered this week' you have to do it, and having that routine has actually been quite a good thing—everybody laughs about you don't know what day of the week it is let alone what month of the year it is, because every day's just the same at the moment, and actually having that regular routine with the fish has been a good thing actually ...” (Interview, Participant 17)</p> <p>“They are normal. They act normal. The routine is normal. They seem to like that I am home more. At home, things are normal. This makes it easier to cope with things not being normal outside the home. And makes it easier to stay home.” (Survey, Participant 699)</p> <p>“Having a dog has definitely helped because I have walked every single day of lockdown so it's a great excuse for exercise, which also gave me the opportunity to get out and explore what's on my doorstep, so I've discovered new things about where I live. The feeling of getting away from the four walls when we could only exercise once a day was a real mental health lifesaver ...” (Survey, Participant 348)</p>
Something good to focus on	<p>“... you feel out of control, you don't know who's going to get sick, when and how badly, there's a lot of fear and those little moments of escaping that to deal with a companion [animal] is invaluable ...” (Interview, Participant 23)</p> <p>“... it's so nice on an evening or something if I'm feeding them, they'll come running in and playing and they're really cute and make me laugh, they're better than the television ...” (Interview, Participant 5)</p> <p>“The fish tank has provided relaxation as you can sit and stare at it for a long time and it keeps interest.” (Survey, Participant 462)</p>
A reason to keep going	<p>“I have struggled with feeling useless due to being furloughed but having the dog to feed/walk/train has given my days structure and purpose” (Survey, Participant 668)</p> <p>“... the responsibility of making sure they are okay is motivating to keep going and look after myself also and, in the extreme times, it's an important reason to stay alive ...” (Survey, Participant 706)</p> <p>“Overall the fish have had a positive influence during this time. But there has been anxiety as my fish needed a bigger tank. Impossible to get a tank during lockdown. I had issues buying seafood for my fish as panic buyers bought it all. I had trouble with buying essential items locally. When I thought I had COVID and was told to go into hospital I had no one to look after my fish. So this influenced my decision to stay in hospital.” (Survey, Participant 469)</p> <p>“... I've got a cupboard absolutely stashed with the kind of food that I think she's probably going to like and it's ok, just because if suddenly I can't go to the shops “oh my gosh” so—and I'm probably more so on her behalf because for myself, ok I'll just have plain pasta and I'm quite ok with that but I feel more responsible for her well-being and I want to make sure that she's got everything she needs ...” (Interview, Participant 20)</p>

Despite being isolated from friends, family or colleagues, having companion animals meant that participants were never truly alone; they were surrogates for interpersonal contact when connections with other humans were restricted. Although the quantitative results showed no evidence of a relationship between companion animal guardianship and loneliness, some participants clarified that their companion animals could not fully replace the need for human-to-human connections. Therefore, the comfort and support provided by companion animals may have been insufficient to alleviate feelings of loneliness to an extent that it was observable via quantitative assessments.

“A substitute for human talk and touch”

Given the need to maintain physical distance from other humans, it is unsurprising that cuddling and other forms of physical affection were an important aspect of the support provided by companion animals during the COVID-19 pandemic. Many participants also reported talking to their companion animals, and their non-verbal responses provided comfort by showing that somebody was listening. Again, these effects were of particular importance to individuals who were more isolated from their social networks, suggesting

that where human-to-human interactions were impossible due to pandemic-related restrictions, companion animals provided an accessible alternative. This corresponds with the quantitative finding that a higher level of engagement with dogs, and to a lesser extent cats, was associated with poorer outcomes for some dependent variables; individuals experiencing greater isolation may have simultaneously experienced poorer mental states and been more inclined to seek support from their companion animals. Furthermore, if the comfort and support provided by companion animals was dependent on these physical and social interactions, it would explain why participants were less positive about the impact of ornamental fishes on their well-being during the pandemic; as put succinctly by one participant, it is “hard to hug a fish” (Survey, Participant 171).

“Bridging interpersonal connections during social distancing”

Companion animals also benefitted their guardians by facilitating interpersonal connections. Even during the tightest restrictions, leaving the house was permitted for reasons related to animal welfare, such as to walk dogs or attend to horses. This often led to brief socially-distanced interactions that were vastly appreciated during the period of isolation. Correspondingly, the quantitative results indicated that walking dogs for less time than average each day was associated with higher loneliness; possibly, those who spent less time walking their dogs had fewer opportunities for these brief social encounters.

Within existing interpersonal relationships, activities such as playing with or exercising companion animals were an opportunity to connect, particularly when other social or leisure activities were unavailable. Even when communication took place via electronic methods, companion animals acted as social catalysts by providing a topic of conversation. However, these benefits may not have been limited to companion animal guardians. Some participants noted that friends, family and strangers were interested in hearing about, or interacting with their companion animals, and it is unclear whether these individuals kept companion animals themselves. As the quantitative results did not account for human-animal interaction outside of the companion animal guardianship dynamic, these interactions could have confounded the results, particularly as participants of a survey about companion animals are likely to have positive attitudes towards animals, irrespective of their current guardianship status.

3.3.2. Theme 2: Companion Animals as Providers of Purpose and Perspective

“They help maintain a normal routine”

Being unable to understand the concept of a pandemic, companion animals continued to adhere to their usual schedules, and expected activities such as meals and walks to occur at specific times of day. As participants recognised their responsibility to their companion animals, they also continued to adhere to these routines. This was beneficial as it added structure to their day and allowed them to experience something which resembled normal life; ornamental fishes were particularly beneficial in this regard, as regular tank maintenance was essential for fish welfare (see Table 4 for supporting quotations). The timing of data collection may explain why these benefits are not reflected in the quantitative findings. Data collection began around three months after COVID-19 was declared a pandemic by the WHO. At this time, many individuals had recommenced work outside the home, while those working remotely will have had the opportunity to develop new working routines. Had data collection commenced earlier during the pandemic, these effects may have been evident as participants had not yet adjusted to the “new normal”.

Exercise routines were also appreciated, and many participants felt that without the need to walk their dogs they would have lacked the motivation to engage in regular physical activity. These routines also gave participants an opportunity to be outdoors, which was greatly valued during the restrictions imposed due to the pandemic. There was quantitative evidence that having primary or shared responsibility for a dog was associated with more positive scores for all dependent variables. As having a greater level of responsibility for a dog presumably increases the likelihood of walking that dog, this

supports the idea that the maintenance of exercise routines was an important benefit of dog guardianship during the pandemic.

“Something good to focus on”

Many participants indicated that their companion animals provided a source of positive distraction throughout the pandemic. Companion animals not only helped to take their guardians' minds off negative thoughts associated with the pandemic, but also provided a much-needed source of pleasure; their antics gave their guardians a reason to smile. Among participants who kept ornamental fishes, watching home aquaria was frequently cited as a beneficial activity; the movement and behaviour of the fishes in the tank captured participants' attention, distracting them and inducing relaxation. These findings suggest that the effect of companion animals on well-being during the pandemic may have been relatively transient; a guardian may have experienced relief from negative mental states while actively watching or interacting with their companion animal, but it is unclear how long this effect was retained once the interaction concluded. As the assessments used in the current study related to well-being over the previous two weeks, they unfortunately provide no insight into the role of companion animals as providers of momentary relief.

“A reason to keep going”

The responsibility of being a companion animal guardian gave many participants a sense of purpose. For those experiencing employment issues, caring for a companion animal was a source of the meaningful activity, whereas others were motivated to ‘carry on’ by the knowledge that their companion animal was entirely dependent on them. Thus, companion animal guardianship may not have protected against the negative psychological impact of the pandemic, but may play a role in how participants cope with these negative consequences going forward.

Conversely, many participants expressed concern about whether the imposed restrictions would impact their ability to care for their companion animals, particularly in relation to obtaining supplies and veterinary treatment. Although for most these concerns were not realised (a finding corroborated by the quantitative data), several participants expressed that this was an added stress during an already stressful time. Some participants also expressed greater concern regarding the impact of the pandemic on their companion animals, than on their own well-being. This suggests any benefits associated with being a companion animal guardian during the pandemic may have been negated by additional stresses associated with this responsibility. Thus, the quantitative analyses may have failed to find evidence of any associations between companion animal guardianship and loneliness and mental well-being during the pandemic because the relationship between these variables is more complex than was accounted for in the statistical models.

4. Discussion

This study aimed to examine the relationship between companion animal guardianship and loneliness and mental well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic. Quantitative data analyses found no evidence of a linear relationship between keeping companion animals and loneliness or mental well-being, either for all animal types collectively or for specific species (dogs, cats, ornamental fishes). However, most participants positively rated the impact of their companion animals on their well-being during the pandemic, and qualitative data indicated that being a companion animal guardian was associated with a range of benefits in the context of COVID-19. These findings correspond with research conducted prior to the pandemic; there is a lack of convincing quantitative evidence to demonstrate differences in loneliness and well-being between companion animal guardians and non-guardians [22,55], yet qualitative studies show that people believe their companion animals positively influence their well-being [14,15,56,57].

4.1. Engagement with Companion Animals during the Pandemic

How people engage with their companion animals may influence the relationships between companion animal guardianship and loneliness and well-being [26,38]. The present study found evidence that spending more time than average talking to or petting dogs tended to be associated with more negative scores for loneliness and well-being, while the reverse was true for more positive scores. Causality cannot be established from the current data, but qualitative findings indicated that companionship, including physical and social interaction, was a benefit of keeping companion animals during the pandemic, particularly for more isolated individuals. This finding is corroborated by other research conducted during the pandemic [58]. More isolated individuals may therefore have experienced greater loneliness and poorer mental well-being during the pandemic, and subsequently spent more time engaging with their dogs as a substitute for interpersonal contact. Correspondingly, previous research has shown that among people with low levels of social support from humans, higher attachment to companion animals is associated with higher levels of loneliness [59]. However, contact with companion animals was an imperfect substitute for contact with other humans. Future research may wish to identify which aspects of interpersonal contact can and cannot be replicated by companion animals in order to identify which populations may benefit most from human–animal interactions.

The relationships between level of engagement with cats and well-being were less clear; more positive scores were associated with both greater than average and lower than average levels of engagement. A possible reason for this finding is that personality differences between dog and cat guardians influenced their experiences of the pandemic. Previous research has shown that self-identified ‘dog people’ tend to be more extraverted than ‘cat people’ [60]. While extraversion is usually associated with less loneliness and greater well-being, these protective effects may have been lost in the context of the pandemic due to restrictions on social interaction [61]. Due to their more extraverted nature, dog guardians may have had a greater desire for interpersonal contact which could not be satisfied through engagement with their companion animals. Cat guardians may have experienced a lesser need for social interaction, and so in some cases found that engagement with their companion animal was sufficient to alleviate the negative impacts of the pandemic. Further research is needed to examine how personality traits may interact with companion animal guardianship to influence the effects of social isolation.

Previous research has suggested that being a dog guardian may have greater benefits than the guardianship of other companion animals [62–65]. The current study found that primary or shared responsibility for a dog was associated with more positive outcomes for all dependent variables, suggesting that actively caring for a dog has benefits beyond the simple presence of a dog in the home. A probable explanation relates to the need to exercise dogs on a regular basis. Not only is there a known link between frequent physical activity and improved mental health [66], qualitative data indicated that dog walking had additional benefits, such as providing opportunities for social interaction and to spend time outdoors. Spending less time than average walking dogs was also associated with higher loneliness, possibly because participants had fewer opportunities for social interaction (although this finding is dependent on self-report data which were not verified with the use of pedometers or activity trackers). Previous research conducted both prior to and during the pandemic corroborates the finding that dog walking is associated with increased social connectedness [58,67–69], while numerous studies have demonstrated benefits associated with spending time in nature [70,71]. As having a greater level of responsibility for a dog presumably increases the likelihood of walking that dog, this would explain why more positive outcomes are associated with primary or shared responsibility of a dog, but not for cats or ornamental fishes.

4.2. Negative Aspects of Companion Animal Guardianship during the Pandemic

Both quantitative and qualitative data indicated that relatively few participants had experienced issues ensuring the welfare of their companion animals during the pandemic.

Despite this finding, qualitative data suggested that proper care of companion animals was a significant source of worry for guardians during this time; this finding is corroborated by other research conducted during the pandemic [72,73]. Previous research has also indicated that people are willing to delay hospitalisation [74] or refuse access to support services [75] for the sake of their companion animals, and similar attitudes were present in the current study. Participants were often more concerned about the potential negative impact of COVID-19 on their companion animals than on themselves. For instance, while most participants had no concerns about transmitting SARS-CoV-2 either to or from their companion animals, a slightly larger proportion reported being concerned about transmitting the virus to their companion animals than the reverse; this finding is replicated in other research [73]. Therefore, the relationship between companion animal guardianship and well-being during the pandemic may have been confounded by the unique stresses associated with keeping companion animals.

A small number of individuals had very negative attitudes regarding the influence of their companion animals on their well-being during the pandemic. Although these individuals were very much in the minority, it is important to acknowledge their experiences, particularly as research in the HAI discipline is subject to self-selection biases; individuals are more likely to partake if they have positive attitudes towards companion animals [27]. As such, the current study findings should be interpreted with this population in mind, and future research should aim to blind study participants wherever possible to reduce the impact of these biases.

4.3. Ornamental Fishes and the Pandemic

A secondary aim of this research was to investigate the specific relationship between keeping ornamental fishes and loneliness and mental well-being during the pandemic. Quantitative analyses provided no evidence of an association between keeping ornamental fishes and scores on the standardised assessments; there was also no evidence that these relationships were influenced by the level of engagement between participants and their fishes. Very little research has examined the relationship between ornamental fish guardianship and loneliness and mental well-being [30], but these findings are in agreement with one study which examined the effects of adopting two goldfish on well-being among older adults; after six months no differences were found in loneliness, anxiety, leisure satisfaction, or happiness between the group who were given the goldfish and a no-treatment control [31].

Most participants rated ornamental fishes as having a positive impact on their well-being during the pandemic, but around a quarter appeared to feel indifferently and reported that their fishes had no effect. A likely explanation is that ornamental fishes are not viewed as companions in the same way as animals such as dogs and cats. Though some people who kept fishes felt they had bonded with their animals, many appreciated their home aquaria on a purely aesthetic level; watching fishes was an enjoyable and relaxing activity but provided little in the way of social or emotional support. Correspondingly, previous research found that many people who kept ornamental fishes associated them with benefits such as stress reduction, but 22% also viewed their home aquarium as 'room decoration' [76]. Physical touch was identified as an important aspect of the support provided by companion animals, a finding corroborated by other research conducted during the pandemic [58,67,72]. As fishes cannot interact with humans in a physical manner, it is therefore unsurprising that they were perceived as having a slightly less positive impact on the well-being of their guardians compared to other types of companion animals.

However, some aspects of fishkeeping were perceived to have positively impacted well-being during the pandemic. The need to provide ongoing care, irrespective of animal type, helped participants maintain a normal routine and made them feel needed. The relaxing effect of watching home aquaria was also commonly cited as a benefit of keeping ornamental fishes, though no association was found between time spent watching fishes each day and outcomes relating to relaxation, such as stress or anxiety. Current evidence

regarding the relaxing effects of fish aquaria is inconclusive; although some studies have demonstrated results indicative of relaxation [37,77,78], others have failed to find evidence of an effect [79,80], and methodological issues make it difficult to draw firm conclusions [30]. Furthermore, most studies finding positive results have assessed outcomes immediately after viewing an aquarium, with a lack of evidence regarding how any transient benefits of watching a fish tank may translate into longer-term effects on well-being. As it is evident from this study and past research [32,76] that people believe watching fishes promotes relaxation, further research is needed to determine the specific circumstances under which this relaxation is induced, and how this may relate to overall well-being among ornamental fish guardians.

4.4. Strengths and Limitations

The mixed-methods design used in the current research provides a more complete understanding of the role that companion animals (and specifically, ornamental fishes) played in loneliness and mental well-being during the pandemic. Quantitative analysis is useful in summarising and comparing large quantities of data, but qualitative findings are needed to support the refinement of theory, and understand why interaction with companion animals may or may not influence well-being outcomes; despite this there is a lack of rigorous qualitative HAI research [28]. While cross-sectional data showed no association between companion animal guardianship and loneliness or well-being, qualitative findings demonstrated that companion animal guardians believe such effects exist. Identifying the specific aspects of keeping companion animals that were beneficial during the pandemic allows researchers to develop and test more nuanced theories regarding the importance of companion animals in the lives of their humans. Furthermore, the use of semi-structured interviews provided a deeper insight into the experiences of companion animal guardians than could be achieved through open-ended survey questions alone. While preferably qualitative data analysis would be conducted collaboratively by two authors, this was not possible due to time constraints. However, the final report was reviewed by a second author familiar with the data to ensure that the dataset was accurately and fully represented.

A cross-sectional design was used as the unprecedented nature of the pandemic precluded collection of baseline data. There were significant correlations between participants' ratings of how their loneliness and well-being had changed during the pandemic and their scores on the standardised assessments, suggesting that to some degree these scores captured how participants had been affected by the pandemic. However, these scores likely also reflected participants' levels of loneliness and mental well-being pre-pandemic. Some research has indicated that companion animal guardians may have poorer mental health than non-guardians [19,21], so it is possible that no associations were found between companion animal guardianship and loneliness and mental well-being in the current study, because existing differences between the groups masked any protective effects of companion animal guardianship. A UK-based study conducted during the first lockdown found that companion animal guardians experienced less deterioration in well-being and smaller increases in loneliness than those without companion animals, but these differences were very small, and the authors cautioned against claiming that companion animals strongly protected against the negative consequences of the pandemic [72].

Unlike other research conducted during the pandemic [58,67,72,81], the current study was not conducted under strict lockdown conditions. Consequently, participants will have experienced greater variation in COVID-19-related restrictions than in other research. This may explain why the statistical models explained relatively little variation in participants' scores on the standardised assessments, despite accounting for a variety of demographic, social and lifestyle factors beyond companion animal guardianship. In particular, variation in employment status was reduced to a dichotomous variable, and it is possible that companion animal guardianship may have had differing influences for those whose employment was affected by the pandemic. Internet access was also required, which likely limited the number of older adults able to participate; as this population was at higher

risk from COVID-19, different effects may have been identified if the sample contained more older adults. The study findings should therefore be interpreted in the context of the sample from which they were derived: predominantly white, female, residents in either the UK or USA, and quite highly educated relative to the general population.

4.5. Future Considerations

It has been argued that the ways individuals engage with their companion animals may influence the relationship between companion animal guardianship and well-being [26,38], and there was evidence to support this in the current study. Further research is needed to consider which elements of HAI are most important for well-being, so they may be accounted for in data analysis; qualitative findings from this study and other research may be used to refine and test existing HAI theories to identify these elements.

While the collection of pre-pandemic data was not possible for the current study, it may be possible to utilise existing data to compare pre- and post-pandemic effects of companion animal guardianship. Previously, data from large-scale longitudinal studies have been used to examine the impact of companion animal guardianship on well-being [82]. Where such studies have collected data pre- and post-pandemic, it may be possible to examine any longer-term influences of companion animal guardianship during the pandemic and beyond.

Finally, further research is needed regarding the specific impact of ornamental fishes on well-being within the context of companion animal guardianship. To date, most research has focused on the shorter-term impacts of fish aquaria in a clinical or health care context [30], and while qualitative data from this and other research [32] have suggested that watching fish aquaria can induce relaxation, there is no quantitative data to support this within the home environment. It is also unclear whether fish guardianship translates to longer-term effects on well-being, and whether certain populations experience greater or lesser benefits from their home aquaria. Future research should aim to address these gaps in the evidence.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, there was no quantitative evidence that being a companion animal guardian was associated with less loneliness and greater mental well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic, nor was this influenced by specific companion animal types (dogs, cats, ornamental fishes). There was some evidence that a greater level of engagement with dogs, and to a lesser extent cats, was associated with higher loneliness and poorer mental well-being, which may indicate that these individuals experienced higher levels of social isolation. Further research is needed to investigate this theory. Qualitative data indicated that companion animal guardians had experienced a range of benefits during the pandemic; these insights may be useful in refining theories regarding the impact of companion animals on human well-being. Negative aspects of companion animal guardianship during the pandemic typically related to animal welfare concerns, but a small number of participants had very negative experiences regarding the impact of their companion animals on their well-being. These experiences warrant further consideration, as they may shed light on conflicting findings within HAI research. Findings regarding ornamental fish guardians generally reflected those of companion animals more broadly, though there was evidence that a larger proportion held indifferent views regarding the impact of their companion animals on their well-being, and level of engagement with ornamental fishes was not associated with loneliness or well-being. More research is needed to understand the impact of ornamental fishes within the context of companion animal guardianship.

Supplementary Materials: The following are available online at <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/ani11082349/s1>, Table S1: Survey participant characteristics by type of companion animal; Table S2: Results of robust hierarchical multiple regression analyses; Table S3: Results of robust hierarchical regression analyses for level of engagement with companion animals.

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Data Availability Statement: The quantitative data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author. These data are not publicly available because permission to share data publicly was not obtained from participants as part of the consent process. To ensure participant confidentiality, qualitative data cannot be shared outside the research team.

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